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Report

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1. Summary

This report was created as part of WP2 'IMTA New Value Chains and Production Methods' of the H2020 All Atlantic Ocean Sustainable, Rentable and Resilient Aquaculture (ASTRAL) project. Throughout the project, several experiments were carried out integrating different species into an IMTA biofloc system (BFT) at the Federal University of Rio Grande - FURG (Brazil). The main results of 7 experiments are presented here and aim to guide future producers interested in adopting a system that does not require water renewal. The experiments were developed to solve the problems of accumulation of organic matter and nutrients arising from the use of the BFT system and thus allow the reuse of water with bioflocs in different production cycles.

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3. Introduction

The H2020 project ASTRAL developed new, sustainable, profitable and resilient value chains for integrated multi-trophic aquaculture (IMTA) production within the framework of existing, emerging and potential Atlantic markets. The project gathered four IMTA labs including open-water (Ireland, Scotland), land-based pump-ashore with partial (50%) recirculation (South Africa) and recirculation 'biofloc' land-based (Brazil) systems as well as one prospective IMTA lab (Argentina), focusing on a regional challenge-based perspective, including fish, mollusc, echinoderm, crustacean and algae species. ASTRAL assessed how to increase circularity using IMTA methods of cultivation by 50-60% compared to monoculture aquaculture and provided a circular business model, boosting revenue diversification for aquaculture producers increasing profitability by at least 30%. New and improved innovative technologies were developed, including biosensors, sensors, Internet of Things (IoT) and an Artificial Intelligence (AI) data analytics platform was validated at the IMTA labs. Potential environmental and climatic risks for Northern and Southern Atlantic regions were addressed, delivering a monitoring programme and recommendations for Harmful Algal Blooms (HABs), pathogens and microplastics. ASTRAL proposed an ambitious and gender-sensitive human capital development plan (HUCAP) that seeks to improve professional skills and create a highly trained workforce. The project gathered a collaborative ecosystem within the project framework bringing together and connecting industrial partners, SMEs, scientists, policy makers, social representatives and other relevant stakeholders promoting data exchange, knowledge sharing and business opportunities.

4. IMTA Brazil - land-based BFT systems

4.1. Site description

The Marine Aquaculture Center (Figure 1) is located 300m away from the shoreline and has 9 experimental shrimp ponds (600m² each one), 3 greenhouses for research with shrimp production in bioflocs, 1 commercial greenhouse for shrimp production (2 tanks with 280m² each) and 1 multi-trophic greenhouse (6 systems with 3 tanks each) (figure 2). In addition, shrimp maturation sector (6 tanks with 10 ton each), shrimp larviculture tanks (8 tanks), sectors of live food production (Artemia and phytoplankton) and water quality laboratory.

Figure 1. Location of Federal University of Rio Grande- FURG in southern Brazil (left) and the Marine Aquaculture Centre (right) (32°17'52.30" S – 52°15'59.80" W).

Figure 2. Shrimp ponds (600m² each), experimental greenhouse (12 tanks with 35m³ each), maturation room (6 tanks with 10m³ each), commercial greenhouse (500 m²)

For all experiments in the IMTA greenhouse (Figure 3), the shrimp were kept in high densities (350 to 550 shrimp/m³) and we stimulated the biofloc formation by organic fertilization. For each 1 mg of ammonia in the water we added 15 mg of carbon (molasses in general) to keep the relation C:N = 15:1. When the microbial community is well formed, all ammonia and nitrite are transformed into nitrate, which accumulates in the system. Then the water was pumped from the shrimp tank to the raceway where the oysters and fish were responsible for filtering out suspended particles in the system. Then the water was driven by gravity into the seaweed tank from where after it flowed back into the shrimp raceway through a central bottom. The seaweed will remove dissolved CO₂, nitrate and phosphate. The choice of the species establishment to be used and the biomass relationship are the key factors for maintaining the system's water quality. In this way, it is not necessary to change the water and it can and must be used for several production cycles. Previous studies indicate better animal performance when water was reused from the production system, as there were no nitrogen peaks and pH variations. When we reuse water with biofloc were reused from the beginning of the cycle, natural food was provided 24 hours a day, 7 days a week, hence lowering FCR, and reducing the food costs considerably.

Figure 3. IMTA greenhouse with shrimp tanks (left) and fish and seaweed tanks (right).

The proposed IMTA system effectively utilises the expertise of the FURG researchers and their partners to develop a new technology that incorporates different species. The resulting, integrated, multi-trophic system is potentially more biologically efficient, more environmentally sustainable, and more economically competitive than the four cultivation systems maintained separately.

Species

Shrimp - *Litopenaeus vannamei*

The Pacific white shrimp *Litopenaeus vannamei* is a native species from the Eastern Pacific and is distributed from Mexico to northern Peru, which shows great resilience and easy adaptation to different culture systems. It also presents one of the best zootechnical indexes and great market acceptance. Besides achieving high growth and survival rates, it has lower nutritional requirements in terms of protein, when compared to other penaeid species.

These characteristics make this organism very easily adaptable to different types of systems, including IMTA, serving as the main species in our system, being the most productive and also of highest aggregated value in our region.

Figure 4. Shrimp after harvest (left and centre) and shrimp tank with biofloc (brown water).

Fish - *Oreochromis niloticus*

The Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) presents some characteristics that make it an ideal species for culture in an IMTA system based on the BFT system. This species has a high tolerance for suspended solids, moderate dissolved oxygen, can be maintained in high stocking densities and can be produced in intermediate salinity. In addition, it is an omnivorous species, presenting filtering structures and a digestive system that allows it to have an organic extractive potential, feeding on natural productivity of the BFT system, and removing the excess of total suspended solids, being used as a bioremediation agent in IMTA systems.

Figure 5. Tilapia fingerlings (left), fish biometry during experiment (center) and tilapia close to commercial size.

Molluscs – *Amarilladesma mactroides*, *Crassostrea gigas* and *Crassostrea gasar*

Sessile filtering organisms are also important in the biological removal of total suspended solids in the IMTA system. Many of these organisms have a high added value in many places, however the characteristic of the IMTA system associated with bioflocs makes their adaptation very difficult in some cases.

In the case of the mussel *Amarilladesma mactroides*, a local and very abundant species, its insertion in the system was not possible because it needs a sandy substrate in which it can remain partially buried, which is not possible in a biofloc system. The species also showed little tolerance to moderate values of total suspended solids (TSS) in some initial tests, and its use as a filtering bivalve in our system was discarded.

Figure 6. Molluscs used in the experiments. *Amarilladesma mactroides* (left), *Crassostrea gigas* (centre) and *Crassostrea gasar* (right).

Regarding oysters, the first species to be tested was the Pacific oyster *Crassostrea gigas*. Despite its high added value, it is an unpromising species to our system because of its little tolerance to the presence of SST and high temperatures. Due to these results, the mangrove oyster, *Crassostrea gasar* was tested instead. Since it is a native species that grows in mangrove areas, it provided to be more tolerant to culture conditions of high TSS values and high temperatures, with promising results in preliminary tests. Therefore, this species was chosen to be one of the filtering organisms to assist in the removal of TSS in our IMTA system.

Seaweed - *Ulva lactuca (fasciata)* and *Ulva flexuosa*

Besides the accumulation of particulate matter in the system, another problem to be solved in IMTA systems is the accumulation of nutrients, in particular nitrogen compounds and phosphorus. Thus, two native species of macroalgae were used in our tests. The species *Ulva lactuca* and *Ulva flexuosa* occur in the region and are easily collected and brought to the laboratory to be acclimated and introduced in the IMTA system to absorb nitrogen and phosphate compounds.

The tests carried out with the two species showed promise in the removal nitrogen and phosphorus from the system. Phosphorus presents slower accumulation in the system when compared to nitrogen compounds that are always present due to the action of nitrifying bacteria present in the system. As these are local species, the use of one or another species will depend on the availability in the environment at the time of collection.

Figure 7. Pictures from the experiments with *Ulva* in different cultivation structures.

Halophytes – *Salicornia neei*

As the seaweed, sea asparagus can be used to control nutrients in the production system. This plant has already been cultivated in marine aquaponics using BFT technology on laminar nutrient flow benches (“nutrient film technique – NFT”) and tanks with floating rafts (Figure 8). Previous experiments found a 25% increase in the efficiency of using nitrogen added to the cultivation of shrimp (*L. vannamei*) in the form of feed, in BFT cultures connected to *S. neei* aquaponic benches compared to those without halophytes. Additionally, production of 2 kg of *S. neei* plants for each kilogram of shrimp was observed in the proposed aquaponic system.

Figure 8. Pictures from experimental unities with sea asparagus, inside (left) and outside (center and right)

4.2. Environmental data

The Marine Aquaculture Station is located in the extreme south of the Brazilian coast and close (250 km) to the border with Uruguay. The climate is sub-tropical, with four seasons well marked, with maximum temperatures reaching 40 °C in the summer and minimum temperatures of 0 °C during the winter. Due to the great temperature variability, the greenhouses are used for experiments concentrated between January and May and between September and December of each year. During the winter months, shrimp and tilapia are no longer produced. The research system was set up on land and is not subject to ocean variations, with the exception of water temperature.

5. IMTA Species Trials

5.1. Shrimp *Penaeus vannamei* integrated with tilapia *Oreochromis niloticus* (Experiment 1)

5.1.1. Introduction

One of the major problems related to super intensive aquaculture is the generation of effluents with high organic loads. Feeding in intensive monocultures increment the discharge effluents with a high pollution potential, with a high concentration of nitrogen and phosphorus¹. These problems have raised concerns in many countries due to the likely environmental impacts of this activity².

The Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture (IMTA) aims at the integration of species with different trophic levels in the culture system, in order to take advantage of the residues from the production of one species for the culture of other species³. Even organisms that occupy the same trophic level in the system can be produced at IMTA if they make use of different food webs in that system². This variety in the combination of organic and inorganic extractive species gives IMTA advantages in terms of biomitigation and economic gain, consequently more sustainability, when compared to monocultures⁴. The biofloc system is another culture technology that has been adopted in shrimp culture. The biofloc system is another culture technology that has been adopted in shrimp culture. This system gives a new direction for the shrimp monoculture in regard to aquaculture sustainability. Due to a better maintenance of water quality, this system can reduce water use by up to 90% compared to traditional systems⁵, allowing culture at high stocking densities⁶, reducing the use of land⁷ and optimizing the use of artificial food⁸.

¹ Briggs M. R. P., Funge-Smith S. J. (1994). A nutrient budget of some intensive marine shrimp ponds in Thailand. *Aquacult. Fish. Manage* 25 (8), 789–811. doi: 10.1111/j.1365-2109.1994.tb00744.x

² Boyd C. E., D'Abramo L. R., Glencross B. D., Huyben D. C., Juarez L. M., Lockwood G. S., et al. (2020). Achieving sustainable aquaculture: Historical and current perspectives and future needs and challenges. *J. World Aquacult. Soc.* 51 (3), 578–633. doi: 10.1111/jwas.12714

³Troell M., Joyce A., Chopin T., Neori A., Buschmann A. H., Fang J. G.. (2009). Ecological engineering in aquaculture - potential for integrated multi-trophic aquaculture (IMTA) in marine offshore systems. *Aquaculture* 297 (1–4), 1–9. doi: 10.1016/j.aquaculture.2009.09.010

⁴ Biswas G., Kumar P., Ghoshal T. K., Kailasam M., De D., Bera A., et al. (2020). Integrated multi-trophic aquaculture (IMTA) outperforms conventional polyculture with respect to environmental remediation, productivity and economic return in brackishwater ponds. *Aquaculture* 516, 734626. doi: 10.1016/j.aquaculture.2019.734626

⁵ Krummenauer D., Samocha T., Poersch L., Lara G., Wasielesky W.. (2014). The reuse of water on the culture of pacific white shrimp, *litopenaeus vannamei*, in BFT system. *J. World Aquacult. Soc.* 45 (1), 3–14. doi: 10.1111/jwas.12093

⁶ Wasielesky W., Froes C., Fóes G., Krummenauer D., Lara G., Poersch L.. (2013). Nursery of *litopenaeus vannamei* reared in a biofloc system: The effect of stocking densities and compensatory growth. *J. Shellfish Res.* 32 (3), 799–806. doi: 10.2983/035.032.0323

⁷ Liu W., Luo G., Li L., Wang X., Wang J., Ma N., et al. (2017). Nitrogen dynamics and biofloc composition using biofloc technology to treat aquaculture solid waste mixed with distillery spent wash. *North Am. J. Aquacult.* 79 (1), 27–35. doi: 10.1080/15222055.2016.1223769

⁸ Santhana Kumar V., Pandey P. K., Anand T., Bhuvaneshwari G. R., Dhinakaran A., Kumar S.. (2018). Biofloc improves water, effluent quality and growth parameters of *penaeus vannamei* in an intensive culture system. *J. Environ. Management.* 215, 206–215. doi: 10.1016/j.jenvman.2018.03.015

This is possible through the increase of the C: N ratio in water, with the use of organic carbon sources and constant aeration, stimulating the production of microorganisms that will both work on the metabolization of nitrogenous compounds and serve as natural food for reared animals^{9,10,11}.

Shrimp production in the biofloc system has numerous economic advantages¹². Nevertheless, there are still environmental constraints such as the accumulation of organic matter during production in a system with minimal water exchange and high densities. This accumulation produces an excess of suspended solids, which increases the biological oxygen demand due to the high concentration of aerobic microorganisms present in bioflocs¹³. Therefore, it is recommended that excess total suspended solids (TSS) in the biofloc system should be removed through clarification processes¹⁴.

Sedimentation (removal of excess biofloc particles by gravity) efficiently removes excess solids suspended in the biofloc system¹⁵ that are normally discarded as effluents. Therefore, the rationale for integrating species in the biofloc system is to take advantage of this excess of microbial protein in the form of suspended solids, to feed other species and thus transform effluent into animal protein, making the system even more sustainable.

Tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) presents some characteristics that make it an ideal species for culture in an IMTA system based on the biofloc system^{16,17,18}. This species has a high tolerance for suspended

⁹ Krummenauer D., Peixoto S., Cavalli R. O., Poersch L. H., Wasielesky W.. (2011). Superintensive culture of white shrimp, *litopenaeus vannamei*, in a biofloc technology system in southern Brazil at different stocking densities. *J. World Aquacult. Soc.* 42 (5), 726–733. doi: 10.1111/j.1749-7345.2011.00507.x

¹⁰ Lara G., Honda M., Poersch L., Wasielesky W.. (2017). The use of biofilm and different feeding rates in biofloc culture system: the effects in shrimp growth parameters. *Aquacult. Int.* 25 (5), 1959–1970. doi: 10.1007/s10499-017-0151-0

¹¹ Khanjani M. H., Mozanzadeh M. T., Sharifinia M., Emerenciano M. G. C.. (2023). Biofloc: A sustainable dietary supplement, nutritional value and functional properties. *Aquaculture* 562 (August 2022), 738757. doi: 10.1016/j.aquaculture.2022.738757

¹² Rego M. A. S., Sabbag O. J., Soares R., Peixoto S.. (2017). Financial viability of inserting the biofloc technology in a marine shrimp *litopenaeus vannamei* farm: a case study in the state of pernambuco, Brazil. *Aquacult. Int. Springer Int. Publ.* 25 (1), 473–483. doi: 10.1007/s10499-016-0044-7

¹³ Ray A. J., Lewis B. L., Browdy C. L., Leffler J. W., et al. (2010). Suspended solids removal to improve shrimp (*Litopenaeus vannamei*) production and an evaluation of a plant-based feed in minimal-exchange, superintensive culture systems. *Aquaculture* 299 (1–4), 89–98. doi: 10.1016/j.aquaculture.2009.11.02

¹⁴ Gaona C. A. P., Serra da F. P., Furtado P. S., Poersch L. H., Wasielesky W.. (2016). Biofloc management with different flow rates for solids removal in the *litopenaeus vannamei* BFT culture system. *Aquacult. Int.* 24 (5), 1263–1275. doi: 10.1007/s10499-016-9983-2

¹⁵ Gaona C. A. P., Souza de Almeida M., Viau V., Poersch L. H., Wasielesky W.. (2017). Effect of different total suspended solids levels on a *litopenaeus vannamei* (Boone 1931) BFT culture system during biofloc formation. *Aquacult. Res.* 48 (3), 1070–1079. doi: 10.1111/are.12949

¹⁶ Azim M. E., Verdegem M. C. J., Mantingh I., Van Dam A.A., Beveridge M. C. M.. (2003). Ingestion and utilization of periphyton grown on artificial substrates by Nile tilapia, *oreochromis niloticus* l. *Aquacult. Res.* 34 (1), 85–92. doi: 10.1046/j.1365-2109.2003.00802.x

¹⁷ Monroy-Dosta M.d. C., de Lara R.A., Castro-Mejía J., Castro-Mejía G., Coelho-Emerenciano M. G.. (2013). Composición y abundancia de comunidades microbianas asociados al biofloc en un cultivo de tilapia. *Rev. Biol. Marina y Oceanogr.* 48 (3), 511–520. doi: 10.4067/S0718-19572013000300009

¹⁸ Poli M. A., Legarda E. C., de Lorenzo M. A., Martins M. A., do Nascimento Vieira F.. (2019). Pacific white shrimp and Nile tilapia integrated in a biofloc system under different fish-stocking densities. *Aquaculture* 498 (August 2018), 83–89. doi: 10.1016/j.aquaculture.2018.08.045

solids, moderate dissolved oxygen, and high stocking densities^{19, 20, 21, 22}. In addition, it is an omnivorous species, presenting filtering structures and a digestive system that allows it to be an organic extractive in potential, feeding on natural productivity of the biofloc system and removing the excess of total suspended solids. It can be used as a bioremediation agent in IMTA systems^{23, 24, 25}. Commercial expansion of IMTA has been troublesome. Although the biological and environmental advantages of this practice are generally accepted by producers and society, some economic-related issues have yet to be overcome for its adoption²⁶.

Thus, pilot-scale studies aimed at integrating super-intensive production of Pacific white shrimp (*Litopenaeus vannamei*) and Nile tilapia in the biofloc system are sorely needed for the development of large-scale integrated multi-trophic cultures.

There are some studies reporting the integrated culture of shrimp and tilapia, though in low production densities and in clear water systems^{27, 28, 29, 30, 31, 32, 33}. More recently, Poli et al.²⁵ studied the integrated

¹⁹ Azim M. E., Little D. C. (2008). The biofloc technology (BFT) in indoor tanks: Water quality, biofloc composition, and growth and welfare of Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*). *Aquaculture* 283 (1–4), 29–35. doi: 10.1016/j.aquaculture.2008.06.036

²⁰ Simão B. R., et al. (2013). Stocking densities and feeding strategies in shrimp and tilapia polyculture in tanks. *Pesquisa Agropecuária Bras.* 48 (8), 1088–1095. doi: 10.1590/S0100-204X2013000800039

²¹ Malpartida Pasco J. J., Carvalho Filho J. W., de Espírito Santo C. M., Vinatea L. (2018). Production of Nile tilapia *Oreochromis niloticus* grown in BFT using two aeration systems. *Aquacult. Res.* 49 (1), 222–231. doi: 10.1111/are.13451

²² Khanjani M. H., Sharifinia M. (2021). Production of Nile tilapia *Oreochromis niloticus* reared in a limited water exchange system: The effect of different light levels. *Aquaculture* 542 (January), 736912. doi: 10.1016/j.aquaculture.2021.736912

²³ Azim M. E., Verdegem M. C. J., Mantingh I., Van Dam A.A., Beveridge M. C. M. (2003). Ingestion and utilization of periphyton grown on artificial substrates by Nile tilapia, *Oreochromis niloticus* L. *Aquacult. Res.* 34 (1), 85–92. doi: 10.1046/j.1365-2109.2003.00802.x

²⁴ Ekasari J., Angela D., Waluyo S. H., Bachtiar T., Surawidjaja E. H., Bossier P., et al. (2014). The size of biofloc determines the nutritional composition and the nitrogen recovery by aquaculture animals. *Aquaculture* 426–427 (April), 105–111. doi: 10.1016/j.aquaculture.2014.01.023

²⁵ Poli M. A., Legarda E. C., de Lorenzo M. A., Martins M. A., Seiffert W. Q., do Nascimento Vieira F., et al. (2019). Integrated multitrophic aquaculture applied to shrimp rearing in a biofloc system. *Aquaculture* 511, 1–6. doi: 10.1016/j.aquaculture.2019.734274

²⁶ Ridler N., Wowchuk M., Robinson B., Barrington K., Chopin T., Robinson S., et al. (2007). Integrated multi-trophic aquaculture (IMTA): A potential strategic choice for farmers. *Aquacult. Econ. Manage.* 11 (1), 99–110. doi: 10.1080/13657300701202767

²⁷ Tendencia E. A., Dela Peña M. R., Fermin A. C., Lio-Po G., Choresca C. H., Inui Y. (2004). Antibacterial activity of tilapia *Oreochromis niloticus* against *Vibrio harveyi*. *Aquaculture* 232 (1–4), 145–152. doi: 10.1016/S0044-8486(03)00531-3

²⁸ Tendencia E. A., Dela Peña M. R., Choresca C. H. (2006). Effect of shrimp biomass and feeding on the anti-*Vibrio harveyi* activity of tilapia sp. in a simulated shrimp-tilapia polyculture system. *Aquaculture* 253 (1–4), 154–162. doi: 10.1016/j.aquaculture.2005.08.004

²⁹ Muangkeow B., Ikejima K., Powtongsook S., Gallardo W. (2007). Effects of white shrimp, *Litopenaeus vannamei* (Boone), and Nile tilapia, *Oreochromis niloticus* L., stocking density on growth, nutrient conversion rate and economic return in integrated closed recirculation system. *Aquaculture* 269 (1–4), 363–376. doi: 10.1016/j.aquaculture.2007.04.002

³⁰ Cruz P. S., Andalecio M. N., Bolivar R. B., Fitzsimmons K. (2008). Tilapia-shrimp polyculture in Negros Island, Philippines: A review. *J. World Aquacult. Soc.* 39 (6), 713–725. doi: 10.1111/j.1749-7345.2008.00207.x

³¹ Yuan D., Yi Y., Yakupitiyage A., Fitzsimmons K., Diana J. S. (2010). Effects of addition of red tilapia (*Oreochromis* spp.) at different densities and sizes on production, water quality and nutrient recovery of intensive culture of white shrimp (*Litopenaeus vannamei*) in cement tanks. *Aquaculture* 298 (3–4), 226–238. doi: 10.1016/j.aquaculture.2009.11.011

³² Muangkeow B., Ikejima K., Powtongsook S., Yi Y. (2011). Growth and nutrient conversion of white shrimp *Litopenaeus vannamei* (Boone) and Nile tilapia *Oreochromis niloticus* L. in an integrated closed recirculating system. *Aquacult. Res.* 42 (9), 1246–1260. doi: 10.1111/j.1365-2109.2010.02713.x

³³ Simão B. R., et al. (2013). Stocking densities and feeding strategies in shrimp and tilapia polyculture in tanks. *Pesquisa Agropecuária Bras.* 48 (8), 1088–1095. doi: 10.1590/S0100-204X2013000800039

culture of shrimp and tilapia in an experimental scale, and this work represents a first step towards a future IMTA using biofloc technology. Nevertheless, until now, there is no work with integrated super-intensive production of shrimps and tilapia in a BFT system, on a pilot scale. The objective of this study was to evaluate the effect of different fish stocking densities in the integrated super-intensive culture of white shrimp *L. vannamei* and Nile tilapia *O. niloticus* reared in biofloc system to promote the maintenance of TSS at the appropriate levels for shrimp culture, through the consumption of the excess of biofloc by the fish.

5.1.2. Trial Methodology

The experiment lasted 78 days and was performed in two treatments with three replicates: 1) T35 – integrated culture of shrimp (550 shrimp m⁻³) and tilapia at a stocking density of 35 fish m⁻³; and 2) T65 - integrated culture of shrimp (550 shrimp m⁻³) and tilapia at a stocking density of 65 fish m⁻³).

The study was carried out at the Marine Station of Aquaculture, Federal University of Rio Grande (EMA-FURG), Southern Brazil (32°12'16S, 52°10'38W) in a greenhouse used for IMTA studies. Nauplii of *L. vannamei* were purchased from the company Aquatec (Aquatec®, Canguaretama; Rio Grande do Norte, Brazil), and larval development was carried out in the Carcinoculture laboratory at EMA-FURG. The fish were purchased from a commercial farm in the municipality of Camaquã, Rio Grande do Sul, Brazil.

Sea water previously diluted in fresh water provided by the local supply company was used to formulate water with salinity of 15 g L⁻¹. The salinity was kept at 15 with chlorinated fresh water and neutralized with vitamin C³⁴. This experiment was approved by the Ethics and Animal Welfare Committee of the Federal University of Rio Grande - FURG (Case number 23116.005895/2016-42).

Before the experiment starts, an inoculum of 20% of the total volume of the shrimp tank, with mature bioflocs (with the complete nitrification process, without detection of ammonia and nitrite, and with detection of nitrate), was used in all treatments. The inoculum was taken from a 60-day culture of *L. vannamei* with a density of 400 m⁻³ in 35 m³ tanks located in a greenhouse. Sugar cane molasses, containing 37% of organic carbon, was used as a carbon source in the initial phases of cultivation for ammonia control. The inoculum's initial concentration was TSS ± 400 mg L⁻¹ and ± 65 mg L⁻¹ of nitrate,

³⁴ Roselet F., Maicá P., Martins T., Abreu P. C.. (2013). Comparison of open-air and semi-enclosed cultivation system for massive microalgae production in sub-tropical and temperate latitudes. *Biomass Bioenergy* 59, 418–424. doi: 10.1016/j.biombioe.2013.09.014

indicating that the nitrification process was taking place in this matrix tank. Organic fertilization was carried out by manipulating the C: N ratio to 15:1^{35,36}.

During the study, shrimps were fed twice a day (9 a.m. and 5 p.m.) with species-specific commercial feed, containing 38% crude protein (Poty Active 38, 1.6 mm, Guabi®, Campinas, SP, Brazil), following the methodology described by Jory et al.³⁷. Fish were fed twice a day (9 a.m. and 5 p.m.) with Guabitech Mirim QS commercial feed (1.0 mm) at the beginning of the experiment, adjusting the feed for Guabitech omnivorous QS (2-3 mm/5-5 mm), throughout the experimental period, as fish grew. Fish were underfed to stimulate the consumption of biofloc. In the first half of the experiment the feed was offered at a rate of 2% of the total fish biomass in each tank. This value was adjusted in the second half of the experiment, when feed was offered at a rate of 1%. Shrimps were stocked in the experimental tanks with an initial weight of 0.96 ± 0.1 g. Tilapia, with an initial weight of 7.17 ± 3.15 g, were previously acclimated to the salinity of the experiment and later stored in the experimental units. The biofloc-IMTA recirculation system includes a circular tank of 10 m^3 , where shrimps were stored, and another similar tank of 4 m^3 of useful volume was stocked with tilapia. The water was pumped from the shrimp tank to the tilapia tank through PVC pipes (40mm in diameter) using submerged pumps (SB 2700, Sarlo better, Brazil), and returned to the shrimp tank by gravity, through tubes (40mm) installed 20 cm from the surface of the tank. The recirculation system operated for 24 hours, with an average flow of $965.6 \pm 92.8 \text{ L h}^{-1}$. Aeration was provided by a 4HP blower connected to the air distribution system by means of microperforated hoses. Each recirculation system contained a cylindrical-conical clarifier made of fiberglass with useful volume of 150 L. A shade cloth was installed on the greenhouse ceiling to attenuate 70% of the luminosity to avoid phytoplankton blooms and favor the heterotrophic nature of the system.

The temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) and dissolved oxygen (mg L^{-1}) in the tanks were monitored twice a day using a digital oximeter (model HI 9146-04, Hanna® instruments), the pH was measured daily, with a bench pH meter (Mettler Toledo, Five-Easy model). Salinity was checked weekly with an optical refractometer

³⁵ Ebeling J. M., Timmons M. B., Bisogni J. J. (2006). Engineering analysis of the stoichiometry of photoautotrophic, autotrophic, and heterotrophic removal of ammonia-nitrogen in aquaculture systems. *Aquaculture* 257 (1–4), 346–358. doi: 10.1016/j.aquaculture.2006.03.019

³⁶ Khanjani M. H., Sharifinia M. (2022). Biofloc technology with addition molasses as carbon sources applied to *Litopenaeus vannamei* juvenile production under the effects of different C/N ratios. *Aquacult. Int. Springer Int. Publ.* 30 (1), 383–397. doi: 10.1007/s10499-021-00803-5

³⁷ Jory D. E., Cabrera T. R., Dugger D. M., Fegan D., Lee P. G., Lawrence L., et al. (2001). A' global review of shrimp feed Management : Status and perspectives. *Aquaculture*, 104–152.

(Atago). Total ammonia³⁸, and nitrite³⁹ were monitored daily. Nitrate³⁸, phosphate⁴⁰, alkalinity⁴¹ and total suspended solids⁴⁰ were measured weekly.

Total suspended solids (TSS) were kept at 500 mg L⁻¹ according to Gaona et al.⁴². When the TSS value exceeded this limit, physical clarification was performed in the systems by removing suspended solids in all treatments⁴³. The pH corrections were made to keep the values above 7.2 by the addition of hydrated lime - Ca(OH)₂ - according to Furtado et al.⁴⁴. Alkalinity was corrected to maintain concentrations above 150 mg L⁻¹, following the same protocol.

Shrimp (n = 40) and fish (n = 20) growth was monitored through weekly and biweekly biometrics, respectively, using a digital scale with accuracy of 0.01g (Mars - Model AD 2000). Anesthetics were used to manipulate fish during weighing (benzocaine hydrochloride, 50 mg L⁻¹). At the end of the experiment, all shrimp and fish remaining in the tanks were counted to determine the survival and growth. The parameters analyzed were: Survival (%) = (final shrimp number/initial shrimp number) × 100; Final average weight (g): final weight of live animals (g)/total number of animals; Total biomass (g): final weight of all live animals (g); Weekly growth rate (g week⁻¹): weight gain (g)/number of weeks; Feed conversion ratio (FCR) = offered feed (g)/(final biomass (g) - initial biomass (g)); Productivity (kg m⁻³): [(final biomass (kg) - initial biomass (kg)) × 1000]/useful tank volume (L).

The parameters analyzed for the IMTA system as a whole (shrimp + fish) were: system productivity (Kg m⁻³): (FBs + FBf) - (IBs + IBf)/Total useful volume (m³), where FBs = final shrimp biomass; FBf = final fish biomass; IBs = Initial biomass of shrimps; IBf = Initial biomass of fish and Total useful volume = sum of the useful volume of the shrimp and fish tanks; FCR: (Fs + Ff)/(FBs + FBf) - (IBs - IBf), where Fs = feed offered for shrimp and Ff = feed offered for fish.

³⁸ UNESCO, I. O. Commission (1983). Chemical methods for use in marine environmental monitoring.

³⁹ Bendschneider K., Robinson R. J. (1952). A new spectrophotometric method for the determination of nitrite in Sea water. *J. Mar. Res.* 11 (8), 87–96

⁴⁰ Strickland J., Parsons T. (1972). A practical handbook of seawater analysis. 2nd edn (Ottawa: Fisheries Research Board of Canada). doi: 10.1007/978-1-4615-5439-4_19

⁴¹ APHA, A. W. W. A, W. P. C. A (2017). Standard methods for the examination of water and wastewater. 23rd edn (Washington DC: W. E. F. American Public Health Association, American Water Works Association. Pharmabooks).

⁴² Gaona C. A. P., Souza de Almeida M., Viau V., Poersch L. H., Wasielesky W.. (2017). Effect of different total suspended solids levels on a *litopenaeus vannamei* (Boone 1931) BFT culture system during biofloc formation. *Aquacult. Res.* 48 (3), 1070–1079. doi: 10.1111/are.12949

⁴³ Gaona C. A. P., et al. (2011). The effect of solids removal on water quality, growth and survival of *litopenaeus vannamei* in a biofloc technology culture system. *Int. J. Recirculating Aquacult.* 12 (1), 54–73. doi: 10.21061/ijra.v12i1.1354

⁴⁴ Furtado P. S., Poersch L. H., Wasielesky W. (2011). Effect of calcium hydroxide, carbonate and sodium bicarbonate on water quality and zootechnical performance of shrimp *litopenaeus vannamei* reared in bio-flocs technology (BFT) systems. *Aquaculture* 321 (1–2), 130–135. doi: 10.1016/j.aquaculture.2011.08.034

After verifying the normality and homoscedasticity of the data, the parameters of water quality and growth performance were submitted to the t-test for comparison of means. The survival data were transformed (arcsine $\times 0.5$) before analysis ⁴⁵(Zar, 2010).

5.1.3. Results

The main water quality parameters registered in the present study are showed in Table 1. The mean temperature was maintained above 28°C, dissolved oxygen above 6.0 mg L⁻¹ and the pH above 7.5 and did not present significant differences between treatments ($p > 0.05$). Alkalinity (Figure 9) showed significantly higher ($p < 0.05$) mean values (143.6 ± 35.2 mg L⁻¹ of CaCO₃) in treatment T35 than in treatment T65 (134.9 ± 33.2 mg L⁻¹ of CaCO₃). Salinity values fluctuated between 13 and 15 throughout the experiment, however, differences between treatments were non-significant ($p > 0.05$).

The concentrations of total ammoniacal nitrogen, nitrate and orthophosphate (Figure 10) did not show significant differences ($p > 0.05$) between treatments. The mean values of nitrite, on the other hand, were significantly higher ($p < 0.05$) in T65 (1.1 ± 1.5 mg L⁻¹) than T35 treatment (0.6 ± 0.6 mg L⁻¹). The TSS concentrations and turbidity (Figure 11) did not show statistical differences ($p > 0.05$) between treatments. The management of total suspended solids (clarification) was necessary in both treatments in order to maintain the TSS values close to 500 mg L⁻¹. The clarification was performed during 52 ± 18.3 h in T65 and for 32 ± 18.3 h in T35, along all the experimental period (Table 1).

Figure 9. - Mean alkalinity concentrations (mg L⁻¹ of CaCO₃) in the T35 and T65 treatments over the 78 day experimental period. Data are presented as mean \pm standard deviation.

⁴⁵ Zar J. H. (2010). Biostatistical analysis. 5th edn. Ed. Zar. J. H. (New Jersey: Prentice Hall).

Figure 10. - Mean concentrations of ammonia, nitrite, nitrate and phosphate (mg L⁻¹) over the 78 day experimental period in T35 and T65 treatments. Data are presented as mean ± standard deviation.

Table 1. Water quality parameters in treatments T35 (540 shrimp m⁻³ + 35 fish m⁻³) and T65 (540 shrimp m⁻³ + 65 fish m⁻³) throughout the experimental period (mean values ± standard deviation).

	T35	T65
Temperature (°C)	28.3 ± 1.9	28.4 ± 1.8
DO (mg L ⁻¹)	6.1 ± 0.6	6.0 ± 0.6
pH	7.5 ± 0.3	7.5 ± 0.3
Alkalinity (mg CaCO ₃ L ⁻¹)	143.6 ± 35.2 ^a	134.9 ± 33.2 ^b
Salinity (g L ⁻¹)	14.2 ± 1.1	14.4 ± 0.8
TSS (mg L ⁻¹)	436.6 ± 140.5	457.2 ± 135.5
Turbidity (NTU)	247.0 ± 81.5	240.1 ± 94.2
Clarification time (hours)	32.0 ± 18.3	52.0 ± 18.3
TAN (mg L ⁻¹)	0.01 ± 0.01	0.01 ± 0.01
Nitrite (mg L ⁻¹)	0.6 ± 0.6 ^a	1.1 ± 1.5 ^b
Nitrate (mg L ⁻¹)	68.7 ± 53.7	70.3 ± 53.5
Orthophosphate (mg L ⁻¹)	2.0 ± 1.5	2.2 ± 1.61

DO, dissolved oxygen; TSS, total suspended solids; TAN, total ammonia nitrogen. Different letters in the same line represents significant differences ($p < 0.05$) between treatments after t- test.

Shrimps showed similar growth in both treatments ($p > 0.05$) during the experiment, reaching a final weight of 10.1 ± 0.7 g and 11.5 ± 1.9 g in treatments T65 and T35, respectively. The results of growth performance in terms of final mean weight, survival, daily growth rate, feed conversion rate and productivity showed no statistical differences ($p > 0.05$) between treatments (Table 2).

Fish growth was significantly higher ($p < 0.05$) in T35 than in T65 treatments. The productivity was higher in the T65 treatment. Survival and FCR, were similar in both treatments (Table 2). For the IMTA system (shrimp + fish), the total final biomass was statistically higher in the T65 treatment. The total productivity of the system as a whole and the FCR showed no statistical differences between treatments (Table 2).

Figure 11. Mean TSS (total suspended solids) concentrations (mg L⁻¹) and turbidity (NTU) in T35 and T65 treatments during the 78 days of experiment. Data are presented as mean ± standard deviation.

Table 2. Performance of *L. vannamei* and *O. niloticus* (mean values \pm standard deviation) during the experimental period.

Shrimp	T35	T65
Survival (%)	75.9 \pm 0.2	88.2 \pm 0.02
Initial weight (g)	0.9 \pm 0.1	0.9 \pm 0.1
Final weight (g)	11.5 \pm 1.9	10.1 \pm 0.7
Final biomass (kg)	73.1 \pm 12.2	75.4 \pm 2.7
WWG (g week ⁻¹)	0.95 \pm 0.16	0.83 \pm 0.07
FCR	1.7 \pm 0.2	1.6 \pm 0.03
Productivity (kg m ⁻³)	6.8 \pm 1.3	7.0 \pm 0.3
Tilapia		
Survival (%)	99.5 \pm 0.008	100 \pm 0.0
Initial weight (g)	7.1 \pm 3.2	7.1 \pm 3.2
Final weight (g)	127.4 \pm 10.9 ^a	99.6 \pm 6.5 ^b
Final biomass (kg)	17.8 \pm 1.5	25.9 \pm 1.6
WWG (g week ⁻¹)	10.79 \pm 0.98 ^b	8.3 \pm 0.58 ^a
FCR	0.7 \pm 0.03	0.7 \pm 0.04
Productivity (kg m ⁻³)	4.3 \pm 0.2 ^b	6.3 \pm 0.6 ^a
System		
Final biomass (kg)	55.5 \pm 18.6 ^b	67.3 \pm 4.6 ^a
Productivity (kg m ⁻³)	6.1 \pm 1.0	6.7 \pm 0.2
FCR	1.7 \pm 0.3	1.6 \pm 0.1

WWG, weekly weight growth; FCR, feed conversion rate. Different letters in the same line represent significant differences ($p < 0.05$) between treatments.

5.1.4. Discussion and Conclusion

Throughout the experimental period, the physical and chemical parameters of water quality were at suitable levels both for *L. vannamei*⁴⁶ and for tilapia growth^{47, 48}. Even with the culture of two species, the dissolved oxygen, a limiting factor for cultured organisms, mainly in a biofloc system, remained above 6 mg L⁻¹, values above those recommended for reared species^{49, 50} (Tran-Duy et al., 2008).

The alkalinity showed a statistical difference between the treatments during the experimental period, however, the average values registered were within the recommended for *L. vannamei*⁵¹ and for tilapia (*O. niloticus*)⁵². The T65 treatment showed a lower mean alkalinity value than T35, which in turn, presented lower mean nitrite values (0.6 ± 0.6 mg L⁻¹) than T65 (1.1 ± 1.1 mg L⁻¹). In T65 was registered a peak of nitrite at 21 days of the study, reaching 4.5 ± 3.31 mg L⁻¹ and, this possibly happened due to the presence of fish in the system at elevated densities, although with the addition of mature biofloc inoculum. The influence of fish density and the imbalance in the nitrification process are reported by Holanda et al.⁵³ in a study integrating shrimp and mullets (*Mugil liza*). In addition, it is possible that the swimming of a great biomass of fish may have altered the size and shape of bioflocs, which affects the nitrification dynamics in the biofloc systems^{54, 55}.

The presence of tilapia integrated in the system did not negatively affect the performance of the shrimp, independently of the fish densities used. The productivity of the shrimp was high, approximately 7.0 kg m⁻³, already expected in cultures in biofloc system and above the reported

⁴⁶Samocha T. M., Prangnell D. I. (2019). System treatment and preparation. *Sustain. Biofloc. Syst. Mar. Shrimp*, 119–131. doi: 10.1016/b978-0-12-818040-2.00006-x

⁴⁷ Atwood H. L., Fontenot Q. C., Tomasso J. R., Isely J. J.. (2001). Toxicity of nitrite to Nile tilapia: Effect of fish size and environmental chloride. *North Am. J. Aquacult.* 63 (1), 49–51. doi: 10.1577/1548-8454(2001)063<0049:TONTNT>2.0.CO;2

⁴⁸ Azim M. E., Little D. C. (2008). The biofloc technology (BFT) in indoor tanks: Water quality, biofloc composition, and growth and welfare of Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*). *Aquaculture* 283 (1–4), 29–35. doi: 10.1016/j.aquaculture.2008.06.036

⁴⁹ Wasielesky W., Atwood H., Stokes A., Browdy C. L.. (2006). Effect of natural production in a zero exchange suspended microbial floc based super-intensive culture system for white shrimp *litopenaeus vannamei*. *Aquaculture* 258 (1–4), 396–403. doi: 10.1016/j.aquaculture.2006.04.030

⁵⁰ Tran-Duy A., Schrama J. W., van Dam A. A., Verreth J. A. J.. (2008). Effects of oxygen concentration and body weight on maximum feed intake, growth and hematological parameters of Nile tilapia, *oreochromis niloticus*. *Aquaculture* 275 (1–4), 152–162. doi: 10.1016/j.aquaculture.2007.12.024

⁵¹ Furtado P. S., Poersch L. H., Wasielesky W. (2014). The effect of different alkalinity levels on *litopenaeus vannamei* reared with biofloc technology (BFT). *Aquacult. Int.* 23 (1), 345–358. doi: 10.1007/s10499-014-9819-x

⁵² Cavalcante D. D. H., Poliato A. D. S., Ribeiro D. C., Magalhães F. B., Sá M. V.. (2009). Effects of CaCO₃ liming on water quality and growth performance of fingerlings of Nile tilapia, *oreochromis niloticus*. *Acta Scientiarum. Anim. Sci.* 31 (3), 327–333. doi: 10.4025/actascianimsci.v31i3.6263

⁵³ Holanda M., Santana G., Furtado P., Vieira R., Ronzani V., Andr L., et al. (2020). Evidence of total suspended solids control by mugil *liza* reared in an integrated system with pacific white shrimp *litopenaeus vannamei* using biofloc technology. *Aquacult. Rep.* 18 (October 2019), 1–7. doi: 10.1016/j.aqrep.2020.100479

⁵⁴ Carvalho G., Meyer R. L., Yuan Z., Keller J. (2006). Differential distribution of ammonia- and nitrite-oxidising bacteria in flocs and granules from a nitrifying/denitrifying sequencing batch reactor. *Enzyme Microbial. Technol.* 39 (7), 1392–1398. doi: 10.1016/j.enzymictec.2006.03.024

⁵⁵ Delatolla R., Tufenkji N., Comeau Y., Lamarre D., Gadbois A., Berk D.. (2009). In situ characterization of nitrifying biofilm: Minimizing biomass loss and preserving perspective. *Water Res.* 43 (6), 1775–1787. doi: 10.1016/j.watres.2009.01.009

productivity values observed in studies evaluating the biofloc monoculture of *L. vannamei* in pilot scale^{56,57}. These authors obtained yields close to 4.1 kg m⁻³.

Even underfed tilapia showed zootechnical performance similar to that reported for tilapia culture in biofloc system. Zaki et al.⁵⁸ showed an average final weight of 115 g for tilapia at a density of 60 fish m⁻³ for 84 days, with an initial weight of 50 grams. Malpartida Pasco et al.⁵⁹, on the other hand, observed productivity of 21 kg m⁻³ in tanks of 10m³ growing tilapia at the density of 70 fish m⁻³ for 56 days in a biofloc system.

The FCR obtained for shrimp was similar to other studies with monoculture of *L. vannamei* in biofloc systems^{60, 61}. In this present study, it is worth noting the low FCR values of tilapia, which were below 1.0 in both T65 (0.7 ± 0.04) and T35 (0.7 ± 0.03) treatments. This indicates that tilapias consumed the natural microbiota present in bioflocs, using it as a substantial part of their diet. A low feed rate was provided to tilapias (1% of biomass), which favored their consumption of bioflocs without impairing their growth despite the low amount of feed provided. A standard feed rate for tilapia in a biofloc system, with an approximate weight of 50 grams, is 3% of wet body weight⁶². The values obtained in the present study are not only beneficial from an environmental point of view, but also economically advantageous as it can decrease production costs due to the reduction of food used (a major cost in terms of production), producing two species at the same time. Environmentally, using less feed implies the generation of effluents with less polluting potential, making aquaculture environmentally friendly

⁵⁶ Krummenauer D., Peixoto S., Cavalli R. O., Poersch L. H., Wasielesky W.. (2011). Superintensive culture of white shrimp, *litopenaeus vannamei*, in a biofloc technology system in southern Brazil at different stocking densities. *J. World Aquacult. Soc.* 42 (5), 726–733. doi: 10.1111/j.1749-7345.2011.00507.x

⁵⁷ Gaona C. A. P., Souza de Almeida M., Viau V., Poersch L. H., Wasielesky W.. (2017). Effect of different total suspended solids levels on a *litopenaeus vannamei* (Boone 1931) BFT culture system during biofloc formation. *Aquacult. Res.* 48 (3), 1070–1079. doi: 10.1111/are.12949

⁵⁸ Zaki M. A. A., Alabssawy A. N., Nour A. E. A. M., El Basuini M. F., Dawood M. A. O., Alkahtani S., et al. (2020). The impact of stocking density and dietary carbon sources on the growth, oxidative status and stress markers of Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) reared under biofloc conditions. *Aquacult. Rep.* 16 (January), 100282. doi: 10.1016/j.aqrep.2020.100282

⁵⁹ Malpartida Pasco J. J., Carvalho Filho J. W., de Espirito Santo C. M., Vinatea L.. (2018). Production of Nile tilapia *oreochromis niloticus* grown in BFT using two aeration systems. *Aquacult. Res.* 49 (1), 222–231. doi: 10.1111/are.13451

⁶⁰ Lara G., Honda M., Poersch L., Wasielesky W.. (2017). The use of biofilm and different feeding rates in biofloc culture system: the effects in shrimp growth parameters. *Aquacult. Int.* 25 (5), 1959–1970. doi: 10.1007/s10499-017-0151-0

⁶¹ Reis W. G., Wasielesky W., Abreu P. C., Brandão H., Krummenauer D.. (2019). Rearing of the pacific white shrimp *litopenaeus vannamei* (Boone 1931) in BFT system with different photoperiods: Effects on the microbial community, water quality and zootechnical performance. *Aquaculture* 508 (February), 19–29. doi: 10.1016/j.aquaculture.2019.04.067

⁶² Zaki M. A. A., Alabssawy A. N., Nour A. E. A. M., El Basuini M. F., Dawood M. A. O., Alkahtani S., et al. (2020). The impact of stocking density and dietary carbon sources on the growth, oxidative status and stress markers of Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) reared under biofloc conditions. *Aquacult. Rep.* 16 (January), 100282. doi: 10.1016/j.aqrep.2020.100282

and socially acceptable^{63,64}. Ekasari et al.⁶⁵ showed the consumption of bioflocs by red tilapia, regardless of the size of the fish. The same study also showed that the absorption capacity is 39 to 117 g of TSS/kg of fish. Poli et al.⁶⁶ also found low FCR values (around 0.2) for Nile tilapia in integrated cultivation with *L. vannamei*, proving the tilapia's potential to consume the excess solids produced by the shrimp. These results indicate that tilapias can feed on bioflocs and the integration of the two species in an IMTA system could be implemented to warrant a more sustainable culture system.

Even with the integration of the fish in the system, it was necessary to remove the excess of total suspended solids through sedimentation process. The sedimentation time was different in the two treatments, with T65 being clarified for longer time, probably due to the high total biomass in this treatment. Gaona et al.⁶⁷ performed clarification during 58 ± 12.2 h in a monoculture of *L. vannamei* with a density of 350 shrimp m⁻², with an initial weight of 0.18 ± 0.06 g for 17 weeks. These data highlight that tilapias could contribute to the management of TSS, since the stocking density of shrimp used in the present study were higher than the reported previously by the authors. In the present study, the lower density of tilapia in T35 required less clarification time (36 ± 12 h), which corroborates that higher stocking densities of fish could contribute with the excess of organic matter in the water, hence increasing the TSS. In addition, the clarification time in T35 was shorter than that reported by Gaona et al.⁶⁷ for *L. vannamei* monoculture at a lower density than the present study. In this study, it was observed that in treatment T65, where there was a greater biomass of fish, longer time of clarification were needed, which indicates that the system produced more TSS compared to treatment T35. Similar results were observed by Zaki et al.⁶² in a monoculture of tilapia in biofloc systems, showing that the increase in biofloc volume was directly proportional to the increase in stocking density.

Azim and Little⁶⁸ reported a difficulty in maintaining TSS levels at 500 mg L⁻¹ even using a clarifier and often the level reached exceeded 1000 mg L⁻¹ TSS, growing tilapia from 80 to 120 grams and density of 12 kg m⁻³. The consumption of bioflocs by fish depends on the species cultivated, the feeding habits

⁶³ Tacon A. G. J., Metian M. (2008). Global overview on the use of fish meal and fish oil in industrially compounded aquafeeds: Trends and future prospects. *Aquaculture* 285 (1–4), 146–158. doi: 10.1016/j.aquaculture.2008.08.015

⁶⁴ Naylor R. L., Hardy R. W., Bureau D. P., Chiu A., Elliott M., Farrell A. P., et al. (2009). Feeding aquaculture in an era of finite resources. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.* 106 (36), 15103–15110. doi: 10.1073/pnas.0905235106

⁶⁵ Ekasari J., Angela D., Waluyo S. H., Bachtiar T., Surawidjaja E. H., Bossier P., et al. (2014). The size of biofloc determines the nutritional composition and the nitrogen recovery by aquaculture animals. *Aquaculture* 426–427 (April), 105–111. doi: 10.1016/j.aquaculture.2014.01.023

⁶⁶ Poli M. A., Legarda E. C., de Lorenzo M. A., Martins M. A., do Nascimento Vieira F.. (2019). Pacific white shrimp and Nile tilapia integrated in a biofloc system under different fish-stocking densities. *Aquaculture* 498 (August 2018), 83–89. doi: 10.1016/j.aquaculture.2018.08.045

⁶⁷ Gaona C. A. P., Serra da F. P., Furtado P. S., Poersch L. H., Wasielesky W.. (2016). Biofloc management with different flow rates for solids removal in the *litopenaeus vannamei* BFT culture system. *Aquacult. Int.* 24 (5), 1263–1275. doi: 10.1007/s10499-016-9983-2

⁶⁸ Azim M. E., Verdegem M. C. J., Mantingh I., Van Dam A.A., Beveridge M. C. M.. (2003). Ingestion and utilization of periphyton grown on artificial substrates by Nile tilapia, *oreochromis niloticus* L. *Aquacult. Res.* 34 (1), 85–92. doi: 10.1046/j.1365-2109.2003.00802.x

of the fish, and the size and density of bioflocs. It is possible that the consumption of bioflocs by fish also depends on the presence and rate of feed added to the tank. Therefore, new studies with different biomass ratios of shrimp and fish should be encouraged.

Most studies of IMTA cultures of *L. vannamei* and tilapia have worked with low shrimp densities (10 to 120 shrimp m⁻²)^{69, 70, 71} and few are the studies of IMTA cultures in super-intensive densities. Poli et al.⁷² observed shrimp yields of up to 4 kg m⁻³ in the integrated culture of shrimp, Nile tilapia and *Sarocornia ambigua* on a laboratory scale. Our work provides useful information for implementing biofloc cultures with shrimp and fish in integrated farming systems, diversifying production without loss in performance of the target species, which in the present study are the shrimp. From the productive perspective, the data presented here encourage the development of integrated shrimp and tilapia harvests in a biofloc system, in tanks on land.

The results obtained in the present study lead to the conclusion that the integrated culture of *L. vannamei* and *O. niloticus* in super-intensive systems using biofloc is possible, allowing the reduction of fish feeding rates without negatively influencing their growth. When higher densities of tilapia are used (65 fish m³), there is an increase in the total suspended solids concentrations in the water, also increasing the clarification time required to keep these concentrations within the levels suitable for the species. This study, on a pilot scale, proves that the IMTA systems of tilapia with *L. vannamei* based on bioflocs diversifies production without compromising the productivity of shrimp.

5.2. Responses of Oyster *Crassostrea gasar* exposed to bioflocs (Experiment 2)

5.2.1. Introduction

The integration of filter-feeding species, such as the oyster *Crassostrea gasar*, into multi-trophic biofloc cultures provides mutual benefits: increased productivity, a reduced organic load in the system, and a

⁶⁹ Yuan D., Yi Y., Yakupitiyage A., Fitzimmons K., Diana J. S. (2010). Effects of addition of red tilapia (*Oreochromis* spp.) at different densities and sizes on production, water quality and nutrient recovery of intensive culture of white shrimp (*Litopenaeus vannamei*) in cement tanks. *Aquaculture* 298 (3–4), 226–238. doi: 10.1016/j.aquaculture.2009.11.011

⁷⁰ Muangkeow B., Ikejima K., Powtongsook S., Yi Y.. (2011). Growth and nutrient conversion of white shrimp *litopenaeus vannamei* (Boone) and Nile tilapia *oreochromis niloticus* L. in an integrated closed recirculating system. *Aquacult. Res.* 42 (9), 1246–1260. doi: 10.1111/j.1365-2109.2010.02713.x

⁷¹ Simão B. R., et al. (2013). Stocking densities and feeding strategies in shrimp and tilapia polyculture in tanks. *Pesquisa Agropecuaria Bras.* 48 (8), 1088–1095. doi: 10.1590/S0100-204X2013000800039

⁷² Poli M. A., Legarda E. C., de Lorenzo M. A., Martins M. A., Seiffert W. Q., do Nascimento Vieira F., et al. (2019). Integrated multitrophic aquaculture applied to shrimp rearing in a biofloc system. *Aquaculture* 511, 1–6. doi: 10.1016/j.aquaculture.2019.734274

constant natural food source for the oysters. The inclusion of molluscs in integrated farming has gradually increased, with a view of using more sustainable and productive crops. According to the FAO⁷³ molluscs are the second most produced group, with the *Crassostrea* genus in first place, representing a group of economic interest with rising production. In addition to profitability, the use of more sustainable systems has been gaining ground in aquaculture, with Lima et al.⁷⁴ showing that the integration of the *Crassostrea sp.* oyster in the cultivation of white shrimp provided lower concentrations of settleable solids and better performance of the species compared with monoculture. The key to a successful integrated system lies in achieving the appropriate species composition as well as ensuring that waste from the feeding species can be utilized by species that consume organic material and that the selected species are tolerant to the conditions of the culture system.

When it comes to integrating species such as oysters that consume fine particulate organic material into biofloc system cultures, uncertainties arise regarding the physiological responses of these bivalves to high solid concentrations in this system. It is not definitively known whether the increased availability of solids might diminish the oysters' filtration potential or even induce stress that could lower their performance. This is because studies involving the optimal concentrations of total suspended solids in bivalve cultures are still limited⁷⁴ [2]. The biological responses caused by environmental stress can affect various levels of organization, ranging from the cellular level to the entire population⁷⁵. This occurs as an attempt to overcome challenges and aid the organism in returning to its normal physiological state⁷⁶. However, these responses can lead to negative consequences, including reduced resilience, impacts on growth and reproduction, and heightened susceptibility to diseases.

However, defining the state of well-being of sessile bivalve molluscs is not a simple task. Indicators can be as conspicuous as the mortality of individuals or as subtle as alterations in the activities of biomolecules, such as enzymes. Enhancing the understanding of the physiological and behavioural reactions of molluscs is crucial for mitigating losses in aquaculture systems⁷⁷.

⁷³ .FAO. The State of the World Fisheries and Aquaculture—2022 (SOFIA); FAO: Rome, Italy, 2022; ISBN 9789251072257

⁷⁴ Lima, P.C.M.; Silva, A.E.M.; Silva, D.A.; Silva, S.M.B.C.; Brito, L.O.; Gálvez, A.O. Effect of stocking density of *Crassostrea sp.* in a multitrophic biofloc system with *Litopenaeus vannamei* in nursery. *Aquaculture* 2021, 530, 735913.

⁷⁵ Iwama, G.K.; Afonso, L.O.B.; Todgham, A.; Ackerman, P.; Nakano, K. Are hsps suitable for indicating stressed states in fish? *J. Exp. Biol.* 2004, 207, 15–19.

⁷⁶ Afonso, L.O.B. Identifying and managing maladaptive physiological responses to aquaculture stressors. *Fish Physiol.* 2020, 38, 163–191.

⁷⁷ Coates, C.J.; Söderhäll, K. The stress–immunity axis in shellfish. *J. Invertebr. Pathol.* 2021, 186, 107492.

In this context, to comprehend the condition of animals in aquaculture environments, a range of analyses can be employed as indicators of environmental comfort⁷⁸. Monitoring the oyster valve opening behaviour through biosensors, oxidative stress biomarkers, and the histological examination of oyster gills are some of the methods utilized to observe animal behaviour and health. The utilization of biosensors allows for the analysis of organism behaviour in response to environmental changes, providing a swift, sensitive, and cost effective approach^{79, 80, 81}. The opening and closing movements of bivalve shells are closely linked to vital activities and environmental conditions⁸⁰, making the monitoring of this movement instrumental in understanding behavioural patterns influenced by environmental characteristics^{82, 83}.

The development of biosensors based on the behavioural analysis of bivalve molluscs has been explored; these biosensors are sensitive tools for detecting pollutants and physicochemical conditions of interest, as well as their impacts on ecosystem services⁸⁴. In terms of behavioural analysis, Le Moullac et al.⁸⁵ emphasized the measurement of valve activity (shell opening and closing) as a potentially valuable tool for biologically monitoring water quality and comprehending metabolic optimization strategies. Likewise, Andrewartha and Elliott⁸⁶ introduced biosensors centred around sentinel animals, combined with the monitoring of environmental variables, as prospective key technologies for managing aquaculture farms.

⁷⁸ Guo, X.; He, Y.; Zhang, L.; Lelong, C.; Jouaux, A. Immune and stress responses in oysters with insights on adaptation. *Fish Shellfish Immunol.* 2015, 46, 107–119.

⁷⁹ Gerhardt, A.; Janssens de Bisthoven, L.; Soares, A.M.V. Evidence for the Stepwise Stress Model: *Gambusia holbrooki* and *Daphnia magna* under Acid Mine Drainage and Acidified Reference Water Stress. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 2005, 39, 4150–4158.

⁸⁰ de Vargas Guterres, B.; da Silveira Guerreiro, A.; Sandrini, J.Z.; da Costa Botelho, S.S. Feasibility of visual signals on the construction

of biosensors based on behavioral analysis of *Perna perna* mussels. *Ecol. Inform.* 2020, 59, 101118

⁸¹ Newton, T.; Gregory Cope, W. Biomarker Responses of Unionid Mussels to Environmental Contaminants. In *Freshwater Bivalve Ecotoxicology*; CRC Press: Boca Raton, FL, USA, 2006; pp. 257–284.

⁸² Comeau, L.A.; Babarro, J.M.F.; Longa, A.; Padin, X.A. Valve-gaping behavior of raft-cultivated mussels in the Ría de Arousa, Spain.

Aquac. Rep. 2018, 9, 68–73.

⁸³ Hartmann, J.T.; Beggel, S.; Auerswald, K.; Geist, J. Determination of the most suitable adhesive for tagging freshwater mussels and its use in an experimental study of filtration behaviour and biological rhythm. *J. Molluscan Stud.* 2016, 82, 415–421.

⁸⁴ Lummer, E.-M.; Auerswald, K.; Geist, J. Fine sediment as environmental stressor affecting freshwater mussel behaviour and ecosystem services. *Sci. Total Environ.* 2016, 571, 1340–1348.

⁸⁵ Le Moullac, G.; Soyez, C.; Lyonard, P.; Chabrier, S.; Milhade, L.; Gueguen, Y.; Beliaeff, B. Non-invasive functional exploration techniques for bivalves with applications to pearl oyster *Pinctada margaritifera*. *Rev. Aquac.* 2020, 12, 1783–1791.

⁸⁶ Andrewartha, S.J.; Elliott, N.G. Aquaculture Sentinels: Smart-farming with Biosensor Equipped Stock. *J. Aquac. Res. Dev.* 2015, 7, 393.

Generally, changes in behaviour associated with bivalves' exposure to harmful algae^{87, 88, 89} and other contaminants include a decrease in mean opening amplitude and an increase in transition frequency. To monitor the amplitude of shell opening in bivalve molluscs, valvometry techniques are employed. Among these techniques, Hall effect sensors in conjunction with magnets offer several advantages, such as durability, lightness, easy attachment, and reduced stress on the animals, which facilitates the measurement of their movements⁸⁸.

In aquaculture, oxidative stress in cultured aquatic organisms can be induced by various conditional factors⁹⁰.

Molecular and biochemical biomarkers have been widely employed to demonstrate the biological responses of organisms to specific environmental conditions⁹¹. They are used to highlight alterations in biomolecules and other aspects of oxidative stress resulting from reactive oxygen species or shifts in redox balance in experimental animals⁹². Sies and Jones⁹³ conceptualized oxidative stress as an imbalance between oxidants and antioxidants in favour of oxidants. This imbalance can lead to changes in redox signalling and control as well as molecular damage. During stressful events, reactive oxygen species are generated^{94, 95}; however, aerobic organisms possess an antioxidant defense system that enables them to manage these species by either neutralizing/intercepting them or repairing the damage they cause^{96, 97}.

Another way of assessing the condition of a cultured animal is through histological analysis, which allows the structure of tissues to be observed through microscopic examination of their components⁹⁸.

⁸⁷ Basti, L.; Nagai, K.; Shimasaki, Y.; Oshima, Y.; Honjo, T.; Segawa, S. Effects of the toxic dinoflagellate *Heterocapsa circularisquama* on the valve movement behaviour of the Manila clam *Ruditapes philippinarum*. *Aquaculture* 2009, 291, 41–47.

⁸⁸ Nagai, K.; Honjo, T.; Go, J.; Yamashita, H.; Oh, S.J. Detecting the shellfish killer *Heterocapsa circularisquama* (Dinophyceae) by measuring bivalve valve activity with a Hall element sensor. *Aquaculture* 2006, 255, 395–401.

⁸⁹ Tran, D.; Haberkorn, H.; Soudant, P.; Ciret, P.; Massabuau, J.-C. Behavioral responses of *Crassostrea gigas* exposed to the harmful algae *Alexandrium minutum*. *Aquaculture* 2010, 298, 338–345.

⁹⁰ da Silva Martins, Á.C.; Artigas Flores, J.; Porto, C.; Wasielesky Junior, W.; Monserrat, J.M. Antioxidant and oxidative damage responses in different organs of Pacific white shrimp *Litopenaeus vannamei* (Boone, 1931) reared in a biofloc technology system. *Mar. Freshw. Behav. Physiol.* 2015, 48, 279–288.

⁹¹ Cogo, A.J.; Siqueira, A.F.; Ramos, A.C.; Cruz, Z.M.; Silva, A.G. Utilização de enzimas do estresse oxidativo como biomarcadoras de impactos ambientais. *Nat. Line* 2009, 7, 37–42.

⁹² Valavanidis, A.; Vlahogianni, T.; Dassenakis, M.; Scoullou, M. Molecular biomarkers of oxidative stress in aquatic organisms in relation to toxic environmental pollutants. *Ecotoxicol. Environ. Saf.* 2006, 64, 178–189.

⁹³ Sies, H.; Jones, D.P. Oxidative stress. In *Encyclopedia of Stress*; Fink, G., Ed.; Elsevier: Amsterdam, The Netherlands, 2007; pp.45–48.

⁹⁴ Jones, D.P. Extracellular Redox State: Refining the Definition of Oxidative Stress in Aging. *Rejuvenation Res.* 2006, 9, 169–181.

⁹⁵ Kunwar, A.; Priyadarsini, K.I. Free radicals, oxidative stress and importance of antioxidants in human health. *J. Med. Allied Sci.* 2011, 1, 53–60.

⁹⁶ Comporti, M.; Signorini, C.; Leoncini, S.; Gardi, C.; Ciccoli, L.; Giardini, A.; Vecchio, D.; Arezzini, B. Ethanol-induced oxidative stress: Basic knowledge. *Genes Nutr.* 2010, 5, 101–109.

⁹⁷ Urso, M.L.; Clarkson, P.M. Oxidative stress, exercise, and antioxidant supplementation. *Toxicology* 2003, 189, 41–54.

⁹⁸ Genten, F.; Terwinghe, E.; Danguy, A. *Atlas of Fish Histology*; Science Publishers: Enfield, NH, USA, 2008.

One of the advantages of this analysis is its ability to provide information on the state of health of the organism at the cellular level⁹⁹. Many tissues can be used in these analyses, but the gills stand out as one of the most important organs for aquatic species.

This study aimed to evaluate the biological responses of *C. gasar* oysters when exposed to different concentrations of total suspended solids in biofloc culture systems on the basis of behavioural, biochemical, and histological analyses of the bivalves. The results obtained will demonstrate the best concentration of solids for the cultivation of *C. gasar* oysters in biofloc systems.

5.2.2. Trial Methodology

The oysters were obtained from a commercial farm in the state of Santa Catarina, Brazil. Upon arrival at the Marine Aquaculture Station (EMA-FURG), they underwent a four-week acclimatization period in the laboratory. During this phase, they were housed in 500 L water tanks filled with filtered seawater (salinity 27) and maintained with continuous aeration. Biofloc water from a marine shrimp farm with a total suspended solids (TSSs) concentration of 100 mg/L was introduced to feed the oysters. The water was completely renewed twice a week. Initially, the oysters' mean weight was 54.18 ± 13.45 g, and they measured 68.2 ± 4.44 mm in mean height, 50.4 ± 3.50 mm in mean length, and 24.1 ± 5.02 mm in mean width.

Water recirculation systems were established comprising one 500 L water reservoir (considered the macrocosm) and three 100 L boxes where the oysters were distributed. The 500 L reservoir was equipped with a pump (Sarlo Better—1000 L/h, São Caetano do Sul, São Paulo, Brazil) that circulated water to the three 100 L boxes, and through gravity, the water returned to the 500 L reservoir. Throughout the experiment, constant water circulation was maintained in the boxes, and aeration was provided via blowers and micro-perforated hoses. Each set consisting of three 100 L boxes and one 500 L reservoir represented one treatment. A suspended screen was placed in each 100 L box to keep the oysters elevated from the bottom of the box (Figure 12). Four times a day, the water in the 100 L boxes was agitated to resuspend the solids that had settled on the box structures.

⁹⁹ Costa, P.M.; Carreira, S.; Costa, M.H.; Caeiro, S. Development of histopathological indices in a commercial marine bivalve (*Ruditapes decussatus*) to determine environmental quality. *Aquat. Toxicol.* 2013, 126, 442–454.

Figure 12. Experimental units (100 L) containing the oysters stored on the screens

The oysters were subjected to varying concentrations of total suspended solids (TSSs) over a 28-day period in order to expose them to the concentrations of solids that can be found in the natural environment¹⁰⁰ and the higher concentrations found in biofloc shrimp farming¹⁰¹. The experiment comprised four treatments involving the exposure of oysters to three distinct TSS concentrations of water sourced from the cultivation of marine shrimps in a mature biofloc system (with the presence of nitrate). The treatments were as follows: control treatment—oysters were fed with microalgae; low treatment—maintained at a low TSS concentration, approximately 100 mg/L TSSs; medium treatment—maintained at a nominal medium TSS concentration ranging from above 100 to 200 mg/L TSSs; and high treatment—maintained at a nominal high TSS concentration exceeding 200 mg/L TSSs. Each 100 L box represented one repetition of a treatment, resulting in a total of four treatments, each with three repetitions. Each experimental unit initially contained 30 oysters.

To feed the oysters in the control treatment, the diatom *Chaetoceros muelleri* was cultivated in *f/2* media¹⁰² with a salinity of 28, a temperature of 20 °C, and a light intensity of 40 $\mu\text{mol photons/m}^2/\text{s}$ in batch-type cultivation. Cell growth was monitored daily using a Neubauer chamber and an optical microscope. Daily counts of the remaining microalgae's density in the control experimental units were also conducted, and if necessary, aliquots of the microalgae culture were added to maintain a density of 16×10^4 cells/mL in the units. Every two weeks, three oysters were collected from each

¹⁰⁰ Barillé, L.; Prou, J.; Héral, M.; Razet, D. Effects of high natural seston concentrations on the feeding, selection, and absorption of the oyster *Crassostrea gigas* (Thunberg). *J. Exp. Mar. Bio. Ecol.* 1997, 212, 149–172.

¹⁰¹ Gaona, C.A.P.; de Almeida, M.S.; Viau, V.; Poersch, L.H.; Wasielesky, W. Effect of different total suspended solids levels on a *Litopenaeus vannamei* (Boone, 1931) BFT culture system during biofloc formation. *Aquac. Res.* 2017, 48, 1070–1079.

¹⁰² Guillard, R.R.L. Culture of phytoplankton for feeding marine invertebrates. In *Culture of Marine Invertebrate Animals*; Smith, W.L., Chanley, M.H., Eds.; Plenum: New York, NY, USA, 1975; pp. 29–60.

experimental unit for biochemical analysis. At the end of the experiment, two oysters were collected from each experimental unit for histological analysis. For biochemical and histological analysis, the oysters' adductor muscles were cut, the shells were opened, the visceral mass was removed from the shell, and only the gills were collected from the visceral mass for analysis. For biochemical analysis, the samples were stored at $-80\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, and for the histological analysis, the samples were stored in a 20% saline formalin solution.

Total suspended solids (TSSs) were measured twice a week using gravimetry, following a methodology adapted from AOAC¹⁰³ with adjustments made in accordance with treatment definitions. As needed, concentrated flake water was introduced to maintain the concentrations in the biofloc treatments. This matured floc, containing nitrate, originated from an ongoing marine shrimp culture and was stored in a 1000 L water tank with continuous aeration. The dissolved oxygen level was 8.6 ± 0.68 mg/L, the total alkalinity was 240 ± 20.8 mg CaCO_3/L , and the TSS concentration was 1460 ± 15.2 mg/L.

In the 100 L boxes where the oysters were stored, the following analyses were carried out twice a week. Settleable solids (SSs) were measured by an Imhoff Cone¹⁰⁴, and turbidity was measured by a portable turbidimeter (2100P, Hach®, Loveland, CO, USA). Temperature and oxygen were measured daily in the early morning and late afternoon using a multiparameter probe e (model Pro-20, YSI Inc., Yellow Springs, OH, USA). The pH reading was also taken daily in the morning by a bench pH meter (Seven2Go S7 Básico, Mettler Toledo, São Paulo, Brazil). Oyster mortality was observed daily.

Salinity, total alkalinity, ammonia, nitrite, nitrate, and phosphate were checked twice a week. Salinity was measured with an optical refractometer. Alkalinity was measured according to APHA¹⁰⁵, ammonia was measured according to UNESCO¹⁰⁶, and nitrite was measured according to Strickland and Parsons¹⁰⁷. When total alkalinity values were below 150 mg CaCO_3/L , they were adjusted with calcium hydroxide according to Furtado et al.¹⁰⁸. Nitrate and phosphate were measured 1x/week according to the methodology of Aminot and Chaussepied¹⁰⁹.

¹⁰³ AOAC. Official Methods of Analysis of the AOAC, 14th ed.; AOAC International: Washington, DC, USA, 1999.

¹⁰⁴ Avnimelech, Y. Feeding with microbial flocs by tilapia in minimal discharge bio-flocs technology ponds. *Aquaculture* 2007, 264, 140–147.

¹⁰⁵ APHA. Standard Methods for the Examination of Water and Waste Water, 16th ed.; American Public Health Association, AWWA, WPCF: New York, NY, USA, 1989.

¹⁰⁶ UNESCO. Chemical Methods for Use in Marine Environmental Monitoring. Manual and Guides 12; Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission: Paris, France, 1983.

¹⁰⁷ Strickland, J.D.H.; Parsons, T.R. A Practical Handbook of Seawater Analysis, 2nd ed.; Fisheries research board of Canada: Ottawa, ON, Canada, 1972.

¹⁰⁸ Furtado, P.S.; Poersch, L.H.; Wasielesky, W. The effect of different alkalinity levels on *Litopenaeus vannamei* reared with biofloc technology (BFT). *Aquac. Int.* 2015, 23, 345–358.

¹⁰⁹ Aminot, A.; Chaussepied, M. Manuel des Analyses Chimiques en Milieu Marin; Centre National Pour L'exploitation des Océans: Brest, France, 1983.

Oyster valve activity was monitored using Hall effect sensors, following the methodology outlined by Guterres et al.¹¹⁰. The Hall effect sensor was affixed to the upper valve using epoxy resin (Araldite 5 min)¹¹¹, while neodymium magnets were attached to the lower valve using cyanoacrylate glue^{112,113,114}. The choice of glue was informed by existing literature, along with the study conducted by Hartmann et al.¹¹¹, which evaluated the performance (mechanical strength and fixation time) of different substances in constructing biosensors based on bivalve behavioural analysis. The sensors were made waterproof using epoxy resin and linked to the electronic system via 3-way cables.

Positioned on opposing sides of the shell (see Figure 13), these sensors registered the oyster's opening by detecting their movement away from each other. The opening amplitudes for each individual were expressed as percentages, considering the maximum and minimum values recorded throughout the experiment¹¹⁵. The sensors were linked to an Arduino MEGA board and a computer to enable real-time recording of oyster openings throughout the experiment. The simultaneous connection of all sensors to the acquisition system was facilitated by employing two multiplexer boards, each with 16 channels. Within each experimental unit, 4 oysters were equipped with sensors, resulting in 12 sensor equipped oysters per treatment and a total of 48 oysters in the experiment. Data were recorded using an SD memory card module.

¹¹⁰ de Vargas Guterres, B.; da Silveira Guerreiro, A.; Sandrini, J.Z.; da Costa Botelho, S.S. Feasibility of visual signals on the construction of biosensors based on behavioral analysis of *Perna perna* mussels. *Ecol. Inform.* 2020, 59, 101118

¹¹¹ Hartmann, J.T.; Beggel, S.; Auerswald, K.; Geist, J. Determination of the most suitable adhesive for tagging freshwater mussels and its use in an experimental study of filtration behaviour and biological rhythm. *J. Molluscan Stud.* 2016, 82, 415–421.

¹¹² Comeau, L.A.; Babarro, J.M.F.; Longa, A.; Padin, X.A. Valve-gaping behavior of raft-cultivated mussels in the Ría de Arousa, Spain. *Aquac. Rep.* 2018, 9, 68–73.

¹¹³ Basti, L.; Nagai, K.; Shimasaki, Y.; Oshima, Y.; Honjo, T.; Segawa, S. Effects of the toxic dinoflagellate *Heterocapsa circularisquama* on the valve movement behaviour of the Manila clam *Ruditapes philippinarum*. *Aquaculture* 2009, 291, 41–47.

¹¹⁴ Nagai, K.; Honjo, T.; Go, J.; Yamashita, H.; Oh, S.J. Detecting the shellfish killer *Heterocapsa circularisquama* (Dinophyceae) by measuring bivalve valve activity with a Hall element sensor. *Aquaculture* 2006, 255, 395–401.

¹¹⁵ Clements, J.C.; Poirier, L.A.; Pérez, F.F.; Comeau, L.A.; Babarro, J.M.F. Behavioural responses to predators in Mediterranean mussels (*Mytilus galloprovincialis*) are unaffected by elevated pCO₂. *Mar. Environ. Res.* 2020, 161, 105148.

Figure 13. Positioning of the Hall sensor and magnet on the right and left valves, respectively, of *C. gasar* oysters

The acquisition system captured two readings per second (2 Hz) in bytes. These bytes were then converted into percentages of open state (%) on the basis of the individual oyster's lowest (0%) and highest (100%) observed values. To analyze the extensive volume of readings gathered during the experiment effectively, the average openings were computed every 1 min. Consequently, the behavioural data collected over the course of 24 h were represented by 1440 observations. To facilitate data organization, this work designated oyster opening levels as follows: closed for 0% opening, slightly open for openings ranging from 0.1% to 25%, moderately open for 25.1% to 50%, open for 50.1% to 75%, and fully open for 75.1% to 100% openings.

After freezing in an ultrafreezer, the gills of the *C. gasar* oysters were homogenized according to Bebianno et al.¹¹⁶ in a chilled buffer solution (TRIS-HCl 50 mM, EDTA 1 mM, sucrose 0.5 M, DTT 1 mM, KCl 0.15 M, PMSF 0.1 M), adjusted to pH 7.6, at a ratio of 1:5 (w/v). Subsequently, the tissue was centrifuged for 30 min at 4 °C and 10,000× *g*, and the resulting supernatant was collected and stored at -80 °C for the analysis of enzyme activity, including glutathione S-transferase (GST), catalase (CAT), and superoxide dismutase (SOD) activity, along with total antioxidant capacity against peroxy radicals (ACAP) and peroxidized lipids (TBARS). For the assessment of reduced glutathione (GSH) and protein-associated sulfhydryl groups (P-SH), the same solution was employed, excluding DTT, and the same protocol as the other analyses was followed.

To determine the total protein in the tissues (gills), the Bradford method¹¹⁷ was adopted using a Sensiprot commercial kit and a microplate reader (BioTek LX 800, Winooski, Vermont, USA). For the analysis of GST enzyme activity, the methodology of Habig et al.¹¹⁸ was adopted, in which the increase in the CDNB-GSH product formed from the consumption of GSH in the presence of the extracts of the tissue samples and 0.1 M potassium phosphate buffer solution at pH 7.0 was monitored. The analysis was performed in a microplate reader at a temperature of 25 °C with a wavelength of 340 nm. The units used were nmol of CDNB per mg of protein per minute.

¹¹⁶ Bebianno, M.J.; Mello, A.C.P.; Serrano, M.A.S.; Flores-Nunes, F.; Mattos, J.J.; Zacchi, F.L.; Piazza, C.E.; Siebert, M.N.; Piazza, R.S.; Gomes, C.H.A.M.; et al. Transcriptional and cellular effects of paracetamol in the oyster *Crassostrea gigas*. *Ecotoxicol. Environ. Saf.* 2017, 144, 258–267.

¹¹⁷ Bradford, M.M. A rapid and sensitive method for the quantitation of microgram quantities of protein utilizing the principle of protein-dye binding. *Anal. Biochem.* 1976, 72, 248–254.

¹¹⁸ Habig, W.H.; Pabst, M.J.; Jakoby, W.B. Glutathione S-Transferases. *J. Biol. Chem.* 1974, 249, 7130–7139.

For catalase (CAT), the methodology described by Beutler¹¹⁹ was adopted, in which the consumption of hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) in the presence of the samples was recorded in a spectrophotometer at 240 nm, pH 8.0, and a temperature of 25 °C. The units adopted were μmol of H₂O₂ per min and per mg of protein, which are expressed as CAT units. The analysis of reduced glutathione (GSH) levels was performed using the protocol described by Sedlak and Lindsay¹²⁰. Samples were adjusted to a concentration of 2 mg of protein per mL, followed by the addition of 50% (w/v) trichloroacetic acid (TCA) and centrifugation at 20,000 $\times g$ for 10 min at 4 °C to precipitate the proteins. The resulting supernatant was collected for GSH analysis and mixed with 0.4 M Tris-base buffer at pH 8.9 along with DTNB. Following a 15 min incubation, the mixture was read at 405 nm for subsequent analysis. The units used for measurement were μmol of GSH per mg of protein. The pellet was collected, resuspended in homogenization buffer, and then treated with 0.2 M Tris-base at pH 8.2 and DTNB. After another 15 min incubation, the mixture was read at 405 nm to assess P-SH levels, with the unit of measurement of μmol of P-SH groups per mg of protein. Lipid peroxidation levels (TBARS) were determined using the methodology outlined by Oakes and Van Der Kraak¹²¹. This method involves the reaction of lipid peroxidation byproducts with thiobarbituric acid (TBA) under conditions of high temperature and acidity, leading to the generation of a chromogen that can be detected through fluorimetry (excitation at 520 nm and emission at 580 nm). The units of measurement used were nmol of malondialdehyde (MDA) per mg of protein. The assessment of total antioxidant capacity against peroxy radicals (ACAP) was conducted in accordance with the methodology established by Amado et al.¹²². This involved quantifying the reactive oxygen species (ROS) in the samples, both treated and untreated, with a peroxy radical generator. The samples were adjusted to a concentration of 2 mg of protein per mL and exposed to peroxy radicals, which reacted with a fluorescent substrate (H₂DCF-DA). Using fluorimetry, with excitation at 485 nm and emission at 520 nm, readings were taken on a microplate reader at 5 min intervals over a 35 min period. The results were expressed as an area relative to the difference between the area of ROS with ABAP (2,2-azobis (2-methylpropionamide) dichloride) and the area of ROS without ABAP. In terms of results interpretation, a larger relative area indicated a lower antioxidant capacity. The SOD (superoxide dismutase) activity in the oyster gills was

¹¹⁹ Beutler, E. The preparation of red cells for assay. In *Red Cell Metabolism: A Manual of Biochemical Methods*; Beutler, E., Ed.; Grune & Straton: New York, NY, USA, 1975; pp. 8–18.

¹²⁰ Sedlak, J.; Lindsay, R.H. Estimation of total, protein-bound, and nonprotein sulfhydryl groups in tissue with Ellman's reagent. *Anal. Biochem.* 1968, 25, 192–205.

¹²¹ Oakes, K.D.; Van Der Kraak, G.J. Utility of the TBARS assay in detecting oxidative stress in white sucker (*Catostomus commersoni*) populations exposed to pulp mill effluent. *Aquat. Toxicol.* 2003, 63, 447–463.

¹²² Amado, L.L.; Garcia, M.L.; Ramos, P.B.; Freitas, R.F.; Zafalon, B.; Ferreira, J.L.R.; Yunes, J.S.; Monserrat, J.M. A method to measure total antioxidant capacity against peroxy radicals in aquatic organisms: Application to evaluate microcystins toxicity. *Sci. Total Environ.* 2009, 407, 2115–2123.

evaluated following the methods described by McCord and Fridovich¹²³ and Bainy et al.¹²⁴. The reduction of cytochrome c absorbance at a wavelength of 550 nm was measured in a potassium phosphate buffer at pH 7.8. The specific activity of the SOD enzyme is expressed as SOD activity per mg of total protein.

At the end of the experiment, 6 oyster samples were collected from each treatment, resulting in a total of 24 oysters. After opening the oysters, the visceral mass was extracted and preserved in 20% formalin saline. Subsequently, only the gills were removed from the visceral mass for analysis. The samples underwent a dehydration process using increasing ethanol concentrations in sequence, followed by clarification in xylene, and were subsequently embedded in Paraplast® using an automatic tissue processor (PT 05, LUPETEC, São Carlos, Brazil). Sections with a thickness of 5 µm were prepared using a microtome (MRP03, LUPETEC, Brazil), stained with hematoxylin and eosin (H&E), and examined using an optical microscope (ZEISS Primo Star) at magnifications of 4× and 40×. The analysis of the gills was qualitative, involving the observation of structures and the identification of any damage. For histochemical assessment, specialized staining with periodic acid-Schiff (PAS) dye was employed, whereby PAS-positive structures were stained in magenta/red¹²⁵.

The statistical analysis of water quality parameters, including pH, turbidity, alkalinity, salinity, ammonia, nitrite, nitrate, and phosphate, was conducted using one-way ANOVA. Assumptions of normality and homoscedasticity were verified using the Shapiro–Wilk and Levene tests, respectively¹²⁶. If these assumptions were not met, the data were subjected to logarithmic transformation. For oxygen, temperature, suspended solids (SS), and total suspended solids (TSS) parameters, the non-parametric Kruskal–Wallis test was employed.

Regarding the statistical analysis of oyster valve activity monitored by the Hall sensor, two separate analyses were carried out. Initially, descriptive statistics were performed, and subsequently, a non-parametric Kruskal–Wallis analysis was conducted to assess the mean opening values within each treatment. The second analysis involved creating a frequency table for the data, categorizing them according to their opening level within each treatment and per week of the experiment. The non-parametric Kruskal–Wallis analysis was then performed to compare the values of each opening level across the weeks. For the statistical analysis of biochemical parameters, including GST, CAT, SOD, GSH, P-SH, TBARS, and ACAP, a two-way ANOVA utilizing parametric statistics was conducted. This analysis

¹²³ McCord, J.M.; Fridovich, I. Superoxide Dismutase. *J. Biol. Chem.* 1969, 244, 6049–6055.

¹²⁴ Bainy, A.C.D.; Saito, E.; Carvalho, P.S.M.; Junqueira, V.B.C. Oxidative stress in gill, erythrocytes, liver and kidney of Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) from a polluted site. *Aquat. Toxicol.* 1996, 34, 151–162.

¹²⁵ Genten, F.; Terwinghe, E.; Danguy, A. *Atlas of Fish Histology*; Science Publishers: Enfield, NH, USA, 2008.

¹²⁶ Zar, J.H. *Biostatistical Analysis*, 5th ed.; Prentice Hall: Upper Saddle River, NJ, USA, 2010.

considered both the cultivation time and the treatment as factors. The assumptions underlying the analysis were assessed using the Shapiro–Wilk and Levene tests. Whenever necessary, mathematical transformations were applied to the data. Significant differences were determined at a significance level of $p < 0.05$, followed by Newman–Keuls post hoc testing for multiple comparisons. Across the experiment results, data are presented as mean values accompanied by standard deviation. The statistical software employed for analysis was Statistica 12. Microsoft Excel was utilized for the generation of tables, while PrismGraph software was utilized for the creation of graphs. A consistent significance level of 5% was adopted for all conducted tests.

5.2.3. Results

The parameters of dissolved oxygen, salinity, alkalinity, and ammonia did not show significant differences between the different treatments applied in this experiment (Table 3). Temperature, pH, nitrite, nitrate, and phosphate exhibited significant differences between the treatments. For pH and nitrite, the control treatment displayed significant differences ($p < 0.05$) compared with the low, medium, and high treatments, but no differences were found between the latter three treatments. Temperature values were significantly lower in the medium and high treatments. Nitrate levels showed the lowest means in the control, low, and medium treatments, while the high treatment had the highest mean, which was not significantly different from the medium treatment. Phosphate levels were higher in the medium and high treatments compared with the control and low treatments. The low treatment showed no significant differences compared with the control for these parameters, but its mean values were lower than those of the medium and high treatments. The high treatment had higher mean values than the medium treatment, in line with the experimental design.

Table 3. Water quality parameters with mean values and standard deviation over the 28 days of cultivation in the treatments: control—oysters fed with microalgae; low treatment—100 mg/L total suspended solids (TSSs); medium treatment—from 100 to 200 mg/L TSSs; high treatment—above 200 mg/L TSSs

Parameters	Treatments			
	Control	Low	Medium	High
Oxygen (mg/L)	6.83 ± 0.67	6.65 ± 0.62	6.84 ± 0.64	6.79 ± 0.63
Temperature (°C)	20.76 ± 1.83 ^a	20.64 ± 1.51 ^a	19.40 ± 1.79 ^b	20.07 ± 1.43 ^b
pH	8.21 ± 0.05 ^b	8.31 ± 0.06 ^a	8.31 ± 0.05 ^a	8.32 ± 0.05 ^a
SS (mL/L)	0.00 ± 0.00 ^a	0.06 ± 0.12 ^a	1.78 ± 2.00 ^b	5.65 ± 4.62 ^c
TSS (mg/L)	83.04 ± 29.18 ^a	71.27 ± 44.74 ^a	189.88 ± 120.15 ^b	291.38 ± 98.26 ^c
Turbidity (NUT)	22.74 ± 18.17 ^a	33.30 ± 35.02 ^a	108.29 ± 72.43 ^b	259.22 ± 142.88 ^c
Alkalinity (mg CaCO ₃ /L)	146.11 ± 10.54	167.22 ± 25.51	173.33 ± 21.94	173.33 ± 41.53
Salinity	33.63 ± 2.39	32.38 ± 1.41	31.63 ± 1.69	32.00 ± 1.07
Ammonia (mg/L)	0.17 ± 0.13	0.09 ± 0.04	0.08 ± 0.04	0.11 ± 0.04
Nitrite (mg/L)	0.65 ± 0.60 ^b	0.07 ± 0.06 ^a	0.12 ± 0.18 ^a	0.13 ± 0.11 ^a
Nitrate (mg/L)	9.56 ± 4.42 ^a	10.87 ± 4.85 ^a	17.20 ± 5.55 ^{ab}	20.76 ± 8.56 ^b
Phosphate (mg/L)	2.64 ± 1.14 ^a	3.80 ± 0.87 ^a	6.76 ± 2.05 ^b	6.50 ± 0.84 ^b

Different letters represent a significant difference ($p \leq 0.05$) between treatments.

For mean valve opening values across each week within each treatment, no significant differences ($p > 0.05$) were observed between treatments during week 1 and week 4. However, significant differences ($p < 0.05$) emerged during weeks 2 and 3 of the experiment, as indicated in Table 4. During week 2, a significant difference ($p < 0.05$) was observed. The control and medium treatments had a greater number of fully open oysters compared with the high treatment. In week 3, differences ($p < 0.05$) between treatments were observed across three ranges of oyster opening: closed, slightly open, and fully open. Notably, the high treatment exhibited a higher occurrence of closed oysters than the control treatment. Furthermore, the medium treatment had a higher frequency of slightly open oysters compared with the high treatment, while the high treatment had a lower frequency of fully open oysters compared with the control treatment. Overall, it is evident that closed oysters predominated in all treatments during the four weeks of cultivation. The second most frequent opening range was fully open, followed by open. The medium open level represented the opening range with the lowest number of records in terms of percentage.

The activities of the enzymes GST and CAT did not exhibit significant differences ($p \geq 0.05$) between the various treatments throughout the experiment, as depicted in Figures 14 and 15, respectively.

Table 4. The frequency distribution (in %) of valve opening values for *C. gasar* oysters over the four weeks of culture in the control, low, medium, and high treatments. Control treatment: oysters fed with microalgae. Low treatment: 100 mg/L total suspended solids (TSSs). Medium treatment: ranging from 100 to 200 mg/L TSSs. High treatment: exceeding 200 mg/L TSSs

Opening Range of Oyster Valves						
Treatment	Week	Closed	Slightly Open	Moderately Open	Open	Fully Open
Control	1	64.54 ± 7.15	0.20 ± 0.45	0.90 ± 0.67	7.06 ± 4.89	27.30 ± 7.25
Low	1	73.23 ± 5.88	0.02 ± 0.02	1.90 ± 1.23	6.78 ± 2.93	18.07 ± 7.79
Medium	1	64.32 ± 7.81	0.24 ± 0.48	0.95 ± 0.71	7.51 ± 5.20	26.97 ± 7.89
High	1	60.86 ± 14.36	0.00 ± 0.00	0.89 ± 0.53	6.40 ± 2.80	31.84 ± 14.02
Control	2	39.35 ± 22.57	0.00 ± 0.00	0.18 ± 0.29	3.87 ± 3.48	56.60 ± 20.75 ^{ab}
Low	2	64.80 ± 26.72	0.07 ± 0.07	0.69 ± 0.60	4.45 ± 2.95	30.00 ± 25.67 ^{bc}
Medium	2	31.01 ± 10.75	0.00 ± 0.00	0.13 ± 0.28	4.37 ± 3.64	64.40 ± 9.03 ^a
High	2	65.04 ± 20.13	0.11 ± 0.13	5.39 ± 10.55	18.00 ± 25.16	11.47 ± 9.71 ^c
Control	3	66.97 ± 15.14 ^a	0.03 ± 0.02 ^{ab}	1.17 ± 1.02	3.77 ± 3.25	28.05 ± 12.88 ^a
Low	3	79.97 ± 4.93 ^{ab}	0.04 ± 0.01 ^{ab}	0.56 ± 0.71	2.99 ± 2.77	16.44 ± 7.64 ^{ab}
Medium	3	79.67 ± 4.57 ^{ab}	0.12 ± 0.05 ^a	1.23 ± 0.77	4.83 ± 2.95	14.14 ± 2.09 ^{ab}
High	3	85.10 ± 6.29 ^b	0.01 ± 0.01 ^b	0.19 ± 0.12	5.66 ± 8.08	9.04 ± 3.91 ^b
Control	4	56.99 ± 27.22	0.02 ± 0.04	1.45 ± 0.13	10.83 ± 5.04	30.71 ± 28.23
Low	4	65.06 ± 14.52	0.04 ± 0.04	0.94 ± 0.73	6.30 ± 2.66	27.66 ± 15.98
Medium	4	54.10 ± 15.54	0.04 ± 0.07	1.38 ± 0.68	10.60 ± 7.24	33.88 ± 15.81
High	4	52.43 ± 17.72	0.00 ± 0.00	0.57 ± 0.33	8.78 ± 7.76	38.22 ± 10.58

Different lowercase letters in the same row represent significant differences ($p < 0.05$) between treatments.

Figure 14. Specific activity of the enzyme GST (Glutathione S-transferase) in the gills of *C. gasar* oysters in the following treatments: control—oysters fed with microalgae; low treatment—100 mg/L total suspended solids (TSSs); medium treatment—100 to 200 mg/L TSSs; high treatment—TSSs exceeding 200 mg/L over a 28-day experimental period. The bars represent the mean enzyme activity values, and the vertical lines above the bars represent the standard deviation of the values.

Regarding the SOD enzyme, a significant difference ($p < 0.05$) was observed between the treatments on day 28. No differences between treatments were evident on days 1 and 14. On day 28, SOD activity displayed higher values for the high treatment than for the control. Notably, the low and medium treatments did not demonstrate significant differences ($p > 0.05$) from each other or when compared with the high and control treatments (Figure 16).

Figure 15. Specific activity of catalase ($\mu\text{m}/\text{mg}$ protein) in the gills of *C. gasar* oysters in the following treatments: control—oysters fed with microalgae; low treatment—100 mg/L total suspended solids (TSSs); medium treatment—100 to 200 mg/L TSSs; high treatment—TSSs exceeding 200 mg/L over a 28-day experimental period. The bars represent the mean enzyme activity values, and the vertical lines above the bars represent the standard deviation of the values

Figure 16. Specific activity of the SOD enzyme (specific SOD activity/mg protein) in the gills of *C. Gasar* oysters in the following treatments: control—oysters fed with microalgae; low treatment—100 mg/L total suspended solids (TSSs); medium treatment—100 to 200 mg/L TSSs; high treatment—TSSs exceeding 200 mg/L over a 28-day experimental period. The bars represent the mean values, and the vertical lines above the bars represent the standard deviation of the values. Lowercase letters for different days and treatments indicate significant differences ($p < 0.05$)

The concentration of GSH did not show significant differences ($p > 0.05$) between the different treatments during the experiment (Figure 17). No significant differences ($p > 0.05$) emerged between treatments or culture days with respect to the concentration of sulfhydryl groups in the gills of *C. gasar* oysters (Figure 18). Regarding lipid peroxidation, significant differences ($p < 0.05$) between treatments

were observed. No significant differences ($p > 0.05$) in lipid damage were observed between treatments on days 1 and 28. However, on day 14, a substantial increase in lipid damage was noted in the medium and high treatments in comparison to the control group. By contrast, the low treatment did not show significant differences ($p > 0.05$) on day 14 (Figure 19).

In relation to the total antioxidant capacity against peroxy radicals, a significant difference ($p < 0.05$) emerged solely on day 28 between the treatments. Specifically, the high treatment exhibited a greater mean area compared with the control treatment. By contrast, the low and medium treatments did not display differences from each other or from the control or high treatments (Figure 20). A higher mean area in the high treatment signified a reduced total antioxidant capacity.

Figure 17. Concentration of reduced glutathione (GSH) (in nmol/mg protein) in the gills of *C. Gasar* oysters in the following treatments: control—oysters fed with microalgae; low treatment—100 mg/L total suspended solids (TSSs); medium treatment—100 to 200 mg/L TSSs; high treatment—TSSs exceeding 200 mg/L over a 28-day experimental period. The bars represent the mean values, and the vertical lines above the bars represent the standard deviation of the values.

Figure 18. P-SH concentration (in $\text{nmol P-SH/mg protein}$) in the gills of *C. Gasar* oysters in the following treatments: control—oysters fed with microalgae; low treatment—100 mg/L total suspended solids (TSSs);

medium treatment—100 to 200 mg/L TSSs; high treatment—TSSs exceeding 200 mg/L over a 28-day experimental period. The bars represent the mean values, and the vertical lines above the bars represent the standard deviation of the values

Figure 19. Lipid peroxidation (TBARS) (in mmol/mg tissue) in the gills of *C. gasar* oysters in the following treatments: control—oysters fed with microalgae; low treatment—100 mg/L total suspended solids (TSSs); medium treatment—100 to 200 mg/L TSSs; high treatment—TSSs exceeding 200 mg/L over a 28-day experimental period. The bars represent the mean values, and the vertical lines above the bars represent the standard deviation of the values. Lowercase letters for different days and treatments indicate significant differences ($p < 0.05$)

Figure 20. Antioxidant capacity (relative area) in the gills of *C. gasar* oysters in the following treatments: control—oysters fed with microalgae; low treatment—100 mg/L total suspended solids (TSSs); medium treatment—100 to 200 mg/L TSSs; high treatment—TSSs exceeding 200 mg/L over four weeks of the experiment. The bars represent the mean values, and the vertical lines above the bars represent the standard deviation of the values. Lowercase letters for different days and treatments indicate significant differences ($p < 0.05$)

Following 28 days of culture, oysters from the control treatment exhibited well-defined gill lamellae characterized by intact edges, organized cells, and the presence of infiltrated hemocytes (Figure 21).

Figure 21. Gill filaments of *C. gasar* oysters after 28 days of culture in the control treatment stained with hematoxylin and eosin, magnification 40X.

After the same cultivation duration, oysters from the low treatment showed well defined gill lamellae with intact edges and organized cells. The hyperplasia of the epithelium within the gill lamellae was more pronounced at the filament ends, accompanied by the presence of infiltrated hemocytes (Figure 22A). In the medium treatment, the gill lamellae structure exhibited poor organization yet intact filaments. Notably, hyperplasia of the gill lamellae's epithelium was evident, particularly at the filament ends, alongside the presence of infiltrated hemocytes (Figure 22B). In the high treatment, the gill lamellae structure was less organized, with filaments lacking consistent height and width patterns. The hyperplasia of the gill lamellae's epithelium was pronounced, and infiltrated hemocytes were observed within the gill filaments (Figure 22C).

Figure 22. Gill filaments of *C. gasar* oysters after 28 days of culture in biofloc treatments, stained with hematoxylin and eosin, magnification 40×. (A): Low treatment; (B): medium treatment; (C): high treatment

Concluding the experiment, the gills of oysters from both the medium and high treatments displayed notable hyperplasia of the gill epithelium and the presence of infiltrated hemocytes. In the low and control treatments, infiltrated hemocytes and filament hyperplasia were also observable, albeit with lower intensity. For the PAS-stained samples, in the control treatment, no PAS-positive cells were observed, and the gill architecture was preserved. The gills of the treatments with biofloc presented gill structures with hyperplasia of the lamellar epithelium and isolated PASpositive cells of a mucosecretory aspect (Figure 23).

Figure 23. Gill filaments of *C. gasar* oysters after 28 days of culture in biofloc treatments, stained with PAS. (A): Magnification 40X; (B): magnification 4X.

5.2.4. Discussion and Conclusion

To maintain a biofloc system with marine shrimps, the recommended TSS concentration falls within 100 to 300 mg/L¹²⁷. Schweitzer et al.¹²⁸[49] indicated that a TSS reduction to 200 mg/L in biofloc systems led to decreased nitrification rates. In addition, although 44.8% of a biofloc volume is composed of particles smaller than 48 µm, which is favourable for filtering oysters¹²⁹, the guidelines for oyster cultivation suggest lower TSS concentrations. Barillé et al.¹³⁰ investigated the impact of high seston (suspended material) concentrations on food selection by *Crassostrea* oysters. They found that

¹²⁷ Gaona, C.A.P.; de Almeida, M.S.; Viau, V.; Poersch, L.H.; Wasielesky, W. Effect of different total suspended solids levels on a *Litopenaeus vannamei* (Boone, 1931) BFT culture system during biofloc formation. *Aquac. Res.* 2017, 48, 1070–1079.

¹²⁸ Schweitzer, R.; Arantes, R.; Costódio, P.F.S.; do Espírito Santo, C.M.; Arana, L.V.; Seiffert, W.Q.; Andreatta, E.R. Effect of different biofloc levels on microbial activity, water quality and performance of *Litopenaeus vannamei* in a tank system operated with no water exchange. *Aquac. Eng.* 2013, 56, 59–70.

¹²⁹ Ekasari, J.; Angela, D.; Waluyo, S.H.; Bachtiar, T.; Surawidjaja, E.H.; Bossier, P.; De Schryver, P. The size of biofloc determines the nutritional composition and the nitrogen recovery by aquaculture animals. *Aquaculture* 2014, 426, 105–111.

¹³⁰ Barillé, L.; Prou, J.; Héral, M.; Razet, D. Effects of high natural seston concentrations on the feeding, selection, and absorption of the oyster *Crassostrea gigas* (Thunberg). *J. Exp. Mar. Bio. Ecol.* 1997, 212, 149–172.

seston concentrations below 90 mg/L were regulated by pseudofecal production, while levels above 90 mg/L exhibited reduced filtration and rejection rates, indicative of physical constraints hindering food acquisition. Consequently, reconciling optimal solids concentrations for shrimp and microorganisms with tolerable levels for oysters in an integrated biofloc system appears to pose challenges given the conflicting concentration requirements.

Usually, elevated levels of suspended solids can potentially lead to health issues in cultured species, although tolerance thresholds vary among species^{131,132}. Cultivated organisms may experience hindered gill function due to excessive particulate matter in the water, rendering them more vulnerable to hypoxia. This scenario applies similarly to oysters.

The monitoring of valve movements in bivalves serves as a common approach to discerning behavioural patterns that might signify the presence of contaminants or alterations in environmental conditions¹³³. For instance, Lombardi et al.¹³⁴ noted that oysters tended to keep their valves closed when exposed to unfavourable salinity levels. Various factors contribute to the modulation of valve opening and closing behaviours, encompassing hypoxia¹³⁵, food availability¹³⁶, pollutants^{137,138}, acoustic disturbances¹³⁹, and other environmental influences. In this context, total suspended solids may impact the valve behaviours of *C. gasar*. Within the scope of the present experiment, a notable observation was that oysters subjected to the control treatment exhibited a higher average valve opening than those in the biofloc treatments. This disparity indicates a certain constraint on valve opening in biofloc cultures, irrespective of the TSS concentration. This implies that TSSs could be a limiting parameter in *C. gasar* cultivation. These results corroborate a study by Lima et al.¹⁴⁰, who tested different concentrations of settleable solids in oyster seeds and juveniles and found low survival at high concentrations (10 and 20 ml/L of settleable solids). Filter-feeding bivalves employ valve

¹³¹ Avnimelech, Y. Bio-filters: The need for a new comprehensive approach. *Aquac. Eng.* 2006, 34, 172–178.

¹³² Hargreaves, J.A. Photosynthetic suspended-growth systems in aquaculture. *Aquac. Eng.* 2006, 34, 344–363.

¹³³ Comeau, L.A.; Babarro, J.M.F.; Longa, A.; Padin, X.A. Valve-gaping behavior of raft-cultivated mussels in the Ría de Arousa, Spain. *Aquac. Rep.* 2018, 9, 68–73.

¹³⁴ Lombardi, S.A.; Harlan, N.P.; Paynter, K.T. Survival, Acid–Base Balance, and Gaping Responses of the Asian Oyster *Crassostrea ariakensis* and the Eastern Oyster *Crassostrea virginica* During Clamped Emersion and Hypoxic Immersion. *J. Shellfish Res.* 2013, 32, 409–415.

¹³⁵ Porter, E.T.; Breitburg, D.L. Eastern oyster, *Crassostrea virginica*, valve gape behavior under diel-cycling hypoxia. *Mar. Biol.* 2016, 163, 218.

¹³⁶ Ballesta-Artero, I.; Witbaard, R.; Carroll, M.L.; van der Meer, J. Environmental factors regulating gaping activity of the bivalve *Arctica islandica* in Northern Norway. *Mar. Biol.* 2017, 164, 116.

¹³⁷ Comeau, L.A.; Sonier, R.; Guyondet, T.; Landry, T.; Ramsay, A.; Davidson, J. Behavioural response of bivalve molluscs to calcium hydroxide. *Aquaculture* 2017, 466, 78–85.

¹³⁸ Liao, C.-M.; Jau, S.-F.; Lin, C.-M.; Jou, L.-J.; Liu, C.-W.; Liao, V.H.-C.; Chang, F.-J. Valve movement response of the freshwater clam *Corbicula fluminea* following exposure to waterborne arsenic. *Ecotoxicology* 2009, 18, 567–576.

¹³⁹ Charifi, M.; Sow, M.; Ciret, P.; Benomar, S.; Massabuau, J.-C. The sense of hearing in the Pacific oyster, *Magallana gigas*. *PLoS ONE* 2017, 12, e0185353.

¹⁴⁰ Lima, P.C.M.; Silva, A.E.M.; Silva, D.A.; Silva, S.M.B.C.; Brito, L.O.; Gálvez, A.O. Effect of stocking density of *Crassostrea* sp. in a multitrophic biofloc system with *Litopenaeus vannamei* in nursery. *Aquaculture* 2021, 530, 735913.

opening to filter water, respire, and feed. Accordingly, well-opened valves denote feeding periods, while partially opened or closed valves suggest decreased or halted respiratory filtration^{141,142,143}.

Schreck et al.¹⁴⁴ proposed that a common initial response¹⁴⁴ of many marine organisms to environmental stressors is to modify their behaviour, either to evade lethal consequences or minimize the metabolic costs related to maintaining physiological equilibrium under stressful conditions. If organisms are unable to escape unfavourable conditions, these circumstances can have cascading effects on various other behaviours¹⁴⁵. In the context of the current experiment, during the initial days of cultivation, the TSS concentrations did not appear to significantly impact the opening behaviour of the oysters. However, in the second and third weeks, the effects became prominently evident, and by the fourth week, the biochemical effects started manifesting in the high treatment. Stressful conditions within culture environments can trigger physiological transformations¹⁴⁶, including changes in metabolism, the initiation of a pro-oxidative state involving modifications in the antioxidant defense system, and the potential generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS), which may or may not be accompanied by oxidative damage. Particularly in confined and intensive aquatic environments like those established in biofloc systems, the oxidative equilibrium of aquatic organisms can be adversely affected. Numerous stressors have been investigated in biofloc systems, including salinity¹⁴⁷, temperature¹⁴⁸, and pH¹⁴⁹, among others^{150,151}.

Regarding the SOD enzyme activity, it became evident that the high treatment induced the production of superoxide anion radicals (O₂⁻). Although no signs of lipid damage were observed during this period,

¹⁴¹ Møhlenberg, F.; Riisgård, H.U. Filtration rate, using a new indirect technique, in thirteen species of suspension-feeding bivalves. *Mar. Biol.* 1979, 54, 143–147.

¹⁴² Newell, C.R.; Wildish, D.; MacDonald, B. The effects of velocity and seston concentration on the exhalant siphon area, valve gape and filtration rate of the mussel *Mytilus edulis*. *J. Exp. Mar. Biol. Ecol.* 2001, 262, 91–111.

¹⁴³ Riisgård, H.U.; Larsen, P.S. Physiologically regulated valve-closure makes mussels long-term starvation survivors: Test of hypothesis. *J. Molluscan Stud.* 2015, 81, 303–307.

¹⁴⁴ Schreck, C.B.; Olla, B.L.; Davis, M.W. Behavioral responses to stress. In *Fish Stress and Health in Aquaculture*; Cambridge University Press: Cambridge, UK, 1997; pp. 145–170.

¹⁴⁵ Clements, J.C.; Comeau, L.A. Use of High-Frequency Noninvasive Electromagnetic Biosensors to Detect Ocean Acidification Effects on Shellfish Behavior. *J. Shellfish Res.* 2019, 38, 811.

¹⁴⁶ Romano, N.; Zeng, C. Toxic Effects of Ammonia, Nitrite, and Nitrate to Decapod Crustaceans: A Review on Factors Influencing their Toxicity, Physiological Consequences, and Coping Mechanisms. *Rev. Fish. Sci.* 2013, 21, 1–21.

¹⁴⁷ Brol, J.; Müller, L.; Prates, E.C.A.; de Farias, B.S.; Pedrosa, V.F.; de Almeida Pinto, L.A.; Sant'anna Cadaval, T.R.; Tesser, M.B.; Wasielesky, W.; Ventura-Lima, J. Dietary chitosan supplementation in *Litopenaeus vannamei* reared in a biofloc system: Effect on antioxidant status facing saline stress. *Aquaculture* 2021, 544, 737034.

¹⁴⁸ de Souza, D.M.; Borges, V.D.; Furtado, P.; Romano, L.A.; Wasielesky, W.; Monserrat, J.M.; de Oliveira Garcia, L. Antioxidant enzyme activities and immunological system analysis of *Litopenaeus vannamei* reared in biofloc technology (BFT) at different water temperatures. *Aquaculture* 2016, 451, 436–443.

¹⁴⁹ Martins, G.B.; da Rosa, C.E.; Tarouco, F.d.M.; Robaldo, R.B. Growth, water quality and oxidative stress of Nile tilapia *Oreochromis niloticus* (L.) in biofloc technology system at different pH. *Aquac. Res.* 2019, 50, 1030–1039.

¹⁵⁰ da Silva Martins, Á.C.; Artigas Flores, J.; Porto, C.; Romano, L.A.; Wasielesky Junior, W.; Caldas, S.S.; Primel, E.G.; KülkampGuerreiro, I.; Monserrat, J.M. Antioxidant effects of nanoencapsulated lipoic acid in tissues and on the immune condition in haemolymph of Pacific white shrimp *Litopenaeus vannamei* (Boone, 1931). *Aquac. Nutr.* 2018, 24, 1255–1262.

¹⁵¹ Pellegrin, L.; Nitz, L.F.; Pinto, D.d.S.B.; Copatti, C.E.; Wasielesky, W.; Garcia, L. Effects of suspended solids in the survival and haematological parameters of pacu juveniles (*Piaractus mesopotamicus*) in a biofloc technology culture system. *Aquac. Res.* 2022, 53, 276–284.

a subsequent reduction in total antioxidant capacity was noticeable. Thus, it can be postulated that within the initial two weeks of culture, the elevated TSSs in the high treatment did not prompt oxidative stress in *C. gasar* oysters. However, after this period, spanning 28 days of culture, discernible alterations in SOD enzyme activity appeared, signifying the emergence of a pro-oxidative scenario in *C. gasar* oysters. In a study by Zanette et al.¹⁵², investigations involving distinct salinities revealed no modifications in CAT and GST enzyme activities over a span of 17 days in *C. gigas* oysters' gills. However, when exposed to diesel oil under varying salinity conditions, just one week of diesel exposure was adequate to elicit biochemical changes in the SOD and GST enzymes. This underscores the influence of the type of contaminant on the pace and nature of biochemical responses.

Organisms' antioxidant defense mechanisms can be categorized into prevention, interception, and repair¹⁵³. When confronted with stressors, an organism's primary line of defense entails employing preventive strategies to counter the exposure. For instance, plankton employ a preventive measure during photooxidative stress by positioning themselves beneath the sea surface to avoid direct solar radiation¹⁵⁴. In the case of oysters, it is plausible that, prior to engaging enzymatic defense mechanisms, they employ physical defense strategies. One such strategy might involve minimizing valve opening as a means of curtailing exposure. This adjustment could serve to limit the contact between the gills and the surrounding water, thereby mitigating the potential adverse effects associated with elevated TSS concentrations. However, as the experiment progressed, the oysters in the high treatment ceased to display distinguishable differences in valve opening compared with the other treatments. Consequently, water ingress into the pallial cavity resumed. This marked a turning point at which enzymatic activity alterations and a decline in total antioxidant capacity manifested, indicative of a pro-oxidative scenario.

A potential influencing factor on the enzymatic defense responses of the organisms in the current experiment was the presence of a biofloc system and the subsequent utilization of biofloc by the oysters. Some studies have indicated increased antioxidant effects in cultured organisms exposed to biofloc compared with those raised in clear water conditions¹⁵⁵. In the context of this study, the absence of observable shifts in antioxidant defenses and macromolecular damage in the low and medium treatments throughout the experiment could be attributed to the antioxidative properties of biofloc. In cases of lower concentrations, such as those found in the low and medium treatments, the

¹⁵² Zanette, J.; de Almeida, E.A.; da Silva, A.Z.; Guzinski, J.; Ferreira, J.F.; Di Mascio, P.; Marques, M.R.F.; Bainy, A.C.D. Salinity influences glutathione S-transferase activity and lipid peroxidation responses in the *Crassostrea gigas* oyster exposed to diesel oil. *Sci. Total Environ.* 2011, 409, 1976–1983.

¹⁵³ Sies, H. Strategies of antioxidant defense. *Eur. J. Biochem.* 1993, 215, 213–219.

¹⁵⁴ Sies, H.; Berndt, C.; Jones, D.P. Oxidative stress. *Annu. Rev. Biochem.* 2017, 86, 715–748.

¹⁵⁵ da Silva Martins, Á.C.; Artigas Flores, J.; Porto, C.; Wasielesky Junior, W.; Monserrat, J.M. Antioxidant and oxidative damage responses in different organs of Pacific white shrimp *Litopenaeus vannamei* (Boone, 1931) reared in a biofloc technology system. *Mar. Freshw. Behav. Physiol.* 2015, 48, 279–288.

TSS levels did not prove detrimental to the gill health of the oysters concerning the analyzed enzymatic and non-enzymatic defense mechanisms. This implies that the presence of biofloc may have conferred a protective effect against oxidative stress induced by elevated TSS concentrations.

On the 28th day of the culture period, a decline in the overall antioxidant capacity of the oyster gills became evident in the high treatment. This shift in the normal pattern compared with the control treatment during the same period signifies a departure from the expected antioxidant response. Simultaneously, an elevation in SOD activity was observed, indicating the organism's reaction to dismutase superoxide anion radicals, which are generated due to the presence of oxygen. Essentially, gas exchange persisted, but it appeared to have had detrimental effects on the oysters in the high treatment. As a result, it is highly plausible that the reduction in the total antioxidant capacity could be attributed to other antioxidant defense mechanisms that were not directly assessed in this study. This is because antioxidant defense systems tend to collaborate¹⁵⁶, and their activities can be either boosted or hindered by stressors¹⁵⁷. In light of this, an approach that evaluates antioxidant capacity in a broader sense, encompassing various antioxidant defenses and offering comprehensive insights into an organism's resilience against ROS-induced toxicity¹⁵⁸, seems better suited to elucidating the redox state of oyster gills.

Interestingly, in the context of bivalves, the presence of food sources like microalgae has been shown to mitigate oxidative stress induced by external factors¹⁵⁹, possibly owing to the antioxidant properties of microalgae.

Notably, in the current study, there was a significant decrease ($p < 0.05$) in lipid damage in the control treatment on day 14 compared with day 1, and this reduction was also observed on day 14 in the control treatment compared with the medium and high treatments, aligning with the findings of Li et al.¹⁵⁹. Pathologies affecting bivalve gills span from inflammatory responses to tissue necrosis. Hyperplasia, a defensive inflammatory pathology, represents an immune reaction in bivalves¹⁶⁰. Interestingly, such hyperplasia was observed in treatments involving biofloc, irrespective of the

¹⁵⁶ Winston, G.W.; Regoli, F.; Dugas, A.J.; Fong, J.H.; Blanchard, K.A. A Rapid Gas Chromatographic Assay for Determining Oxyradical Scavenging Capacity of Antioxidants and Biological Fluids. *Free Radic. Biol. Med.* 1998, 24, 480–493.

¹⁵⁷ Sabatini, S.E.; Rocchetta, I.; Nahabedian, D.E.; Luquet, C.M.; Eppis, M.R.; Bianchi, L.; Ríos de Molina, M.d.C. Oxidative stress and histological alterations produced by dietary copper in the fresh water bivalve *Diplodon chilensis*. *Comp. Biochem. Physiol. Part C Toxicol. Pharmacol.* 2011, 154, 391–398.

¹⁵⁸ Amado, L.L.; Garcia, M.L.; Ramos, P.B.; Freitas, R.F.; Zafalon, B.; Ferreira, J.L.R.; Yunes, J.S.; Monserrat, J.M. A method to measure total antioxidant capacity against peroxy radicals in aquatic organisms: Application to evaluate microcystins toxicity. *Sci. Total Environ.* 2009, 407, 2115–2123.

¹⁵⁹ Li, Z.; Chang, X.; Hu, M.; Fang, J.K.-H.; Sokolova, I.M.; Huang, W.; Xu, E.G.; Wang, Y. Is microplastic an oxidative stressor? Evidence from a meta-analysis on bivalves. *J. Hazard. Mater.* 2022, 423, 127211.

¹⁶⁰ Basti, L.; Endo, M.; Segawa, S.; Shumway, S.E.; Tanaka, Y.; Nagai, S. Prevalence and intensity of pathologies induced by the toxic dinoflagellate, *Heterocapsa circularisquama*, in the Mediterranean mussel, *Mytilus galloprovincialis*. *Aquat. Toxicol.* 2015, 163, 37–50.

concentration of solids. However, the morphological changes in the gills of *C. gasar* oysters did not display notably more pronounced alterations compared with those in the control treatment. As Au¹⁶¹ suggested, gill histopathological changes are generally indicative of responsiveness rather than specificity to pollutant exposure, implying that they can signify a broad spectrum of contaminants, signifying environmental toxicity.

In terms of the gill lamellae structure of *C. gasar* oysters exposed to biofloc, the mild effects observed in the medium and high treatments suggest the influence of higher solids concentrations on the bivalves. Nevertheless, these effects did not compromise the overall integrity of the gill structure. Notably, the presence of biofloc in the low, medium, and high treatments did not result in significant damage to the gill morphology of *C. gasar* oysters during the 28-day culture period under the conditions of this experiment.

However, a noticeable variation was observed in mucus production in the gills of oysters subjected to biofloc treatments. Through the use of the PAS method, the presence of PAS-positive cells was discerned in the branchial filaments of oysters from the biofloc treatments, indicative of the activity of mucosecretory cells in these treatment groups. This observation underscores the potential influence of biofloc on the mucous production of the oysters' gills.

A study conducted by Salas-Yanquin et al.¹⁶² provided relevant insights into the relationship between molluscs and the production of mucus in response to environmental conditions. Their analysis of different ash concentrations in water and the subsequent increase in mucus production in mussels highlighted the ability of molluscs to separate ingested material from material to be expelled as pseudofeces, often involving substantial amounts of mucus. In the context of the present experiment, the observed increase in mucus production associated with the biofloc treatments aligns with the presence of cells displaying mucus production. This phenomenon may be attributed to the requirement for greater pseudofeces production in bivalves within the biofloc treatments. The bioflocculation process could potentially necessitate enhanced pseudofeces production by bivalves, contributing to the selection of food items.

The findings of Garrido et al.¹⁶³ further support this notion. Their observations of the food particle selection process in bivalves through endoscopy revealed that particles reaching the mantle cavity are intercepted by gill filaments and transported toward the food groove in small mucous aggregates

¹⁶¹ Au, D.W.T. The application of histo-cytopathological biomarkers in marine pollution monitoring: A review. *Mar. Pollut. Bull.* 2004, 48, 817–834.

¹⁶² Salas-Yanquin, L.P.; Navarro, J.M.; Pechenik, J.A.; Montory, J.A.; Chaparro, O.R. Volcanic ash in the water column: Physiological impact on the suspension-feeding bivalve *Mytilus chilensis*. *Mar. Pollut. Bull.* 2018, 127, 342–351.

¹⁶³ Garrido, M.V.; Chaparro, O.R.; Thompson, R.J.; Garrido, O.; Navarro, J.M. Particle sorting and formation and elimination of pseudofaeces in the bivalves *Mulinia edulis* (siphonate) and *Mytilus chilensis* (asiphonate). *Mar. Biol.* 2012, 159, 987–1000.

facilitated by the frontal cilia. Particles slated for rejection, to be eliminated as pseudofeces, are expelled from the mantle cavity through mucous channels that actively engage in mucus secretion. This process's demand for high mucus production could explain the presence of a greater quantity of mucosecretory cells within the gills of oysters exposed to biofloc treatments in the present experiment. Another explanation for the presence of mucocytes could be the interaction with biofloc, since the diversity of microorganisms in this system is high, especially when compared with the control treatment. The production of mucus in aquatic organisms is for protection against pathogenic organisms.

David et al.¹⁶⁴ analyzed changes in the gills of *Mytella falcata* collected in polluted regions of the Santos estuary. Among other histopathological changes, they observed morphological alterations in the epithelium and an increase in the number of mucous cells, possibly as an attempt to prevent the entry of pollutants through the gill filaments to the entire organism. Zannella et al.¹⁶⁵ reinforced that the production of antimicrobial substances, mainly peptides or polypeptides, is an ancient mechanism of innate immunity. These substances are produced by different types of cells and secretions and are synthesized at the time of infection.

The initial defense response of *C. gasar* oysters to elevated concentrations of biofloc involved the regulation of valve closure behaviour, followed by subsequent biochemical reactions. Hemocytes were consistently present in the gills, serving as an active defense mechanism for the oysters across all treatments in this study. Furthermore, the gill morphology of the oysters remained relatively stable in the biofloc treatments, with no significant structural changes.

Exposure to total suspended solids (TSSs) concentrations comparable to those in the high treatment prompted alterations in the valve opening behaviour of *C. Gasar* oysters from the second week of exposure onward. Prolonged exposure exceeding 14 days to such TSS concentrations could impact the antioxidant capacity of *C. gasar* oysters while also influencing the modulation of superoxide dismutase (SOD) enzyme activity under similar conditions.

Total suspended solids (TSSs) concentrations below 200 mg/L, under conditions comparable to those in this study, did not induce oxidative stress, alterations in behaviour, or histological changes in *C. gasar* oysters cultured over a 28-day biofloc period. However, higher TSS concentrations exceeding 200 mg/L prompted shifts in valve opening behaviour and led to oxidative stress in *C. gasar* oysters, making them unsuitable for cultivation.

¹⁶⁴ de Oliveira David, J.A.; Salaroli, R.B.; Fontanetti, C.S. Fine structure of *Mytella falcata* (Bivalvia) gill filaments. *Micron* 2008, 39, 329–336.

¹⁶⁵ Zannella, C.; Mosca, F.; Mariani, F.; Franci, G.; Folliero, V.; Galdiero, M.; Tiscar, P.G.; Galdiero, M. Microbial Diseases of Bivalve Mollusks: Infections, Immunology and Antimicrobial Defense. *Mar. Drugs* 2017, 15, 182.

5.3. Macroalgae *Ulva lactuca* integrated with the shrimp *Penaeus vannamei* in a biofloc system (Experiment 3)

5.3.1. Introduction

Large-scale production of macroalgae comes from open and coastal areas, totalling 35.1 million tons, according to the FAO in 2022¹⁶⁶. However, these cultures are affected by the availability of nutrients, wave action, and the presence of herbivores, factors that can influence the growth of macroalgae. To address these challenges, the integration of macroalgae cultivation with animal production systems that generate nutrient-rich effluents, such as shrimp farming, has gained prominence. This approach enables indoor cultivation of macroalgae while concurrently serving as a means of bioremediation for aquaculture wastewater. Studies by Alencar et al.¹⁶⁷ and Copertino et al.¹⁶⁸ have demonstrated the effectiveness of cultivating *Ulva* algae using effluents from shrimp farms. They achieved growth rates exceeding 8.0% per day and ammonia absorption rates of up to 90%, indicating enhanced macroalgae development while effectively removing nutrients from the effluents.

More sustainable farming has also gained importance over time, with the aim of producing animals with less environmental impact and effluent treatment systems. The integration of different species in cultivation represents an alternative for improving water quality and the use of waste. This approach is known as Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture (IMTA), which stands out for its sustainability. IMTA involves the cultivation of both feeding species and consuming species that play a crucial role in recycling organic matter and residual nutrients¹⁶⁹. Macroalgae participate in the absorption of nutrients, sequestration of carbon dioxide (CO₂), and maintenance of dissolved oxygen¹⁷⁰. Integrating macroalgae into shrimp farming increases the system's productivity, and two or more species can be cultivated in the same area without negatively affecting their performance, thus increasing economic viability¹⁷¹. The advantages of integrated systems have been shown to be effective in studies such as

¹⁶⁶ FAO. State of the World Fisheries and Aquaculture—2022 (SOFIA); FAO: Rome, Italy, 2022; ISBN 9789251072257.

¹⁶⁷ de Alencar, J.R.; Junior, P.A.H.; Celino, J.J. Cultivo de Camarão Branco *Litopenaeus vannamei* (Boone, 1931) Com a Macroalga *Ulva lactuca* Linneaus (Chlorophyta) No Tratamento de Efluentes Em Sistema Fechado de Recirculação. *Rev. Biol. Ciências Terra* 2010, 10, 117–137.

¹⁶⁸ Copertino, M.D.S.; Tormena, T.; Seeliger, U. Biofiltering Efficiency, Uptake and Assimilation Rates of *Ulva clathrata* (Roth) J. Agardh (Chlorophyceae) Cultivated in Shrimp Aquaculture Waste Water. *J. Appl. Phycol.* 2009, 21, 31–45.

¹⁶⁹ Chopin, T. Marine Aquaculture in Canada: Well-Established Monocultures of Finfish and Shellfish and an Emerging Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture (IMTA) Approach Including Seaweeds, Other Invertebrates, and Microbial Communities. *Fisheries* 2015, 40, 28–31.

¹⁷⁰ Chopin, T.; Buschmann, A.H.; Halling, C.; Troell, M.; Kautsky, N.; Neori, A.; Kraemer, G.P.; Zertuche-González, J.A.; Yarish, C.; Neefus, C. Integrating Seaweeds into Marine Aquaculture Systems: A Key toward Sustainability. *J. Phycol.* 2001, 37, 975–986.

¹⁷¹ Troell, M.; Joyce, A.; Chopin, T.; Neori, A.; Buschmann, A.H.; Fang, J.G. Ecological Engineering in Aquaculture—Potential for Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture (IMTA) in Marine Offshore Systems. *Aquaculture* 2009, 297, 1–9.

Nobre et al.¹⁷² with macroalgae and alone, Holanda et al.¹⁷³ with shrimp and fish, Verdian et al.¹⁷⁴, which showed improvements in zootechnical performance when integrating shrimp, fish, and macroalgae, and Poli et al.¹⁷⁵ with shrimp, fish, and halophytes.

Biofloc technology is a production approach characterized by minimal water exchange, high productivity, and a reduced environmental impact. Central to this technology is the role of heterotrophic bacteria. These bacteria play a vital role in assimilating the ammonia produced by converting it into bacterial biomass, resulting in an increase in total suspended solids-TSS and oxygen consumption¹⁷⁶. In parallel, chemoautotrophic bacteria within the system convert ammonia into nitrate while consuming inorganic carbon¹⁷⁶. For shrimp farming, the solids level should be kept between 100 and 300 mg L⁻¹, with the excess being removed from the system using clarifiers¹⁷⁷ or partial water changes. The constant use of clarifiers to maintain a low concentration of solids can lead to greater energy expenditure. In addition, the low concentration of solids can affect water quality, causing nitrite spikes due to the low availability of bacteria in the system¹⁷⁸.

The minimal water exchange in cultures operated in biofloc systems favours the accumulation of nutrients and solids in the system, which, when released at the end of cultivation into the receiving body of water, can cause eutrophication¹⁷⁹. Although the accumulation of nutrients is favourable to macroalgae growth, the successful production of macroalgae biomass in a biofloc system requires adaptation to the environment due to the distinct characteristics compared with the natural environment. Legarda et al.¹⁸⁰ showed that introducing macroalgae collected from the natural environment into the biofloc system can lead to stress and loss of biomass.

¹⁷² Nobre, A.M.; Robertson-Andersson, D.; Neori, A.; Sankar, K. Ecological-Economic Assessment of Aquaculture Options: Comparison between Abalone Monoculture and Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture of Abalone and Seaweeds. *Aquaculture* 2010, 306, 116–126.

¹⁷³ Holanda, M.; Wasielesky, W.; de Lara, G.R.; Poersch, L.H. Production of Marine Shrimp Integrated with Tilapia at High Densities and in a Biofloc System: Choosing the Best Spatial Configuration. *Fishes* 2022, 7, 283. *Phycology* 2024, 4 50

¹⁷⁴ Verdian, A.H.; Effendi, I.; Budidardi, T.; Diatin, I. Production Performance Improvement of White Shrimp (*Litopenaeus vannamei*) Culture with Integrated Multi Trophic Aquaculture System in Seribu Islands, Jakarta, Indonesia. *Iran. J. Fish. Sci.* 2020, 19, 1415–1427.

¹⁷⁵ Poli, M.A.; Legarda, E.C.; de Lorenzo, M.A.; Pinheiro, I.; Martins, M.A.; Seiffert, W.Q.; do Nascimento Vieira, F. Integrated Multitrophic Aquaculture Applied to Shrimp Rearing in a Biofloc System. *Aquaculture* 2019, 511, 734274.

¹⁷⁶ Ferreira, G.S.; Santos, D.; Schmachtl, F.; Machado, C.; Fernandes, V.; Bögner, M.; Schleder, D.D.; Seiffert, W.Q.; Vieira, F.N. Heterotrophic, Chemoautotrophic and Mature Approaches in Biofloc System for Pacific White Shrimp. *Aquaculture* 2021, 533, 736099.

¹⁷⁷ Gaona, C.A.P.; de Almeida, M.S.; Viau, V.; Poersch, L.H.; Wasielesky, W. Effect of Different Total Suspended Solids Levels on a *Litopenaeus vannamei* (Boone, 1931) BFT Culture System during Biofloc Formation. *Aquac. Res.* 2017, 48, 1070–1079.

¹⁷⁸ Fleckenstein, L.J.; Tierney, T.W.; Fisk, J.C.; Ray, A.J. The Effects of Different Solids and Biological Filters in Intensive Pacific White Shrimp (*Litopenaeus vannamei*) Production Systems. *Aquac. Eng.* 2020, 91, 102120.

¹⁷⁹ Queiroz, H.M.; Ferreira, T.O.; Taniguchi, C.A.K.; Barcellos, D.; do Nascimento, J.C.; Nóbrega, G.N.; Otero, X.L.; Artur, A.G. Nitrogen Mineralization and Eutrophication Risks in Mangroves Receiving Shrimp Farming Effluents. *Environ. Sci. Pollut. Res.* 2020, 27, 34941–34950.

¹⁸⁰ Legarda, E.C.; da Silva, D.; Miranda, C.S.; Pereira, P.K.M.; Martins, M.A.; Machado, C.; de Lorenzo, M.A.; Hayashi, L.; do Nascimento Vieira, F. Sea Lettuce Integrated with Pacific White Shrimp and Mullet Cultivation in Biofloc Impact System Performance and the Sea Lettuce Nutritional Composition. *Aquaculture* 2021, 534, 736265.

The production of solids in the water can harm the macroalgae since these solids block the entry of light into the photosynthetic tissues¹⁸¹. In addition, the presence of these solids limits the penetration of light into the water column, especially at greater depths¹⁸². Therefore, for the best development of macroalgae, the concentration of solids in the system must be optimized. The use of water exchanges can help to decrease the concentration of solids in the system, but it will increase energy costs and cause environmental problems with the disposal of effluents. According to Queiroz et al.¹⁷⁹, the disposal of effluent from shrimp farming in mangroves increases the nitrogen content in the soil and its mineralization, factors that trigger the eutrophication of mangrove areas. Water exchange in cultivation also leads to nutrient dilution, which can become a limiting factor or change the N:P ratio for macroalgae growth¹⁸³.

Thus, adjusting water quality parameters for integrated macroalgae cultivation can be used as a way of boosting macroalgae performance in biofloc systems. In addition to the growth of macroalgae, their cultivation in an environment with different physical and chemical factors can lead to changes in their biochemical and nutritional composition, which may be of interest to the pharmaceutical and food industries¹⁸⁴. Previous studies have shown an increase in the protein content of the macroalgae *Ulva lactuca* when cultivated in an integrated biofloc system. The values reached 22.4%, in contrast to the 12.40% observed when cultivated in laboratory solution, highlighting its nutritional value¹⁸⁵. He et al.¹⁸⁶ described some factors that influence the increase in antioxidant capacity and phenol content, such as salinities below 25, as well as the depletion or high concentrations of nutrients that can influence the concentration of amino acids and fatty acids in macroalgae. Therefore, the medium and conditions under which macroalgae are cultivated can enhance the biomass produced.

Therefore, the aim of this study is to evaluate nutrient absorption, nutritional composition, and bioactive compounds in the macroalgae *Ulva lactuca* when cultivated under varying concentrations of

¹⁸¹ Brito, L.O.; Arantes, R.; Magnotti, C.; Derner, R.; Pchara, F.; Olivera, A.; Vinatea, L. Water Quality and Growth of Pacific White Shrimp *Litopenaeus vannamei* (Boone) in Co-Culture with Green Seaweed *Ulva lactuca* (Linnaeus) in Intensive System. *Aquac. Int.* 2014, 22, 497–508.

¹⁸² Reis, W.G.; Wasielesky, W.; Abreu, P.C.; Brandão, H.; Krummenauer, D. Rearing of the Pacific White Shrimp *Litopenaeus vannamei* (Boone, 1931) in BFT System with Different Photoperiods: Effects on the Microbial Community, Water Quality and Zootechnical Performance. *Aquaculture* 2019, 508, 19–29

¹⁸³ Duke, C.S.; Litaker, W.; Ramus, J. Effects of the Temperature, Nitrogen Supply and Tissue Nitrogen on Ammonium Uptake Rates of the Chlorophyte Seaweeds *Ulva curvata* and *Codium decorticans*. *J. Phycol.* 1989, 25, 113–120.

¹⁸⁴ Duke, C.S.; Litaker, W.; Ramus, J. Effects of the Temperature, Nitrogen Supply and Tissue Nitrogen on Ammonium Uptake Rates of the Chlorophyte Seaweeds *Ulva curvata* and *Codium decorticans*. *J. Phycol.* 1989, 25, 113–120.

¹⁸⁵ Carvalho, A.; Costa, L.C.d.O.; Holanda, M.; Poersch, L.H.; Turan, G. Influence of Total Suspended Solids on the Growth of the Sea Lettuce *Ulva lactuca* Integrated with the Pacific White Shrimp *Litopenaeus vannamei* in a Biofloc System. *Fishes* 2023, 8, 163.

¹⁸⁶ He, J.; Xu, Y.; Chen, H.; Sun, P. Extraction, Structural Characterization, and Potential Antioxidant Activity of the Polysaccharides from Four Seaweeds. *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* 2016, 17, 1988.

nutrients and total suspended solids (biofloc) within an integrated system with the white shrimp *Penaeus vannamei*.

5.3.2. Trial Methodology

The experiment was carried out at the Marine Aquaculture Station, Institute of Oceanography of the Federal University of Rio Grande (IO-FURG), located on Cassino Beach, Rio Grande, Rio Grande do Sul. The macroalgae species used was *U. lactuca*, collected in a natural environment (32°17'05.2" S–52°15'05.9" W). After collection, the macroalgae were taken to the laboratory to remove the epiphyte species and identified using a molecular analysis and observing quadratic cells and a bilayer of cells characteristic of this species, as also identified by Alencar et al.¹⁸⁷. After confirming the species, it was cultivated for 27 days before being stocked in the experimental units in a 1 m³ circular tank with 10% biofloc inoculum, resulting in a concentration of 35.1 ± 2.74 mg L⁻¹ of nitrate and 2.24 ± 1.2 mg L⁻¹ of phosphate. The shrimp came from a biofloc system grow-out tank at the EMA/IO-FURG Carcinoculture Laboratory. The shrimp, with an initial weight of 3.85 ± 0.73 g, were stocked at a density of 200 shrimp m⁻³ to maintain the biofloc.

The experiment lasted 45 days and was carried out in an agricultural greenhouse. The experimental units were kept under constant aeration using a blower (4 HP), which injected air into the experimental units through two pieces of micro-perforated hose (each piece 20 cm long) per tank. During the experiment, the average light intensity was 28.68 ± 8.53 μmol m⁻² s⁻¹, with a natural photoperiod of 14 h light and 10 h dark. Fifteen tanks were used, arranged randomly in the greenhouse, with a base diameter of 0.81 m, a height of 0.53 m, and a useful volume of 180 L (Figure 1). The shrimp and macroalgae were kept in the same tank, but to separate the animals, the macroalgae were cultivated inside a circular floating structure near the surface with a diameter of 0.60 m, with 5 mm mesh openings, with a depth of 10 cm to allow the macroalgae to move within the structure, at a density of 0.88 kg m⁻² (Figure 24). The shrimp were fed with a commercial feed of 36% protein (Guabi Aqua QS 2–3 mm, Guabi Nutrition and Animal Health S.A., Campinas, São Paulo, Brazil), according to the methodology proposed by Jory et al.¹⁸⁸ [21], twice a day, with the feed being adjusted weekly.

¹⁸⁷ de Alencar, J.R.; Junior, P.A.H.; Celino, J.J. Cultivo de Camarão Branco *Litopenaeus vannamei* (Boone, 1931) Com a Macroalga *Ulva lactuca* Linnaeus (Chlorophyta) No Tratamento de Efluentes Em Sistema Fechado de Recirculação. *Rev. Biol. Ciências Terra* 2010, 10, 117–137.

¹⁸⁸ Jory, D.E.; Cabrera, T.R.; Dugger, D.M.; Fegan, D.; Lee, P.G.; Lawrence, L.; Jackson, C.J.; McIntosh, R.P.; Castañeda, J.I.; McIntosh, R.; et al. A Global Review of Shrimp Feed Management: Status and Perspectives. *Aquaculture* 2011, 318, 104–152.

Figure 24. Diagram of the experimental units used for shrimp and macroalgae. (A) Tanks with a useful volume of 180 L, with constant aeration, and a circular structure for the macroalgae. (B) Circular structure with a diameter of 0.60 cm for the cultivation of macroalgae

The experiment used a mature biofloc inoculum from a grow-out shrimp farm ¹⁸⁹. The nutrient concentrations of the inoculum were 0.09, 0.03, 73.33, and 1.60 mg L⁻¹ of total ammoniacal nitrogen, nitrite, nitrate, and phosphate, respectively, 20 mL L⁻¹ of settleable solids, 304 NTU for turbidity and 325 mg L⁻¹ of total suspended solids. This inoculum was placed in different percentages in each treatment and diluted with seawater to complete the useful volume of the tank, arriving at different concentrations of nutrients and solids (Table 5).

Table 5. Initial characteristics of the treatments CONT (cultivation in clear water), T100 (use of 25% biofloc inoculum, a concentration of approximately 100 mg L⁻¹ of total suspended solids), T200 (use of 50% biofloc inoculum, a concentration of approximately 200 mg L⁻¹ of total suspended solids), T250 (use of 75% biofloc inoculum, a concentration of approximately 250 mg L⁻¹ of total suspended solids), T300 (use of 100% biofloc inoculum, a concentration of approximately 300 mg L⁻¹ of total suspended solids).

Parameters	Treatments				
	CONT	T100	T200	T250	T300
Total ammonia N-NH ₃ (mg L ⁻¹)	0.02 ± 0.00	0.04 ± 0.01	0.04 ± 0.01	0.05 ± 0.03	0.09 ± 0.01
Nitrite NO ₂ -N (mg L ⁻¹)	0.01 ± 0.01	0.02 ± 0.00	0.02 ± 0.00	0.01 ± 0.03	0.01 ± 0.03
Nitrate NO ₃ -N (mg L ⁻¹)	0.05 ± 0.04 ^a	28.33 ± 5.77 ^b	45.00 ± 0.00 ^c	56.67 ± 5.77 ^d	73.33 ± 5.77 ^e
Phosphate P-PO ₄ ⁻³ (mg L ⁻¹)	0.14 ± 0.03 ^a	0.81 ± 0.12 ^b	1.25 ± 0.05 ^c	1.55 ± 0.14 ^d	1.60 ± 0.00 ^e
SS (mL L ⁻¹)	0.00 ± 0.00 ^a	1.97 ± 1.38 ^b	8.00 ± 1.00 ^c	11.67 ± 0.58 ^d	19.67 ± 0.58 ^e
TSS (mg L ⁻¹)	11.67 ± 2.89 ^a	111.67 ± 63.31 ^b	213.33 ± 50.08 ^c	246.67 ± 2.89 ^d	325.00 ± 21.21 ^e
Turbidity (NTU)	2.57 ± 0.37 ^a	26.23 ± 18.01 ^b	74.63 ± 62.35 ^c	176.10 ± 18.36 ^d	304.10 ± 12.77 ^e

SS (Settleable Solids); TSS (Total Suspended Solids). Different letters in the same line represent significant differences ($p \leq 0.05$) between treatments after one-way ANOVA with Tukey's post-hoc test.

The experiment consisted of five treatments with three replicates each. Presenting a control treatment CONT—cultivation in clear water, with the addition of organic carbon when ammonia reached

¹⁸⁹ Ferreira, G.S.; Santos, D.; Schmachtl, F.; Machado, C.; Fernandes, V.; Bögnner, M.; Schleder, D.D.; Seiffert, W.Q.; Vieira, F.N. Heterotrophic, Chemoautotrophic and Mature Approaches in Biofloc System for Pacific White Shrimp. *Aquaculture* 2021, 533, 736099.

concentrations of 1 mg L^{-1} ¹⁹⁰; and treatments with different percentages of biofloc inoculum, with 25, 50, 75 and 100% biofloc, resulting in: T100—concentration of approximately 100 mg L^{-1} of total suspended solids; T200—concentration of approximately 200 mg L^{-1} of total suspended solids; T250—concentration of approximately 250 mg L^{-1} of total suspended solids; T300—concentration of approximately 300 mg L^{-1} of total suspended solids (Table 1).

Temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$), dissolved oxygen (DO, mg L^{-1}), and pH were measured daily in all tanks using a multi-parameter probe (model Pro-20, YSI Inc., Yellow Springs, OH, USA) and a bench pH meter (Seven2Go S7 Basic, Mettler Toledo, São Paulo, Brazil). Salinity was measured weekly using a multi-parameter probe (model Pro-20, YSI Inc., Yellow Springs, OH, USA). For the water quality analyses, the samples were collected in plastic containers and taken immediately for analysis. Total ammonia (N-NH₃, mg L^{-1}) and nitrite (NO₂-N, mg L^{-1}) were analyzed twice a week according to the methodology of UNESCO¹⁹¹ and Bendschneider & Robinson¹⁹², respectively. Nitrate (NO₃-N) and phosphate (P-PO₄-3) (mg L^{-1}) were analyzed using the methodology described by Aminot & Chaussepied¹⁹³ and monitored twice a week. Turbidity and TSS were determined weekly. Turbidity (NTU) was measured using a portable turbidimeter (2100P, Hach™, Loveland, CO, USA), and total suspended solids (TSS) were quantified using filtration and gravimetry according to the methodology described by Strickland and Parsons¹⁹⁴. Total alkalinity ($\text{mg CaCO}_3 \text{ L}^{-1}$) was measured twice a week and monitored according to the methodology presented by APHA¹⁹⁵. Calcium hydroxide was used to maintain alkalinity above 150 mg L^{-1} ¹⁹⁶. The settleable solids (SS) were measured weekly using the Imhoff cone¹⁹⁵.

The biomass yield of the macroalgae was measured weekly by weighing the fresh biomass, where the macroalgae were removed from the water and left in the open air for 20 min to remove excess water.

The following formula was used to calculate the Relative Growth Rate (RGR)¹⁹⁷:

¹⁹⁰ Wasielesky, W.; Krummenauer, D.; Lara, G.; Fôes, G. Cultivo de Camarões Em Sistema de Bioflocos: Realidades e Perspectivas. *Rev. ABCC* 2013, 15, 16–26.

¹⁹¹ Unesco. *Chemical Methods for Use in Marine Environmental Monitoring*; Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission: Paris, France, 1983.

¹⁹² Bendschneider, K.; Robinson, R.J. New Spectrophotometric Method for the Determination of Nitrite in Water. *Fresenius Environ. Bull.* 1952, 10, 781–784.

¹⁹³ Aminot, A.; Chaussepied, M. *Manuel Des Analyses Chimiques En Milieu Marin*; Centre National pour l'exploitation des océans: Paris, France, 1983.

¹⁹⁴ Bogue, J.P.; Smith, L.F.; Lipsett, L. *A Practical Handbook*. *J. High. Educ.* 1957, 28, 405.

¹⁹⁵ American Public Health Association APHA; American Water Works Association; Water Pollution Control Association. *Standard Methods for the Examination of Water and Wastewater*, 21st ed.; American Public Health Association: Washington, DC, USA, 2005.

¹⁹⁶ Furtado, P.S.; Poersch, L.H.; Wasielesky, W. Effect of Calcium Hydroxide, Carbonate and Sodium Bicarbonate on Water Quality and Zootechnical Performance of Shrimp *Litopenaeus vannamei* Reared in Biofloc Technology (BFT) Systems. *Aquaculture* 2011, 321, 130–135.

¹⁹⁷ Loureiro, R.R.; Reis, R.P.; Critchley, A.T. In Vitro Cultivation of Three *Kappaphycus alvarezii* (Rhodophyta, Areschougiales) Variants (Green, Red and Brown) Exposed to a Commercial Extract of the Brown Alga *Ascophyllum nodosum* (Fucaceae, Ochrophyta). *J. Appl. Phycol.* 2010, 22, 101–104.

$$\text{RGR (\% d}^{-1}\text{)}: 100 \times [\ln (\text{final weight (g)}/\text{initial weight (g)})/(\text{final time} - \text{initial time})] \quad (1)$$

The nutrient absorption efficiency (NRR) of macroalgae was calculated using the following formula¹⁹⁷:

$$\text{NRR (\%)}: 100 \times [(\text{nutrient concentration at initial time (mg L}^{-1}\text{)} - \text{nutrient concentration at final time (mg L}^{-1}\text{)})/\text{nutrient concentration at initial time (mg L}^{-1}\text{)}] \quad (2)$$

Proximal composition analysis was carried out on the treatment with the biofloc inoculum that showed the best growth performance and nutrient absorption at the end of cultivation (T250) and on the CONT treatment for comparison. Random samples of algae were collected manually from each experimental unit, washed in running water, and then with distilled water. Excess water was removed using a manual centrifuge, followed by drying with paper towels. The samples were weighed to determine their wet weight and placed in an oven at 60 °C for 24 h, after which they were weighed again to obtain their dry weight. The samples were then ground for analysis.

The nitrogen content of the algae was determined using the Kjeldahl titration method according to AOAC¹⁹⁸ at the Laboratory of Aquatic Organism Nutrition-LANOA (EMA, FURG, Rio Grande, Brazil). The formula used to convert nitrogen into protein was:

$$\text{Protein (\% of dry weight)} = [(0.085 \times \text{Vol} \times 0.014/\text{sample}) \times 5.45] \times 100 \quad (3)$$

where Vol is the volume spent on titration, and sample is the dry weight of the sample¹⁹⁹.

The crude fat content was determined using the Soxhlet method based on solvent extraction (petroleum ether), and the ash content was obtained using the gravimetric method in a muffle furnace at 600 °C. The crude fiber was obtained using washes in acidic and basic media.

The macroalgae extract was obtained using the methodology of Barbarino & Lourenço²⁰⁰, with the addition of 1 mL of sodium hydroxide and centrifugation to prepare the crude extract for protein analysis. The macroalgae protein was analyzed using the Biuret method, following the methodology of Barbarino & Lourenço²⁰⁰. The extract and trichloroacetic acid (TCA) (25%) were added in a ratio of 2.5:1 (v/v) to precipitate the protein and kept in an ice-cold bath for 30 min. The solution was then centrifuged and washed with dilutions of TCA (10 and 5%), removing the supernatant until the protein

¹⁹⁸ AOAC. Official Methods of Analysis; Association of Official Analytical Chemists: Arlington, VA, USA, 2005; p. 245.

¹⁹⁹ Baethgen, W.E.; Alley, M. A Manual Colorimetric Procedure for Measuring Ammonium Nitrogen in Soil and Plant Kjeldahl Digests. Commun. Soil Sci. Plant Anal. 1989, 20, 961–969.

²⁰⁰ Barbarino, E.; Lourenço, S.O. An Evaluation of Methods for Extraction and Quantification of Protein from Marine Macro and Microalgae. J. Appl. Phycol. 2005, 17, 447–460.

pellet was formed. 0.5 mL of sodium hydroxide (0.1 N) was added to the pellet suspension, and 20 μL of the solution and 1 mL of the total protein kit were removed.

To determine the concentration of chlorophyll-a, chlorophyll-b, carotenoids, phenolic compounds, and DPPH (2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl), 500 mg of sample and 5 mL of methanol were used. The samples were macerated, then incubated in the dark for 60 min at 4 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, and centrifuged ($12,000\times g \times 10$ min). Finally, the supernatant was collected for analysis. The absorbances at 664 and 647 nm were measured to calculate chlorophyll-a ($\text{Chla} = 11.75 \times A_{664} - 2.35 \times A_{647}$), chlorophyll-b ($\text{Chlb} = 18.61 \times A_{647} - 3.91 \times A_{664}$) and carotenoids ($\text{Car} = (1000 \times A_{470} - 2.27 \times \text{Chla} - 81.4 \text{ Chlb})/227$) according to the methodology of Lichtenthaler & Wellburn²⁰¹.

Total phenolic compounds were determined by the Folin–Ciocalteu colorimetric method using the methodology described by Schiavon et al.²⁰² with modifications. A total volume of 2 mL of 2% Na_2CO_3 and 150 μL of Folin–Ciocalteu reagent (Sigma-Aldrich) were added to 200 μL of macroalgae extract. After 15 min of incubation in the dark, the samples were measured at 750 nm. The gallic acid standard curve was used (Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, MO, USA—100–1250 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$, $y = 0.0008x - 0.0156$, $R^2 = 0.999$). The results were presented as mg of gallic acid equivalent per g of mass (mg GAE g^{-1}).

The DPPH radical scavenging effects of the samples were carried out using the methodology of Farasat et al.²⁰³ with some modifications. A total volume of 400 μL of extract and 400 μL of 0.16 mM DPPH methanolic solution were used. The mixture was vortexed for 1 min and then incubated for 30 min in the dark. The absorbance was read at 517 nm in a spectrophotometer, where the antioxidant capacity was calculated using the following equation:

$$\% \text{ Inhibition} = (\text{A}_{\text{control}} - (\text{A}_{\text{sample}} - \text{A}_{\text{blank}}))/\text{A}_{\text{control}} \times 100 \quad (4)$$

where $\text{A}_{\text{control}}$ is the absorbance of the control (DPPH without extract), A_{sample} is the absorbance of the extract (extract plus DPPH solution), and A_{blank} is the absorbance of the extract (extract without DPPH solution).

Shrimp growth data were obtained from weekly biometrics that included the following formulas:

1. Mean final weight (g): final biomass of live animals (g)/total number of animals;
2. Weekly weight gain (g week⁻¹): weight gain (g)/number of weeks.

²⁰¹ Lichtenthaler, H.K.; Wellburn, A.R. Determinations of Total Carotenoids and Chlorophylls a and b of Leaf Extracts in Different Solvents. *Biochem. Soc. Trans.* 1983, 11, 591–592. *Phycology* 2024, 4 51

²⁰² Schiavon, M.; Moro, I.; Pilon-Smits, E.A.H.; Matozzo, V.; Malagoli, M.; Dalla Vecchia, F. Accumulation of Selenium in *Ulva* Sp. and Effects on Morphology, Ultrastructure and Antioxidant Enzymes and Metabolites. *Aquat. Toxicol.* 2012, 122–123, 222–231.

²⁰³ Farasat, M.; Khavari-Nejad, R.-A.; Nabavi, S.M.B.; Namjooyan, F. Antioxidant Properties of Two Edible Green Seaweeds from Northern Coasts of the Persian Gulf. *Jundishapur J. Nat. Pharm. Prod.* 2013, 8, 47–52.

3. Final biomass (g): \sum final weight of all live animals (g);
4. Survival (%) = (final number of animals/initial number of animals) \times 100;
5. Feed conversion factor (FCR) = \sum ration offered (g)/(biomass gains (g));
6. Productivity (kg m⁻³): (final biomass (kg))/tank volume (m³);

The normality and homoscedasticity of these data were checked using the Shapiro–Wilk and Levene tests, respectively. Once these assumptions had been met, ANOVA was carried out, followed by Tukey’s post-hoc test for water quality, macroalgae, and shrimp performance. Spearman’s correlation was carried out for each week of the experiment between the variables treatment, nitrate concentration, phosphate concentration, total suspended solids concentration, macroalgae weight gain, nitrate removal rate, and phosphate removal rate. A student’s t-test was applied to the proximal and biochemical composition of only the two treatments, CONT and T250. When the assumptions of ANOVA and the student’s t-test were not met, the non-parametric Kruskal–Wallis test was used. A minimum significance level of 5% ($p \leq 0.05$) was applied in all analyses.

5.3.3. Results

There were no significant differences ($p > 0.05$) between the treatments in the parameters temperature, dissolved oxygen (D.O), and ammonia. The pH remained higher in the T250 and T300 treatments, along with the alkalinity, which was also higher ($p > 0.05$) in the same treatments. Salinity differed between treatments ($p < 0.05$), ranging from 28 to 30. The lowest nitrite concentrations were observed in the CONT treatment. Nitrate and settleable solids (SS) had higher concentrations as the inoculum concentration increased. Phosphate and turbidity were lower in the CONT and T100 treatments and remained the same in the other treatments. Total suspended solids (TSS) in the CONT treatment increased compared with the initial concentration but remained lower than in the other treatments. The concentration of solids increased in the treatments in relation to the initial inoculum concentrations (Table 6).

When looking at the nitrate values, the initial concentrations of the T300, T250, T200, and T100 treatments were higher than the final concentrations, showing a removal of the nitrogenous compound (Figure 25). In the control treatment, there was an increase in nitrate concentration on the 32nd day of the trial period. At the end of cultivation, the nitrate concentrations between treatments T300, T250, T200, and T100 were statistically similar.

Table 6. Water quality during the 45 days of cultivation, in treatments CONT (cultivation in clear water), T100 (use of 25% biofloc inoculum, a concentration of approximately 100 mg L⁻¹ of total suspended solids), T200 (use of 50% biofloc inoculum, a concentration of approximately 200 mg L⁻¹ of total suspended solids), T250 (use of 75% biofloc inoculum, a concentration of approximately 250 mg L⁻¹ of total suspended solids), T300 (use of 100% biofloc inoculum, a concentration of approximately 300 mg L⁻¹ of total suspended solids).

Parameters	Treatments				
	CONT	T100	T200	T250	T300
Temperature (°C)	26.92 ± 2.30	26.55 ± 2.18	26.56 ± 2.18	26.79 ± 2.46	26.56 ± 2.19
DO (mg L ⁻¹)	5.89 ± 0.70	6.03 ± 0.71	6.00 ± 0.70	5.90 ± 0.74	5.98 ± 0.71
pH	8.15 ± 0.09 ^c	8.18 ± 0.07 ^c	8.16 ± 0.08 ^b	8.23 ± 0.07 ^a	8.22 ± 0.07 ^a
Salinity (‰)	30.43 ± 1.81 ^a	30.00 ± 0.51 ^a	29.43 ± 1.57 ^a	29.19 ± 1.40 ^{ab}	27.90 ± 0.66 ^b
Alkalinity (mg CaCO ₃ L ⁻¹)	173.33 ± 23.93 ^{cb}	174.36 ± 21.40 ^{cb}	175.66 ± 24.69 ^{cb}	205.92 ± 34.15 ^a	183.08 ± 27.05 ^b
Total ammonia N-NH ₃ (mg L ⁻¹)	0.12 ± 0.07	0.11 ± 0.03	0.09 ± 0.03	0.10 ± 0.02	0.10 ± 0.03
Nitrite NO ₂ -N (mg L ⁻¹)	0.26 ± 0.55 ^a	1.06 ± 1.36 ^b	1.30 ± 1.96 ^b	1.40 ± 2.43 ^b	0.35 ± 0.40 ^b
Nitrate NO ₃ -N (mg L ⁻¹)	1.56 ± 3.13 ^a	19.53 ± 3.53 ^b	32.25 ± 4.85 ^c	44.97 ± 9.01 ^d	59.38 ± 6.80 ^e
Phosphate P-PO ₄ ⁻³ (mg L ⁻¹)	0.56 ± 0.36 ^a	0.79 ± 0.38 ^{ab}	1.21 ± 0.39 ^b	1.16 ± 0.30 ^b	1.67 ± 0.26 ^c
SS (mL L ⁻¹)	2.65 ± 2.34 ^a	5.93 ± 3.33 ^b	11.15 ± 3.17 ^c	15.08 ± 4.39 ^d	21.71 ± 4.98 ^e
TSS (mg L ⁻¹)	134.05 ± 81.36 ^a	232.62 ± 92.76 ^b	290.48 ± 65.36 ^b	354.05 ± 88.69 ^c	403.69 ± 79.03 ^c
Turbidity (NTU)	80.37 ± 62.71 ^a	106.26 ± 79.79 ^a	167.31 ± 95.65 ^{ab}	232.91 ± 101.9 ^b	287.48 ± 104.59 ^b
Calcium hydroxide (g L ⁻¹) [#]	0.13 ± 0.03	0.10 ± 0.00	0.13 ± 0.06	0.07 ± 0.06	0.08 ± 0.03
Removal rate					
Nitrate (%)	00.00 ± 00.00 ^c	28.0 ± 13.0 ^b	17.0 ± 15.0 ^{bc}	55.0 ± 4.0 ^a	38.0 ± 11.0 ^{ab}
Phosphate (%)	00.00 ± 00.00 ^b	00.00 ± 00.00 ^b	00.00 ± 00.00 ^b	31.0 ± 10.0 ^a	00.00 ± 00.00 ^b

DO (dissolved oxygen); SS (Settleable Solids); TSS (Total Suspended Solids); # Use of calcium hydroxide per treatment. Different letters in the same line represent significant differences ($p \leq 0.05$) between treatments after one-way ANOVA with Tukey's post-hoc test.

As shown in Table 6, the best nitrate and phosphate removal rates were found in the T250 treatment with 55.0 ± 4.0 and $31.0 \pm 10.0\%$, respectively. In contrast, the CONT treatment had an increase in nitrate and phosphate throughout the experiment.

In general, there was a positive correlation between treatment and the concentration of total suspended solids, nitrate, and phosphate in all weeks of cultivation. In the first week, there was a positive correlation between the weight gain of the macroalgae and nitrate removal rate (correlation coefficient = 0.575; p valor = 0.025) and phosphate removal rate (correlation coefficient = 0.627; p valor = 0.012). The second week showed a positive correlation between the weight gain of the macroalgae and nitrate removal rate (correlation coefficient = 0.596; p valor = 0.019). The third week showed a positive correlation between treatment and nitrate removal rate (correlation coefficient = 0.542; p valor = 0.037). The fourth week showed a positive correlation between nitrate removal rate, treatment (correlation coefficient = 0.676; p valor = 0.006), nitrate concentration (correlation coefficient = 0.657; p valor = 0.008), and phosphate concentration (correlation coefficient = 0.738; p valor = 0.002). The fifth week showed a positive correlation between the nitrate removal rate with treatment (correlation coefficient = 0.873; p valor = 0.000), nitrate concentration (correlation coefficient = 0.864; p valor = 0.000), phosphate concentration (correlation coefficient = 0.555; p valor = 0.032) and total suspended solids (correlation coefficient = 0.717; p valor = 0.003). In the last week, there was a positive correlation between the treatment and the phosphate removal rate (correlation

coefficient = 0.683; p valor = 0.005) and a negative correlation between the weight gain of the macroalgae and the nitrate removal rate (correlation coefficient = -0.729; p valor = 0.002).

Figure 25. Nitrate concentrations in treatments CONT (cultivation in clear water), T100 (use of 25% biofloc inoculum, a concentration of approximately 100 mg L⁻¹ of total suspended solids), T200 (use of 50% biofloc inoculum, a concentration of approximately 200 mg L⁻¹ of total suspended solids), T250 (use of 75% biofloc inoculum, a concentration of approximately 250 mg L⁻¹ of total suspended solids), T300 (use of 100% biofloc inoculum, a concentration of approximately 300 mg L⁻¹ of total suspended solids). Different lowercase letters on the same line represent a significant difference ($p \leq 0.05$) in the same treatment at the beginning and end. Different capital letters represent a significant difference ($p \leq 0.05$) between treatments on the same day after performing a one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey’s test.

The average initial weight of the macroalgae in the treatments was 250.18 ± 0.28 g, with a gain in biomass throughout the experiment indicated by the growth rate (Table 7). There was no significant difference in final weight and relative growth rate (RGR) between treatments.

Table 7. Performance of macroalgae during 45 days of cultivation, in treatments CONT (cultivation in clear water), T100 (use of 25% biofloc inoculum, a concentration of approximately 100 mg L⁻¹ of total suspended solids), T200 (use of 50% biofloc inoculum, a concentration of approximately 200 mg L⁻¹ of total suspended solids), T250 (use of 75% biofloc inoculum, a concentration of approximately 250 mg L⁻¹ of total suspended solids), T300 (use of 100% biofloc inoculum, a concentration of approximately 300 mg L⁻¹ of total suspended solids).

	Treatments				
	CONT	T100	T200	T250	T300
Initial mean weight (g—FW)	250.31 ± 0.31	250.05 ± 0.02	250.0 ± 0.00	250.51 ± 0.41	250.06 ± 0.04
Final mean weight (g—FW)	387.33 ± 115.09	317.67 ± 60.86	289.0 ± 73.75	304.33 ± 76.20	275.0 ± 36.69
RGR (% dia ⁻¹)	0.89 ± 0.61	0.49 ± 0.41	0.27 ± 0.52	0.38 ± 0.52	0.19 ± 0.30

RGR (relative growth rate); FW (fresh weight).

The proximate and biochemical composition was carried out on the control treatment (CONT), and the treatment with the best performance in nutrient absorption, the T250 treatment, was used. Table 8 shows that the highest protein and chlorophyll-a values were found in the treatment with biofloc inoculum (T250), and the highest ash values were found in the CONT treatment.

Table 8. Proximal composition and biocompounds of the macroalgae (dry matter) at the end of cultivation in the CONT (cultivation in clear water) and T250 (use of 75% biofloc inoculum, a concentration of approximately 250 mg L⁻¹ of total suspended solids) treatments.

Proximal Composition	Treatments	
	CONT	T250
Moisture (%) #	77.42 ± 0.09 ^b	75.50 ± 0.23 ^a
Protein content (%)	22.85 ± 0.37 ^b	24.26 ± 0.89 ^a
Lipids (%)	0.53 ± 0.19	0.48 ± 0.19
Ash (%)	30.17 ± 1.80 ^b	28.30 ± 0.64 ^a
Fiber (%)	10.65 ± 0.78	11.59 ± 3.41
Non-nitrogenous extract (%)	35.77 ± 1.30	35.58 ± 1.44
Biochemical Analysis		
Protein (%)	23.30 ± 1.59	25.85 ± 2.81
DPPH (%)	90.31 ± 5.38	92.97 ± 5.80
Chlorophyll- <i>a</i> (mg g ⁻¹)	2.18 ± 0.03 ^b	2.27 ± 0.03 ^a
Chlorophyll- <i>b</i> (mg g ⁻¹)	2.99 ± 0.28	3.31 ± 0.10
Carotenoids (mg g ⁻¹)	0.19 ± 0.10	0.10 ± 0.03
Total Polyphenols (mg GAE g ⁻¹)	0.38 ± 0.12	0.33 ± 0.09

NNE (non-nitrogenous extract); # humid matter. Different letters represent significant differences ($p \leq 0.05$) between treatments after Student's *t*-test.

No significant differences were observed in shrimp performance parameters between the treatments during the experimental period (Table 9). The shrimp grew during the experimental period and survived successfully at the end of cultivation.

Table 9. Performance of the shrimp during the 45 days of cultivation, in the treatments CONT (cultivation in clear water), T100 (use of 25% biofloc inoculum, a concentration of approximately 100 mg L⁻¹ of total suspended solids), T200 (use of 50% biofloc inoculum, a concentration of approximately 200 mg L⁻¹ of total suspended solids), T250 (use of 75% biofloc inoculum, a concentration of approximately 250 mg L⁻¹ of total suspended solids), T300 (use of 100% biofloc inoculum, a concentration of approximately 300 mg L⁻¹ of total suspended solids).

Shrimp	Treatments				
	CONT	T100	T200	T250	T300
Final mean weight (g)	6.47 ± 0.27	6.60 ± 0.80	5.89 ± 0.25	6.72 ± 0.26	6.31 ± 0.16
WGW (g week ⁻¹)	0.38 ± 0.04	0.40 ± 0.12	0.30 ± 0.04	0.42 ± 0.04	0.36 ± 0.03
Final biomass (g)	232.78 ± 9.84	227.72 ± 12.62	211.97 ± 8.96	235.07 ± 4.38	216.45 ± 17.65
Survival (%)	96.30 ± 6.41	96.30 ± 6.41	100.0 ± 0.0	97.22 ± 4.81	95.37 ± 8.02
FCR	1.90 ± 0.19	2.13 ± 0.30	2.18 ± 0.27	2.03 ± 0.09	2.41 ± 0.59
Productivity (kg m ⁻³)	1.28 ± 0.04	1.26 ± 0.07	1.18 ± 0.05	1.31 ± 0.02	1.20 ± 0.10

FCR (Food Conversion Rate); WGW (Weekly Weight gain).

5.3.4 Discussion and Conclusion

Chopin²⁰⁴ mentions that integrated systems increase the productivity of a system, with the production of two organisms in the same area with added economic value. The conditions of salinity²⁰⁵, dissolved oxygen²⁰⁶, pH²⁰⁷, alkalinity²⁰⁸, and TSS²⁰⁹ were kept ideal for the cultivation of *P. vannamei* shrimp. However, the temperature was below the optimum level, decreasing the animal's metabolism and affecting its growth²¹⁰, which explains the low weekly weight gain found in this study. Another factor that may have influenced shrimp growth was the movement of the feed into the macroalgae structure through aeration, making it impossible for the shrimp to consume all food. The FCR obtained in this

²⁰⁴ Chopin, T. Marine Aquaculture in Canada: Well-Established Monocultures of Finfish and Shellfish and an Emerging Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture (IMTA) Approach Including Seaweeds, Other Invertebrates, and Microbial Communities. *Fisheries* 2015, 40, 28–31.

²⁰⁵ Decamp, O.; Cody, J.; Conquest, L.; Delanoy, G.; Tacon, A.G.J. Effect of Salinity on Natural Community and Production of *Litopenaeus vannamei* (Boone), within Experimental Zero-Water Exchange Culture Systems. *Aquac. Res.* 2003, 34, 345–355.

²⁰⁶ Van Wyk, P.; Davis-Hodgkins, M.; Laramore, R.; Main, K.L.; Mountain, J.; Scarpa, J. Farming Marine Shrimp in Recirculating Freshwater Systems Harbor Branch Oceanographic Institution. *Farming Mar. Shrimp. Recirc. Freshw. Syst.* 1999, 220, 125–140.

²⁰⁷ Krummenauer, D.; Peixoto, S.; Cavalli, R.O.; Poersch, L.H.; Wasielesky, W. Superintensive Culture of White Shrimp, *Litopenaeus vannamei*, in a Biofloc Technology System in Southern Brazil at Different Stocking Densities. *J. World Aquac. Soc.* 2011, 42, 726–733.

²⁰⁸ Furtado, P.S.; Poersch, L.H.; Wasielesky, W. Effect of Calcium Hydroxide, Carbonate and Sodium Bicarbonate on Water Quality and Zootechnical Performance of Shrimp *Litopenaeus vannamei* Reared in Biofloc Technology (BFT) Systems. *Aquaculture* 2011, 321, 130–135.

²⁰⁹ Gaona, C.A.P.; de Almeida, M.S.; Viau, V.; Poersch, L.H.; Wasielesky, W. Effect of Different Total Suspended Solids Levels on a *Litopenaeus vannamei* (Boone, 1931) BFT Culture System during Biofloc Formation. *Aquac. Res.* 2017, 48, 1070–1079.

²¹⁰ Wyban, J.; Walsh, W.A.; Godin, D.M. Temperature Effects on Growth, Feeding Rate and Feed Conversion of the Pacific White Shrimp (*Penaeus vannamei*). *Aquaculture* 1995, 138, 267–279.

study (overall FCR of 2.26 ± 0.55) was similar to that found by Samocha et al.²¹¹ in a biofloc system and Morais et al.²¹² with integrated cultivation of shrimp and macroalgae in biofloc.

The use of integrated culture with the biofloc system has been widely studied, but there are few studies using macroalgae due to the high organic load and different variables in the system. The difference in salinity between the treatments in this study is probably due to the lower salinity found in the biofloc inoculum used compared with the salinity found in seawater. However, the genus *Ulva* can tolerate wide ranges of salinity and can grow well in salinities above 20²¹³. As a result, the difference in salinity between the treatments did not represent a stressful situation for the macroalgae, as it was within the macroalgae optimum performance range.

In cultivation systems that work with biofloc, alkalinity decreases throughout cultivation, and the medium becomes more acidic. This is due to the nitrification process carried out by the systems chemoautotrophic bacteria, which consume 7.0 g of alkalinity for metabolism and produce 5.85 g of carbon dioxide²¹⁴. According to Furtado et al.²¹⁵, it is recommended that alkalinity be kept above 150 mg CaCO₃ L⁻¹. To maintain it at this ideal level, calcium carbonate or calcium hydroxide can be used. Using a biofloc inoculum characterized as mature, Ferreira et al.²¹⁶ used 112.91 ± 2.99 g of calcium hydroxide in a useful volume of 300 L, resulting in 0.38 g L⁻¹ of calcium hydroxide consumption over 35 days of cultivation. Data from this study showed reduced use of calcium hydroxide to correct alkalinity, with the lowest value in the BIO75 treatment being 0.07 ± 0.06 g L⁻¹ of calcium hydroxide over 45 days of cultivation. The greater steadiness of alkalinity in our treatments is probably related to the absorption of CO₂ by the macroalgae. For macroalgae, carbon absorption is essential to maintain a balanced C:N:P (carbon:nitrogen:phosphorus) ratio, participating in the sequestration of carbon dioxide and reducing the acidity of the environment²¹⁷. Another explanation could be the consumption

²¹¹ Samocha, T.M.; Patnaik, S.; Speed, M.; Ali, A.M.; Burger, J.M.; Almeida, R.V.; Ayub, Z.; Harisanto, M.; Horowitz, A.; Brock, D.L. Use of Molasses as Carbon Source in Limited Discharge Nursery and Grow-out Systems for *Litopenaeus vannamei*. *Aquac. Eng.* 2007, 36, 184–191.

²¹² de Morais, A.P.M.; Santos, I.L.; Carneiro, R.F.S.; Routledge, E.A.B.; Hayashi, L.; de Lorenzo, M.A.; do Nascimento Vieira, F. Integrated Multitrophic Aquaculture System Applied to Shrimp, Tilapia, and Seaweed (*Ulva ohnoi*) Using Biofloc Technology. *Aquaculture* 2023, 572, 739492.

²¹³ Bews, E.; Booher, L.; Polizzi, T.; Long, C.; Kim, J.H.; Edwards, M.S. Effects of Salinity and Nutrients on Metabolism and Growth of *Ulva lactuca*: Implications for Bioremediation of Coastal Watersheds. *Mar. Pollut. Bull.* 2021, 166, 112199.

²¹⁴ Ebeling, J.M.; Timmons, M.B.; Bisogni, J.J. Engineering Analysis of the Stoichiometry of Photoautotrophic, Autotrophic, and Heterotrophic Removal of Ammonia-Nitrogen in Aquaculture Systems. *Aquaculture* 2006, 257, 346–358.

²¹⁵ Furtado, P.S.; Poersch, L.H.; Wasielesky, W. Effect of Calcium Hydroxide, Carbonate and Sodium Bicarbonate on Water Quality and Zootechnical Performance of Shrimp *Litopenaeus vannamei* Reared in Biofloc Technology (BFT) Systems. *Aquaculture* 2011, 321, 130–135.

²¹⁶ Ferreira, G.S.; Santos, D.; Schmachtl, F.; Machado, C.; Fernandes, V.; Bögner, M.; Schleder, D.D.; Seiffert, W.Q.; Vieira, F.N. Heterotrophic, Chemoautotrophic and Mature Approaches in Biofloc System for Pacific White Shrimp. *Aquaculture* 2021, 533, 736099.

²¹⁷ Chopin, T. Marine Aquaculture in Canada: Well-Established Monocultures of Finfish and Shellfish and an Emerging Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture (IMTA) Approach Including Seaweeds, Other Invertebrates, and Microbial Communities. *Fisheries* 2015, 40, 28–31.

of ammonia by the macroalgae, reducing the nitrification process in the system, and the use of inorganic carbon, which is economically advantageous to the system.

According to Silva et al.²¹⁸, only 22% of the nitrogen input is converted into shrimp biomass, 14% remains deposited in the sediment, and 57% is discarded into the environment, suggesting little efficiency in the use of available nitrogen. Ammonia is the most toxic nitrogenous compound in cultivation, and its control methods include water renewal in conventional cultivation or organic fertilization in biofloc systems²¹⁹. The CONT treatment, without the use of biofloc inoculum, aimed to use organic fertilization with molasses when concentrations exceeded 1 mg L⁻¹ in order to encourage the growth of heterotrophic bacteria to convert the ammonia in the system into bacterial biomass²²⁰. However, our study showed that despite the high shrimp stocking (200 shrimp m⁻³) and no water renewal in the control treatment, there was no increase in ammonia concentrations. The highest daily concentration in the control treatment was 0.54 mg L⁻¹, so it was not necessary to use molasses throughout the experimental period. Macroalgae have a greater affinity for absorbing ammonia because they require less energy during assimilation processes²²¹. In this study, the macroalgae in the CONT treatment were probably responsible for the primary absorption of the ammonia produced in the culture, thus delaying the nitrification process and an increase in nitrate concentrations in the culture, which was only seen in the last week of cultivation. Only at the end of cultivation (day 32) was there an increase in nitrate concentration, showing a possible growth of chemoautotrophic bacteria. According to Ferreira et al.²²², the establishment of these bacteria is slow, requiring at least 30 days with the use of chemical fertilizer for them to occur. The use of macroalgae to absorb the compost is advantageous because of the use of residual nutrients to produce biomass with commercial value, minimizing the impacts of the toxicity of this compost on the animals.

In a biofloc system, nitrate is the most concentrated nitrogenous compound at the end of cultivation and is constantly accumulated throughout the experiment due to nitrification by bacteria, which convert ammonia into nitrite and then nitrate²²³. Improper disposal of high levels of nitrate in water

²¹⁸ Da Silva, K.R.; Wasielesky, W.; Abreu, P.C. Nitrogen and Phosphorus Dynamics in the Biofloc Production of the Pacific White Shrimp, *Litopenaeus vannamei*. *J. World Aquac. Soc.* 2013, 44, 30–41.

²¹⁹ Lin, Y.C.; Chen, J.C. Acute Toxicity of Ammonia on *Litopenaeus vannamei* Boone Juveniles at Different Salinity Levels. *J. Exp. Mar. Biol. Ecol.* 2001, 259, 109–119.

²²⁰ Wasielesky, W.; Krummenauer, D.; Lara, G.; Fóes, G. Cultivo de Camarões Em Sistema de Bioflocos: Realidades e Perspectivas. *Rev. ABCC* 2013, 15, 16–26.

²²¹ Castelar, B.; Reis, R.P.; dos Santos Calheiros, A.C. *Ulva lactuca* and *U. flexuosa* (Chlorophyta, Ulvophyceae) Cultivation in Brazilian Tropical Waters: Recruitment, Growth, and Ulvan Yield. *J. Appl. Phycol.* 2014, 26, 1989–1999.

²²² Ferreira, G.S.; Santos, D.; Schmachtl, F.; Machado, C.; Fernandes, V.; Bögner, M.; Schleder, D.D.; Seiffert, W.Q.; Vieira, F.N. Heterotrophic, Chemoautotrophic and Mature Approaches in Biofloc System for Pacific White Shrimp. *Aquaculture* 2021, 533, 736099.

²²³ Krummenauer, D.; Peixoto, S.; Cavalli, R.O.; Poersch, L.H.; Wasielesky, W. Superintensive Culture of White Shrimp, *Litopenaeus vannamei*, in a Biofloc Technology System in Southern Brazil at Different Stocking Densities. *J. World Aquac. Soc.* 2011, 42, 726–733.

bodies can cause diseases such as methemoglobinemia in the population²²⁴. Therefore, the use of macroalgae as a biological treatment can provide improvements in water quality and effluent treatment. In the absence of high concentrations of ammonia, the macroalgae tend to absorb the nitrate present in the water, which occurred in this experiment, showing an absorption rate of 55% of nitrate by the macroalgae in the T250 treatment. Testing variations from 5 to 400 mg L⁻¹ of nitrate in the water, Farahdiba et al.²²⁵ found an absorption rate of around 90% of nitrate in five days in a static system. Our system is considered to be continuous, where ammonia is produced daily from animal excretion and feed waste and converted into bacterial biomass and nitrate by the bacteria present in the biofloc system. Even though nitrate is produced in the system, there was a rate of removal by the macroalgae, where the final concentration was lower than the initial concentration of the culture.

Phosphate is produced through the leaching of feed and is accumulated throughout cultivation in a biofloc system, being important for macroalgae in the formation of tissues and the process of photosynthesis. As observed by Ramos et al.²²⁶, the use of a form of biological phosphorus removal, such as macroalgae, can be more efficient than filtration and sedimentation. The better rate of nitrate and phosphate absorption may be related to the nitrogen:phosphorus (N:P) balance during the experimental period. According to Zirino et al.²²⁷, the most appropriate N:P ratio for macroalgae would be 30:1, and when it is below 29, nitrogen can be limiting, and when it is above 29, phosphorus can be limiting. During the 12 nutrient samplings, six times the N:P ratio in the T250 treatment was close to ideal, unlike the other treatments which showed a phosphorus limitation in most of the samplings.

The production of solids can come from heterotrophic bacteria, feces production, and leaching from the feed²²⁸. As there was no addition of organic carbon in the control treatment, the increase in total suspended solids was due to zero water renewal and the accumulation of particulate organic matter, reaching an average of 134.05 ± 81.36 mg L⁻¹ of total suspended solids. Therefore, at the end of the experiment, all treatments had a load of solids present in the system. Even without a significant difference in final weight between the treatments, the growth of the macroalgae may still have been affected due to the low availability of light caused by the biofloc. Macroalgae are sessile organisms in the system and can interfere with the movement of water and cause the accumulation of solids on its

²²⁴Macedo, C.F.; Sipaúba-Tavares, L. Eutrofização E Qualidade Da Água Na Piscicultura: Consequências E Recomendações Eutrophication and Water Quality in Pisciculture: Consequences and Recommendations. *Bol. Inst. Pesca* 2010, 36, 149–163.

²²⁵Farahdiba, A.U.; Hidayah, E.N.; Asmar, G.A.; Myint, Y.W. Growth and Removal of Nitrogen and Phosphorus by a Macroalgae *Cladophora glomerata* under Different Nitrate Concentrations. *Nat. Environ. Pollut. Technol.* 2020, 19, 809–813.

²²⁶Ramos, R.; Vinatea, L.; Santos, J.; Da Costa, R. Tratamiento de Efluentes Del Cultivo de *Litopenaeus vannamei* Mediante Procesos de Sedimentación, Filtración y Absorción. *Lat. Am. J. Aquat. Res.* 2010, 38, 188–200.

²²⁷Zirino, A.; Elwany, H.; Facca, C.; Maicu', F.; Neira, C.; Mendoza, G. Nitrogen to Phosphorus Ratio in the Venice (Italy) Lagoon (2001–2010) and Its Relation to Macroalgae. *Mar. Chem.* 2016, 180, 33–41.

²²⁸Gaona, C.A.P.; de Almeida, M.S.; Viau, V.; Poersch, L.H.; Wasielesky, W. Effect of Different Total Suspended Solids Levels on a *Litopenaeus vannamei* (Boone, 1931) BFT Culture System during Biofloc Formation. *Aquac. Res.* 2017, 48, 1070–1079.

surface, as seen in studies such as Carvalho et al.^{229, 230}. The deposition of solids causes a “shading” effect on the macroalgae and limits their absorption of light. The use of a larger surface area of the cultivation structure adopted in this study compared with Carvalho et al.²²⁹ may have minimized the effect of overlap due to greater movement of the macroalgae in the water column.

The different concentrations of nutrients and solids are directly linked to greater biomass production and nutrient uptake. In this study, the relative growth rate (RGR) of algae had an overall average of $0.45 \pm 0.27\% \text{ day}^{-1}$, showing an increase in biomass during cultivation. These data differed from those found by Morais et al.²³¹, who obtained a growth rate of $8.00 \pm 0.01\% \text{ day}^{-1}$ with *U. ohnoi* at a density of 1 g L^{-1} in a biofloc system, where the shrimp water was filtered and pumped into the macroalgae tank once a week, presenting a lower solids load. This difference in growth can be explained by the fact that the macroalgae in this experiment were grown in the same experimental unit as the shrimp and were subject to the accumulation of solids, nutrients, and fluctuations in water quality parameters. This system was used as a way of evaluating the insertion of macroalgae into adapted shrimp farms. The low light incidence for the macroalgae was also a key factor in the low growth rate caused by the greenhouse and the accumulation of solids. It was also shown that the weight gain of the macroalgae was positively linked to the rate of nutrient removal, indicating that the macroalgae were absorbing nutrients for growth in the first and second weeks. However, in the last week, it was seen that a greater absorption of nitrate was related to weight loss of the macroalgae. Lower growth rates can also be caused by stress, which triggers reproductive events, with the loss of biomass for spore formation²³² [3], so it is likely that the macroalgae were absorbing nutrients and converting this energy into reproductive events rather than growth. Drastic changes in temperature in agricultural greenhouses have been reported, where the lowest temperatures were recorded in the morning and the highest temperatures in the afternoon, which can cause intense spore release, as seen by Carl et al.²³³ [52]. In this experiment, the maximum temperature was 30.3, and the minimum was 21.7 °C. A reproduction event can be noticed due to the presence of “ghost tissues,” which are transparent parts due to the release of spores²³¹, which was noticed in this study throughout the experiment. However, the

²²⁹ Carvalho, A.; Costa, L.C.d.O.; Holanda, M.; Poersch, L.H.; Turan, G. Influence of Total Suspended Solids on the Growth of the Sea Lettuce *Ulva lactuca* Integrated with the Pacific White Shrimp *Litopenaeus vannamei* in a Biofloc System. *Fishes* 2023, 8, 163.

²³⁰ Carvalho, A.; Costa, L.C.d.O.; Holanda, M.; Gonçalves, M.; Santos, J.; Costa, C.S.B.; Turan, G.; Poersch, L.H. Growth of the Macroalgae *Ulva lactuca* Cultivated at Different Depths in a Biofloc Integrated System with Shrimp and Fish. *Phycology* 2023, 3, 280–293.

²³¹ de Morais, A.P.M.; Santos, I.L.; Carneiro, R.F.S.; Routledge, E.A.B.; Hayashi, L.; de Lorenzo, M.A.; do Nascimento Vieira, F. Integrated Multitrophic Aquaculture System Applied to Shrimp, Tilapia, and Seaweed (*Ulva ohnoi*) Using Biofloc Technology. *Aquaculture* 2023, 572, 739492.

²³² Copertino, M.D.S.; Tormena, T.; Seeliger, U. Biofiltering Efficiency, Uptake and Assimilation Rates of *Ulva clathrata* (Roth) J. Agardh (Chlorophyceae) Cultivated in Shrimp Aquaculture Waste Water. *J. Appl. Phycol.* 2009, 21, 31–45.

²³³ Carl, C.; De Nys, R.; Lawton, R.J.; Paul, N.A. Methods for the Induction of Reproduction in a Tropical Species of Filamentous *Ulva*. *PLoS ONE* 2014, 9, 2–11.

performance of the macroalgae obtained in this study differed from that presented by Martins et al.²³⁴ [53], who obtained a decrease in biomass during the experiment, which may be associated with the natural environment where the macroalgae were collected and the acclimatization of the macroalgae to the system.

The composition of macroalgae can change according to the environment in which it is found, which can affect its nutritional composition²³⁵. Msuya & Neori²³⁶ showed that the protein content increases significantly with increasing nutrient addition, reaching $44.3 \pm 2.7\%$ protein at the highest level of nutrient addition ($38 \text{ g N m}^{-2} \text{ day}^{-1}$). The macroalgae cultivated with a concentration of $56.67 \pm 5.77 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$ of nitrate (T250) showed higher protein concentrations, probably due to the greater availability of nitrogen in the water compared with the CONT treatment. Even so, the CONT treatment had a higher protein content than studies carried out in clear water, such as Tabarsa et al.²³⁷, who found values of $10.69 \pm 0.67 \text{ g } 100 \text{ g}^{-1}$ of protein in the macroalgae. This high concentration is probably due to the continuous absorption of ammonia excreted by the shrimp. As for the result found for ash, little is known about ash variations in the proximal composition of macroalgae; however, some factors can alter this concentration, such as high macroalgae densities and an inverse proportion of nitrogen concentration in the tissue²³⁸. Therefore, the higher the nitrogen concentration in the macroalgae tissue, the lower the ash concentration, both factors being verified in this study.

Chlorophylls are green pigments present in thylakoids and are essential in the reaction to capture light and carry out photosynthesis, and their increase is associated with the need to increase the number of pigments to maximize photosynthesis²³⁹. Therefore, the higher concentrations of chlorophyll-a present in the treatment with inoculum (T250) are associated with the higher organic load present in this treatment, compared with the control, which started in clear water. The biofloc system contains microbial flocs that make up the total suspended solids. This organic load reduces the entry of light into the water and can negatively influence the growth of macroalgae.

²³⁴ Martins, M.A.; da SILVA, V.F.; Tarapuez, P.R.; Hayashi, L.; Vieira, F.D.N. Cultivation of the Seaweed *Ulva* Spp. with Effluent from a Shrimp Biofloc Rearing System: Different Species and Stocking Density. *Bol. Inst. Pesca* 2020, 46.

²³⁵ Duke, C.S.; Litaker, W.; Ramus, J. Effects of the Temperature, Nitrogen Supply and Tissue Nitrogen on Ammonium Uptake Rates of the Chlorophyte Seaweeds *Ulva curvata* and *Codium decorticatum*. *J. Phycol.* 1989, 25, 113–120.

²³⁶ Msuya, F.E.; Neori, A. Effect of Water Aeration and Nutrient Load Level on Biomass Yield, N Uptake and Protein Content of the Seaweed *Ulva lactuca* Cultured in Seawater Tanks. *J. Appl. Phycol.* 2008, 20, 1021–1031.

²³⁷ Tabarsa, M.; Rezaei, M.; Ramezani, Z.; Waaland, J.R. Chemical Compositions of the Marine Algae *Gracilaria salicornia* (Rhodophyta) and *Ulva lactuca* (Chlorophyta) as a Potential Food Source. *J. Sci. Food Agric.* 2012, 92, 2500–2506.

²³⁸ Queirós, A.S.; Circuncisão, A.R.; Pereira, E.; Válega, M.; Abreu, M.H.; Silva, A.M.S.; Cardoso, S.M. Valuable Nutrients from *Ulva rigida*: Modulation by Seasonal and Cultivation Factors. *Appl. Sci.* 2021, 11, 6137.

²³⁹ Holdt, S.L.; Kraan, S. Bioactive Compounds in Seaweed: Functional Food Applications and Legislation. *J. Appl. Phycol.* 2011, 23, 543–597.

The chlorophyll-b values found in this study were also higher than those found by Silva et al.²⁴⁰, who showed maximum values of $1.21 \pm 0.10 \mu\text{g mg}$ in the macroalgae *U. rigida* cultivated in a multitrophic system. According to Levavasseur²⁴¹, macroalgae increase their absorption spectrum to maximize the capture of light energy. Therefore, the macroalgae in this experiment increased the concentration of chlorophyll-b as a way of capturing light. Fillit.²⁴², evaluating the effect of seasonal changes on the pigment concentration of the macroalgae *U. rigida* showed that at times of the year with greater light intensity and photoperiod, the pigment content decreased and that shading effects caused by a greater density of algae also increased the pigment concentration.

Carotenoids are photosynthetic pigments responsible both for collecting light energy and for preventing the formation of reactive oxygen species caused by light and air stress²⁴³. Our values were similar to those found by Yildiz et al.²⁴⁴ in the macroalgae *U. rigida* collected in the environment. However, Eismann et al.²⁴⁵ show that the variation in total carotenoids is influenced by the growth rates of macroalgae. Therefore, high growth rates increase the carotenoid content, which can reach $0.92 \pm 0.57 \text{ mg g}^{-1}$. The low RGR values found in this study may be due to the deposition of solids in the macroalgae because of their accumulation during cultivation and temperature variations, which may have influenced lower concentrations of total carotenoids compared with those found in the literature.

Sampath-Wiley et al.²⁴⁶ showed that different stressors can affect antioxidant levels in macroalgae. Macroalgae cultivated in the lower intertidal zone that were protected from exposure to light and moisture loss showed a decrease in antioxidant levels. In contrast the macroalgae cultivated in this study, which were subjected to temperature variations and high concentrations of solids and nutrients and consequently showed a high DPPH inhibition percentage, promoted an increase in antioxidant levels. For phenolic compounds, according to Mabeau & Fleurence²⁴⁷, the concentrations vary according to the group of macroalgae studied. Green and red macroalgae have a higher protein

²⁴⁰ Silva, A.F.R.; Abreu, H.; Silva, A.M.S.; Cardoso, S.M. Effect of Oven-Drying on the Recovery of Valuable Compounds from *Ulva rigida*, *Gracilaria* Sp. and *Fucus vesiculosus*. *Mar. Drugs* 2019, 17, 90.

²⁴¹ Levavasseur, G. Analyse Comparée Des Complexes Pigment-Protéines de Chlorophycophytes Marines Benthiques. *Phycologia* 1989, 28, 1–14. *Phycology* 2024, 4 52

²⁴² Fillit, M. Seasonal Changes in the Photosynthetic Capacities and Pigment Content of *Ulva rigida* in a Mediterranean Coastal Lagoon. *Bot. Mar.* 1995, 38, 271–280.

²⁴³ Astorg, P. Food Carotenoids and Cancer Prevention: An Overview of Current Research. *Trends Food Sci. Technol.* 1997, 8, 406–413.

²⁴⁴ Yildiz, G.; Celikler, S.; Vatan, O.; Dere, S. Determination of the Anti-Oxidative Capacity and Bioactive Compounds in Green Seaweed *Ulva rigida* C. Agardh. *Int. J. Food Prop.* 2012, 15, 1182–1189.

²⁴⁵ Eismann, A.I.; Perpetuo Reis, R.; Ferreira da Silva, A.; Negrão Cavalcanti, D. *Ulva* Spp. Carotenoids: Responses to Environmental Conditions. *Algal Res.* 2020, 48, 101916.

²⁴⁶ Sampath-Wiley, P.; Neefus, C.D.; Jahnke, L.S. Seasonal Effects of Sun Exposure and Emersion on Intertidal Seaweed Physiology: Fluctuations in Antioxidant Contents, Photosynthetic Pigments and Photosynthetic Efficiency in the Red Alga *Porphyra umbilicalis* Kützting (Rhodophyta, Bangiales). *J. Exp. Mar. Biol. Ecol.* 2008, 361, 83–91.

²⁴⁷ Mabeau, S.; Fleurence, J. Seaweed in Food Products: Biochemical and Nutritional Aspects. *Trends Food Sci. Technol.* 1993, 4, 103–107.

content and lower levels of phenolic compounds compared with brown macroalgae. Our study showed values similar to those found by Silva et al.²⁴⁸ of 0.74 ± 0.13 mg GAE g⁻¹ with the macroalgae *U. rigida* cultivated in an integrated system.

The utilization of macroalgae within an integrated system alongside shrimp proved to be feasible in the nitrate and total suspended solids concentrations at 56.67 ± 5.77 mgL⁻¹ and 246.67 ± 2.89 mgL⁻¹, respectively. It also makes the system more sustainable by reusing water from existing biofloc cultivation. The macroalgae exhibited favorable nitrate and phosphate removal rates, indicating the assimilation of these compounds into biomass formation and an increase in economically valuable pigments within the macroalgae. Furthermore, in addition to nutrient absorption, the system effectively maintained alkalinity and pH levels, facilitating the efficient upkeep of biofloc cultivation.

²⁴⁸ Silva, A.F.R.; Abreu, H.; Silva, A.M.S.; Cardoso, S.M. Effect of Oven-Drying on the Recovery of Valuable Compounds from *Ulva rigida*, *Gracilaria* Sp. and *Fucus vesiculosus*. *Mar. Drugs* 2019, 17, 90.

5.4 Effects of Total Suspended Solids on the Sea lettuce *Ulva Lactuca* integrated with shrimp *Penaeus vannamei* (Experiment 4)

5.4.1 Introduction

Shrimp production using biofloc technology (BFT), normally carried out without water renewal, results in the accumulation of nutrients in the system²⁴⁹. This occurs due to the action of microorganisms that transform shrimp excreta and food remains into protein and inorganic nutrients²⁵⁰. Chemoautotrophic and heterotrophic bacteria grow during the culture. The first group of bacteria works in the oxidation of ammonia to nitrite and later to nitrate, which is accumulated in the system, along with phosphorus from the feed²⁵¹. Heterotrophic bacteria participate in the conversion of ammonia into bacterial biomass and, together with the accumulation of feces and feed remains, increase the concentration of total suspended solids in the system. The production of waste is constant during cultivation, and when it is not properly disposed of or treated, it can generate problems in the water quality in the production system and environmental problems in the release of effluents without treatment²⁵².

The total suspended solids are important in the water quality of the system and must be maintained between 100 to 300 mg L⁻¹²⁵³. In addition to water quality, microbial flocs function as a complementary source of natural food within the crop²⁵⁴. Azim and Little²⁵⁵ nutritionally described biofloc containing 38% protein and 3% lipid in dry matter, showing a high nutritional value, which may depend on the carbon source used in the system. Wasielesky et al.²⁵⁶ showed that it is possible to reduce the feeding frequency of shrimp *L. vannamei* when cultivated in a biofloc system.

²⁴⁹ Da Silva, K.R.; Wasielesky, W.; Abreu, P.C. Nitrogen and Phosphorus Dynamics in the Biofloc Production of the Pacific White Shrimp, *Litopenaeus vannamei*. *J. World Aquac. Soc.* 2013, 44, 30–41. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jwas.12009>.

²⁵⁰ Krummenauer, D.; Abreu, P.C.; Poersch, L.; Reis, P.A.C.P.; Suita, S.M.; dos Reis, W.G.; Wasielesky, W. The Relationship between Shrimp (*Litopenaeus vannamei*) Size and Biofloc Consumption Determined by the Stable Isotope Technique. *Aquaculture* 2020, 529, 735635. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2020.735635>.

²⁵¹ Ferreira, G.S.; Santos, D.; Schmachtl, F.; Machado, C.; Fernandes, V.; Bögner, M.; Schleder, D.D.; Seiffert, W.Q.; Vieira, F.N. Heterotrophic, Chemoautotrophic and Mature Approaches in Biofloc System for Pacific White Shrimp. *Aquaculture* 2021, 533, 736099. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2020.736099>.

²⁵² Verdian, A.H.; Effendi, I.; Budidardi, T.; Diatin, I. Production Performance Improvement of White Shrimp (*Litopenaeus vannamei*) Culture with Integrated Multi Trophic Aquaculture System in Seribu Is-lands, Jakarta, Indonesia. *Iran. J. Fish. Sci.* 2020, 19, 1415–1427. <https://doi.org/10.22092/ijfs.2019.120676>.

²⁵³ Gaona, C.A.P.; de Almeida, M.S.; Viau, V.; Poersch, L.H.; Wasielesky, W. Effect of Different Total Suspended Solids Levels on a *Litopenaeus vannamei* (Boone, 1931) BFT Culture System during Biofloc Formation. *Aquac. Res.* 2017, 48, 1070–1079. <https://doi.org/10.1111/are.12949>.

²⁵⁴ Ahmad, I.; Babitha Rani, A.M.; Verma, A.K.; Maqsood, M. Biofloc Technology: An Emerging Avenue in Aquatic Animal Healthcare and Nutrition. *Aquac. Int.* 2017, 25, 1215–1226. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10499-016-0108-8>.

²⁵⁵ Azim, M.E.; Little, D.C. The Biofloc Technology (BFT) in Indoor Tanks: Water Quality, Biofloc Composition, and Growth and Welfare of Nile Tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*). *Aquaculture* 2008, 283, 29–35. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2008.06.036>.

²⁵⁶ Wasielesky, W.; Bezerra, A.; Poersch, L.; Hoffling, F.B.; Krummenauer, D. Effect of Feeding Frequency on the White Shrimp *Litopenaeus vannamei* during the Pilot-Scale Nursery Phase of a Superintensive Culture in a Biofloc System. *J. World Aquac. Soc.* 2020, 51, 1175–1191. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jwas.12694>.

Despite the benefits of microbial flocs in the shrimp culture system, its effect on macroalgae growth is unknown. As macroalgae are photosynthetic organisms, the concentration of solids can interfere with the light capture that is essential for their growth. Brito et al.²⁵⁷ showed the deposition of solids on macroalgae, which may have a negative effect on its growth. However, the nutritional value of macroalgae can also change when grown in biofloc. Legarda et al.²⁵⁸ showed an increase in nitrogen, phosphorus, chlorophyll a, and carotenoids when macroalgae were cultivated in an integrated system in biofloc.

One way to take advantage of the nitrogen and phosphorus accumulated in the system is integration with other species of different trophic levels in production, as proposed by Chopin²⁵⁹ in an integrated multi-trophic aquaculture (IMTA). In the system, residues are reused by different species, increasing the final productivity of the cultivation and sustainability. The IMTA system is composed of a species fed with commercial feed, such as shrimp or fish, and then a species capable of absorbing inorganic compounds dissolved in the water, such as macroalgae, and a species that consumes organic compounds, such as oyster, is inserted into the system, which will feed on suspended particles in the culture²⁶⁰.

Considering the precepts in the IMTA and associating them with the biofloc, the presence of macroalgae in integrated cultures with shrimp can promote the absorption of nutrients from the culture, such as ammonia, nitrate and phosphate. Thus, the use of cultivation effluents for the cultivation of macroalgae or integrated cultivations can be an alternative with lower financial and environmental costs, bearing in mind that enrichment culture media, such as von Stosch, have a high cost due to expensive chemical compounds including essential vitamins that make their use unfeasible for large-scale production²⁶¹.

The choice of species for the composition of the systems can be a limiting factor for the success of the production. Macroalgae have rapid growth due to the efficiency on converting solar energy into

²⁵⁷ Brito, L.O.; Arantes, R.; Magnotti, C.; Derner, R.; Pchara, F.; Olivera, A.; Vinatea, L. Water Quality and Growth of Pacific White Shrimp *Litopenaeus vannamei* (Boone) in Co-Culture with Green Seaweed *Ulva lactuca* (Linnaeus) in Intensive System. *Aquac. Int.* 2014, 22, 497–508. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10499-013-9659-0>.

²⁵⁸ Legarda, E.C.; da Silva, D.; Miranda, C.S.; Pereira, P.K.M.; Martins, M.A.; Machado, C.; de Lorenzo, M.A.; Hayashi, L.; do Nascimento Vieira, F. Sea Lettuce Integrated with Pacific White Shrimp and Mullet Cultivation in Biofloc Impact System Performance and the Sea Lettuce Nutritional Composition. *Aqua-culture* 2021, 534, 736265. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2020.736265>.

²⁵⁹ Chopin, T. Marine Aquaculture in Canada: Well-Established Monocultures of Finfish and Shellfish and an Emerging Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture (IMTA) Approach Including Seaweeds, Other Invertebrates, and Microbial Communities. *Fisheries* 2015, 40, 28–31. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03632415.2014.986571>.

²⁶⁰ Troell, M.; Joyce, A.; Chopin, T.; Neori, A.; Buschmann, A.H.; Fang, J.G. Ecological Engineering in Aquaculture—Potential for Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture (IMTA) in Marine Offshore Systems. *Aquaculture* 2009, 297, 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2009.09.010>.

²⁶¹ Mansilla, A.; Rodriguez, J.P.; Souza, J.M.C.; Rosenfeld, S.; Ojeda, J.; Yokoya, N.S. Growth Responses to Temperature, Salinity and Nutrient Variations, and Biomass Variation and Phenology of *Ahnfeltia plicata* (Rhodophyta, Ahnfeltiales): A Commercially Interesting Agarophyte from the Magellanic Region, Chile. *J. Appl. Phycol.* 2014, 26, 1133–1139. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10811-013-0150-0>.

biomass, due to their simple cellular structures compared to terrestrial plants²⁶², generating large biomasses in a short time. Alencar et al.²⁶³ showed that the use of effluents from a shrimp culture provided a relative growth rate of 8.8% day⁻¹ of the macroalgae *U. lactuca* and an absorption efficiency with an average of 90% for ammonium (NH₄⁺) and orthophosphate (PO₄⁻³). Ramos et al.²⁶⁴, analyzing integration of another macroalgae, *U. fasciata*, with the cultivation of Pacific white shrimp (*L. vannamei*) with sedimentation and filtration systems by oysters, showed that the combination of systems enabled improvements in several aspects of water quality, using macroalgae in the removal of dissolved nutrients in the system.

Another factor to be considered is the commercial importance of the macroalgae cultivated in the system. Seaweed cultivation is economically viable due to the presence of high-value compounds in algae cells, which are extracted and used for the manufacture of cosmetics, pharmaceuticals, and chemical compounds. El-baz et al.²⁶⁵ showed that among species of red and green algae, *U. lactuca* had a higher lipid concentration and inhibitory actions on viral and bacterial activities. In industry, macroalgae have wide applicability, with them being a good nutritional alternative and having a good acceptability, as shown by Turan and Tekogul²⁶⁶.

The use of macroalgae as bioremediators has been widely used and has been shown to be efficient. Copertino et al.²⁶⁷, carrying out a study with *U. clathrata* recirculating water from a *L. vannamei* culture, showed a maximum relative growth rate of 20% day⁻¹ and an uptake of 90% of total ammonia nitrogen (TAN) of the system, demonstrating the feasibility of this integration. However, depending on the area and dispersion of the effluent, large macroalgae biomasses are necessary and may be unfeasible²⁶⁸. There has been an attempt to adjust the proportion of macroalgae in the crop so that the absorption

²⁶² Kılınc, B.; Cirik, S.; Turan, G. Seaweeds for Food and Industrial Applications. In Food Industry; IntechOpen: London, UK, 2013; pp. 735–748.

²⁶³ Alencar, J.R. de; Junior, P.A.H.; Celino, J.J. Cultivo de Camarão Branco *Litopenaeus vannamei* (Bo-one, 1931) Com a Macroalga *Ulva lactuca* Linnaeus (Chlorophyta) No Tratamento de Efluentes Em Sistema Fechado de Recirculação. *Rev. Biol. Ciências Terra* 2010, 10, 117–137.

²⁶⁴ Ramos, R.; Vinatea, L.; Santos, J.; Da Costa, R. Tratamiento de Efluentes Del Cultivo de *Litopenaeus vannamei* Mediante Procesos de Sedimentación, Filtración y Absorción. *Lat. Am. J. Aquat. Res.* 2010, 38, 188–200. <https://doi.org/10.3856/vol38-issue2-fulltext-3>.

²⁶⁵ El Baz, F.K.; El-Baroty, G.S.; Ibrahim, A.E.; Abd El Baky, H.H. Cytotoxicity, Antioxidants and Antimicrobial Activities of Lipids Extracted from Some Marine Algae. *J. Aquac. Res. Dev.* 2014, 5, 5–9. <https://doi.org/10.4172/2155-9546.1000284>.

²⁶⁶ Turan, G.; Tekogul, H. The Turkish Mezzes Formulated with Protein-Rich Green Sea Vegetable (Chlorophyta), *Ulva rigida*, Cultured in Onshore Tank System. *J. Aquat. Food Prod. Technol.* 2014, 23, 447–452. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10498850.2012.723307>.

²⁶⁷ Copertino, M.D.S.; Tormena, T.; Seeliger, U. Biofiltering Efficiency, Uptake and Assimilation Rates of *Ulva clathrata* (Roth) J. Agardh (Chlorophyceae) Cultivated in Shrimp Aquaculture Waste Water. *J. Appl. Phycol.* 2009, 21, 31–45. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10811-008-9357-x>.

²⁶⁸ Wei, Z.; You, J.; Wu, H.; Yang, F.; Long, L.; Liu, Q.; Huo, Y.; He, P. Bioremediation Using *Gracilaria lemaneiformis* to Manage the Nitrogen and Phosphorous Balance in an Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture System in Yantian Bay, China. *Mar. Pollut. Bull.* 2017, 121, 313–319. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2017.04.034>.

of nutrients is still effective. Alencar et al.²⁶⁹ found better growth and nutrient absorption results with a density of 3 g L⁻¹; this high density is convenient in small volumes of water. Del Río et al.²⁷⁰, using *U. rigida* as a biofilter for fish tanks, found that the results are good at densities between 1.5 and 2.5 g L⁻¹. However, in shrimp farming in a biofloc system with high organic load and nutrients, little is known about the ideal density for the maintenance of the system and on the performance of macroalgae in cultivation in a biofloc system and alternatives to optimize nutrient absorption. Therefore, the objective of this work is to evaluate the influence of the seaweed *Ulva lactuca* in the cultivation of the shrimp *Litopenaeus vannamei* in a biofloc system.

5.4.2 Trial Methodology

The experiments were carried out at the Marine Aquaculture Station (EMA), Institute of Oceanography of the Federal University of Rio Grande (IO-FURG), located at Cassino Beach, Rio Grande, Rio Grande do Sul, Brazil. Two experiments were carried out with the macroalgae *U. lactuca*. Macroalgae were collected at Cassino Beach (32° 17' 52.30" S—52° 15' 59.80" W), Rio Grande, RS, Brazil. After collection, the algae samples were taken to the laboratory for removal of epiphytes and acclimatized until the beginning of the experiments. The shrimp used in the second experiment came from cultivation in a greenhouse at the Shrimp Culture Laboratory, Marine Aquaculture Station (EMA).

This experiment aimed to evaluate the growth of macroalgae *U. lactuca* with different concentrations of solids from a cultivation in a biofloc system compared with a specific culture medium.

The experimental design was carried out with three treatments in triplicate, namely: (1) BFT: cultivation of *U. lactuca* in effluent from shrimp cultivation in a biofloc system, with 400 mg L⁻¹ of TSS; (2) DEC: cultivation of *U. lactuca* in effluent from shrimp culture in a biofloc system, after a period of decantation of solids, with 30 mg L⁻¹ of TSS; (3) VS: cultivation of *U. lactuca* in standard von Stosch enrichment solution²⁷¹ at a concentration of 10 mL L⁻¹ (Table 10) and sea water, without the presence of TSS.

Five litter transparent plastic containers (or carboys) with 3 L useful volume and an area of 0.13 m⁻² exposed to light were used for lab cultivation of the macroalgae. After algae were transferred into the

²⁶⁹ Alencar, J.R. de; Junior, P.A.H.; Celino, J.J. Cultivo de Camarão Branco *Litopenaeus vannamei* (Bo-one, 1931) Com a Macroalga *Ulva lacuata* Linneaus (Chlorophyta) No Tratamento de Efluentes Em Sistema Fechado de Recirculação. Rev. Biol. Ciências Terra 2010, 10, 117–137.

²⁷⁰ del Río, M.J.; Ramazanov, Z.; García-Reina, G. *Ulva rigida* (Ulvales, Chlorophyta) Tank Culture as Biofilters for Dissolved Inorganic Nitrogen from Fishpond Effluents. Hydrobiologia 1996, 326, 61–66.

²⁷¹ Guiry, M.D.; Cunningham, E.M. Photoperiodic and Temperature Responses in the Reproduction of North-Eastern Atlantic *Gigartina acicularis* (Rhodophyta: Gigartinales). Phycologia 1984, 23, 357–367. <https://doi.org/10.2216/i0031-8884-23-3-357.1>.

culture units, the top of the containers was covered with a transparent PVC film to prevent water evaporation and contamination.

The experiment was carried out for 35 days under controlled conditions of a temperature of 26.58 ± 0.05 , with 12:12 h light/dark photoperiod, $3,013.89 \pm 107.64$ LUX light intensity, and total light per day of 2.39 ± 0.09 micromole day⁻¹. Constant aeration was provided using a blower (3900 L hour⁻¹) that directed air through a porous airstone of 15 cm in length in each experimental unit. To carry out the experiment in the laboratory, a density of 2 g L⁻¹ ²⁷² of macroalgae was used.

For the treatments with biofloc, an effluent from a shrimp culture in a BFT system in a greenhouse was used, which lasted 43 days, at a density of 400 shrimp m³. The water quality of the system was measured with 66 mg L⁻¹ of nitrate, 5.6 mg L⁻¹ of phosphate and 400 mg L⁻¹ of total suspended solids (TSS), indicating that the system was mature ²⁷³, and with an acceptable solids concentration for the cultivation of shrimp in biofloc²⁷⁴.

Table 10. Composition of von Stosch enrichment medium modified and adapted by Guiry and Cunningham [22].

Chemical Compounds	Medium Solution (g·L ⁻¹ dH ₂ O)	Concentration Used	Concentration in the Final Medium (M)
Na ₂ β-glycerophosphate	5.36	10 mL	2.48×10^{-4}
NaNO ₃	42.52	10 mL	5.00×10^{-3}
FeSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	0.28	10 mL	1.00×10^{-5}
MnCl ₂ ·4H ₂ O	1.96	10 mL	1.00×10^{-4}
Na ₂ EDTA·2H ₂ O	3.72	10 mL	1.00×10^{-4}
Vitamins	-	10 mL	
Vitamins			
Thiamine HCl	-	200 mg	5.93×10^{-6}
Biotin	0.1	1 mL	4.09×10^{-9}
Cyanocobalamin	0.2	1 mL	1.48×10^{-9}

This effluent was placed in natura in the BFT treatment for the macroalgae culture, with a concentration of 400 mg L⁻¹ of total solids in suspension. For the DEC treatment, the effluent underwent a decantation process for 30 min, so that the denser solids could settle and be removed

²⁷² del Río, M.J.; Ramazanov, Z.; García-Reina, G. Ulva rigida (Ulvales, Chlorophyta) Tank Culture as Biofilters for Dissolved Inorganic Nitrogen from Fishpond Effluents. *Hydrobiologia* 1996, 326, 61–66.

²⁷³ Ferreira, G.S.; Santos, D.; Schmachtl, F.; Machado, C.; Fernandes, V.; Bögner, M.; Schleder, D.D.; Seiffert, W.Q.; Vieira, F.N. Heterotrophic, Chemoautotrophic and Mature Approaches in Biofloc System for Pacific White Shrimp. *Aquaculture* 2021, 533, 736099. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2020.736099>.

²⁷⁴ Gaona, C.A.P.; de Almeida, M.S.; Viau, V.; Poersch, L.H.; Wasielesky, W. Effect of Different Total Suspended Solids Levels on a Litopenaeus vannamei (Boone, 1931) BFT Culture System during Biofloc Formation. *Aquac. Res.* 2017, 48, 1070–1079. <https://doi.org/10.1111/are.12949>.

from the water. This resulted in a concentration of solids lower (30 mg L^{-1}) than that found in the shrimp tanks (400 mg L^{-1}).

For the control treatment, a 10 mL L^{-1} von Stosch enrichment solution modified by Guiry and Cunningham²⁷⁵ was used. None of the treatments were renewed in order to maintain a standard. Therefore, the von Stosch solution was only inoculated into the experimental units at the beginning of the experiment. To prepare the von Stosch enrichment solution, 940 mL of filtered seawater was used and 10 mL of each solution made was added (Table 1). To prepare the vitamins, 950 mL of filtered and sterilized water was used, the Thiamine HCl was dissolved, and 1 mL of the other solutions produced was added (Table 10). The initial concentrations of nutrients in the treatment von Stosch solution were 0.0 ± 0.0 , 0.0 ± 0.0 , 5.0 ± 0.0 , and $1.2 \pm 0.0 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$ of total ammonium nitrogen, nitrite, nitrate, and phosphate, respectively.

The experiment was carried out in a greenhouse structure unit with the objective of evaluating the optimum density of the macroalgae, *U. lactuca*, in the integrated culture with the shrimp *L. vannamei*, to optimize the absorption of nutrients from the system during the 35 days of the experimental period. Four treatments with three replications were applied as follows: IMTA 1 treatment: integrated shrimp culture with *U. lactuca* (1 g L^{-1}); IMTA 2 treatment: integrated shrimp culture with *U. lactuca* (2 g L^{-1}); IMTA 3 treatment: integrated shrimp culture with *U. lactuca* (3 g L^{-1}); and MONO C treatment: monoculture of shrimp without *U. lactuca*.

A total of 12 shrimp tanks with 300 L of total capacity with a base diameter of 0.81 m and a height of 0.53 m and 150 L of useful volume for each tank were used for this experiment. Six rectangular floating structures ($40 \times 30 \times 5 \text{ cm}$) were used as *U. lactuca* cultivation units. Each shrimp tank contained a single floating structure for the macroalgae; they were placed close to the surface, by using a rectangular structure ($40 \times 30 \times 5 \text{ cm}$) made of sponge and a 5 mm polyethylene mesh, covering an area of 0.12 m^2 of the tank surface, and were subject to a daily light intensity of $28.68 \pm 8.53 \text{ moles day}^{-1}$ (Figure 26).

The water exchange was not applied, and the aeration was maintained by a blower (4 CV) that injected air into three 20 cm-long micro-perforated hoses per tank. The density used in all the experimental treatments was 300 shrimp m^3 according to Kruppenauer et al.²⁷⁶.

²⁷⁵ Guiry, M.D.; Cunningham, E.M. Photoperiodic and Temperature Responses in the Reproduction of North-Eastern Atlantic *Gigartina acicularis* (Rhodophyta: Gigartinales). *Phycologia* 1984, 23, 357–367. <https://doi.org/10.2216/i0031-8884-23-3-357.1>.

²⁷⁶ Kruppenauer, D.; Peixoto, S.; Cavalli, R.O.; Poersch, L.H.; Wasielesky, W. Superintensive Culture of White Shrimp, *Litopenaeus vannamei*, in a Biofloc Technology System in Southern Brazil at Different Stocking Densities. *J. World Aquac. Soc.* 2011, 42, 726–733. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1749-7345.2011.00507.x>.

To carry out the experiment in a greenhouse, water from shrimp cultivation in a biofloc system in progress (inoculum) was used. The experimental units were filled with 120 L of seawater (80%) and 30 L (20%) of inoculum from a shrimp biofloc culture.

Figure 26. The rectangular floating structure used for *U. lactuca* cultivation in the shrimp tank.

The inoculum had 45 days of culture, with a well-established bacterial community according to Ferreira et al.²⁷⁷, showing 70 mg L⁻¹ of nitrate, 4 mg L⁻¹ of phosphate, and 650 mg L⁻¹ of total suspended solids (TSS). The concentrations of total ammonia nitrogen, nitrite, nitrate, phosphate, and total suspended solids were measured as 0.8 ± 0.1, 0.1 ± 0.0, 14.0 ± 0.0, 0.7 ± 0.1 and 127.5 ± 23.8 mg L⁻¹, respectively. For water quality, parameters such as temperature (°C), salinity (‰), dissolved oxygen (DO, mg L⁻¹), and pH were measured daily in all of the experimental tanks, with the aid of a multiparameter probe (YSI, model Pro-20, USA) and a benchtop pH meter (Mettler To-ledo, FEP20, Brazil). Salinity was measured weekly using a multiparameter (YSI, model Pro-20, USA). Water samples were collected from near the surface and near the aeration points from each experimental tank and the water samples were kept in plastic containers and taken for analysis immediately. The daily total ammonia nitrogen (or TAN, mg L⁻¹) and nitrite (NO₂, mg L⁻¹) were analyzed according to the methodology of UNESCO²⁷⁸ and Bendschneider and Robinson²⁷⁹. When the concentration of total ammonia nitrogen

²⁷⁷ Ferreira, G.S.; Santos, D.; Schmachtl, F.; Machado, C.; Fernandes, V.; Bögner, M.; Schleder, D.D.; Seiffert, W.Q.; Vieira, F.N. Heterotrophic, Chemoautotrophic and Mature Approaches in Biofloc System for Pacific White Shrimp. *Aquaculture* 2021, 533, 736099. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2020.736099>.

²⁷⁸ Unesco. *Chemical Methods for Use in Marine Environmental Monitoring*; Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission: Paris, France, 1983.

²⁷⁹ Bendschneider, K.; Robinson, R.J. *A New Spectrophotometric Method for the Determination of Nitrite in Water*; Technical Report No. 8; Office of Naval Research: Seattle, WA, USA, 1952.

(TAN) was greater than 1 mg L^{-1} , molasses was used in ratio 6:1 carbon: nitrogen to control water quality²⁸⁰. Nitrate (NO_3 , mg L^{-1}) and phosphate (PO_4 , mg L^{-1}) were analyzed using the methodology described by Aminot and Chaussepied²⁸¹ and they were monitored three times a week. Turbidity (NTU) was measured by a portable turbidimeter (Hach®, 2100P, Portugal) and total suspended solids (or TSS, mg L^{-1}) were quantified by filtration and gravimetry according to the methodology described by Baumgarten et al.²⁸². Turbidity and TSS were determined weekly. The total alkalinity ($\text{mg CaCO}_3 \text{ L}^{-1}$) was monitored according to the methodology presented by APHA²⁸³ and it was measured weekly in the lab-scale experiments and twice a week in the pilot-scale experiments in greenhouse conditions. To maintain CaCO_3 above 150 mg L^{-1} , calcium hydroxide was used²⁸⁴. Weekly sedimentable solids (or SS, ml L^{-1}) were measured by using the Imhoff cone method²⁸³ in the pilot-scale experiments conducted under greenhouse conditions.

Initial and final algal biomass yields were measured. In order to determine the wet (or fresh) biomass, *Ulva* thallus was first collected by hand from the rectangular floating structures. The excess water was removed by using a hand centrifuge, followed by using paper towels. The samples were weighed in a Digital Balance machine (MARTE® BL3200H, SP Labor, São Paulo, Brazil) to determine their wet weight. The following equations were used to calculate the relative growth rate (RGR)²⁸⁵:

$$\text{RGR (\% day}^{-1}\text{): } [\ln(\text{final weight (g)/initial weight (g)})/(\text{final time/initial time}) \times 100]. \quad (1)$$

The nutrient absorption efficiency of *U. lactuca* was calculated as follows:

$$\text{Nutrient removal rate—NRR (\%)} = [(\text{concentration of nutrient in the initial time (mg L}^{-1}\text{)} - \text{concentration of nutrients in the final time (mg L}^{-1}\text{)})/(\text{concentration of nutrient in the initial time (mg L}^{-1}\text{)}) - 1] \times 100. \quad (2)$$

Random algal samples with three replicates for protein analysis were hand-collected from each experimental unit, washed under running tap water, and rinsed with distilled water at the beginning

²⁸⁰ Samocha, T.M.; Patnaik, S.; Speed, M.; Ali, A.M.; Burger, J.M.; Almeida, R.V.; Ayub, Z.; Harisanto, M.; Horowitz, A.; Brock, D.L. Use of Molasses as Carbon Source in Limited Discharge Nursery and Grow out Systems for *Litopenaeus vannamei*. *Aquac. Eng.* 2007, 36, 184–191. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaeng.2006.10.004>.

²⁸¹ Aminot, A.; Chaussepied, M. *Manuel Des Analyses Chimiques En Milieu Marin*; Centre National pour l'exploitation des océans: Paris, France, 1983.

²⁸² Baumgarten, M.D.G.Z.; De Barros Rocha, J.M.; Niencheski, L.F.H. *Manual de Análises Em Oceanografia Química*; Universidade Federal do Rio Grande: Rio Grande, Brazil, 1996.

²⁸³ American Public Health Association APHA; American Water Works Association; Water Pollution Control Association. *Standard Methods for the Examination of Water and Wastewater*, 21st ed.; American Public Health Association: Washington, DC, USA, 2005.

²⁸⁴ Furtado, P.S.; Poersch, L.H.; Wasielesky, W. Effect of Calcium Hydroxide, Carbonate and Sodium Bicarbonate on Water Quality and Zootechnical Performance of Shrimp *Litopenaeus vannamei* Reared in Biofloc Technology (BFT) Systems. *Aquaculture* 2011, 321, 130–135. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2011.08.034>.

²⁸⁵ Loureiro, R.R.; Reis, R.P.; Critchley, A.T. In Vitro Cultivation of Three *Kappaphycus alvarezii* (Rhodophyta, Areschougiales) Variants (Green, Red and Brown) Exposed to a Commercial Extract of the Brown Alga *Ascophyllum nodosum* (Fucaceae, Ochrophyta). *J. Appl. Phycol.* 2010, 22, 101–104. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10811-009-9412-2>.

and at the end of the experiments. The excess water was removed by using a hand centrifuge, followed by drying with paper towels. The samples were weighed to determine the wet weight and placed in an oven at 60 °C for 24 h and weighed again to obtain the dry weight. Subsequently, the samples were ground to powder by using a coffee bean grinder machine (Cadance®, Brazil).

The nitrogen content of the algae was determined by using the Kjeldahl titration method according to AOAC²⁸⁶ at the Laboratory of Nutrition of Aquatic Organisms-LANOVA (EMA, FURG, Rio Grande, Brazil). The following formula used for converting nitrogen to protein was:

$$\text{Protein (\% of dry weight)} = [(0.1 \times \text{Vol} \times 0.014/\text{Sample}) \times 5.45] \times 100(3)$$

where Vol is the volume spent on titration and Sample is the dry weight of the sample ²⁸⁷.

After shrimp storage, weekly biometrics were made to adjust the amount of feed offered. At the end of the experiment, all of the animals were weighed and counted. The performance variables collected at the end of the experiment were final average weight (g), final biomass yield (g) survival (%), feed conversion rate (FCR), specific growth rate (g week⁻¹), and productivity (kg m⁻³).

The performance of the shrimp was analyzed from the weekly biometric measurements that included the following equations:

Final average weight (g) = final biomass of live animals (g)/total number of animals;

1. Final biomass yield (g): final weight of all live animals (g);

2. Survival (%) = (final number of animals/initial number of animals) × 100;

3. Feed conversion rate (FCR) = feed offered (g)/(final biomass (g)—initial biomass (g));

4. Specific growth rate (g week⁻¹): weight gain (g)/number of weeks;

5. Productivity (kg m⁻³): [(final biomass (kg)—initial biomass (kg)) × 100]/tank volume (L).

The normality and homoscedasticity of the data were verified using the Shapiro–Wilk and Levene tests, respectively. Once the assumptions were met, ANOVA was performed followed by Tukey's post-hoc test or t-test. When ANOVA's assumptions were not satisfied, the Kruskal–Wallis nonparametric test was used. A minimum level of significance of 5% ($p \leq 0.05$) was applied in all analyzes.

²⁸⁶ AOAC. Official Methods of Analysis; Association of Official Analytical Chemists: Arlington, VA, USA, 2005; p. 245.

²⁸⁷ Baethgen, W.E.; Alley, M. A Manual Colorimetric Procedure for Measuring Ammonium Nitrogen in Soil and Plant Kjeldahl Digests. *Commun. Soil Sci. Plant Anal.* 1989, 20, 961–969.

5.4.3 Results

The final weight of the algae was higher ($p \leq 0.05$) than the initial weight of the algae at the beginning of the experiment. However, there was no significant difference ($p \leq 0.05$) in the final weight of the algae between the treatment groups, showing only an increase in the relative growth rate (RGR) in all treatments (Table 11).

The protein concentrations were evaluated at the end of cultivation and showed a significant difference ($p \leq 0.05$) between the treatment groups. The lower protein value was recorded in the experimental group where the algae were grown in von Stosch enrichment solution (Table 12).

Table 11. Initial and final biomass, relative growth rates, and protein contents (% of dry weight) (mean \pm standard deviation) of *U. lactuca* growth in the treatments of BFT (in shrimp culture effluent with 400 mg L⁻¹ of TSS), DEC (in effluent from shrimp culture after the settling period, with 30 mg L⁻¹ of TSS) and vs. (cultivation of *U. lactuca* in standard von Stosch enrichment solution at a concentration of 10 mL L⁻¹) during the 35 days of the experimental period.

Parameters	Treatments		
	BFT	DEC	VS
Initial weight (g)	6.2 \pm 0.1	6.2 \pm 0.1	6.3 \pm 0.1
Final weight (g)	9.1 \pm 2.2	7.9 \pm 1.1	8.3 \pm 1.8
RGR (% day ⁻¹)	1.0 \pm 0.7	0.7 \pm 0.4	0.8 \pm 0.6
Protein content (%)	18.4 \pm 0.5 ^a	19.6 \pm 1.4 ^a	10.8 \pm 2.4 ^b

^{a,b} = Different letters represent a significant difference ($p \leq 0.05$) between treatments after one-way ANOVA with Tukey's post-hoc test. RGR: relative growth rate.

The water quality parameters in the treatment groups are summarized in Table 12. The results show that the water temperature, dissolved oxygen, pH, salinity and alkalinity did not show any significant difference between the treatments ($p \leq 0.05$) (Table 3). The total suspended solids (TSS) concentrations were significantly lower ($p \leq 0.05$) in the DEC treatment where *U. lactuca* was cultivated in the shrimp effluent water with 30 mg L⁻¹ of TSS. Turbidity, however, showed similar results between the DEC (with 30 mg L⁻¹ of TSS) and BFT groups (with 400 mg L⁻¹ of TSS).

Table 12. Water quality parameters (mean \pm standard deviation) in the treatment groups where *U. lactuca* was cultivated in different shrimp effluent concentrations (BFT: with 400 mg L⁻¹ of TSS; DEC: with 30 mg L⁻¹

of TSS; and VS: cultivation of *U. lactuca* in von Stosch enrichment solution at a concentration of 10 mL L⁻¹) during the 35 days of the experimental period.

Parameters	Treatments		
	BFT	DEC	VS
Temperature (°C)	26.6 ± 0.8	26.6 ± 0.8	26.5 ± 0.7
D.O (mg L ⁻¹)	7.6 ± 0.2	7.8 ± 0.2	7.8 ± 0.2
pH	8.3 ± 0.1	8.4 ± 0.1	8.4 ± 0.1
Salinity (‰)	29.2 ± 2.9	29.1 ± 3.0	29.3 ± 2.3
Turbidity (NTU)	30.3 ± 37.4 ^a	3.3 ± 1.4 ^a	1.0 ± 0.4 ^b
Alkalinity (mg CaCO ₃ L ⁻¹)	145.8 ± 6.0	140.3 ± 6.8	Nd
TSS (mg L ⁻¹)	228.0 ± 109.8 ^b	22.5 ± 6.8 ^a	Nd
TAN (mg L ⁻¹)	0.1 ± 0.0 ^a	0.1 ± 0.0 ^a	0.1 ± 0.0 ^a
Nitrite (mg L ⁻¹)	0.2 ± 0.1 ^a	0.2 ± 0.1 ^a	0.0 ± 0.0 ^b
Nitrate (mg L ⁻¹)	64.3 ± 4.6 ^a	62.2 ± 4.6 ^a	10.3 ± 2.9 ^b
Phosphate (mg L ⁻¹)	4.5 ± 0.8 ^a	4.0 ± 0.7 ^a	0.9 ± 0.2 ^b

^{a, b} = represent a significant difference ($p \leq 0.05$) between treatments along the same lines, after one-way ANOVA with Tukey's post-hoc test. Nd: not determined.

The turbidity values did not differ statistically ($p \leq 0.05$) between the initial and final concentrations in the VS treatment where *U. lactuca* cultivation took place in von Stosch enrichment solution at a concentration of 10 ml L⁻¹. For the biofloc treatments (DEC and BFT), there was a decrease ($p \leq 0.05$) in turbidity concentration on the fourth day of sampling and throughout the experiment (Figure 27). There was no significant difference ($p \geq 0.05$) with the vs. treatment at the end of cultivation.

Figure 27. Weekly turbidity values in the DEC (with 30 mg L⁻¹ of TSS), BFT (with 400 mg L⁻¹ of TSS), and vs. (with von Stosch enrichment solution at a concentration of 10 mL L⁻¹) treatment groups during the 35 days of the experimental period. a; b; c = Different letters on the same day represent a significant difference ($p \leq 0.05$) between the treatments.

The macroalgae biomass yields decreased in all the treatment groups compared to the initial biomass values and the difference was significant ($p \leq 0.05$). However, at the end of the experiment there was no significant difference ($p \leq 0.05$) in fresh biomass values between the treatment groups (Table 13). There was a significant difference ($p \leq 0.05$) in the protein content of *U. lactuca* in the initial samples compared to the final samples taken from different treatment groups after 35 days of culture (Table 14). However, there was no significant differences between the treatments with biofloc in the protein content of *U. lactuca*.

Table 13. Relative growth rates (% day⁻¹) of *U. lactuca* (mean \pm standard deviation) in the IMTA 1 (with 1 g *Ulva* L⁻¹), IMTA 2 (2 g *Ulva* L⁻¹), and IMTA 3 (3 g *Ulva* L⁻¹) treatment groups during the 35 days of cultivation.

Parameters	Treatments		
	IMTA 1	IMTA 2	IMTA 3
Initial fresh weight (g)	150.5 \pm 0.3 ^a	300.5 \pm 0.4 ^b	450.6 \pm 0.4 ^c
Final fresh weight (g)	88.5 \pm 31.6	120.9 \pm 18.8	195.8 \pm 69.8
RGR (% day ⁻¹)	-1.7 \pm 1.2	-2.6 \pm 0.4	-2.5 \pm 0.9

^{a, b, c} = indicate significant differences ($p \leq 0.05$) on the same line between the treatments after one-way ANOVA after Tukey's post-hoc test. RGR: relative growth rate.

Table 14. Initial and final protein concentration (% of dry weight) (mean \pm standard deviation) of *U. lactuca* in the IMTA 1 (with 1 g *Ulva* L⁻¹), IMTA 2 (2 g *Ulva* L⁻¹), and IMTA 3 (3 g *Ulva* L⁻¹) treatment groups during the 35 days of cultivation.

	Initial Protein Content	Final Protein Content		
		IMTA 1	IMTA 2	IMTA 3
<i>U. lactuca</i>	11.8 \pm 0.0 ^b	20.1 \pm 0.7 ^a	20.1 \pm 1.3 ^a	20.1 \pm 1.0 ^a

^{a, b} = Different lowercase letters represent significant differences ($p \leq 0.05$) between the initial and final values after one-way ANOVA after Tukey's post-hoc test.

During the 35 days of cultivation in non-climatized greenhouse conditions, the water quality parameters, such as temperature, dissolved oxygen, pH, salinity, phosphate, and nitrite showed no significant difference ($p \geq 0.05$) between the treatments (Table 15). However, the introduction of *U. lactuca* into the shrimp cultivation system resulted in significantly lower mean values of nitrate,

turbidity, and settleable solids for treatments IMTA 1 (with 1 g *Ulva* L⁻¹), IMTA 2 (2 g *Ulva* L⁻¹), and IMTA 3 (3 g *Ulva* L⁻¹), compared to those found in MONO C (with no *Ulva*) (Table 15, Figures 28 and 29).

The alkalinity was higher in treatments with *U. lactuca* (Table 15), requiring a smaller amount of calcium hydroxide for its maintenance. The IMTA 1 (with 1 g *Ulva* L⁻¹) treatment required the least amount of calcium hydroxide (90 g in the entire crop), while the IMTA 2 (2 g *Ulva* L⁻¹), IMTA 3 (3 g *Ulva* L⁻¹), and MONO C (with no *Ulva*) treatments required 120, 105, and 157 g of calcium hydroxide to maintain the alkalinity, respectively.

In general, the total ammonium nitrogen (TAN) values showed no significant difference in the treatment groups including algal biomass *U. lactuca* ($p \leq 0.05$) (Table 15). However, TAN in the MONO C (with no *Ulva*) treatment group showed significantly ($p \leq 0.05$) higher values in the first week, with 1.1 ± 0.1 mg L⁻¹ when compared to the treatments including the algae, with 0.7 ± 0.1 ; 0.7 ± 0.1 , and 0.6 ± 0.0 mg L⁻¹ in the treatments IMTA 1, IMTA 2 and IMTA 3, respectively, thus requiring the application of organic carbon, such as molasses, to control of nitrogen in the MONO C treatment.

Table 15. Water quality parameters (mean \pm standard deviation) of treatments: the MONO C (with no *Ulva*), IMTA 1 (with 1 g *Ulva* L⁻¹), IMTA 2 (2 g *Ulva* L⁻¹), and IMTA 3 (3 g *Ulva* L⁻¹) treatment groups during the 35 days of the experiment.

Parameters	Treatments			
	MONO C	IMTA 1	IMTA 2	IMTA 3
Temperature (°C)	26.3 \pm 1.0	26.5 \pm 0.8	26.5 \pm 1.0	26.7 \pm 0.9
D.O (mg L ⁻¹)	7.3 \pm 0.2	7.3 \pm 0.2	7.3 \pm 0.2	7.3 \pm 0.2
pH	8.1 \pm 0.1	8.2 \pm 0.1	8.2 \pm 0.1	8.1 \pm 0.1
Salinity (‰)	30.0 \pm 0.3	29.8 \pm 0.3	28.8 \pm 0.6	29.6 \pm 0.5
Turbidity (NTU)	243.6 \pm 66.8 ^b	142.6 \pm 43.0 ^b	117.5 \pm 30.2 ^a	121.1 \pm 45.4 ^a
Alkalinity (mg CaCO ₃ L ⁻¹)	136.7 \pm 12.4 ^b	152.0 \pm 8.7 ^a	143.2 \pm 9.8 ^{ab}	148.8 \pm 8.7 ^a
TSS (mg L ⁻¹)	423.3 \pm 109.7	295.3 \pm 92.7	297.3 \pm 92.1	302.0 \pm 78.7
SS (ml L ⁻¹)	13.9 \pm 7.80 ^b	5.5 \pm 2.7 ^a	4.6 \pm 2.3 ^a	6.4 \pm 3.5 ^a
TAN (mg L ⁻¹)	0.3 \pm 0.1	0.3 \pm 0.1	0.2 \pm 0.1	0.2 \pm 0.1
Nitrite (mg L ⁻¹)	1.3 \pm 0.7	1.7 \pm 0.8	1.3 \pm 0.6	1.5 \pm 0.7
Nitrate (mg L ⁻¹)	62.0 \pm 4.0 ^b	42.0 \pm 2.0 ^a	51.3 \pm 3.5 ^{ab}	50.7 \pm 5.5 ^{ab}
Phosphate (mg L ⁻¹)	3.4 \pm 0.8	4.6 \pm 1.1	2.7 \pm 0.4	3.2 \pm 0.0

^{a, b} = Different lowercase letters represent a significant difference ($p \leq 0.05$) between the weeks of the same treatment, after performing one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's post-hoc test. O.D (dissolved oxygen); TSS (total suspended solids); SS (settleable solids); TAN (total ammonium nitrogen).

Figure 28. Variations in the nitrate concentrations in the IMTA 1 (with 1 g *Ulva* L⁻¹), IMTA 2 (2 g *Ulva* L⁻¹), IMTA 3 (3 g *Ulva* L⁻¹), and MONO C (with no *Ulva*) treatment groups during the 35 days of cultivation. a; b= Different lowercase letters represent a significant difference ($p \leq 0.05$) on the same days between the treatments after performing one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey’s post-hoc test.

In the control treatment (MONO C where there was no *Ulva*), in the first weeks of the experiment, the TSS (total suspended solids) concentrations raised above the established maximum limit of 500 mg L⁻¹ (Figure 4). The clarifiers started to be used to keep optimal shrimp performance as recommended by Gaona et al.²⁸⁸. For this reason, during the experiment, the treatments of IMTA 1 (with 1 g *Ulva* L⁻¹), IMTA 2 (2 g *Ulva* L⁻¹), and IMTA 3 (3 g *Ulva* L⁻¹) needed 3, 3, and 5 h of clarification, respectively. These three treatment groups had smaller amounts of tailings compared to the treatment MONO C (with no *Ulva*) which needed 8 h of clarification.

²⁸⁸ Gaona, C.A.P.; Poersch, L.H.; Krummenauer, D.; Foes, G.K.; Wasielesky, W.J. Effect of Solids Re-moval on Production of Shrimp. *Int. J. Recirc. Aquac.* 2011, 12, 54–73.

Figure 29. Variations in the total suspended solids (TSS) in the IMTA 1 (with 1 g *Ulva* L⁻¹), IMTA 2 (2 g *Ulva* L⁻¹), IMTA 3 (3 g *Ulva* L⁻¹), and MONO C (with no *Ulva*) treatment groups during the 35 days of cultivation. a; b= Different lowercase letters on the same day represent a significant difference ($p \leq 0.05$) between the treatments after ANOVA followed by Tukey’s post-hoc test.

There was no significant difference ($p \leq 0.05$) in the shrimp performance parameters between the treatment groups (Table 16).

Table 16. The performance of shrimp *L. vannamei* (mean \pm standard deviation) in treatments of MONO C (with no *Ulva*) in the IMTA 1 (with 1 g *Ulva* L⁻¹), IMTA 2 (2 g *Ulva* L⁻¹), and IMTA 3 (3 g *Ulva* L⁻¹) treatment groups during the 35 days of culture.

Parameters	Treatments			
	MONO C	IMTA 1	IMTA 2	IMTA 3
Final average weight (g)	6.5 \pm 0.5	6.8 \pm 0.3	7.6 \pm 0.3	7.4 \pm 0.2
Survival (%)	99.3 \pm 0.7	100.0 \pm 0.0	99.3 \pm 0.7	99.3 \pm 0.7
FCR	2.0 \pm 0.1	1.8 \pm 0.1	1.7 \pm 0.0	1.8 \pm 0.1
WGW (g week ⁻¹)	0.8 \pm 0.3	0.9 \pm 0.2	1.1 \pm 0.2	1.0 \pm 0.1
Final biomass (g)	187.3 \pm 22.4	205.2 \pm 16.0	239.2 \pm 11.5	230.4 \pm 9.0
Productivity (kg m ⁻³)	1.9 \pm 0.1	2.0 \pm 0.1	2.3 \pm 0.1	2.2 \pm 0.1

FCR (food conversion rate); WGW (weekly weight gain).

5.4.4 Discussion and conclusions

The introduction of species in integrated aquaculture is related to their ability to adapt according to system conditions and their interaction with other organisms²⁸⁹. In offshore systems, with low water turbidity and water renewal by currents, the integration of the macroalgae into the cultures shows better results. Verdian et al.²⁹⁰ showed that in these systems the relative growth rate was $14.3 \pm 4.3\%$ day⁻¹, probably due to the easy adaptation of the macroalgae to the system because of the similarity with the natural environment. In land based biofloc systems, the environmental characteristics are different. The system is characterized by a high organic load and nutrient accumulation throughout the production cycle. When cultured under unfavorable environmental conditions, such as high solids and nutrient loading in closed systems, such changes may influence the macroalgae's performance. Different management protocols should be applied for the best adaptation and performance of macroalgae in these systems.

This laboratory experiment showed that different concentrations of solids in the biofloc system did not cause biomass loss of macroalgae (see Table 11). However, the system did not provide the best conditions to seaweed growth compared to offshore cultivation. The relative growth rate of the macroalgae was similar between the treatments, demonstrating the feasibility of using shrimp culture water in biofloc systems as culture medium. The laboratory environmental conditions were controlled, with a direct light source on the macroalgae and temperature regulation. Another way to favor macroalgae growth under these conditions was the use of transparent experimental units that allow greater light incidence, which may have influenced the processes of light absorption by the macroalgae even with the deposition of solids.

In the laboratory experimental conditions, there was also no increase in solids throughout the experiment. Since there were no shrimp present, the feces and feed waste were not being produced in the culture, which was characterized as a static system. In controlled and fixed conditions, the macroalgae were able to adapt to the different culture media and grow. In contrast, the conditions of the greenhouse experiment simulated real culture conditions, resulting in biomass loss (see Table 13). The integrated culture of shrimp and macroalgae in an intensive system and with a high feed intake generated an increase in solids. Even with intense aeration, the macroalgae culture structure allowed for greater deposition of organic matter on the macroalgae. This effect was smaller in the laboratory experiment, because the macroalgae were loose in the carboy. Such conditions can be stressful to the

²⁸⁹ Khanjani, M.H.; Zahedi, S.; Mohammadi, A. Integrated Multitrophic Aquaculture (IMTA) as an Environmentally Friendly System for Sustainable Aquaculture: Functionality, Species, and Application of Biofloc Technology (BFT). *Environ. Sci. Pollut. Res.* 2022, 29, 67513–67531. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-022-22371-8>.

²⁹⁰ Verdian, A.H.; Effendi, I.; Budidardi, T.; Diatin, I. Production Performance Improvement of White Shrimp (*Litopenaeus vannamei*) Culture with Integrated Multi Trophic Aquaculture System in Seribu Is-lands, Jakarta, Indonesia. *Iran. J. Fish. Sci.* 2020, 19, 1415–1427. <https://doi.org/10.22092/ijfs.2019.120676>.

macroalgae, impacting their growth throughout the culture, which was verified in this experiment with the loss of biomass. A similar result was also observed by Legarda et al.²⁹¹, working in a closed system with integrated culture of the macroalgae *U. fasciata*, the shrimp *L. vannamei*, and the fish *Mugil liza* in a biofloc system, confirming the difficulty of adaptation of the macroalgae in this system.

The availability of nutrients in the biofloc system is advantageous for macroalgae cultures²⁹². However, the presence of solids can be an inhibiting factor for macroalgae growth. In both experiments, solids were deposited on the macroalgae, and lower concentrations of suspended solids were found in the water. In the laboratory experiment, a decrease in turbidity was observed in the treatment with the highest concentration of solids (400 mg L⁻¹) on the fourth day of culture (Figure 27), showing that most of the solids were deposited on the macroalga, even with constant aeration.

In the greenhouse experiment, a similar process was verified, with the aggravating factor that the production of solids was persistent due to the presence of the shrimp in the culture. The settleable solids (ml L⁻¹) showed a significant difference between the integrated culture and monoculture treatments. The lowest concentrations of settleable solids were observed in the *U. lactuca* treatment. As the individuals of this species are sessile organisms, they probably interfered with the dynamic movement of biofloc particles in the water column, causing the deposition of particles on them, unlike in the monoculture where there was no physical barrier for the particles to decant. Brito et al.²⁹³ also found a decrease in solids levels due to the deposition of flocs on the photosynthetic macroalgae leaves, going from a suspended to a decanted solid. This result also induced the need to use the clarifier to control excess solids in the system. The treatments with the presence of *U. lactuca* required less clarification time compared to the shrimp monoculture treatments. However, removing the macroalgae from the system will cause solids to become suspended in the water again. Excess solids in the water can cause rapid oxygen depletion²⁹⁴ and growth performance problems to the shrimp²⁹⁵.

²⁹¹ Legarda, E.C.; da Silva, D.; Miranda, C.S.; Pereira, P.K.M.; Martins, M.A.; Machado, C.; de Lorenzo, M.A.; Hayashi, L.; do Nascimento Vieira, F. Sea Lettuce Integrated with Pacific White Shrimp and Mullet Cultivation in Biofloc Impact System Performance and the Sea Lettuce Nutritional Composition. *Aqua-culture* 2021, 534, 736265. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2020.736265>.

²⁹² Brito, L.O.; Arantes, R.; Magnotti, C.; Derner, R.; Pchara, F.; Olivera, A.; Vinatea, L. Water Quality and Growth of Pacific White Shrimp *Litopenaeus vannamei* (Boone) in Co-Culture with Green Seaweed *Ulva lactuca* (Linnaeus) in Intensive System. *Aquac. Int.* 2014, 22, 497–508. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10499-013-9659-0>.

²⁹³ Brito, L.O.; Arantes, R.; Magnotti, C.; Derner, R.; Pchara, F.; Olivera, A.; Vinatea, L. Water Quality and Growth of Pacific White Shrimp *Litopenaeus vannamei* (Boone) in Co-Culture with Green Seaweed *Ulva lactuca* (Linnaeus) in Intensive System. *Aquac. Int.* 2014, 22, 497–508. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10499-013-9659-0>.

²⁹⁴ Granada, L.; Lopes, S.; Novais, S.C.; Lemos, M.F.L. Modelling Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture: Optimizing a Three Trophic Level System. *Aquaculture* 2018, 495, 90–97. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2018.05.029>.

²⁹⁵ Gaona, C.A.P.; de Almeida, M.S.; Viau, V.; Poersch, L.H.; Wasielesky, W. Effect of Different Total Suspended Solids Levels on a *Litopenaeus vannamei* (Boone, 1931) BFT Culture System during Biofloc Formation. *Aquac. Res.* 2017, 48, 1070–1079. <https://doi.org/10.1111/are.12949>.

Some alternatives to control solids presented by Khanjani et al.²⁹⁶ would be the use of organic consumers in inte-grated cultivation. Thus, the solids would be controlled without the use of clarifiers and there would not be a large amount of solids deposited on the macroalgae.

The deposition of solids on the macroalgae can be a stressing factor for the species, which may prevent the absorption of light and the performance of photosynthesis (see Figure 29). Such factors can trigger reproduction events such as the release of gametes or spores. These events can be initiated due to several environmental factors, such as high tempera-tures, the concentration of nutrients, and even the short life cycle of the species, thus re-sulting in the loss of biomass²⁹⁷. During the cultivation period, the presence of “ghost tissues” was also observed in *U. lactuca* as a sign of sporulation. The loss of macroalgae biomass was also verified by Legarda et al.²⁹⁸ when cultivating *U. fasciata* in an inte-grated system, probably because of the different characteristics of the biofloc system compared to the natural environment where the macroalgae were collected.

The von Stosch nutrient solution used in the laboratory experiment is composed of balanced minerals and nutrients²⁹⁹. Despite the biomass gain, the relative growth rate of *U. lactuca* in this experiment in the laboratory condition was lower compared to the studies with a maximum of 16.9% day⁻¹ for *U. prolifera*, when cultivated in the laboratory condi-tions with the nutrient medium F/2³⁰⁰. The von Stosch medium used for the cultivation of *U. lactuca* and the concentration of the medium used may not be adequate to cause low growth of the algal biomass. In addition, the treatment water was not renewed nor were more nutrients added, which could have limited the growth of the algae. For the production of culture media, specific compounds of high economic value are needed, so alterna-tive culture media and better management practices can facilitate the production of *U. lactuca*.

The increase in the protein content of *U. lactuca* cultivated in the biofloc system probably occurred because of the nutritional composition of the macroalgae changes according to the physical and chemical factors of the culture environment. For example, higher con-centrations of nitrogen available

²⁹⁶ Khanjani, M.H.; Zahedi, S.; Mohammadi, A. Integrated Multitrophic Aquaculture (IMTA) as an Environmentally Friendly System for Sustainable Aquaculture: Functionality, Species, and Application of Biofloc Technology (BFT). *Environ. Sci. Pollut. Res.* 2022, 29, 67513–67531. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-022-22371-8>.

²⁹⁷ Copertino, M.D.S.; Tormena, T.; Seeliger, U. Biofiltering Efficiency, Uptake and Assimilation Rates of *Ulva clathrata* (Roth) J. Agardh (Clorophyceae) Cultivated in Shrimp Aquaculture Waste Water. *J. Appl. Phycol.* 2009, 21, 31–45. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10811-008-9357-x>.

²⁹⁸ Legarda, E.C.; da Silva, D.; Miranda, C.S.; Pereira, P.K.M.; Martins, M.A.; Machado, C.; de Lorenzo, M.A.; Hayashi, L.; do Nascimento Vieira, F. Sea Lettuce Integrated with Pacific White Shrimp and Mullet Cultivation in Biofloc Impact System Performance and the Sea Lettuce Nutritional Composition. *Aqua-culture* 2021, 534, 736265. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2020.736265>.

²⁹⁹ Mansilla, A.; Rodriguez, J.P.; Souza, J.M.C.; Rosenfeld, S.; Ojeda, J.; Yokoya, N.S. Growth Responses to Temperature, Salinity and Nutrient Variations, and Biomass Variation and Phenology of *Ahnfeltia plicata* (Rhodophyta, Ahnfeltiales): A Commercially Interesting Agarophyte from the Magellanic Region, Chile. *J. Appl. Phycol.* 2014, 26, 1133–1139. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10811-013-0150-0>.

³⁰⁰ Luo, M.B.; Liu, F.; Xu, Z.L. Growth and Nutrient Uptake Capacity of Two Co-Occurring Species, *Ulva prolifera* and *Ulva linza*. *Aquat. Bot.* 2012, 100, 18–24. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquabot.2012.03.006>.

in the culture system, such as in the biofloc system, provide an increase in tissue nitrogen. According to Duke et al.³⁰¹, greater availability of nitrogen in the medium results in its absorption and its transformation into protein, stored in the form of amino acids and pigments³⁰². Treatments with biofloc effluent contained higher concentrations of nitrate and phosphate than treatment with von Stosch culture medium. This is due to the origin of the biofloc effluent, which came from a shrimp culture with 43 days of cultivation, with a gradual accumulation of nutrients. This high availability of nitrogen in the water favored the increase in the protein content of the macroalgae. The results obtained were superior to those observed by Fong et al.³⁰³, who obtained protein concentrations ranging from 0.6 to 5.4% in algae grown in nutrient solutions in the laboratory. The high protein value of *U. lactuca* in the present study shows its importance for human food as a food supplement, for muscle tissue reconstruction, and in vegan foods, similar to the previous study conducted by Bleakley and Hayes³⁰⁴.

Even with 20% biofloc inoculum in the greenhouse experiment, the ammonia concentrations in the first days of cultivation exceeded the concentration of 1 mg L⁻¹ in the tanks without *U. lactuca*. Although ammonia concentrations were well controlled in the biofloc system, at times throughout the production cycle it may be necessary to add organic carbon to stimulate the development of heterotrophic bacteria in the system³⁰⁵. When using a low percentage of inoculum diluted in seawater, the bacteria can undergo adaptation in the system. Together with the feed supply and continuous excretion of the animals, these bacteria were not able to convert all the ammonia in the system and its concentration increased, with the use of molasses in shrimp monoculture being necessary to increase the number of heterotrophic bacteria, in this experiment. Such instability of the bacteria also occurred in the integrated treatment, but due to the absorption capacity by *U. lactuca*, there was no increase of ammonia concentration in the system. Castelar et al.³⁰⁶ observed that the genus *Ulva* tends to have a preference for ammonia, making its assimilation faster and thus controlling nitrogen in the crop as a consequence.

³⁰¹ Duke, C.S.; Litaker, W.; Ramus J Effects of the Temperature, Nitrogen Supply and Tissue Nitrogen on Ammonium Uptake Rates of the Chlorophyte Seaweeds *Ulva Curvata* and *Codium Decorticatum*. *J. Phycol.* 1989, 25, 113–120.

³⁰² Baethgen, W.E.; Alley, M. A Manual Colorimetric Procedure for Measuring Ammonium Nitrogen in Soil and Plant Kjeldahl Digests. *Commun. Soil Sci. Plant Anal.* 1989, 20, 961–969.

³⁰³ Fong, P.; Boyer, K.E.; Desmond, J.S.; Zedler, J.B. Salinity Stress, Nitrogen Competition, and Facilitation: What Controls Seasonal Succession of Two Opportunistic Green Macroalgae? *J. Exp. Mar. Bio. Ecol.* 1996, 206, 203–221. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-0981\(96\)02630-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-0981(96)02630-5).

³⁰⁴ Bleakley, S.; Hayes, M. Algal Proteins: Extraction, Application, and Challenges Concerning Production. *Foods* 2017, 6, 33. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods6050033>.

³⁰⁵ Samocha, T.M.; Patnaik, S.; Speed, M.; Ali, A.M.; Burger, J.M.; Almeida, R.V.; Ayub, Z.; Harisanto, M.; Horowitz, A.; Brock, D.L. Use of Molasses as Carbon Source in Limited Discharge Nursery and Grow out Systems for *Litopenaeus vannamei*. *Aquac. Eng.* 2007, 36, 184–191. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaeng.2006.10.004>.

³⁰⁶ Castelar, B.; Reis, R.P.; dos Santos Calheiros, A.C. *Ulva lactuca* and *U. flexuosa* (Chlorophyta, Ulvophyceae) Cultivation in Brazilian Tropical Waters: Recruitment, Growth, and Ulvan Yield. *J. Appl. Phycol.* 2014, 26, 1989–1999. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10811-014-0329-z>.

Nitrate was another nitrogenous compound absorbed by *U. lactuca*. Its accumulation is constant throughout the production cycle in the biofloc system, with it reaching high concentrations. The *U. lactuca* absorbed the nitrate, as it is the nitrogenous compound with the highest availability in the system, with the best absorption result occurring in the treatment with the lowest density of *U. lactuca* (1 g L^{-1}). High densities, above 1 g L^{-1} are likely to increase intraspecific competition, due to *U. lactuca* overlap in the structure, and negatively affect nutrient absorption. Alencar et al.³⁰⁷, testing different densities with *U. lactuca*, also observed that nutrient removal was impaired when the algae density and growth rate increased. Therefore, unlike the gradual accumulation of nitrate that occurred in the monoculture, the treatment with the density of 1 g L^{-1} of *U. lactuca* resulted in a lower concentration of nitrate at the end of the cultivation. Due to absorption by the macroalgae, this compound is used for the production of biomass and pigments.

In addition to nutrient absorption, the integration of *U. lactuca* into shrimp cultivation also interferes with other components in the system. For the biofloc system, calcium carbonate or calcium hydroxide is required to maintain alkalinity³⁰⁸. The integrated cultivation of *L. vannamei* and *U. lactuca* required a smaller number of corrections with Ca(OH)_2 , maintaining a more stable level of alkalinity compared to the monoculture treatment where there was no *U. lactuca*. This possibly occurred due to the absorption of carbon dioxide from the medium by *U. lactuca*³⁰⁹. Chopin³¹⁰ comments on the decrease in water acidification due to the absorption of gases by macroalgae, acting on the greenhouse effect. The same pattern can occur in cropping systems integrated with *U. lactuca*.

³⁰⁷ Alencar, J.R. de; Junior, P.A.H.; Celino, J.J. Cultivo de Camarão Branco *Litopenaeus vannamei* (Bo-one , 1931) Com a Macroalga *Ulva lacuata* Linneaus (Chlorophyta) No Tratamento de Efluentes Em Sistema Fechado de Recirculação. *Rev. Biol. Ciências Terra* 2010, 10, 117–137.

³⁰⁸ Furtado, P.S.; Poersch, L.H.; Wasielesky, W. Effect of Calcium Hydroxide, Carbonate and Sodium Bicarbonate on Water Quality and Zootechnical Performance of Shrimp *Litopenaeus vannamei* Reared in Biofloc Technology (BFT) Systems. *Aquaculture* 2011, 321, 130–135. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2011.08.034>.

³⁰⁹ Granada, L.; Lopes, S.; Novais, S.C.; Lemos, M.F.L. Modelling Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture: Optimizing a Three Trophic Level System. *Aquaculture* 2018, 495, 90–97. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2018.05.029>.

³¹⁰ Chopin, T. Marine Aquaculture in Canada: Well-Established Monocultures of Finfish and Shellfish and an Emerging Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture (IMTA) Approach Including Seaweeds, Other Invertebrates, and Microbial Communities. *Fisheries* 2015, 40, 28–31. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03632415.2014.986571>.

The physical and chemical parameters of water quality were kept in the ideal ranges for *L. vannamei* cultivation, such as temperature³¹¹, salinity³¹², dissolved oxygen³¹³, pH³¹⁴, alkalinity³¹⁵ and TSS³¹⁶. The shrimp cultivated in this study had a similar performance to that found in the literature for monoculture systems³¹⁷. Therefore, the integration of *U. lactuca* in the system did not interfere in the performance of the shrimp, with it being environmentally advantageous. In the study of Brito et al.³¹⁸, a higher average final weight of the shrimp was observed when cultivated with the macroalgae, possibly due to nutritional advantages provided by the macroalgae to the shrimp. Although the macroalgae are grown in a separate floating structure from the shrimp, they are both grown in the same tank. Therefore, the reduction in the production of biomass served by *Ulva* can also be explained by its consumption by shrimp. In future studies, it is recommended to observe and monitor if the shrimp consume algae when they are integrated in the same tank as well as when they are in a separated cultivation structure.

In a conventional farming system, there is a significant loss of nitrogen that is not incorporated by the animals and becomes available in the water as a residue that can be toxic and the main source of environmental pollution³¹⁹. The use of macroalgae for the absorption of nutrients from the system has been widely used due to greater sustainability and productivity gain³²⁰. The use of macroalgae *U. lactuca* at a density of 1 g L⁻¹ in an integrated system with shrimp *L. vannamei* in biofloc was also viable

³¹¹ Wyban, J.; Walsh, W.A.; Godin, D.M. Temperature Effects on Growth, Feeding Rate and Feed Conversion of the Pacific White Shrimp (*Penaeus vannamei*). *Aquaculture* 1995, 138, 267–279. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0044-8486\(95\)00032-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/0044-8486(95)00032-1).

³¹² Khanjani, M.H.; Sharifinia, M.; Hajirezaee, S. Effects of Different Salinity Levels on Water Quality, Growth Performance and Body Composition of Pacific White Shrimp (*Litopenaeus vannamei* Boone, 1931) Cultured in a Zero Water Exchange Heterotrophic System. *Ann. Anim. Sci.* 2020, 20, 1471–1486. <https://doi.org/10.2478/aoas-2020-0036>.

³¹³ Schweitzer, R.; Arantes, R.; Costódio, P.F.S.; do Espírito Santo, C.M.; Arana, L.V.; Seiffert, W.Q.; Andreatta, E.R. Effect of Different Biofloc Levels on Microbial Activity, Water Quality and Performance of *Litopenaeus vannamei* in a Tank System Operated with No Water Exchange. *Aquac. Eng.* 2013, 56, 59–70. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.AQUAENG.2013.04.006>.

³¹⁴ Wasielesky, W.; Krummenauer, D.; Lara, G.; Fôes, G. Cultivo de Camarões Em Sistema de Bioflocos: realidade e perspectivas. *Revista ABCC.* 2013, 15, 16–26.

³¹⁵ Furtado, P.S.; Poersch, L.H.; Wasielesky, W. Effect of Calcium Hydroxide, Carbonate and Sodium Bicarbonate on Water Quality and Zootechnical Performance of Shrimp *Litopenaeus vannamei* Reared in Biofloc Technology (BFT) Systems. *Aquaculture* 2011, 321, 130–135. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2011.08.034>.

³¹⁶ Gaona, C.A.P.; de Almeida, M.S.; Viau, V.; Poersch, L.H.; Wasielesky, W. Effect of Different Total Suspended Solids Levels on a *Litopenaeus vannamei* (Boone, 1931) BFT Culture System during Biofloc Formation. *Aquac. Res.* 2017, 48, 1070–1079. <https://doi.org/10.1111/are.12949>.

³¹⁷ Samocha, T.M.; Patnaik, S.; Speed, M.; Ali, A.M.; Burger, J.M.; Almeida, R.V.; Ayub, Z.; Harisanto, M.; Horowitz, A.; Brock, D.L. Use of Molasses as Carbon Source in Limited Discharge Nursery and Grow out Systems for *Litopenaeus vannamei*. *Aquac. Eng.* 2007, 36, 184–191. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaeng.2006.10.004>.

³¹⁸ Brito, L.O.; Arantes, R.; Magnotti, C.; Derner, R.; Pchara, F.; Olivera, A.; Vinatea, L. Water Quality and Growth of Pacific White Shrimp *Litopenaeus vannamei* (Boone) in Co-Culture with Green Seaweed *Ulva lactuca* (Linnaeus) in Intensive System. *Aquac. Int.* 2014, 22, 497–508. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10499-013-9659-0>.

³¹⁹ Poli, M.A.; Legarda, E.C.; de Lorenzo, M.A.; Pinheiro, I.; Martins, M.A.; Seiffert, W.Q.; do Nascimento Vieira, F. Integrated Multitrophic Aquaculture Applied to Shrimp Rearing in a Biofloc System. *Aquaculture* 2019, 511, 734274. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2019.734274>.

³²⁰ Verdian, A.H.; Effendi, I.; Budidardi, T.; Diatin, I. Production Performance Improvement of White Shrimp (*Litopenaeus vannamei*) Culture with Integrated Multi Trophic Aquaculture System in Seribu Islands, Jakarta, Indonesia. *Iran. J. Fish. Sci.* 2020, 19, 1415–1427. <https://doi.org/10.22092/ijfs.2019.120676>.

due to the incorporation of nitrogen by the algae, resulting in a biomass with higher protein content, in addition to increasing the system productivity and sustainability.

The cultivation of macroalgae in biofloc promoted changes in water quality in both experiments. The concentration of total suspended solids decreased in both experiments with macroalgae integration. When cultivated in an integrated system with shrimp, the addition of macroalgae at a density of 1 g L⁻¹ in the system promoted the absorption of nitrogen, nitrate, and ammonia, generating lower final concentrations of these nutrients at the end of cultivation compared to shrimp monoculture conditions. In addition, the integration of the macroalga into the system resulted in less use of inputs, such as molasses and calcium hydroxide. Finally, the use of *U. lactuca* did not negatively affect the performance of the shrimp. Despite the loss of biomass under the conditions tested in the integrated system, the macroalgae *U. lactuca* showed potential for the consumption of nutrients available in the system.

5.5 Applying metagenomics to sustainable aquaculture management of bacterial dynamics in IMTA systems (Experiment 5)

5.5.1 Introduction

The intensification of aquaculture, driven by increasing demand for seafood, has resulted in a few environmental consequences. This primarily includes water pollution caused by the discharge of excess nutrients, antibiotics, and waste materials from aquaculture into adjacent waters. Such inputs can lead to water pollution and eutrophication and alter the ecological balance and vitality of aquatic ecosystems^{321, 322}. In addition, the increased stocking densities characteristic of aquaculture facilities can promote the proliferation and spread of diseases among farmed populations³²³. The potential for disease transmission is exacerbated by the interconnectedness between aquaculture systems and surrounding natural habitats, thus posing risks to wild populations through the release of pathogens into the environment. In addition, the expansion of aquaculture operations often leads to habitat degradation, manifested in habitat destruction, loss of biodiversity and disruption of coastal ecosystems³²⁴. These environmental impacts highlight the need for sustainable aquaculture practices that mitigate negative impacts on the aquatic environment while meeting the needs of seafood production³²⁵.

The Integrated Multi-trophic Aquaculture (IMTA) system has emerged as an approach that promotes environmental sustainability, economic stability and social acceptance by simultaneously producing multiple aquatic species and utilizing different trophic levels to optimize biological and chemical processes³²⁶. Proper selection of cultivated species and careful management of population size are essential to achieving optimal biological and chemical processes, thereby improving ecosystem health and industry sustainability³²⁷. The IMTA system and biofloc technology (BFT) are closely associated because of the potential of IMTA to regulate suspended solids in aquaculture systems

³²¹ Luo M, Zhang Y, Xiao K, et al (2023) Effect of submarine groundwater discharge on nutrient distribution and eutrophication in Liaodong Bay, China. *Water Res* 247:120732. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2023.120732>

³²² Yu Y, Dong L, Zhang L, et al (2023) Effect of flowing water on the pharmacokinetic properties of norfloxacin in channel catfish (*Ictalurus punctatus*) after single-dose oral administration. *Vet Med Sci* 9:1201–1210. <https://doi.org/10.1002/vms3.1108>

³²³ Tapia-Paniagua ST, Vidal S, Lobo C, et al (2014) The treatment with the probiotic *Shewanella putrefaciens* Pdp11 of specimens of *Solea senegalensis* exposed to high stocking densities to enhance their resistance to disease. *Fish Shellfish Immunol* 41:209–221. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fsi.2014.08.019>

³²⁴ Hall-Spencer JM, Harvey BP (2019) Ocean acidification impacts on coastal ecosystem services due to habitat degradation. *Emerg Top Life Sci* 3:197–206. <https://doi.org/10.1042/etls20180117>

³²⁵ Froehlich HE, Gentry RR, Rust MB, et al (2017) Public perceptions of aquaculture: Evaluating spatiotemporal patterns of sentiment around the world. *PLoS One* 12:e0169281. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0169281>

³²⁶ Jerónimo D, Lillebø AI, Santos A, et al (2020) Performance of polychaete assisted sand filters under contrasting nutrient loads in an integrated multi-trophic aquaculture (IMTA) system. *Sci Rep* 10:. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-77764-x>.

³²⁷ Khanjani MH, Zahedi S, Mohammadi A (2022) Integrated multitrophic aquaculture (IMTA) as an environmentally friendly system for sustainable aquaculture: functionality, species, and application of biofloc technology (BFT). *Environ Sci Pollut Res Int* 29:67513–67531. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-022-22371-8>

with restricted water exchange³²⁸. IMTA systems that combine fed aquaculture species with inorganic and organic extractive species can help recycle excess nutrients and reduce the environmental footprint of aquaculture³²⁹. These systems can also be expanded into temperate marine waters, further increasing their potential to improve environmental impacts. To ensure responsible and sustainable development of aquaculture, it is important to consider the specific species, culture methods and stocking densities and implement best management practices. In addition, careful site selection, control of stocking density, improved feed formulation and integrated culture can further reduce the environmental impact of marine fish culture^{330, 331, 332}.

Microbial communities in aquaculture systems can provide valuable information about the impact of aquaculture practices on the surrounding environment, thereby contributing to the development of sustainable and environmentally friendly aquaculture practices³³³. Metagenomics enables the study of symbiotic and antagonistic relationships between microbes and eukaryotes in aquaculture systems and provides insights into how these interactions affect the health and productivity of aquatic organisms³³⁴. Additionally, metagenomic analysis can help in the early detection of pathogens and disease-causing microbes in aquaculture systems and enable the development of targeted disease management strategies to prevent outbreaks and minimize economic losses³³⁵.

Metagenomics has the potential to unlock a world of secrets that are critical to animal welfare and mortality reduction in aquaculture³³⁶ (Rajeev et al. 2023). This tool can reliably identify pathogens that pose a threat to human health as well as previously undiscovered species by observing the complete microbiome and classifying organisms according to their distinct genetic

³²⁸ Martín Ríos LD, Betancourt Monteagudo E, Corrales Barrios Y, et al (2023) Biofloc technology and immune response of penaeid shrimp: A meta-analysis and meta-regression. *Fish Shellfish Immunol* 138:108805. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fsi.2023.108805>

³²⁹ Troell M, Joyce A, Chopin T, et al (2009) Ecological engineering in aquaculture — Potential for integrated multi-trophic aquaculture (IMTA) in marine offshore systems. *Aquaculture* 297:1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2009.09.010>

³³⁰ Wu RSS (1995) The environmental impact of marine fish culture: Towards a sustainable future. *Mar Pollut Bull* 31:159–166. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0025-326x\(95\)00100-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/0025-326x(95)00100-2)

³³¹ Chopin T, Buschmann AH, Halling C, et al (2001) Integrating seaweeds into marine aquaculture systems: A key toward sustainability. *J Phycol* 37:975–986. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1529-8817.2001.01137.x>

³³² Primavera JH (2006) Overcoming the impacts of aquaculture on the coastal zone. *Ocean Coast Manag* 49:531–545. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocecoaman.2006.06.018>

³³³ Sharma M, Sudheer S, Usmani Z, et al (2020) Deciphering the omics of plant-microbe interaction: Perspectives and new insights. *Curr Genomics* 21:343–362. <https://doi.org/10.2174/1389202921999200515140420>

³³⁴ Lian W-H, Mohamad OAA, Dong L, et al (2023) Culturomics and metagenomics-based insights into the microbial community and function of rhizosphere soils in Sinai desert farming systems. *Environ Microbiome* 18:. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40793-023-00463-3>

³³⁵ Sanches-Fernandes GMM, Sá-Correia I, Costa R (2022) Vibriosis outbreaks in aquaculture: Addressing environmental and public health concerns and preventive therapies using gilthead seabream farming as a model system. *Front Microbiol* 13:. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2022.904815>

³³⁶ Rajeev M, Jung I, Lim Y, et al (2023) Metagenome sequencing and recovery of 444 metagenome-assembled genomes from the biofloc aquaculture system. *Sci Data* 10:. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-023-02622-0>

makeup³³⁷. This information can be used to build databases of characterized species, uncover the intricacies of microbiome population dynamics, and develop effective disease prevention strategies^{338,339}.

5.5.2 Trial Methodology

The experiment was conducted in an aquaculture greenhouse. Each culture system comprised a 20 m² tank for shrimp, *Penaeus vannamei* (at a density of 400 shrimp m⁻²), and a 4 m³ tank for juvenile tilapia, *Oreochromis niloticus* (at a density of 45 fishes m⁻³). Shrimp post-larvae were obtained from a commercial hatchery facility, while tilapia fingerlings (weighing between 15g and 25g) were procured from a commercial fish farm. The shrimp underwent an initial nursery phase and were stocked once they reached an average weight of approximately 1g. In this study other species were cultured at the IMTA systems that include sea lettuce (*Ulva fasciata*).

In compartment 1 were the shrimps and the source of feed, carbon, and oxygen, in compartment 2 were the tilapia (biofloc consumers) and in the compartment 3 were the seaweed (CO₂, nitrogen and phosphorus consumers). Firstly, water is introduced into the system through compartment 1, where shrimps are fed. In compartment 1, oxygen, carbon, and uneaten feed are transformed into biofloc (aggregated microorganisms). Subsequently, water from this compartment is transferred via a pump system to compartment 2, where tilapia and oysters participate in organic matter consumption and biofloc stabilization. Following this, water with lower organic matter concentration is directed to seaweed tanks, where nitrogen compounds are transformed into seaweed biomass. This process helps maintain water quality, allowing for the reuse of the same water across multiple production cycles. All samples were collected from triplicate systems, with triplicates of each sample type.

For the land-based recirculating biofloc system, samples were collected from various sources including biofloc, shrimp gut, fish gills/gut, and seaweed, originating from two distinct types of biofloc dominance within Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture (IMTA) systems. One system exhibited dominance by heterotrophic biofloc, established through organic fertilization, while the other displayed dominance by chemoautotrophic biofloc, established through inorganic fertilization. Each system comprised three compartments, with 100% water recirculation ensuring consistent water

³³⁷ Rieder J, Kapopoulou A, Bank C, Adrian-Kalchauer I (2023) Metagenomics and metabarcoding experimental choices and their impact on microbial community characterization in freshwater recirculating aquaculture systems. *Environ Microbiome* 18: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40793-023-00459-z>

³³⁸ Martínez-Porchas M, Vargas-Albores F (2017) Microbial metagenomics in aquaculture: a potential tool for a deeper insight into the activity. *Rev Aquac* 9:42–56. <https://doi.org/10.1111/raq.12102>

³³⁹ Chithira MS, Aishwarya PV, Mohan AS, Antony SP (2021) Metagenomic analysis of microbial communities in the sediments of a semi-intensive penaeid shrimp culture system. *J Genet Eng Biotechnol* 19:136. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s43141-021-00237-9>

quality and enabling multiple production cycles. Sampling was conducted in triplicate systems, with triplicate samples collected for each sample type. Over three sampling periods (T0: initial, T1: middle, T2 final), a total of 195 samples were processed for next-generation sequencing (NGS) analysis.

Samples from this study were processed followed standard practices in bacterial community analysis. Microbial DNA extraction was performed using the ZymoBIOMICS DNA Miniprep kit (Zymo Research, Irvine, Canada), following the manufacturer's protocol. Sequencing of the hyper-variable regions V3-V4 was conducted using the forward and reverse primers V3-V4 – 341F/805R(5'ACACTCTTCCCTACACGACGCTCTTCCGATCTCCTACGGGNGGCWGCAG/5'GTGACTGGAGTTCAGACGTGTGCTCTTCCGATCTGACTACHVGGGTATCTAATCC). The underlined sequences represent the adaptor overhang nucleotide sequences utilized in the Illumina 16S metagenomics workflow, resulting in approximately 450 base pairs of the 16S rRNA gene being amplified. PCR products were normalized to equal concentrations and subsequently sequenced using an Illumina® MiSeq sequencing platform. The sequencing was performed at Genome Québec Inc. (Centre d'expertise et de services Génome Québec, Montréal (Québec), Canada), generating 2 x 300 paired end reads for each sample.

5.5.3 Results

The taxonomic analysis revealed significant changes in the representation of the 30 most abundant phyla within the system, indicating shifts in bacterial communities across all three compartments under both dietary conditions compared to the initial timepoint (Figure 30A). Furthermore, a substantial proportion of the microbial community in all samples remained unidentified at the genus level, with unclassified Amplicon Sequence Variants (ASVs) representing a predominant portion (Biofloc: 42–48%; Shrimp gut: 19–42%; Fish gills: 40–45%; Fish gut: 32–66%; Seaweed: 31–39%) (Figure 30B).

Among the 30 most abundant genera, only the potential pathogenic genus *Vibrio* was identified. In Compartment 1, the abundance of *Vibrio* decreased from the initial sampling point (Biofloc = 5%, Shrimp Gut = 4.2%) to the middle and end of the experiment under both fertilization strategies (Inorganic T1-T2: Biofloc = 0.06 - 0.04%, Shrimp gut = 0.24 – 0.08%; Organic T1-T2: Biofloc = 0.04 - 0.07%, Shrimp Gut = 0.48 – 0.17%). For Compartment 2, statistically significant reductions compared to the initial point were observed only for the *Vibrio* genus in the tilapia gill bacterial communities (Initial: 1.4%; Inorganic T1-T2: 0.5 – 0.2 %, Organic T1-T2: 1 – 0.3%), while the abundance in the tilapia gut remained marginal throughout the experiment (Initial: 0.5 %; Inorganic T1-T2: 0.7 – 0.5%, Organic T1-T2: 0.7 – 0.4%). In Compartment 3, *Vibrio*, although detected, exhibited low relative abundance with no significant changes observed within the bacterial communities present in *Ulva* tissues (Initial: 0.03%; Inorganic T1-T2: 0.08 – 0.03%, Organic T1-T2: 0.1 – 0.02%).

Additionally, other potentially pathogenic genera identified included *Tenacibaculum* and *Coxiella* (Rickettsia-like organisms), although they were not prominently represented in Figure 1B due to their low abundance across most samples. Notably, the initial biofloc bacterial communities exhibited a notable presence of the *Coxiella* genus (2.5%), which was significantly reduced under both fertilization conditions at T1 and T2 (Inorganic T1-T2: 0.18 – 0.07%; Organic T1-T2: 0.08 - 0.08%). Comparing fertilization methods, none of the three potential pathogenic genera showed significant differences in abundance within each sample type studied. However, the genus *Mycobacterium* exhibited increased relative abundance in the inorganic fertilization compared to the organic at T1 (ANOVA, $P=0.05$) and T2 (ANOVA, $P<0.05$). Consequently, further investigations into the presence of *Mycobacterium* in biofloc systems and the impact of different fertilization methods on this genus are warranted, particularly considering the high pathogenicity associated with several strains within this genus, such as *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*.

Meanwhile, the bacterial communities from biofloc, shrimp gut, and tilapia gut exhibited a similar arrangement in the NMDS graph, while *Ulva* and tilapia gills bacterial communities displayed a slightly different disposition compared to the former ones. When divided by timepoint, the biofloc bacterial communities showed no statistical differences when compared to the tilapia gut under both fertilizations at T1 and T2. This observation also held true for the comparison between biofloc and shrimp gut under organic fertilization, but differences were observed at T2 in the inorganic one. Moreover, a clear similar evolution was observed in the shrimp gut and tilapia gut microbial communities under both fertilizations, with no significant differences among them. Regarding *Ulva*-associated bacterial communities, they tended to be more similar to fish gut and shrimp gut under organic fertilizer, while the inorganic fertilizer showed more similarities compared to biofloc and fish gills (Figure 31).

Figure 30. Bar graph showing the mean relative ASV abundance at (A) phylum and (B) genus level across the different conditions included in this study. Within each bar, different colours were assigned to the 30 most abundant phyla or genera, grouping the remaining ones in the category “Other”. Comp1 = Compartment 1, Comp 2 = Compartment 2, Comp 3 = Compartment 3.

Figure 31. Non-metric multidimensional analysis (NMDS), computed from Bray–Curtis distance matrix, divided by each diet type. The two timepoints after the beginning of the experiment are shown in different shapes: circles for 45 days (T1) and triangles for 90 days.

5.5.4 Discussion and Conclusions

Nitrifying and denitrifying genera are found in the diverse phylum of Proteobacteria, and they are crucial for the recycling of nutrients and remineralization of organic matter³⁴⁰. Proteobacteria is the most prevalent phylum supported by this study and it is associated with numerous processes in aquaculture systems, including nitrification, heterotrophic and autotrophic denitrification, nitrate reduction to ammonia, anaerobic ammonia oxidation, and some pathogenic

³⁴⁰ Schreier HJ, Mirzoyan N, Saito K (2010) Microbial diversity of biological filters in recirculating aquaculture systems. *Curr Opin Biotechnol* 21:318–325. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.copbio.2010.03.011>

bacteria such as *Mycobacterium* sp³⁴¹. There are more than 190 species in the genus *Mycobacterium*, some of which are important because of their broad host range, financial value in aquaculture, and zoonotic potential. Aquatic species are among the many domesticated and wild species that are afflicted with mycobacteriosis, a chronic bacterial disease caused by *Mycobacterium* species³⁴². In this study, we observed the prevalence of *Mycobacterium* sp. this should be considered in further studies using different types of farmed organisms and fertilizer management in Biofloc systems. Authors working with the same system found a dominance of Proteobacteria phylum and *Mycobacterium* genus. This may be a red flag for the aquaculture sector, and this must monitor crop conditions in real time to avoid disease outbreaks³⁴³.

The structure and function of bacterial communities in water, biofloc, and intestinal samples from a shrimp aquaculture system using biofloc were compared in a study using metagenomic sequencing. The results showed that Proteobacteria could be potential hosts in biofloc-based aquaculture environments, indicating the widespread presence of resistance genes in environmental microbes as well as human gut microbes. The effective use of metagenomics in the tracking of environmental pollution points to a viable strategy for source tracking based on antibiotic resistance genes variants, providing a streamlined procedure for upcoming studies and intervention initiatives³⁴⁴.

A diversified and advantageous microbial community that can outcompete pathogenic bacteria, including *Mycobacterium* species, is promoted by biofloc systems, which may enhance the microbiome status in a contaminated agricultural system with *Mycobacterium*³⁴⁵. Studies demonstrate that biofloc systems sustain higher *Lactobacillus* spp. counts which has the ability to stop the spread of harmful bacteria, such as *Mycobacterium* species and the microbial bioremediation process in biofloc systems can immobilize or remove contamination from a system, making it a cost-effective and preferred method for removing contaminants³⁴⁶.

In this study of bacterial diversity in the Biofloc IMTA system with organic and inorganic fertilizations revealed a remarkable evolution during the aquaculture culture process. The presence of potential

³⁴¹ Chithira MS, Aishwarya PV, Mohan AS, Antony SP (2021) Metagenomic analysis of microbial communities in the sediments of a semi-intensive penaeid shrimp culture system. *J Genet Eng Biotechnol* 19:136. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s43141-021-00237-9>

³⁴² Davidovich N, Morick D, Carella F (2020) Mycobacteriosis in aquatic invertebrates: A review of its emergence. *Microorganisms* 8:1249. <https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms8081249>

³⁴³ Yanong RPE, Pouder DB, Falkinham JO III (2010) Association of mycobacteria in recirculating aquaculture systems and Mycobacterial disease in fish. *J Aquat Anim Health* 22:219–223. <https://doi.org/10.1577/h10-009.1>

³⁴⁴ Chen X, He Z, Zhao J, et al (2022) Metagenomic analysis of bacterial communities and antibiotic resistance genes in *Penaeus monodon* biofloc-based aquaculture environments. *Front Mar Sci* 8:. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2021.762345>

³⁴⁵ Kumar V, Roy S, Behera BK, et al (2021) Biofloc Microbiome With Bioremediation and Health Benefits. *Front Microbiol* 12:. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2021.741164>

³⁴⁶ Chen X, He Z, Zhao J, et al (2022) Metagenomic analysis of bacterial communities and antibiotic resistance genes in *Penaeus monodon* biofloc-based aquaculture environments. *Front Mar Sci* 8:. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2021.762345>

pathogens was either minimal in all samples examined or showed a significant decline over time, indicating the favorable microbiome status of this system. However, further studies using more precise molecular tools or traditional microbiological techniques are required to determine the potential pathogenicity of the observed increase in the relative abundance of mycobacteria.

5.6 Monoculture of marine shrimp *litopenaeus vannamei* versus integrated culture with oysters of the genus *crassostrea* in BFT systems (Experiment 6)

5.6.1 Introduction

The food production industry has faced a challenge in recent times due to the growing demand from the world's population. The Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations estimates that by 2050 the world population will exceed nine billion people and considers that aquaculture, as a food production sector, also has tasks to fulfill within this context³⁴⁷. The challenge lies in achieving production that meets a greater number of sustainability criteria³⁴⁸ while also meeting the need for increased intensification in production³⁴⁹. This intensification of systems aims at greater food production with less use of natural resources.

However, with the increase in fish and shrimp stocking densities in cultivation tanks, the metabolites generated by the cultured animals and the residues in cultivation lead to a higher concentration of toxic substances such as nitrogen compounds in the water³⁵⁰. In traditional farming, this problem is solved by water renewal and disposal of organic matter and nutrients into the natural environment^{351, 352, 353}. This renewal practice has a high environmental and financial cost. To reduce environmental costs, water should not be exchanged, but this has consequences for the environmental quality of cultivation, such as eutrophication and, in some cases, mortality^{351,354,355}.

Biofloc culture, or BFT (Biofloc Technology), is a closed production system with minimal or no water exchange. It is based on stimulating the proliferation of microorganisms in the cultivation water that

³⁴⁷ FAO. (2020). The state of world fisheries and aquaculture. Sustainability in Action.

<http://www.fao.org/3/ca9229en/ca9229en.pdf>.

³⁴⁸ Valenti, W. C., Kimpara, J. M., Preto, B. de L., & Moraes-Valenti, P. (2018). Indicators of sustainability to assess aquaculture systems. *Ecological Indicators*, 88, 402–413. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2017.12.068>

³⁴⁹ Ahmed, N., & Thompson, S. (2019). The blue dimensions of aquaculture: A global synthesis. *Science of The Total Environment*, 652, 851–861. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2018.10.163>

³⁵⁰ Timmons, M. B., & Ebeling, J. M. (2010). Recirculating Aquaculture. In *Cayuga Aqua Ventures* (2nd ed.).

³⁵¹ Burford, M. A., Costanzo, S. D., Dennison, W. C., Jackson, C. J., Jones, A. B., McKinnon, A. D., Preston, N. P., & Trott, L. A. (2003). A synthesis of dominant ecological processes in intensive shrimp ponds and adjacent coastal environments in NE Australia. *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 46(11), 1456–1469. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0025-326X\(03\)00282-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0025-326X(03)00282-0)

³⁵² Trang, N. T. D., & Brix, H. (2014). Use of planted biofilters in integrated recirculating aquaculture-hydroponics systems in the Mekong Delta, Vietnam. *Aquaculture Research*, 45(3), 460–469. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2109.2012.03247.x>

³⁵³ Ottinger, M., Clauss, K., & Kuenzer, C. (2016). Aquaculture: Relevance, distribution, impacts and spatial assessments – A review. *Ocean & Coastal Management*, 119, 244–266. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocecoaman.2015.10.015>

³⁵⁴ Sugiura, S. H., Marchant, D. D., Kelsey, K., Wiggins, T., & Ferraris, R. P. (2006). Effluent profile of commercially used low-phosphorus fish feeds. *Environmental Pollution*, 140(1), 95–101. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2005.06.020>

³⁵⁵ Wu, H., Peng, R., Yang, Y., He, L., Wang, W., Zheng, T., & Lin, G. (2014). Mariculture pond influence on mangrove areas in south China: Significantly larger nitrogen and phosphorus loadings from sediment wash-out than from tidal water exchange. *Aquaculture*, 426–427, 204–212. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2014.02.009>

contribute to the improvement of water quality^{356,357,358}. Nitrifying bacteria and heterotrophic bacteria use nitrogen compounds for their growth and also remove toxic compounds from the water for the target organisms of the culture³⁵⁶; As a consequence of the growth of microorganisms in the water, there is an increase in suspended solids in the cultivation tanks³⁵⁹.

Within the BFT system, the cultivation of marine shrimp *Litopenaeus vannamei* has seen many advances since the early research and industry applications^{360, 361}. Currently, some refinements and improvements are being sought, such as the regulation of total suspended solids throughout the cultivation period^{362,363,364}.

Another form of intensification in aquaculture production is Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture (IMTA) or integrated multitrophic aquaculture^{365,366}. This system is based on the existence of a target species that is fed with commercial feed, and secondary species that indirectly benefit from the diet provided to the primary species and from production residues³⁶⁷.

³⁵⁶ Avnimelech, Y. (2007). Feeding with microbial flocs by tilapia in minimal discharge bio-flocs technology ponds. *Aquaculture*, 264(1–4), 140–147. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2006.11.025>

³⁵⁷ Wasielesky, W., Atwood, H., Stokes, A., & Browdy, C. L. (2006). Effect of natural production in a zero exchange suspended microbial floc based super-intensive culture system for white shrimp *Litopenaeus vannamei*. *Aquaculture*, 258(1–4), 396–403. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2006.04.030>

³⁵⁸ Krummenauer, D., Samocha, T., Poersch, L., Lara, G., & Wasielesky, W. (2014). The Reuse of Water on the Culture of Pacific White Shrimp, *Litopenaeus vannamei*, in BFT System. *Journal of the World Aquaculture Society*, 45(1), 3–14. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jwas.12093>

³⁵⁹ Gaona, C. A. P., da Paz Serra, F., Furtado, P. S., Poersch, L. H., & Wasielesky, W. (2016). Effect of different total suspended solids concentrations on the growth performance of *Litopenaeus vannamei* in a BFT system. *Aquacultural Engineering*, 72–73, 65–69. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaeng.2016.03.004>

³⁶⁰ Schweitzer, R., Arantes, R., Costódio, P. F. S., do Espírito Santo, C. M., Arana, L. V., Seiffert, W. Q., & Andreatta, E. R. (2013). Effect of different biofloc levels on microbial activity, water quality and performance of *Litopenaeus vannamei* in a tank system operated with no water exchange. *Aquacultural Engineering*, 56, 59–70. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaeng.2013.04.006>

³⁶¹ Krummenauer, D., Poersch, L. H., Fóes, G., Lara, G., & Wasielesky, W. (2016). Survival and growth of *Litopenaeus vannamei* reared in Bft System under different water depths. *Aquaculture*, 465, 94–99. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2016.09.002>

³⁶² Gaona, C. A. P., de Almeida, M. S., Viau, V., Poersch, L. H., & Wasielesky, W. (2017). Effect of different total suspended solids levels on a *Litopenaeus vannamei* (Boone, 1931) BFT culture system during biofloc formation. *Aquaculture Research*, 48(3), 1070–1079. <https://doi.org/10.1111/are.12949>

³⁶³ Holanda, M., Santana, G., Furtado, P., Rodrigues, R. V., Cerqueira, V. R., Sampaio, L. A., Wasielesky, W., & Poersch, L. H. (2020). Evidence of total suspended solids control by *Mugil liza* reared in an integrated system with pacific white shrimp *Litopenaeus vannamei* using biofloc technology. *Aquaculture Reports*, 18, 100479. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aqrep.2020.100479>

³⁶⁴ Brandão, H., Xavier, Í. V., Santana, G. K. K., Santana, H. J. K., Krummenauer, D., & Wasielesky, W. (2021). Heterotrophic versus mixed BFT system: Impacts on water use, suspended solids production and growth performance of *Litopenaeus vannamei*. *Aquacultural Engineering*, 95, 102194. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaeng.2021.102194>

³⁶⁵ Martins, C. I. M., Eding, E. H., Verdegem, M. C. J., Heinsbroek, L. T. N., Schneider, O., Blancheton, J. P., D'Orbcastel, E. R., & Verreth, J. A. J. (2010). New developments in recirculating aquaculture systems in Europe: A perspective on environmental sustainability. *Aquacultural Engineering*, 43(3), 83–93. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaeng.2010.09.002>

³⁶⁶ Rosa, J., Lemos, M. F. L., Crespo, D., Nunes, M., Freitas, A., Ramos, F., Pardal, M. Â., & Leston, S. (2020). Integrated multitrophic aquaculture systems – Potential risks for food safety. *Trends in Food Science & Technology*, 96, 79–90.

³⁶⁷ Chopin, T., Buschmann, A. H., Halling, C., Troell, M., Kautsky, N., Neori, A., Kraemer, G. P., Zertuche-González, J. A., Yarish, C., & Neefus, C. (2001). Integrating seaweeds into marine aquaculture systems: a key toward sustainability. *Journal of Phycology*, 37(6), 975–986. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1529-8817.2001.01137.x>

The models currently produced are composed of high-value commercial fish species, such as salmon, bivalve mollusks such as oysters and mussels, and marine macroalgae. The integrated multitrophic aquaculture model, as defined by Clements and Chopin³⁶⁸, is structured in open sea using cage culture systems and with the placement of bivalve mollusks and algae around the production structures, so that the material leaving the cage systems is directed to the secondary species. This same concept has also been adopted in land-based cultivation sites³⁶⁹.

Some of the main advantages of the system are: increased productivity with the optimization of resources used in production and the ecosystem services that the species can bring to cultivation and the environment as a whole³⁶⁸. Some of the challenges for the realization of integrated multitrophic systems include synchronization between the choice of species and their acceptance of the established environmental conditions at the cultivation sites so that each species can provide the projected ecosystem services³⁷⁰.

Bivalve mollusks are potential organisms for inclusion in multitrophic systems due to their filtering characteristics and market demand^{371,372,373}. The most widely produced bivalve mollusks in the world are oysters of the genus *Crassostrea*³⁷⁴.

In Brazil, *Crassostrea gigas* (Thunberg, 1793) is among the most produced mollusks. However, native species like *C. gasar* (Adanson, 1757) and *C. rhizophorae* (Guilding, 1828) are beginning to gain prominence. These species are common in mangrove environments and tolerate variations in environmental parameters observed on the Brazilian coast, especially temperature and total suspended solids.

Considering factors such as the need for better control of solids in biofloc production, the generation of large amounts of production residues, and minimal or zero water exchange in the system, constructing a system that maintains the production of *L. vannamei* shrimp while adding another

³⁶⁸ Clements, J. C., & Chopin, T. (2017). Ocean acidification and marine aquaculture in North America: potential impacts and mitigation strategies. *Reviews in Aquaculture*, 9(4), 326–341. <https://doi.org/10.1111/raq.12140>

³⁶⁹ Poersch, L., Brunson, J., Gaona, C. A. P., Stokes, A., Richardson, J., Pitts, K., & Leffler, J. (2021). Pacific white shrimp, red drum, and tilapia integrated in a biofloc system: Use of tilapia as a consumer of total suspended solids. *Journal of the World Aquaculture Society*, 52(6), 1168–1177. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jwas.12832>

³⁷⁰ Barrington, K., Chopin, T., & Robinson, S. (2009). Integrated multi-trophic aquaculture (IMTA) in marine temperate waters. *Advancing the Aquaculture Agenda*, 529, 7–46. https://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/agriculture-and-food/advancing-the-aquaculture-agenda/integrated-multi-trophic-aquaculture_9789264088726-15-

³⁷¹ Ahmed, N., & Thompson, S. (2019). The blue dimensions of aquaculture: A global synthesis. *Science of The Total Environment*, 652, 851–861. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2018.10.163>

³⁷² Omont, A., Elizondo-González, R., Quiroz-Guzmán, E., Escobedo-Fregoso, C., Hernández-Herrera, R., & Peña-Rodríguez, A. (2020). Digestive microbiota of shrimp *Penaeus vannamei* and oyster *Crassostrea gigas* co-cultured in integrated multi-trophic aquaculture system. *Aquaculture*, 521, 735059. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2020.735059>

³⁷³ Rosa, J., Lemos, M. F. L., Crespo, D., Nunes, M., Freitas, A., Ramos, F., Pardal, M. Â., & Leston, S. (2020). Integrated multitrophic aquaculture systems – Potential risks for food safety. *Trends in Food Science & Technology*, 96, 79–90.

³⁷⁴ FAO. (2020). The state of world fisheries and aquaculture. Sustainability in Action. <http://www.fao.org/3/ca9229en/ca9229en.pdf>.

species to the production could optimize the use of resources in cultivation, reduce effluents, and increase system productivity.

The aim of this study is to analyze the effects of incorporating two species of oysters into BFT shrimp cultivation systems, observing their influence on water quality parameters and system productivity. Two species were experimented with to select the one that best adapts to the systems and shows the best production results.

5.6.2 Trial Metodology

Experimental Site The experiment was conducted at the Marine Aquaculture Station (EMA) of the Institute of Oceanography at the Federal University of Rio Grande - FURG, located on Cassino Beach, city of Rio Grande, RS, Brazil (32° 12'14" S, 52° 10'40" W), from December 21, 2020, to February 8, 2021.

The marine shrimp *L. vannamei* were acquired from a larviculture company in the state of Santa Catarina and underwent a nursery period at EMA-FURG. After reaching an average weight of 0.3 g, they were transferred from the nursery to the experiment. The oysters *C. gasar* and *C. gigas* originated from a commercial farm located in Florianópolis, SC, and were acquired as adults, with an average length of 60 mm. The oysters were transported to the city of Rio Grande via land transport in thermal boxes without water and at low temperature for a period of 10 hours. Upon arrival at the laboratory, they were acclimatized for 15 days in 300-liter water tanks with filtered seawater. The oysters were placed in lanterns with four tiers, at a density of 40 oysters per tier. They were fed daily with bioflocs from the cultivation of marine shrimp *L. vannamei*. The water in the tanks with oysters was completely exchanged daily, and the bioflocs were added to this water so that the concentration of total suspended solids remained approximately at 50 mg/L. The water quality parameters during the acclimatization period were: temperature: 24.50 ± 0.92 °C; dissolved oxygen: 6.68 ± 0.61 mg/L; salinity: 31.74 ± 0.97 ; and pH: 7.66 ± 0.24 .

The experiment lasted for 50 days and was conducted in 300 L tanks with a useful volume of 250 L, with constant aeration provided by an air blower and rough hose (AeroTube™) (Figure 32). Three treatments were adopted, with four replicates each: Mono Treatment - monoculture of *L. vannamei* shrimp in bioflocs; Gasar Treatment - IMTA of *L. vannamei* shrimp and *C. gasar* oysters; and Gigas Treatment - IMTA of *L. vannamei* shrimp and *C. gigas* oysters in bioflocs. The stocking density of shrimp was 300 cam/m³, and in the treatments with oysters, the stocking density was 300 oysters/m³. The oysters were distributed in lanterns (Figure 32) with two upper tiers, each containing 40 individuals. The lantern was suspended from the bottom of the tank.

Figure 32. Tanks of 300 L with constant aeration for the cultivation of *L. vannamei* shrimp and *C. gasar* and *C. gigas* oysters stocked in lanterns. Source: personal file.

The tanks were filled with filtered saltwater (salinity 28), and at the beginning of the experiment, they received an inoculum of 10% bioflocs from an ongoing production with the presence of nitrate to characterize the maturity of the bioflocs. The average parameters of the inoculum were: temperature 29.34 ± 1.47 °C; oxygen 6.08 ± 0.38 mg/L; pH 8.26 ± 0.23 ; salinity 28.83 ± 1.76 ; nitrite 4.30 ± 5.48 mg/L; nitrate 16.57 ± 25.5 mg/L; and phosphate 1.35 ± 1.40 mg/L. Throughout the experiment, KERRAQUA probiotic was added, and administration was according to the manufacturer's instructions.

The shrimp were fed with 1.6 mm (40% PB) feed (Guabi Active - Guabi Nutrition and Animal Health), which was administered in all tanks based on shrimp biomass, following the table contained in the review article by Jory et al.³⁷⁵ and Garza de Yta et al.³⁷⁶. The use of feeding trays was also adopted to monitor shrimp feed intake.

Temperature and dissolved oxygen were measured twice daily using a multiparameter probe (Ecosense DO200). The pH was measured daily using a benchtop pH meter (Mettler Toledo). Salinity (measured using an optical refractometer), alkalinity³⁷⁷, ammonia³⁷⁸, and nitrite³⁷⁹ were checked three times a week and adjusted when necessary. When the total alkalinity values were below 150 mg

³⁷⁵ Jory, D. E., Cabrera, T. R., Dugger, D. M., Fegan, D., Lee, P. G., Lawrence, A. L., Jackson, C. J., McIntosh, R. P., & Castañeda, J. (2001). A global review of shrimp feed management: status and perspectives. In C. L. Browdy & D. Jory (Eds.), *The New Wave: Proceedings of the Special Session on Sustainable Shrimp Culture*. (pp. 104–152). The World Aquaculture Society.

³⁷⁶ Garza de Yta, A., Rouse, D. B., & Davis, D. A. (2004). Influence of Nursery Period on the Growth and Survival of *Litopenaeus vannamei* Under Pond Production Conditions. *Journal of the World Aquaculture Society*, 35(3), 357–365. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1749-7345.2004.tb00099.x>

³⁷⁷ APHA. (1989). *Standard Methods for the Examination of Water and Waste Water* (16th ed.). American Public Health Association, AWWA, WPCF.

³⁷⁸ UNESCO. (1983). *Chemical Methods for Use in Marine Environmental Monitoring. Manual and Guides 12*. Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission.

³⁷⁹ Strickland, J. D. H., & Parsons, T. R. (1972). *A Practical Handbook of Seawater Analysis* (2nd ed.). Fisheries Research Board of Canada.

CaCO₃/L, calcium hydroxide was applied to the tanks, following Furtado et al.³⁸⁰. Nitrate and phosphate were measured once a week³⁸¹.

Total suspended solids (TSS), settleable solids (SS), volatile solids (VS), turbidity, organic matter (OM), and inorganic matter (IM) were checked twice a week. Turbidity was measured using a portable turbidimeter (HACH 2100P). TSS were calculated by gravimetry, following a methodology adapted from AOAC³⁸²; SS were obtained using an Imhoff cone, according to Eaton et al. adapted by Avnimelech³⁸³; VS were obtained following the methodology of Hawkins et al.³⁸⁴, with the burning of filters (used for TSS determination) in a muffle furnace at 450 °C for four hours and subsequent weighing; organic matter (OM) and inorganic matter (IM) in percentage were defined from VS according to the equation: $OM = VS/TSS \times 100$ $IM = (TSS-VS) / TSS \times 100$ A limit was established for maximum TSS concentrations at 250 mg/L. When TSS values exceeded this limit, excess bioflocs were removed through clarification. In this process, cultivation water was pumped and passed through a 50 µm mesh bag filter and returned to the cultivation tanks. The clarification time was recorded in hours. Samples of cultivation water and material present in the stomachs of oysters were collected in the first week (day 1), fourth week (day 22), and seventh week (day 43) for microorganism analysis. For the analysis of microorganisms present in the stomachs, the oysters were sacrificed, and the stomach was removed. They were then cross-sectioned, and their contents were removed and fixed in 4.0% formalin. The samples were kept in amber bottles for subsequent microorganism counting. For bacterial counting, the samples were filtered through polycarbonate membranes (Nuclepore, 0.2 µm pore size, 2.5 mm diameter, pre-darkened with Irgalan Black) and stained with 1.0% Acridine Orange, at a concentration of 1.0 µg/mL³⁸⁵. The bacteria were photographed using a camera attached to an epifluorescence microscope (Axioplan-Zeiss), with a magnification of 1000X, for subsequent field counting. Only cocci bacteria were counted, as they prevailed in the collected samples. For protozoan counting, the samples were placed on a slide with a sedimentation chamber, taken to an inverted microscope (Olympus IX51) with a final magnification of 200X, and protozoans were counted in the

³⁸⁰ Furtado, P. S., Poersch, L. H., & Wasielesky, W. (2014). The effect of different alkalinity levels on *Litopenaeus vannamei* reared with biofloc technology (BFT). *Aquaculture International*, 23(1), 345–358. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10499-014-9819-x>

³⁸¹ Aminot, A., & Chaussepied, M. (1983). *Manuel des analyses chimiques en milieu marin*. CNEXO.

³⁸² AOAC. (1999). *Official methods of analysis of the AOAC*. (14th ed.). Washington: AOAC International.

³⁸³ Avnimelech, Y. (2007). Feeding with microbial flocs by tilapia in minimal discharge bio-flocs technology ponds. *Aquaculture*, 264(1–4), 140–147. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2006.11.025>

³⁸⁴ Hawkins, A., Smith, R., Bayne, B., & Héral, M. (1996). Novel observations underlying the fast growth of suspension-feeding shellfish in turbid environments: *Mytilus edulis*. *Marine Ecology Progress Series*, 131, 179–190. <https://doi.org/10.3354/meps131179>

³⁸⁵ Hobbie, J. E., Daley, R. J., & Jasper, S. (1977). Use of nuclepore filters for counting bacteria by fluorescence microscopy. *Applied and Environmental Microbiology*, 33(5), 1225–1228. <https://doi.org/10.1128/aem.33.5.1225-1228.1977>

fields according to Utermöhl's methodology³⁸⁶. Only flagellates and ciliates in the protozoan group were counted. All counts were conducted in the Phytoplankton and Marine Microorganisms Ecology Laboratory at EMA-FURG.

The zootechnical performance of the shrimp was determined through weekly biometrics to monitor weight using a digital scale (Marte BL3200H). From this parameter, the following were calculated:

- Final average weight (g): Σ final weight of live animals (g) / total number of animals;
- Weekly Weight Gain (WWG) (g/week) = (FW – IW) / number of weeks of cultivation;
- Final biomass (g): final average weight x number of individuals;
- Apparent Feed Conversion Ratio (FCR) = feed offered/biomass increment;
- Survival rate (%): (final biomass/individual average weight) / total number of stocked individuals) x 100.
- Productivity (kg/m³): (final biomass - initial biomass) / tank volume.

The zootechnical performance of the oysters was obtained through biometrics recording height (mm), length (mm), and width (mm) using an analog caliper according to Galtsoff³⁸⁷, and weight (g) using a digital scale (Marte BL3200H). Oyster biometrics were conducted at three points during cultivation: beginning (day 0), middle (day 25), and end (day 50). Weekly, the presence of open oysters indicating bivalve mortality was checked in the lanterns. If mortality occurred, dead oysters were removed.

The condition index (CI) of the oysters was obtained by removing them from the water and placing them on paper towels to reduce excess water from the shell surface for 30 minutes. Then, the total weight of the oysters was recorded. Subsequently, the oysters were opened, and the visceral mass of the animals was removed, placed on paper towels, and after removing excess water, the meat was weighed. The shells separated from the meat were left to dry at room temperature on paper towels and then weighed. The meat yield was calculated according to the equation:

- Meat yield (%): fresh meat weight / total oyster weight x 100.

After weighing the fresh meat, it was taken to an oven at 60 °C for 48 hours for subsequent weighing and recorded as dry weight (g), according to Lawrence and Scott³⁸⁸. With this data, the CI could be calculated following the methodology described by Crosby and Gale³⁸⁹, according to the equation:

³⁸⁶ Utermöhl, H. (1958). Zur Vervollkommnung der quantitativen phytoplankton-methodik. Hydrobiologischen Anstalt der Max-Planck-Gesellschaft.

³⁸⁷ Galtsoff, P. S. (1964). The American Oyster, *Crassostrea virginica* Gmelin. US Government Printing Office.

³⁸⁸ Lawrence, D. R., & Scott, G. I. (1982). The Determination and Use of Condition Index of Oysters. *Estuaries*, 5(1), 23. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1352213>

³⁸⁹ Crosby, M. P., & Gale, D. G. (1990). A review of bivalve condition index methodologies with a suggested standard method. *Journal of Shellfish Research*, 9(1), 233–237.

- Condition index (CI): $\text{dry weight} / (\text{total live weight of the oyster} - \text{dry weight of the valve}) \times 100$.

Biomass, survival rate, and productivity were also calculated according to the equations:

- Initial biomass (g): $\text{initial average weight} \times \text{number of individuals}$;
- Final biomass (g): $\text{final average weight} \times \text{number of individuals}$;
- Survival rate (%): $\text{final quantity} / \text{initial quantity} \times 100$;
- Productivity (kg/m³): $(\text{final biomass} - \text{initial biomass}) / \text{tank volume}$.

For the proximate composition analysis, samples of flocs, shrimp, and oysters were collected at the beginning and end of the experiment. The flocs were filtered through a 50 µm screen and then dried in an oven. The shrimp were collected, and the cephalothorax and exoskeleton of the abdominal region were removed, leaving only the abdominal meat for analysis. The fillet was then dried in an oven. The oysters were collected, and only the oyster meat was extracted and dried in an oven. The collected material was placed in an oven at 60°C for 48 hours. Afterward, it was ground, and the analyses were conducted in the Laboratory of Aquatic Organism Nutrition at EMA - FURG, following AOAC protocols³⁹⁰.

For ash quantification, the material was incinerated in a muffle furnace at 450°C for four hours. For crude protein analysis, the Kjeldahl method was adopted, involving the pre-digestion of samples followed by nitrogen distillation and titration. For lipids, the Soxhlet extraction method was used, employing petroleum ether as a solvent.

Initially, normality and homoscedasticity tests were conducted for all datasets. If the data met these assumptions, a one-way ANOVA was performed, followed by Tukey's post-hoc test. However, if the assumptions were not met, mathematical transformations such as cosine or sine functions were applied. If the assumptions were still not met after transformations, a non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis analysis was conducted.

For water quality data (total alkalinity, lime use, and clarification time), microorganisms, shrimp zootechnical performance, and proximate composition, a one-way ANOVA was conducted. Dissolved oxygen, temperature, salinity, pH, ammonia, nitrite, nitrate, phosphate, total suspended solids (TSS), settleable solids (SS), and volatile solids (VS), as well as oyster performance parameters, height, length, width, weight, condition index (CI), biomass, survival, productivity, and ash in the bioflocs, were analyzed using the Kruskal-Wallis non-parametric test. The results were expressed as mean and standard deviation³⁹¹ (Zar, 2010).

³⁹⁰ AOAC. (2000). Association of Official Analytical Chemists. (14th ed.). Official methods of analysis of AOAC International.

³⁹¹ Zar, J. H. (2010). Biostatistical Analysis (5th ed.). Prentice Hall.

5.6.3 Results

The mean values of dissolved oxygen, temperature, and salinity did not show significant differences ($p > 0.05$) (Table 17). Only pH, ammonia, and nitrite showed significant differences ($p < 0.05$) among the treatments. Ammonia was lower in the Mono treatment than in the treatments with oysters. Nitrite was lower in the Mono treatment, followed by the Gigas and Gasar treatments. There was no significant difference ($p > 0.05$) among the treatments for nitrate and phosphate values. Alkalinity showed significant differences ($p < 0.05$) among the treatments, with the mean values in the Mono treatment being higher than those in the Gasar treatment, which were higher than those in the Gigas treatment. The reduction in alkalinity was greater for the cultivation with *C. gigas* oysters than for the cultivation with *C. gasar* oysters. The Gigas treatment was significantly different ($p < 0.05$) from the others, requiring a greater amount of calcium hydroxide use throughout the cultivation.

Table 17. Average values and standard deviation of water quality parameters for the Mono, Gasar and Gigas treatments over the 50 days of the experiment.

	Mono	Gasar	Gigas
	Average \pm SD	Average \pm SD	Average \pm SD
Dissolved Oxygen (mg/L)	6,70 \pm 0,66	6,66 \pm 0,64	6,62 \pm 0,64
Temperature ($^{\circ}$ C)	26,47 \pm 1,37	26,42 \pm 1,38	26,47 \pm 1,35
pH	7,90 \pm 0,23 ^b	7,85 \pm 0,20 ^{ab}	7,82 \pm 0,18 ^a
Salinity	29,82 \pm 1,03	29,69 \pm 1,07	29,73 \pm 1,02
Amonia (mg/L)	0,11 \pm 0,05 ^b	0,14 \pm 0,07 ^a	0,15 \pm 0,12 ^a
Nitrite (mg/L)	0,33 \pm 0,40 ^a	0,52 \pm 0,27 ^c	0,42 \pm 0,21 ^b
Nitrate (mg/L)	15,26 \pm 7,98	16,05 \pm 7,18	18,61 \pm 9,36
Phosphate (mg/L)	0,63 \pm 0,44	0,69 \pm 0,52	0,68 \pm 0,50
Alkalinity (mg CaCO ₃ /L)	161,67 \pm 17,82 ^a	152,98 \pm 16,34 ^b	146,14 \pm 17,02 ^c
Calcium Hidroxyde (g)	84,38 \pm 15,73 ^a	109,38 \pm 15,73 ^a	150 \pm 10,21 ^b
TSS (mg/L)	181,13 \pm 75,86	168,90 \pm 91,46	177,35 \pm 85,34
SS (mL/L)	3,94 \pm 6,53	6,02 \pm 11,19	21,71 \pm 44,57
Turbidity (NTU)	60,37 \pm 53,31	53,76 \pm 54,26	63,65 \pm 57,14
SV (mg/L)	89,91 \pm 43,48	78,92 \pm 51,59	81,11 \pm 43,11
OM (%)	54,27 \pm 9,85	54,15 \pm 14,48	51,59 \pm 8,66
IM (%)	45,73 \pm 9,85	45,85 \pm 14,48	48,41 \pm 8,66
Clarification (hours)	0,41 \pm 0,16	0,54 \pm 0,16	0,72 \pm 0,23

The parameters related to the quantity of solids in the cultivation did not show significant differences ($p > 0.05$) among the treatments. Overall, total suspended solids (TSS) (Figure 33 A), volatile solids (VS) (Figure 33 C), and turbidity (Figure 33 D) showed an increase throughout the cultivation period. Settleable solids (SS) (Figure 33 B) increased in the Gigas treatment starting from day 31 due to the appearance of filamentous bacteria in some replicates of the treatment, although it was not sufficient to show a significant difference ($p > 0.05$) compared to the other treatments. The percentage of organic material remained stable throughout the experiment.

Figure 33. Average values and standard deviation of total suspended solids (TSS) (A), settleable solids (SS) (B), volatile solids (SV) (C), turbidity (D) and organic matter (OM) (E) in the Mono, Gigas and Gasar treatments over the 50 days of the experiment. The values in the graphs are means of the treatments and the vertical bars represent the standard deviation values.

The counts of cocoid bacteria present in the water (Figure 34 A) did not show significant differences ($p > 0.05$) among the treatments on days 1 and 22, but they did show differences ($p < 0.05$) on day 43, where the mono treatment had higher means compared to the treatments with oysters. Regarding

flagellate protozoa present in the water (Figure 34 B), there was a statistical difference ($p < 0.05$) between the results on days 1 and 22. On day 43, there was no difference ($p > 0.05$) among the treatments. For ciliated protozoa present in the water (Figure 34 C), there was no significant difference ($p > 0.05$) among the treatments.

Figure 34. Average values and standard deviation of the concentration of microorganisms (organisms/mL) present in the culture water on day 1, day 22 and day 43 of the experiment. (A) Cocoid bacteria, (B) flagellated protozoa and (C) ciliated protozoa. The values in the graphs are means of the treatments and the vertical bars represent the standard deviation values.

Regarding the microorganisms present in the stomach of the oysters (Figure 35), there was no significant difference ($p > 0.05$) for bacteria and flagellates among the different oyster species. Ciliates were not detected in the stomach of the oysters.

Figure 35. Average values and standard deviation of the concentration of microorganisms (organisms/mL) present in the stomach of oysters on day 1, day 22 and day 43 of the experiment. (A) Coccoid bacteria and (B) flagellated protozoa. The values in the graphs are means of the Gasar and Gigas treatments and the vertical bars represent the standard deviation values.

There was no significant difference ($p > 0.05$) in any of the zootechnical performance parameters of the shrimp among the different treatments (Table 18).

Table 18. Zootechnical performance parameters (with mean and standard deviation) of *L. vannamei* shrimp in 50 days of cultivation in the Mono, Gasar and Gigas treatments.

	MONO	GASAR	GIGAS
	Average ± SD	Average ± SD	Average ± SD
final weight (g)	4,41 ± 0,63	4,60 ± 1,19	4,50 ± 0,97
weight gain (g)	4,03 ± 0,63	4,22 ± 1,19	4,12 ± 0,97
GPS (g)	0,58 ± 0,09	0,60 ± 0,17	0,59 ± 0,14
CAA	2,52 ± 1,02	2,44 ± 1,03	2,18 ± 0,76
Survival (%)	74 ± 23,29	72,67 ± 17,06	80 ± 11,52
Final biomass (g)	222,52 ± 74,4	253,96 ± 101,04	273,2 ± 77,62
Productivity (kg/m ³)	1,21 ± 0,16	1,24 ± 0,32	1,24 ± 0,31

Figure 36. Average weight (g) and standard deviation of shrimp throughout the experiment. The values in the graphs are means of the treatments and the vertical bars represent the standard deviation values.

Regarding the oysters, the initial reference parameter for cultivation was the height of 60mm for both species. The other measurements showed significant differences ($p < 0.05$) among the treatments, such as greater total weight, length, and initial biomass for *C. gasar* oysters (Figure 36). Only the parameter of width was greater for *C. gigas* oysters (Table 19).

Table 19. Mean values and standard deviation of biometric parameters of *C. gasar* and *C. gigas* oysters at the beginning of the experiment

Treatment	Weight (g)	Height (mm)	Length (mm)	Width (mm)	Initial biomass (g)
	Média ± DP				
Gasar	42,04 ± 6,29a	63,95 ± 3,42a	47,83 ± 4,40a	21,92 ± 1,92b	3153,15 ± 72,86a
Gigas	38,35 ± 6,90b	65,13 ± 4,02a	44,7 ± 3,96b	23,33 ± 3,18a	2876,54 ± 165,45b

Different letters on the same line represent significant differences ($p < 0.05$).

The *C. gasar* oysters showed a higher condition index (CI) at the beginning of the experiment compared to the *C. gigas* oysters. The shells and fresh meat weight represent a higher percentage of weight in *C. gasar* oysters than in *C. gigas* oysters (Table 20).

Table 20. Mean values and standard deviation of weight (in percentage) referring to valves and fresh meat of oysters and oyster condition index at the beginning of the experiment.

Treatment	Valve weight (%)	Fresh meat weight (%)	CI
	Média ± DP	Média ± DP	Média ± DP
Gasar	71,16 ± 2,30 ^a	17,00 ± 2,38 ^a	16,41 ± 1,54 ^a
Gigas	57,96 ± 4,47 ^b	14,47 ± 3,89 ^b	6,18 ± 1,20 ^b

Different letters on the same line represent significant differences ($p < 0.05$). SD: standard deviation. CI: Condition index

Both *C. gasar* and *C. gigas* oysters showed growth throughout the cultivation period (Figure 37). Considering total weight, height, length, and width, *C. gasar* exhibited growth rates of 3.37%, 0.20%, 1.56%, and 2.60%, respectively, while *C. gigas* showed growth rates of 7.77%, 1.30%, 5.54%, and 6.17%, respectively. The *C. gigas* species exhibited more significant growth than the *C. gasar* species. However, concerning meat yield (Figure 38), there was a reduction for both species compared to the beginning of the experiment, indicating a decrease in the relative amount of meat in the oysters over the cultivation period.

Figure 37. Mean values and standard deviation of total weight (g) (A), height (mm) (B), length (mm) (C) and width (mm) (D) of oysters *C. gasar* and *C. gigas* throughout the experiment. The values in the graphs are means of the treatments and the vertical bars represent the standard deviation values.

Figure 38. Average values and standard deviation of yield (in percentage) of *C. gasar* and *C. gigas* oysters throughout the experiment. The values in the graphs are means of the treatments and the vertical bars represent the standard deviation values.

The survival of oysters began to decline from the third week of cultivation for both species (Figure 39), reaching average values below 50% at the end of the cultivation period. For the *C. gasar* species, the survival rate at 50 days of cultivation was $47.00 \pm 35.65\%$, and for *C. gigas*, it was $32.33 \pm 6.19\%$, with no significant difference ($p > 0.05$) between the treatments. The average values of final biomass for *C. gasar* were 1533.41 ± 678.78 g, and for *C. gigas* were 904.00 ± 241.43 g, but they did not show significant differences ($p > 0.05$).

Figure 39. Mean values and standard deviation of survival (in percentage) of *C. gasar* and *C. gigas* oysters throughout the experiment. The values in the graphs are means of the treatments and the vertical bars represent the standard deviation values.

There was no significant difference ($p > 0.05$) in productivity between the different oyster species. The oyster productivity was low due to the high mortality of both analyzed species (Table 6).

Table 21. Zootechnical performance parameters, with mean and standard deviation, of oysters over the 50 days of cultivation in the Gasar and Gigas treatments.

	GASAR	GIGAS
	Average \pm SD	Average \pm SD
Final weight (g)	43,52 \pm 1,40	41,56 \pm 1,55
Weight gain (g)	1,44 \pm 1,99	3,21 \pm 1,54
Grow. Height (mm)	0,50 \pm 1,83	0,91 \pm 0,77
Grow. Length (mm)	0,49 \pm 0,72	2,58 \pm 1,12
Grow. Width (mm)	0,88 \pm 0,84	1,44 \pm 0,43
Survival (%)	47,00 \pm 35,65	32,33 \pm 6,19
Final biomass (g)	1533,41 \pm 678,78	1003,48 \pm 164,18
Productivity (kg/m ³)	-6,48 \pm 4,51	-7,49 \pm 1,09

The average values of proteins, lipids, and ashes of the bioflocs, shrimp, and oysters at the beginning of the cultivation can be seen in Table 22. The proximal composition values were compared between the oyster species, and there was a significant difference ($p < 0.05$) regarding the protein, lipid, and ash content of the meat. *C. gasar* oysters had lower protein and ash values than *C. gigas* oysters. *C. gasar* oysters showed a higher amount of lipids than *C. gigas*.

Table 22. Proximate composition (%) of biofloc, shrimp and oysters, with mean and standard deviation at the beginning of cultivation.

Sample	Protein (%)	Lipids (%)	Ash (%)
	Average \pm SD	Average \pm SD	Average \pm SD
Biofloc	12,9 \pm 0,31	0,79 \pm 0,16	69,35 \pm 0,08
<i>L. vannamei</i>	81,61 \pm 7,32	14,01 \pm 4,65	5,93 \pm 0,06
<i>C. gasar</i>	44,00 \pm 1,51	20,96 \pm 1,55	7,60 \pm 0,17
<i>C. gigas</i>	56,12 \pm 1,39	7,75 \pm 0,11	13,73 \pm 0,14

The proximate composition values of the bioflocs, shrimp, and oysters are shown in Table 23. The proximate composition of the bioflocs differed significantly ($p < 0.05$) in proteins and ashes. The Mono treatment had a higher protein content than the Gigas treatment and a lower ash content than the Gasar and Gigas treatments. For the shrimp, there was no significant difference ($p > 0.05$) in proteins, lipids, and ashes between the treatments.

Table 23. Proximate composition (%) of biofloc, shrimp and oysters at the end of the cultivation period, with mean values and standard deviation.

	PROTEIN (%)		
	Gasar	Gigas	Mono
	Average ± SD	Average ± SD	Average ± SD
Biofloc	21,19 ± 1,76 ^{ab}	18,5 ± 6,15 ^b	24,91 ± 4,90 ^a
Shrimp	85,21 ± 2,59	83,36 ± 3,32	83,68 ± 2,46
Oysters	44,39 ± 2,27	51,72 ± 1,48	-
	LIPIDS (%)		
	Gasar	Gigas	Mono
	Average ± SD	Average ± SD	Average ± SD
Biofloc	0,63 ± 0,43	1,26 ± 0,45	0,78 ± 0,46
Shrimp	3,88 ± 0,89	5,27 ± 2,91	4,65 ± 2,27
Oysters	16,85 ± 3,34	12,3 ± 4,88	-
	ASH (%)		
	Gasar	Gigas	Mono
	Average ± SD	Average ± SD	Average ± SD
Biofloc	56,06 ± 2,50 ^b	56,75 ± 2,67 ^b	51,13 ± 1,48 ^a
Shrimp	5,46 ± 0,21	5,43 ± 0,22	5,45 ± 0,64
Oysters	8,66 ± 0,83	19,41 ± 3,05	-

For the oysters, two comparisons were made: first, between different species at the end of the cultivation period, and second, within the same species comparing the beginning and end of the cultivation. At the end of the cultivation, there was no significant difference ($p > 0.05$) between oyster species in lipids. There was a difference ($p < 0.05$) in proteins and ash; *C. gasar* had lower amounts of proteins and ashes than *C. gigas*.

Comparing the centesimal composition within the same oyster species, for *C. gasar*, there was no difference ($p > 0.05$) in the percentages of proteins, lipids, and ashes from the beginning to the end of the experiment. For *C. gigas*, there was no difference ($p > 0.05$) in lipid content between the beginning and end of the experiment, but there was a significant difference ($p < 0.05$) in proteins and ashes. The proteins were lower at the end of the experiment, and the ash content were higher at the end of the experiment.

5.6.4 Discussion and Conclusions

Water quality parameters remained within the ideal range for *L. vannamei* shrimp, with dissolved oxygen levels ranging from 5.0 to 9.0 mg/L, and they were not influenced by the presence of oysters. The intense aeration in the BFT system maintained adequate oxygen levels even with high demands

from shrimp, oysters, microorganisms, and the biochemical demands of the system. Although the average temperature of the treatments was below the ideal range for *L. vannamei* growth, between 28 and 32°C, it remained within an acceptable range for the shrimp. Salinity also remained within the appropriate range for the shrimp.

For oysters, the most influential parameters on their performance are temperature and salinity, despite species of the genus *Crassostrea* being euryhaline and eurythermal. *C. gigas* tolerates a wide range of temperatures, with an optimal growth and survival range between 26°C and 28°C, and it grows optimally in salinities ranging from 20 to 25 but can occur in salinities below 10 and survive at salinities above 35.

The oyster *C. gasar* performs well in temperatures ranging between 23°C and 31°C. Salinity levels between 15 and 25 are the most recommended for its cultivation, but it can survive in waters with salinity ranging from 8 to 34. Results from previous studies suggest that *C. gasar* can be cultivated in elevated salinities, above the normal variation limit observed in estuarine environments, allowing for production in marine waters. These findings are supported by studies that found promising growth of *C. gasar* oysters cultivated in marine environments in the state of Santa Catarina (Freire 2021). Some authors mention that increased temperature can accelerate numerous physiological processes in bivalves. In this experiment, the temperature remained within the suitable range for oyster production, and the salinity was within the tolerable range for both *C. gasar* and *C. gigas*.

The average pH values ranged between 7.8 and 7.9, therefore within the appropriate range for shrimp as described by Van Wyk and Scarpa³⁹². There are no studies indicating the ideal pH range for oyster cultivation. Generally, oysters are cultivated in estuarine areas with pH above 6. Freire³⁹³, in an experiment with *C. gigas* oysters fed with bioflocs, recorded a mean pH of 7.96 ± 0.10 , similar to the values recorded in this experiment. The presence of *C. gigas* oysters caused a significant difference ($p < 0.05$) in pH, possibly due to the presence of a greater quantity of organisms in the tanks, leading to increased carbon dioxide production and consequently lower pH. However, the reduction was not significant enough to compromise the quality of the cultivation environment.

A similar situation occurred with ammonia and nitrite, where the increased quantity of organisms in the tank led to an increase in these compounds due to the activity of the animals. Despite the elevation in treatments with IMTA, the total ammonia and nitrite values remained within safe levels for *L.*

³⁹² Van Wyk, P., & Scarpa, J. (1999). Water quality requirements and management. In P. Van Wyk, M. Davis-Hodgkins, R. Laramore, K. Main, J. Mountain, & J. Scarpa (Eds.), *Farming Marine Shrimp in Recirculating Freshwater Systems* (p. 128). Florida Department of Agriculture.

³⁹³ Freire, T. B. (2021). Bioflocos na alimentação de ostras do Pacífico *Crassostrea gigas* (Thunberg, 1793) [Universidade Federal de Santa Catarina]. <https://repositorio.ufsc.br/handle/123456789/229759?show=full>

vannamei, which according to Lin and Chen³⁹⁴ is 2.44 mg/L (at salinity 15, pH 8.05, and temperature of 23°C) for total ammonia and according to Lin and Chen³⁹⁵ is 6.10 mg/L at salinity 15 for juvenile *L. vannamei*.

In the multitrophic cultivation of marine shrimp with tilapia, Barboza et al.³⁹⁶ observed an increase in ammonia and nitrite during cultivation due to (1) the effect of fish swimming that could disrupt the structure of bioflocs or inhibit bacterial action; (2) the passage of bioflocs through the fish's digestive tract affecting the microbial community, reducing the abundance of ammonia-oxidizing bacteria (AOB) and nitrite-oxidizing bacteria (NOB), or (3) the fish feeding on bioflocs in a way that affected nitrifying bacteria due to lack of substrate for their development.

In the case of oysters, their selective filtration may have influenced ammonia and nitrite parameters through excretion because unlike tilapia, they do not perform swimming agitation in the water to disrupt bioflocs, and in filtration, they do not have preferences for bacteria. The oysters' filtration process occurs in the gills, where part of the material is selected and conducted to the mouth, and part of the material is discarded in the form of pseudofeces.

In the filtration process, the filtered material returns to the cultivation water, reintegrating the material present in the environment. Lima et al.³⁹⁷ also recorded an increase in ammonia and nitrite levels in integrated cultivation with *C. gasar* oysters and *L. vannamei* shrimp in BFT compared to monoculture shrimp in BFT systems. In this experiment, there was no observed increase in nitrate and phosphate concentration, likely due to the removal of total suspended solids (TSS) through clarification, similar to observations by Gaona et al.³⁹⁸.

For shrimp cultivation in BFT systems, alkalinity should be kept high (above 100 mg CaCO₃/L) in systems with little or no water exchange to favor biofloc formation and maintain nitrifying bacteria³⁹⁹.

For mollusks, alkalinity is important for shell formation, which consists of calcium carbonates, often in

³⁹⁴ Lin, Y.-C., & Chen, J.-C. (2001). Acute toxicity of ammonia on *Litopenaeus vannamei* Boone juveniles at different salinity levels. *Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology*, 259(1), 109–119. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-0981\(01\)00227-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-0981(01)00227-1)

³⁹⁵ Lin, Y.-C., & Chen, J.-C. (2003). Acute toxicity of nitrite on *Litopenaeus vannamei* (Boone) juveniles at different salinity levels. *Aquaculture*, 224(1–4), 193–201. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0044-8486\(03\)00220-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0044-8486(03)00220-5)

³⁹⁶ Barboza, M. H. P. (2019). Cultivo multitrófico integrado de *Litopenaeus vannamei* e peixes para controle dos sólidos suspensos totais em sistema de bioflocos [UNIVERSIDADE FEDERAL DO RIO GRANDE - FURG]. <https://ppgaquicultura.furg.br/dissertacoes-e-teses/teses/146-teses-de-2019/449-tese-mariana-holanda>

³⁹⁷ Lima, P. C. M., Silva, A. E. M., Silva, D. A., Silva, S. M. B. C., Brito, L. O., & Gálvez, A. O. (2021). Effect of stocking density of *Crassostrea* sp. in a multitrophic biofloc system with *Litopenaeus vannamei* in nursery. *Aquaculture*, 530, 735913. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2020.735913>

³⁹⁸ Gaona, C. A. P., Poersch, L. H., Krummenauer, D., Foes, G. K., & Wasielesky, W. J. (2011). The Effect of Solids Removal on Water Quality, Growth and Survival of *Litopenaeus vannamei* in a Biofloc Technology Culture System. *International Journal of Recirculating Aquaculture*, 12(1). <https://doi.org/10.21061/ijra.v12i1.1354>

³⁹⁹ Ebeling, J. M., Timmons, M. B., & Bisogni, J. J. (2006). Engineering analysis of the stoichiometry of photoautotrophic, autotrophic, and heterotrophic removal of ammonia–nitrogen in aquaculture systems. *Aquaculture*, 257(1–4), 346–358. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2006.03.019>

the form of aragonite and calcite⁴⁰⁰. The reduction in alkalinity in treatments with oysters may have been caused by the oysters' demand for carbonates for shell formation, reflecting the need for greater use of calcium hydroxide in IMTA treatments.

The TSS remained within the recommended range for shrimp in BFT systems. Gaona et al.⁴⁰¹ suggest that to maintain beneficial levels of ammonia and nitrite in BFT systems, the TSS concentration should be between 100 and 300 mg/L. However, for oysters, high TSS concentrations can be detrimental to their performance. Thus, in this experiment, it was established that TSS would be maintained at a maximum concentration of 250 mg/L. The use of clarifiers helped maintain concentrations of total suspended solids, settleable solids, volatile solids, and the percentage of organic matter without significant differences in these parameters.

Regarding the possible effects of the presence of oysters on total suspended solids (TSS), their sessile nature can influence the dynamics of these solids. According to Absher⁴⁰², species of the genus *Crassostrea* are sessile and exhibit a wide diversity in shell morphology, related to the substrate to which they are attached. This characteristic is particularly relevant for their cultivation in biofloc systems, as they can act as a "barrier" in the water movement dynamics of the system. This characteristic did not seem to affect water quality in the tested system; however, observations at the cultivation site revealed a significant concentration of floc deposited on the oyster shells.

This indicated that the valve facing the top of the tanks could be considered a "calm" area of water and therefore a deposition zone for solids (Figure 18). This concentration may not affect system parameters but could be detrimental to the oysters due to the increased solid concentration in their vicinity. Upon the death of some specimens and subsequent valve opening, a large amount of solids deposition was observed inside the valves.

Unlike the results found in this experiment, Miranda et al.⁴⁰³ reported a reduction in total suspended solids (TSS) in integrated cultivation of oysters with tilapia in treatments with 2, 4, and 8 oysters compared to the control without oysters, but the TSS concentration in the systems was approximately 7.0 mg/L. The high concentrations of total suspended solids in this experiment, compared to

⁴⁰⁰ Addadi, L., Joester, D., Nudelman, F., & Weiner, S. (2006). Mollusk Shell Formation: A Source of New Concepts for Understanding Biomineralization Processes. *Chemistry - A European Journal*, 12(4), 980–987. <https://doi.org/10.1002/chem.200500980>

⁴⁰¹ Gaona, C. A. P., de Almeida, M. S., Viau, V., Poersch, L. H., & Wasielesky, W. (2017). Effect of different total suspended solids levels on a *Litopenaeus vannamei* (Boone, 1931) BFT culture system during biofloc formation. *Aquaculture Research*, 48(3), 1070–1079. <https://doi.org/10.1111/are.12949>

⁴⁰² Absher, T. M. (1989). Populações naturais de ostras do gênero *Crassostrea* do litoral do Paraná -Desenvolvimento larval, recrutamento e crescimento. Tese de doutorado. Universidade de São Paulo.

⁴⁰³ Miranda, A., Lizarraga-Armenta, J., Rivas-Vega, M., López-Elías, J. A., & Nieves-Soto, M. (2010). Pacific Oyster, *Crassostrea gigas*, Cultured With Tilapia, *Oreochromis mossambicus*×*Oreochromis niloticus* in a Recirculation System. *Journal of the World Aquaculture Society*, 41(5), 764–772. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1749-7345.2010.00418.x>

environments where oysters are usually produced, made the removal effect of suspended material from the water by bivalves imperceptible.

Lima et al.⁴⁰⁴ reported significant differences ($p < 0.05$) for solid parameters between monoculture shrimp treatment and IMTA treatment of oysters with shrimp, with higher concentrations of total suspended solids (431.13 mg/L), volatile suspended solids (217.49 mg/L), and sedimentable solids (13.19 mL/L) in monoculture shrimp treatment than in integrated treatment with oysters in BFT system, but the positioning of the oysters in the cultivation system was different from that adopted in the present experiment. Lima et al.⁴⁰⁴ state that oysters can feed in turbid waters, but the level of solids influences the survival of these bivalves, justifying the statement by the negative correlation found between the survival of oysters and the amount of sedimentable solids in tests conducted prior to the experiment.

In multitrophic systems, the absence of ammonia and nitrite accumulation and the presence of nitrate indicate that the microbial community is performing nitrification. In the BFT system, with the increase in ammonia concentration, it is common practice to add organic carbon to reduce ammonia when nitrifying bacteria are not performing nitrification. In the present experiment, it was not necessary to apply organic carbon, possibly because the initial use of inoculum from a mature system⁴⁰⁵ was efficient for maintaining nitrifying bacteria, and the presence of oysters did not affect this community to the extent of compromising the nitrification process.

Analyzing the behavior of microorganisms in the control treatment (Mono) and using this situation as a reference for comparison, it can be affirmed that: (1) ciliates were more abundant at the end of the experiment, reaching over 4,000 organisms/mL; (2) flagellates showed an increase in density in the middle of the culture period and then decreased their concentration towards the end of the experiment; (3) bacteria showed an increase in density at the end of the culture period compared to the initial stage. Overall, it can be noted that the increase in ciliates led to a reduction in flagellates at the end of the experiment; with the reduction in flagellates, there was a slight increase in the bacterial community.

Taking the scenario of microorganisms in the control treatment (Mono) as a basis and considering the microorganisms found in the stomach contents of the oysters in greater quantity, it can be affirmed that oysters prefer flagellates in their filtration process and direction towards the stomach. This preference for flagellates is reflected in the lower densities of flagellates on day 01 and day 22 of the

⁴⁰⁴ Lima, P. C. M., Silva, A. E. M., Silva, D. A., Silva, S. M. B. C., Brito, L. O., & Gálvez, A. O. (2021). Effect of stocking density of *Crassostrea* sp. in a multitrophic biofloc system with *Litopenaeus vannamei* in nursery. *Aquaculture*, 530, 735913. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2020.735913>

⁴⁰⁵ Krummenauer, D., Samocha, T., Poersch, L., Lara, G., & Wasielesky, W. (2014). The Reuse of Water on the Culture of Pacific White Shrimp, *Litopenaeus vannamei*, in BFT System. *Journal of the World Aquaculture Society*, 45(1), 3–14. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jwas.12093>

experiment in treatments with oysters, when compared to the concentrations of the Mono treatment. These data corroborate information from Costa et al.⁴⁰⁶, who state that oysters select flagellates in their filtration process in BFT systems.

The process of structuring trophic chains and microbial loops can be explained by top-down and bottom-up controls. In top-down control, organisms at higher levels of the trophic chain control the density of organisms at the level immediately below theirs through predation. In bottom-up control, the high density of one level in the trophic chain is responsible for the increase in density of the level immediately above it, due to the high food supply. In the situation of introducing oysters into the cultivation system, they act as predators of flagellates, reducing their growth rate compared to the Mono treatment on day 22 of cultivation, confirming top-down control over flagellates. From this date onwards, oyster mortality increased significantly, reducing their effect on flagellates along with the increase in SST. However, overall, the pressure exerted by oysters on microorganisms was not sufficient to compromise the nitrification process in the BFT system; their most significant effect was on the flagellate population.

The presence of oysters *C. gasar* and *C. gigas* did not influence the performance parameters of the shrimp, unlike the results found by Holanda et al.⁴⁰⁷ when they analyzed the growth of marine shrimp integrated with mullet (*Mugil spp.*), where the presence of mullets in the same tank as the shrimp negatively influenced the growth of the shrimp. The difference in results between the experiments may be related to the biological characteristics between fish and oysters. The type of feeding and swimming performed by fish may have caused stress to the shrimp. In the case of oysters, this stress is not noticed due to the sessile condition of the bivalves, in addition to the fact that oysters had little effect on reducing the solids present in the system and because they do not feed directly on shrimp feed, as done by fish.

The shrimp had low weekly growth compared to results from integrated cultivation of shrimp *L. vannamei* with Nile tilapia *Oreochromis niloticus* and red drum *Sciaenops ocellatus* (1.33 ± 0.07 g/week) and shrimp *L. vannamei* with mullets (from 1.3 to 1.8 g/week)^{408, 407}, possibly due to the effect of temperature. Shrimp survival was above 70%, considered acceptable for commercial systems.

⁴⁰⁶ Costa, L. C. de O., Poersch, L. H. da S., & Abreu, P. C. (2021). Biofloc removal by the oyster *Crassostrea gasar* as a candidate species to an Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture (IMTA) system with the marine shrimp *Litopenaeus vannamei*. *Aquaculture*, 540, 736731. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2021.736731>

⁴⁰⁷ Holanda, M., Santana, G., Furtado, P., Rodrigues, R. V., Cerqueira, V. R., Sampaio, L. A., Wasielesky, W., & Poersch, L. H. (2020). Evidence of total suspended solids control by *Mugil liza* reared in an integrated system with pacific white shrimp *Litopenaeus vannamei* using biofloc technology. *Aquaculture Reports*, 18, 100479. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aqrep.2020.100479>

⁴⁰⁸ Poersch, L., Brunson, J., Gaona, C. A. P., Stokes, A., Richardson, J., Pitts, K., & Leffler, J. (2021). Pacific white shrimp, red drum, and tilapia integrated in a biofloc system: Use of tilapia as a consumer of total suspended solids. *Journal of the World Aquaculture Society*, 52(6), 1168–1177. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jwas.12832>

Similar results were found by Poersch et al.⁴⁰⁸ for shrimp *L. vannamei* cultured with Nile tilapia *Oreochromis niloticus* and red drum *Sciaenops ocellatus*: 72% survival.

The productivity of the shrimp was below the results found by Poersch et al.⁴⁰⁸ in integrated shrimp farming with Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) and red drum (*Sciaenops ocellatus*) (2.06 ± 0.76). However, when considering only the production of *L. vannamei* shrimp in monoculture and in treatments integrated with oysters, there was no difference in productivity, meaning that the oysters did not influence shrimp productivity. On the other hand, when considering the total productivity of the treatments, by adding the production of shrimp and oysters in the integrated treatments, there was a decrease in productivity due to the high mortality of the *C. gasar* and *C. gigas* oysters. Therefore, in treatments integrated with oysters, productivity was greatly affected by the high mortality of the bivalves. Lima et al.⁴⁰⁹, cultivating *Crassostrea* oysters in bioflocs with SS of 5.0 mL/L, 10 mL/L, and 20 mL/L, had survivals close to 90%, 70%, and 40%, respectively, in 15 days of cultivation.

Oysters are sessile bivalves that feed on suspended particles in the water through the filtration process^{410,411}. Water enters the oysters' pallial cavity through the valve openings; the water with suspended material comes into contact with the gills and their cilia, from which particulate materials are removed⁴¹².

In environments where oysters occur naturally or in natural environments where they are cultivated, this filtration process reduces turbidity, improves water quality⁴¹³, controls phytoplankton biomass, and makes systems more resistant to increases in external nutrient loads⁴¹⁴. Additionally, they remove nutrients from the water column, such as protein for tissues and shell⁴¹⁵, as well as transfer them to the sediment from feces and pseudofeces⁴¹³. In summary, oysters capture suspended material in the water, pass it through the gills and/or digestive tract, and return part of the material in a more compact form, which, due to its higher density, is directed to the bottom of water bodies. In the present

⁴⁰⁹ Lima, P. C. M., Silva, A. E. M., Silva, D. A., Silva, S. M. B. C., Brito, L. O., & Gálvez, A. O. (2021). Effect of stocking density of *Crassostrea* sp. in a multitrophic biofloc system with *Litopenaeus vannamei* in nursery. *Aquaculture*, 530, 735913. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2020.735913>

⁴¹⁰ Gosling, E. (2015). Ecology of bivalves. In *Marine Bivalve Molluscs* (Second, pp. 44–98). John Wiley & Sons, Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781119045212.ch3>

⁴¹¹ Nascimento, V. S. (2020). Taxa de filtração e biodepósitos de ostras do gênero *Crassostrea* [Universidade Federal de Santa Catarina]. <https://repositorio.ufsc.br/handle/123456789/219532>

⁴¹² Dame, R. F. (2016). Ecology of Marine Bivalves. CRC Press. <https://doi.org/10.1201/b11220>

⁴¹³ Newell, R. I. E., Fisher, T. R., Holyoke, R. R., & Cornwell, J. C. (2005). Influence of Eastern Oysters on Nitrogen and Phosphorus Regeneration in Chesapeake Bay, USA. In *The Comparative Roles of Suspension-Feeders in Ecosystems* (pp. 93–120). Springer-Verlag. https://doi.org/10.1007/1-4020-3030-4_6

⁴¹⁴ Sroczynska, K., Barroso, G., & Chicharo, L. (2012). In situ effective clearance rate measurement of mangrove oysters (*Crassostrea rhizophorae*) in a tropical estuary in Brazil. *Ecology & Hydrobiology*, 12(4), 301–310. <https://doi.org/10.2478/v10104-012-0024-0>

⁴¹⁵ Rice, M. A. (2008). Environmental effects of shellfish aquaculture in the northeast.

https://www.academia.edu/66252074/Environmental_Effects_of_Shellfish_Aquaculture_in_the_Northeast

experiment, overall growth of the oysters was noted, considering total weight, height, length, and width, but this growth may be attributed solely to shell growth, with no increase in meat.

In natural environments where oysters are cultivated, the particulate material retained in the gills of bivalve molluscs originates from the production zones, consisting of bacteria, phytoplankton, small invertebrate larvae, suspended debris in the water, and protozoa, which contribute to the varied diet of these organisms⁴¹⁶, resembling items observed in BFT systems. According to Wasielesky et al.⁴¹⁷, bioflocs are composed of diatoms, microalgae, fungi, bacteria, protozoa, rotifers, nematodes, fecal remains and feed, exoskeletons, bacteria, among others, forming an aggregate of living and dead organic matter suspended in the culture water. Therefore, bioflocs contain organic material that can serve as food for oysters.

However, other characteristics make these locations (natural cultivation environments and intensive production tanks) very different in relation to oyster farming. Nascimento⁴¹¹ conducted experiments with oyster biodeposits in Florianópolis, SC, Brazil, and found total particulate material (equivalent to TSS) for oyster cultivation sites in natural environments ranging from 6.0 to 36 mg/L of particulate material.

In the case of the cultivation environment like the BFT system, the material can be filtered, passed through the gills or gills and digestive tract, and returned to the culture water, but due to the system's dynamics, it does not remain in the lower layers and thus returns to the suspended material condition. And, surely, it is filtered again by the bivalve. This filtration has an energetic cost for the oysters. When analyzing performance parameters of oysters that consider the weight of the bivalves' meat, such as meat yield, a decrease in the animal is noted. The weight of the shells does not decrease under unfavorable growth conditions; however, the weight of the oysters' meat may decrease, indicating this energetic cost of filtration.

The CI is an eco-physiological index that can be affected by various abiotic factors and physiological activities⁴¹⁸. Miranda et al.⁴¹⁹ recorded a reduction in CI of oysters after 30 days of cultivation in systems integrated with tilapia, but they associated the reduction with the possibility of a lack of food for oysters in the system. In the system with bioflocs, it was possibly not the scarcity of food but rather

⁴¹⁶ Shumway, S. E., & Parsons, G. J. (2016). *Scallops: Biology, Ecology and Aquaculture* (3rd ed.). Elsevier Science

⁴¹⁷ Wasielesky, W., Atwood, H., Stokes, A., & Browdy, C. L. (2006). Effect of natural production in a zero exchange suspended microbial floc based super-intensive culture system for white shrimp *Litopenaeus vannamei*. *Aquaculture*, 258(1–4), 396–403. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2006.04.030>

⁴¹⁸ Barraza-Guardado, R. H., Chávez-Villalba, J., Atilano-Silva, H., & Hoyos-Chairez, F. (2008). Seasonal variation in the condition index of Pacific oyster postlarvae (*Crassostrea gigas*) in a land-based nursery in Sonora, Mexico. *Aquaculture Research*, 40(1), 118–128. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2109.2008.02076.x>

⁴¹⁹ Miranda, A., Lizarraga-Armenta, J., Rivas-Vega, M., López-Elías, J. A., & Nieves-Soto, M. (2010). Pacific Oyster, *Crassostrea gigas*, Cultured With Tilapia, *Oreochromis mossambicus* × *Oreochromis niloticus* in a Recirculation System. *Journal of the World Aquaculture Society*, 41(5), 764–772. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1749-7345.2010.00418.x>

the exacerbated need for filtration that led to the reduction in CI. Liu et al.⁴²⁰ state that the reduction in CI can be explained by the derivation of energy from endogenous resources, where tissues are lost due to catabolic activities. Bayne⁴²¹ asserts that some species of the genus *Crassostrea* can withstand up to 200 mg/L of total particulate material (TPM) before signs of gill clogging occur. Barillé et al.⁴²² concluded that high concentrations of suspended material in the water column can lead to overload of the oysters' labial palps, and from 160 mg/L of TSS onwards, there is a decline in the selection capacity of the species *C. gigas*, which can cause overload or morphological alterations in the gills of *C. gigas* and justify mortalities.

Lima et al.⁴²³ achieved oyster survival rates between 83% and 93% at the end of a 45-day cultivation integrated with *L. vannamei* shrimp in a BFT system; possibly, the advantage of this system over the system in the present experiment was the adoption of a recirculation system between tanks with oysters, where water was transferred to the tank with oysters and remained stagnant for 24 hours, with daily water exchange with the tank where the shrimp were kept. In contrast, Lopes⁴²⁴ recorded low survival rates (33% to 41%) of *Crassostrea brasiliensis* oysters in a BFT system with marine shrimp *Farfantepenaeus paulensis* after 60 days of cultivation in BFT in the same tank as the shrimp. In this experiment, from day 22 onwards, TSS reached a concentration of 200 mg/L and remained above that until the end of the cultivation. This high concentration may have been responsible for the mortality of oysters, both of the *C. gigas* and *C. gasar* species, as they were in the same tank as the shrimp. Considering the natural environments where *C. gasar* oysters are found in Brazil, it was expected that the survival and zootechnical performance of this species would be better than *C. gigas*, but this result was not observed in the mentioned experiment.

The presence of oysters reduced the proteins in the microbial floccules, indicating that bivalves utilize food items contained in the floccule. Barboza⁴²⁵ found similar protein values in bioflocs from systems integrated with fish and shrimp (17% to 20% in systems integrated with fish and shrimp and 22% and 25% in fish monoculture and shrimp monoculture, respectively). Barboza⁴²⁵ recorded lower

⁴²⁰ Liu, W., Li, Q., Gao, F., & Kong, L. (2010). Effect of starvation on biochemical composition and gametogenesis in the Pacific oyster *Crassostrea gigas*. *Fisheries Science*, 76(5), 737–745. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12562-010-0274-y>

⁴²¹ Bayne, B. (2017). *Biology of Oysters* (1st ed.). Academic Press.

⁴²² Barillé, L., Prou, J., Héral, M., & Razet, D. (1997). Effects of high natural seston concentrations on the feeding, selection, and absorption of the oyster *Crassostrea gigas* (Thunberg). *Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology*, 212(2), 149–172. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-0981\(96\)02756-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-0981(96)02756-6)

⁴²³ Lima, P. C. M., Silva, A. E. M., Silva, D. A., Silva, S. M. B. C., Brito, L. O., & Gálvez, A. O. (2021). Effect of stocking density of *Crassostrea* sp. in a multitrophic biofloc system with *Litopenaeus vannamei* in nursery. *Aquaculture*, 530, 735913. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2020.735913>

⁴²⁴ Lopes, G. R., Gomes, C. H. A. de M., Tureck, C. R., & Melo, C. M. R. de. (2013). Growth of *Crassostrea gasar* cultured in marine and estuary environments in Brazilian waters. *Pesquisa Agropecuária Brasileira*, 48(8), 975–982. <https://doi.org/10.1590/S0100-204X2013000800024>

⁴²⁵ Barboza, M. H. P. (2019). Cultivo multitrófico integrado de *Litopenaeus vannamei* e peixes para controle dos sólidos suspensos totais em sistema de bioflocos [UNIVERSIDADE FEDERAL DO RIO GRANDE - FURG]. <https://ppgaquicultura.furg.br/dissertacoes-e-teses/teses/146-teses-de-2019/449-tese-mariana-holanda>

concentrations of crude protein in the floccule in the integrated shrimp with tilapia treatment than in the tilapia monoculture treatment. Lima et al.⁴²⁶ also recorded lower protein values in bioflocs in the integrated system of *C. gasar* oysters and *L. vannamei* shrimp than in the monoculture of shrimp in BFT and higher ash values. In this experiment, the bioflocs from the Mono treatment showed a higher protein quantity than the IMTA treatment with *C. gigas* oysters. Proteins may have been consumed by oysters during their selective filtration, resulting in a reduction in protein levels in the bioflocs. *C. gigas* oysters had a greater influence on the reduction of proteins than *C. gasar* oysters. Regarding the amount of ash, the bioflocs from the Mono treatment showed less inorganic material. This effect may have been indirectly caused by the oysters, due to the greater application of the alkalizing agent in the treatments integrated with oysters.

Regarding the centesimal composition of *C. gasar* and *C. gigas* oysters, natural differences between the species were noticeable from the beginning of the experiment, and these differences remained at the end of the experiment as well. However, analyzing the species separately, *C. gasar* showed no change in its centesimal composition from the beginning to the end of the experiment. On the other hand, *C. gigas* showed changes, reducing the quantity of proteins and increasing the quantity of ashes. Liu et al.⁴²⁷ analyzed biochemical responses in oysters after periods of starvation and stated that under conditions of food restriction, glycogen reserves are more rapidly mobilized and depleted as a protective measure against the loss of proteins and lipids, since these are structural components of the animal. In other words, lipids and proteins are only consumed in extreme situations of energy need from reserves. Liu et al.⁴²⁷ listed the order of consumption of energy reserves for *C. gigas* as firstly glycogen, followed by proteins, and lastly lipids.

One of the described responses in bivalves when they need to access endogenous reserves is the increase in water and ash content and a corresponding decrease in the condition index, where tissues are lost due to catabolic activities. To maintain essential body volume and internal turgidity during hunger, the lost tissue mass is replaced by water⁴²⁷. The ash content, mainly chloride salts, presumably increases due to cellular hydration⁴²⁸. A similar situation occurred with *C. gigas* oysters in the present experiment, but this situation was not observed for *C. gasar*.

The presence of oysters did not affect the zootechnical performance of shrimp in BFT systems and did not alter water quality parameters to levels detrimental to shrimp cultivation maintenance.

⁴²⁶ Lima, P. C. M., Silva, A. E. M., Silva, D. A., Silva, S. M. B. C., Brito, L. O., & Gálvez, A. O. (2021). Effect of stocking density of *Crassostrea* sp. in a multitrophic biofloc system with *Litopenaeus vannamei* in nursery. *Aquaculture*, 530, 735913. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2020.735913>

⁴²⁷ Liu, W., Li, Q., Gao, F., & Kong, L. (2010). Effect of starvation on biochemical composition and gametogenesis in the Pacific oyster *Crassostrea gigas*. *Fisheries Science*, 76(5), 737–745. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12562-010-0274-y>

⁴²⁸ Whyte, J. N. C., Englar, J. R., & Carswell, B. L. (1990). Biochemical composition and energy reserves in *Crassostrea gigas* exposed to different levels of nutrition. *Aquaculture*, 90(2), 157–172. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0044-8486\(90\)90338-N](https://doi.org/10.1016/0044-8486(90)90338-N)

The BFT system, under the conditions of this experiment, did not prove favorable for the growth of *C. gasar* and *C. gigas* oysters. Therefore, bivalves do not represent a suitable species for reducing solids present in the BFT system under the conditions of this experiment, nor do they serve as a secondary species for production diversification, as their high mortality did not allow satisfactory oyster productivity values in the system.

C. gasar and *C. gigas* oysters were not able to control the solids present in the BFT systems due to the high concentrations they reached during cultivation, which became detrimental to the bivalves. The adoption of oysters to compose the multi-trophic system with marine shrimp in BFT in the same cultivation tank is not technically viable, under the conditions of this experiment.

5.7 Halophyte Aquaponics in Integrated Multi-Trophic Saline Aquaculture Using Biofloc Technology (Experiment 7)

5.7.1 Introduction

Integrated Multitrophic Aquaculture (IMTA) has emerged as a crucial approach to meet the growing demand for sustainable aquaculture production. IMTA involves the interaction of species from different trophic levels, where waste and nutrients generated by one species are recycled as food or nutrient sources for others. The implementation of IMTA, particularly in marine aquaculture, has shown promising results, especially with species like *Litopenaeus vannamei* shrimp. Various organisms, including macroalgae and halophytic vascular plants like *Salicornia*, play vital roles in IMTA systems by absorbing nutrients and contributing to biomass production^{429,430,431}.

The use of Biofloc Technology (BFT) enhances IMTA systems productivity by minimizing water exchange and promoting specific microbial communities to maintain water quality. BFT involves stimulating the growth of heterotrophic nitrifying bacteria, which convert ammonia into protein-rich bacterial biomass, serving as secondary food for cultivated animals. Additionally, the cultivation of autotrophic nitrifying bacteria can further improve water quality by converting ammonia to less toxic nitrate. IMTA-BFT systems have demonstrated higher productivity and nutrient utilization efficiency compared to conventional systems^{432,433,434}.

Furthermore, the integration of halophyte aquaponics into saline IMTA-BFT systems holds promise but requires a deeper understanding of how microbial communities and environmental conditions influence plant growth. Halophytes not only contribute to nutrient phytoremediation but also influence various physicochemical parameters of recirculated water. Evaluating different biofloc

⁴²⁹ Knowler, D, Chopin, T, Martínez - Espiñeira, R, Neori, A, Nobre, A, Noce, Av & Reid, G. 2020. The economics of Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture: where are we now and where do we need to go? *Reviews in Aquaculture*, 12: 1579-1594.

⁴³⁰ Biswas, G, Kumar, P, Ghoshal, T, Kailasam, M, De, D, Bera, A, Vijayan, K. 2020. Integrated multi-trophic aquaculture (IMTA) outperforms conventional polyculture with respect to environmental remediation, productivity and economic return in brackishwater ponds. *Aquaculture*, 516, 734626.

⁴³¹ Rosa, J, Lemos, Mfl, Crespo, D, Nunes, M, Freitas, A, Ramos, F, Leston, S. 2020. Integrated multitrophic aquaculture systems – Potential risks for food safety. *Trends in Food Science & Technology*, 96, 79-90.

⁴³² Samochoa, T, Patnaik, S, Speed, M, Ali, A, Burger, J Almeida, R V & Brock, DI. 2007. Use of molasses as carbon source in limited discharge nursery and grow-out systems for *Litopenaeus vannamei*. *Aquacultural Engineering*, 36(2), 184-191.

⁴³³ Avnimelech, Y. 2009. *Biofloc technology: A practical guide book*. The World Aquaculture Society, Baton Rouge, 182p.

⁴³⁴ Emerenciano, M, Gaxiola, G & Cuzon, G. 2013. Biofloc technology (BFT): a review for aquaculture application and animal food industry. In: Matovic, M. D. (Ed.). *Biomass now-cultivation and utilization*. InTech, Rijeka (Croatia), 301-328.

formation strategies and climatic conditions will be essential for the successful development of saline IMTA systems with halophyte aquaponics^{435,436}.

Salicornia species, in particular, are of interest due to their nutritional value and potential as functional food. These plants contain high levels of proteins, vitamins, minerals, phenolic compounds, and polyunsaturated fatty acids, making them valuable for the food and nutraceutical industries. However, their growth and productivity are influenced by genetic lineage, salinity, and environmental factors such as light availability and temperature^{437,438}.

In Brazil, experimental cultivation of *Salicornia neei* under saline irrigation has shown promising results in various climatic zones. However, further research is needed to understand its response to different environmental conditions, particularly regarding solar radiation and temperature. Additionally, evaluating the potential of *Salicornia* species to thrive in lower temperatures and under different biofloc formation strategies will be crucial for their successful integration into saline IMTA systems^{439,440}.

The integration of diverse species and technologies in IMTA systems, along with the cultivation of halophytes like *Salicornia*, holds significant potential for sustainable aquaculture production. However, further research and experimentation are necessary to optimize these systems and maximize their benefits in different environmental contexts. Our goal is to evaluate the integration of aquaponic production of the native halophyte *S. neei* in the Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture (IMTA) with biofloc technology of the marine shrimp *L. vannamei*, Nile tilapia *Oreochromis niloticus*, oyster *Crassostrea gasar*, and macroalgae *Ulva lactuca*.

5.7.2 Trial Methodology

Two experiments were conducted to evaluate the integration of aquaponic cultivation of the native halophyte *S. neei* in Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture (IMTA), using biofloc technology. These experiments took place at the Marine Aquaculture Station (EMA) of the Federal University of Rio Grande (FURG), located at Cassino Beach (Rio Grande, RS; 32°12'19"S; 52°10'45"W). The studies were

⁴³⁵ Costa, CSB; Kadereit, G; Freitas, GPM. 2019. Molecular markers indicate the phylogenetic identity of southern Brazilian sea asparagus: first record of *Salicornia neei* in Brazil. *Rodriguésia*, 70, e03122017.2019

⁴³⁶ Poli, M, Legarda, E, De Lorenzo, M, Pinheiro, I, Martins, M, Seiffert, W & Do Nascimento Vieira, F. 2019. Integrated multitrophic aquaculture applied to shrimp rearing in a biofloc system. *Aquaculture*, 511, e734274.

⁴³⁷ Barreira, L, Resek, E, Rodrigues, M, Rocha, M, Pereira, H, Bandarra, N, Custódio, L. 2017. Halophytes: Gourmet food with nutritional health benefits? *Journal of Food Composition and Analysis*, 59, 35-42.

⁴³⁸ Doncato, K & Costa, CSB. 2018. Growth and mineral composition of two lineages of the sea asparagus *Sarcocornia ambigua* irrigated with shrimp farm saline effluent. *Experimental Agriculture*, 54(3), 399-416.

⁴³⁹ Costa, CSB & Herrera, OB. 2016. Halófitas brasileiras: Formas de cultivo e usos. In: Gheyi, HR, Dias, NS, Lacerda, CF, Filho, EG. (2a ed). *Manejo da salinidade na agricultura: estudos básicos e aplicados*. Fortaleza, INCTSal/CNPq, 243-258.

⁴⁴⁰ Pinheiro, I, Carneiro, RFS, Nascimento Vieira, F, Gonzaga, LV, Fett, R, Oliveira Costa, AC, Magallón-Barajas, FJ, Seiffert, WQ. 2020. Aquaponic production of *Sarcocornia ambigua* and Pacific white shrimp in biofloc system at different salinities. *Aquaculture*, 519, e734918.

conducted during the winter of 2021 (4 weeks; June 23, 2021, to July 22, 2021) and the summer of 2022 (8 weeks; February 11, 2022, to April 12, 2022).

Each experiment had a different composition of integrated species in IMTA and employed different water treatment strategies for biofloc formation (organic and inorganic carbon sources), with specific objectives. Additionally, the temporal repetition of cultivation allowed for the assessment of the effects of air temperature and incident solar radiation variation on the growth of *S. neei*, and its adaptation to seasonal climatic conditions in southern Brazil.

The insertion of aquaponic cultivation of *S. neei* in saline IMTA systems during the winter of 2021 aimed to evaluate the development and productivity of this plant irrigated with saline water using biofloc technology, during the winter period in the southernmost region of Brazil. This study also allowed assessing the effect of the aquaponic cultivation of these halophytes on the water quality of the IMTA cultivation.

Six multitrophic systems were established in an unheated agricultural greenhouse covered with 70% shade cloth, with three systems randomly allocated for integration with hydroponic benches with *S. neei* and three systems without hydroponic benches. Each IMTA system consisted of three components: (1) a 20 m³ circular raceway (useful volume of 15 m³) containing the biofloc community and *L. vannamei* shrimp, (2) a 4 m³ circular tank housing the fish (Nile tilapia; *O. niloticus*), and (3) a 4 m³ circular tank containing suspended *U. lactuca* macroalgae by floating structures (both tanks with useful volumes of 3 m³). The IMTA systems with halophytes were connected to nutrient film technique (NFT) PVC hydroponic benches containing *S. neei* plants, positioned on the outside of the greenhouse. Each hydroponic bench had 6 tubes of 85 mm X 45 mm and 3 m in length (area = 4.8 m²), containing 10 plants in each tube and a total of 60 plants. Consequently, the experimental design was factorial with two treatments: IMTA with and without halophytes.

In each IMTA system, an aeration system injected air into the tanks of the animals and macroalgae through a blower interconnected with microporous hoses (aerotubes). It also had a submersible pump (Sarlo Better® 2700C), which, through PVC pipes, moved water from the shrimp raceway to the fish tank, and by gravity, moved to the macroalgae tank and returned to the shrimp tank. The same submersible pump transported, through a connection in the piping and hoses, water from the shrimp tank to the hydroponic bench, with an average flow rate of 384 L h⁻¹, which returned to the shrimp tank by gravity. Each IMTA system also had a cylindrical-conical fiberglass clarifier-decanter with a useful volume of 150 L, which received water from the submersible pump in the shrimp tank through pipes. This clarifier was activated when TSS levels exceeded 300 mg L⁻¹.

For the formation of microbial bioflocs, a biofloc inoculum was used from an ongoing shrimp culture, where the formation of microbial bioflocs was conducted using the methodology of heterotrophic

bacteria stimulation^{441, 442, 443}. This inoculum contained concentrations of 0.13, 0.25, 90.00, 4.70, and 600.00 mg L⁻¹, respectively, of total ammoniacal nitrogen, nitrite, nitrate, phosphate, and total suspended solids (TSS). Each experimental unit received 30% inoculum and 70% saltwater. When the plants were transferred for acclimation to the benches, the average TSS value (338.33±38.77 mg L⁻¹) in the shrimp raceways was lower than that of the inoculum, but the concentrations of total ammoniacal nitrogen (0.16±0.03 mg L⁻¹), nitrite (1.00±0.15 mg L⁻¹), nitrate (70±5.00 mg L⁻¹), and phosphate (6.57±0.46 mg L⁻¹) were very similar to the original mature heterotrophic system.

Salicornia neei plants were placed on the hydroponic benches connected to the IMTA systems thirty-six (36) days after stocking the shrimp in the raceways, consequently under nitrifying conditions characteristic of a well-developed biofloc microbial community. *Salicornia neei* is a perennial plant capable of regrowth from its stem after pruning⁴⁴⁴. All plants were acclimated to the hydroponic benches for 20 days before being cut 4 cm above the upper edge of each cup (leveling pruning; occurred 56 days after shrimp stocking), and their growth was evaluated through regrowth.

The initial stocking densities of shrimp and fish were, respectively, 204 ind. m⁻² (average weight 1g) and 35 ind. m⁻³ (average weight 25 g). The initial abundance of macroalgae was 0.11 g m⁻³. Shrimp and tilapia were fed with specific commercial dry diets for each species (38% crude protein). Shrimp were fed twice daily (8:00 a.m. and 3:00 p.m.) following the methodology described by Jory⁴⁴⁵, while tilapia was underfed (once a day) with about 1% of their biomass, encouraging fish to feed on the bioflocs⁴⁴⁶. The feeding rate of shrimp was adjusted weekly, and that of tilapia was adjusted biweekly, according to the growth observed during the study. All management and evaluation of animal and macroalgae development were conducted by students and technicians associated with the Laboratory for Aquaculture Impact Assessment (EMA-FURG).

⁴⁴¹ Avnimelech, Y. (1999). Carbon/nitrogen ratio as a control element in aquaculture systems. *Aquaculture*, 176(3–4), 227–235. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0044-8486\(99\)00085-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0044-8486(99)00085-X)

⁴⁴² Ebeling, J. M., Timmons, M. B., & Bisogni, J. J. (2006). Engineering analysis of the stoichiometry of photoautotrophic, autotrophic, and heterotrophic removal of ammonia–nitrogen in aquaculture systems. *Aquaculture*, 257(1–4), 346–358. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2006.03.019>

⁴⁴³ Samocha, T.M.; Patnaik, S.; Speed, M.; Ali, A.M.; Burger, J.M.; Almeida, R.V.; Ayub, Z.; Harisanto, M.; Horowitz, A.; Brock, D.L. Use of Molasses as Carbon Source in Limited Discharge Nursery and Grow-out Systems for *Litopenaeus vannamei*. *Aquac. Eng.* 2007, 36, 184–191.

⁴⁴⁴ Costa, CSB & Herrera, OB. 2016. Halófitas brasileiras: Formas de cultivo e usos. In: Gheyi, HR, Dias, NS, Lacerda, CF, Filho, EG. (2a ed). Manejo da salinidade na agricultura: estudos básicos e aplicados. Fortaleza, INCTSal/CNPq, 243-258.

⁴⁴⁵ Jory, D. E., Cabrera, T. R., Dugger, D. M., Fegan, D., Lee, P. G., Lawrence, A. L., Jackson, C. J., McIntosh, R. P., & Castañeda, J. (2001). A global review of shrimp feed management: status and perspectives. In C. L. Browdy & D. J. Jory (Eds.), *The New Wave: Proceedings of the Special Session on Sustainable Shrimp Culture*. (pp. 104–152). The World Aquaculture Society.

⁴⁴⁶ Holanda, M., Santana, G., Furtado, P., Rodrigues, R. V., Cerqueira, V. R., Sampaio, L. A., Wasielesky, W., & Poersch, L. H. (2020). Evidence of total suspended solids control by *Mugil liza* reared in an integrated system with pacific white shrimp *Litopenaeus vannamei* using biofloc technology. *Aquaculture Reports*, 18, 100479. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aqrep.2020.100479>

The integration of hydroponic cultivation of *S. neei* into saline IMTA during the summer of 2022 aimed to assess how the physicochemical and nutritional conditions of water with microbial bioflocs, formed from inorganic energy sources (i.e., ammonia and nitrite oxidation; chemioautotrophic formation) and organic sources (organic carbon oxidation; heterotrophic formation), influence the development and productivity of plants in aquaponics. Additionally, this experiment evaluated the effect on water quality passing through the hydroponic bench, as well as enabled comparison of plant development with that of winter 2021.

In the second experiment, six IMTA systems were employed, with the same seawater circulation method and aeration system, as well as the infrastructure of shrimp and tilapia tanks described in the winter 2021 experiment, but with oysters (*Crassostrea gasar* Adanson, 1757) instead of macroalgae. The oysters were cultivated in asbestos tanks with a useful volume of 1 m³. The useful volume in the shrimp tanks was 17 m³. Three IMTA systems were randomly allocated to each biofloc formation strategy treatment. All IMTA systems had an NFT PVC hydroponic bench with *S. neei* halophyte plants. Each hydroponic bench consisted of 6 tubes measuring 85 mm X 45 mm and 3 m in length (area = 4.8 m²), containing 19 plants in each tube (total per bench = 114 plants). The average water flow from the shrimp tank to the hydroponic benches was 455.3 L h⁻¹.

The experimental design was factorial, with two treatments (IMTA TC = Chemioautotrophic and IMTA TH = Heterotrophic) and three replicates per treatment. For the development of the chemioautotrophic system, over a period of 45 days before stocking the shrimp, three raceways were fertilized once a day with 1 mg L⁻¹ of ammonium chloride (NH₄Cl) and 1 mg L⁻¹ of sodium nitrite (NaNO₂) to stimulate the growth of nitrifying bacteria, based on the methodology proposed by Ferreira et al.⁴⁴⁷. In the remaining three raceways, the heterotrophic system was established using the same methodology employed in the formation of the BFT inoculum in the tanks of the winter 2021 experiment, as defined by Avnimelec⁴⁴⁸, Ebeling et al.⁴⁴⁹, and Samocha et al.⁴⁵⁰. After stocking the shrimp, the concentration of total ammoniacal nitrogen (TAN) was monitored daily until it reached 1.0 mg L⁻¹. From this point onwards, an organic carbon source (sugarcane molasses) was added, which stimulated the growth of bacterial biomass, considering the carbon:nitrogen ratio (15C:1N), until a reduction in TAN levels was observed. *S. neei* plants were placed in the hydroponic benches connected

⁴⁴⁷ Ferreira, GS, Santos, D, Schmachtl, F, Machado, C, Fernandes, V, Boegner, M, Vieira, FN. 2021. Heterotrophic, chemoautotrophic and mature approaches in biofloc system for Pacific white shrimp. *Aquaculture*, 533, 736099.

⁴⁴⁸ Avnimelech, Y. (1999). Carbon/nitrogen ratio as a control element in aquaculture systems. *Aquaculture*, 176(3–4), 227–235. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0044-8486\(99\)00085-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0044-8486(99)00085-X)

⁴⁴⁹ Ebeling, J. M., Timmons, M. B., & Bisogni, J. J. (2006). Engineering analysis of the stoichiometry of photoautotrophic, autotrophic, and heterotrophic removal of ammonia–nitrogen in aquaculture systems. *Aquaculture*, 257(1–4), 346–358. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2006.03.019>

⁴⁵⁰ Samocha, T.M.; Patnaik, S.; Speed, M.; Ali, A.M.; Burger, J.M.; Almeida, R.V.; Ayub, Z.; Harisanto, M.; Horowitz, A.; Brock, D.L. Use of Molasses as Carbon Source in Limited Discharge Nursery and Grow-out Systems for *Litopenaeus vannamei*. *Aquac. Eng.* 2007, 36, 184–191.

to the IMTA systems ten (10) days after stocking the shrimp in the raceways, still under conditions of development of the biofloc microbial community and fluctuating levels of TAN and nitrite. *S. neei* plants were acclimated to the hydroponic benches for 17 days, and leveling pruning occurred 27 days after stocking the shrimp.

The initial stocking densities of shrimp, fish, and oysters were, respectively, 400 ind. m⁻² (average weight 1 g), 44 ind. m⁻³ (average weight 25 g), and 300 ind. m⁻³ (average weight 42 g). The diet and feeding frequency of shrimp and tilapia were similar to those of the winter 2021 experiment. Oysters fed only on particulate matter/bioflocs recirculating in the IMTA. As in the first experiment, all management and assessment of animal development were conducted by students and technicians affiliated with the Laboratory for Aquaculture Impact Assessment (EMA-FURG).

The *S. neei* seedlings of the BTH2 lineage were obtained through vegetative propagation of plants maintained in the germplasm of the Laboratory of Halophyte Biotechnology (BTH-EMA-FURG), using the cutting technique. The seedlings were transplanted into 50 ml tubes filled with fine beach sand and kept in a saturated condition within trays with Hoagland nutrient solution (10%). The solution was renewed weekly, and the seedlings were grown in a climate-controlled room with a 12-hour photoperiod (photosynthetically active radiation of 115 μmol m⁻² s⁻¹ ≈ 23.12 W m⁻² ≈ 2.0 MJ m⁻² day⁻¹; conversion as per Thimijan & Reins⁴⁵¹ and an average temperature of 23 °C. When the seedlings reached a height of 10-15 cm, they were transferred to 200 ml plastic mesh cups with a gravel substrate (1-2 cm gravel) and placed on the hydroponic benches for an acclimatization period before the start of each experiment.

The macroalgae *U. lactuca* were collected from the Altair ship at Cassino Beach (32°17.523' S, 52°15.598' W), placed in plastic boxes with constant aeration, and subjected to a 12-hour photoperiod (photosynthetically active radiation of ≈ 2.0 MJ m⁻² day⁻¹) and an average temperature of 23 °C for five days for acclimatization before the start of each experiment. The postlarvae (PL 12) of *L. vannamei* were commercially acquired from Aquatec LTDA (Canguaretama, Rio Grande do Norte, Brazil), and Nile tilapia (*O. niloticus*) fingerlings were obtained from Dalferth company (Teutônia, RS). The oysters used in the summer 2022 experiment were sourced from the commercial farm Paraíso das Ostras (Florianópolis, SC). Larvae and fingerlings were acclimated in bioflocs with 20 ups (standard salinity units; 1 ups ≈ 1 g NaCl L⁻¹).

Daily meteorological data were obtained from the INMET automatic station on the FURG campus (32°04'43"S; 52°10'03"W), available at <https://portal.inmet.gov.br/dadoshistoricos>. During the experiments in winter 2021 and summer 2022, periodic water samples were collected from the inlet

⁴⁵¹ Thimijan, R.W. & Reins, R.D. 1983. Photometric, radiometric, and quantum light units of measure: A review of procedures for interconversion. HortScience 18:818-822.

and outlet of each AMTI system's hydroponic bench, respectively, in the shrimp tank and in the bench return pipe.

Dissolved oxygen and water temperature were monitored using an HACH HQ40d[®] multiparameter device. pH was measured with a Mettler Toledo[®] FEP20 pH meter, and salinity was measured using a multiparameter probe (HANNA HI9829). Alkalinity was monitored according to the method presented by APHA⁴⁵², maintained above 150 mg CaCO₃ L⁻¹, with the use of calcium hydroxide for corrections. Water samples (50 ml) were collected at the same points, and total suspended solids (TSS) levels were estimated by gravimetry after filtration with pre-weighed Whatman GF/C filters⁴⁵³. Total ammonia nitrogen, nitrite, nitrate, and phosphate concentrations were estimated by spectrophotometry⁴⁵⁴. During the winter 2021 experiment, pH, temperature, and dissolved oxygen were measured 5 times per week, while alkalinity, salinity, nutrients, and TSS were measured 2 times per week. In the summer 2022 experiment, temperature and dissolved oxygen were measured 3 times per week, pH and nutrients were estimated 2 times per week, and alkalinity, salinity, and TSS were measured 1 time per week.

In the winter 2021 experiment, plant growth was evaluated after 30 days of growth with a single pruning. In the summer 2022 experiment, growth was assessed through two prunings, performed every 30 days of cultivation. During each pruning, all *S. neei* plants on the benches were identified and cut 4 cm above the top edge of each cup.

After pruning, the fresh above-ground biomass of each plant (stems with branches) was estimated using a precision balance (± 0.01 g). The fresh biomass of the roots of each plant, which developed outside the cups, was quantified only at the end of each experiment, also through weighing on a scale. In each experiment, the stem and root biomass of 10 plants from each bench were dried in an oven (60°C for 48 hours) and weighed on a precision balance (± 0.01 g), allowing the estimation of dry biomass. Stem succulence was estimated by the percentage difference between fresh and dry biomass. The percentage of biomass allocated to stems (above-ground biomass) was estimated by dividing the stem biomass values by the total biomass formed (stems + roots) and multiplying by 100. Biomass production per bench area was also estimated by summing the individual biomasses of all plants on the bench and then dividing this value by the bench area (4.8 m²). Additionally, in the summer 2022 experiment, the stem height (in cm) and the number of its branches with more than 10 cm in length of each plant were quantified.

⁴⁵² APHA. Standard Methods for the Examination of Water and Waste Water, 16th ed.; American Public Health Association, AWWA, WPCF: New York, NY, USA, 1989.

⁴⁵³ Strickland, J. D. H., & Parsons, T. R. (1972). A Practical Handbook of Seawater Analysis (2nd ed.). Fisheries Research Board of Canada.

⁴⁵⁴ Aminot, A., & Chaussepied, M. (1983). Manuel des analyses chimiques en milieu marin. CNEXO

In the first experiment (winter 2021), the mean values of water physico-chemical parameters (salinity, pH, dissolved oxygen, temperature, and alkalinity), SST, and dissolved nutrients (NAT, nitrite, nitrate, and phosphate) collected in the shrimp raceways of IMTA systems with and without halophytes, as well as the performance of animals and macroalgae from both experiments, were compared using Student's t-tests⁴⁵⁵. Additionally, the same parameters mentioned above from water samples collected at the inputs (shrimp raceway waters) and outputs of the hydroponic benches in winter 2021 were compared through one-way repeated measures ANOVAs⁴⁵⁵, with the fixed factor being the collection date (week).

In the second experiment (summer 2022), all water quality data collected were evaluated through two-way repeated measures ANOVAs⁴⁵⁵, with the fixed factors being the biofloc formation strategy treatments (IMTA-TC = Chemioautotrophic and IMTA-TH = Heterotrophic) and the collection date (week). For each parameter considered, the results of the ANOVAs were analyzed for the statistical significance of the factors, as well as the percentage of total variability in the experiment accounted for by each factor. Variability accounting was performed using the eta squared coefficient, which was calculated by dividing the Sum of Squares of factor "i" (SSi) by the Total Sum of Squares (TSS) of the variable. The eta squared coefficient was expressed as a percentage "%SSi".

Regarding the development of *S. neei*, in the first experiment, the mean values (\pm standard error) of plant survival rate, stem and root biomass production per plant, stem succulence, and biomass production per bench area were presented. In the second experiment, data on *S. neei* regrowth after repeated stem pruning (stem height, number of stem branches cut ≥ 10 cm, fresh aerial biomass, and stem succulence) were compared between biofloc formation strategies using one-way repeated measures ANOVAs (1st and 2nd pruning). Data on final root biomass, percentage allocation of biomass to stems, and plant survival rate from the two biofloc formation strategy treatments were compared using Student's t-test. Student's t-test was also used for the evaluation of zootechnical performance and macroalgae.

The physico-chemical water parameters, growth of animals and macroalgae, as well as the biometric and biomass values of *S. neei* plants, were tested for normality (Kolmogorov-Smirnov test) and homoscedasticity (Levene's test). Variables that did not show normality and/or homoscedasticity were mathematically transformed. In the summer 2022 experiment, the stem height variable was transformed using the Log₁₀(x) function. For ANOVAs and t-tests, differences between means were considered significant at a probability level of $p < 0.05$. In ANOVAs, means were compared "post-hoc" using the Tukey HSD test ($p < 0.05$)⁴⁵⁵.

⁴⁵⁵ Zar, J. H. (2010). Biostatistical Analysis (5th ed.). Prentice Hall.

5.7.3 Results

Throughout the 30-day winter 2021 experiment, the air temperature ranged between 5 and 23°C (mean \pm standard error = $14.7 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$), and the solar radiation intensity did not exceed $2.2 \text{ J m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ (2200 W m^{-2} ; mean daily radiation = $8.84 \pm 0.63 \text{ MJ m}^{-2} \text{ day}^{-1}$). The mean concentrations of alkalinity, dissolved phosphate, and salinity of the water were significantly different between the IMTA treatments with and without halophytes. Alkalinity and salinity values were higher in the IMTA treatment with halophytes, while phosphate levels were lower in the same system.

Regarding the significant effects of water passage through the hydroponic benches, small reductions were observed in the average levels of dissolved oxygen (-0.2 mg L^{-1}) and total suspended solids (SST) (-33.9 mg L^{-1}), along with increases in dissolved phosphate ($+1.4 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$), nitrite ($+0.01 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$), and pH ($+0.03$).

Except for alkalinity, total ammonia nitrogen (NAT), phosphate, SST, and salinity, the physicochemical parameters and dissolved nutrients in the water varied significantly over the weeks of cultivation. SST levels were more stable in the AMTI treatment with halophytes, maintaining concentrations between 300 and 350 mg L^{-1} for most of the experiment. However, both treatments showed a reduction in solid concentrations towards the end of the study. The mean concentrations of NAT and nitrite remained below 0.3 and 1 mg L^{-1} , respectively. Nitrate levels remained between 65 and 115 mg L^{-1} over time, indicating a mature and nitrifying biofloc system. Regarding phosphate, in the IMTA treatment with halophytes, there were few variations, and concentrations remained lower than those in the treatment without halophytes throughout the experiment.

During the winter period, cultivated *S. neei* plants demonstrated a high survival rate (92.2%). The individual biomass of stems after 30 days of growth (post-pruning) ranged from 0.37 g to 27.89 g (mean \pm standard error = $4.86 \pm 0.32 \text{ g}$), and the biomass of roots ranged from 0.10 g to 18.28 g (mean = $2.63 \pm 0.17 \text{ g}$), with an average allocation of production to stem biomass of $64.69 \pm 0.67\%$. Stems showed an average succulence of $89.96 \pm 0.72\%$. The average stem productivity per bench area was $0.06 \pm 0.003 \text{ kg m}^{-2}$.

In IMTA systems with halophytes, *L. vannamei* shrimp showed a higher average survival rate and consequent higher productivity per volume than in IMTA systems without halophytes. Similarly, macroalgae showed better development in IMTA with halophytes. The average weight of shrimp and the performance of tilapia showed no differences between IMTA systems.

During the summer 2022 experiment, the outside air temperature varied between 9.0 and 32.5 °C (mean = $22.0 \pm 0.4^\circ\text{C}$), and the maximum observed solar radiation was $3.9 \text{ J m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ (3900 W m^{-2} ; daily average radiation = $17.87 \pm 0.76 \text{ MJ m}^{-2} \text{ day}^{-1}$).

The waters of IMTA systems with chemoautotrophic bioflocs (IMTA TC) showed significantly higher overall averages of NAT, nitrate, dissolved phosphate, and SST than AMTI systems with heterotrophic bioflocs (IMTA TH) (Table 24). Particularly for phosphate and nitrate, the differences between IMTA treatments were more pronounced before the first pruning of *S. neei* plants (Figure 40). Conversely, higher average levels of pH, salinity, nitrite, and dissolved oxygen were observed in the IMTA TH treatment. The effect of water passing through the halophyte bench was significant for the parameters dissolved oxygen and temperature, showing slight reductions in their overall mean values (combined data from both biofloc treatments), and for NAT, nitrate, and pH concentrations, which showed a slight increase in overall mean values.

Table 24. Average values (\pm standard error) of water quality parameters in IMTA systems with microbial bioflocs formed from inorganic carbon (chemoautotrophic formation = CHE) and organic carbon (heterotrophic formation = HET) sources. Water samples were collected during the 8 weeks, at the entrance (IN) and exit (OU) of each *S. neei* hydroponic bench. Legend: DO = Dissolved oxygen; NAT= Total ammonia nitrogen; TSS = Total suspended solids. The parameters DO, alkalinity, NAT, nitrite, nitrate, phosphate and TSS are presented in mg L⁻¹. Temperature in °C and salinity in standard salinity units. Different lowercase letters in the lines indicate significantly different means ($p < 0.05$) according to the Tukey test.

Parameter	Treatment							
	CHE				HET			
	IN		OUT		IN		OUT	
DO	5.78 \pm 0.05	a	5.69 \pm 0.05	a	6.21 \pm 0.06	c	6.10 \pm 0.05	b
Temperature	25.37 \pm 0.24	c	25.03 \pm 0.25	ab	25.09 \pm 0.26	bc	24.78 \pm 0.27	a
pH	7.78 \pm 0.02	a	7.82 \pm 0.02	ab	7.83 \pm 0.03	ab	7.88 \pm 0.02	b
Alkalinity	158.13 \pm 3.86		157.71 \pm 4.75		165.83 \pm 4.12		163.75 \pm 3.96	
NAT	0.14 \pm 0.01	b	0.16 \pm 0.01	c	0.11 \pm 0.01	a	0.14 \pm 0.01	b
Nitrite	1.06 \pm 0.14	a	1.04 \pm 0.12	a	5.42 \pm 1.18	b	5.16 \pm 1.14	b
Nitrate	95.09 \pm 5.70	b	101.78 \pm 6.52	b	59.80 \pm 5.40	a	64.61 \pm 5.87	a
Phosphate	4.49 \pm 0.36	b	4.74 \pm 0.35	b	3.32 \pm 0.30	a	3.27 \pm 0.26	a
TSS	350.83 \pm 16.64	b	343.54 \pm 17.98	b	305.00 \pm 19.60	a	316.26 \pm 22.32	a
Salinity	20.74 \pm 0.35	a	20.76 \pm 0.34	a	24.44 \pm 0.31	b	24.37 \pm 0.31	b

All water parameters, except alkalinity and salinity, showed marked and significant variations throughout the experiment, with the water collection date accounting for 11 to 74% of the total observed variance (SQ%, percentage of sum of squares). The average values of TSS (Figure 41), nitrate (Figure 40), and phosphate (Figure 42) increased during cultivation, while nitrite averages (Figure 40) tended to decrease and other parameters fluctuated between cultivation weeks (e.g., dissolved oxygen had values inversely related to water temperature, ranging from 4.74 to 7.86 mg L⁻¹ and from 20.3 to 28.6 °C). These temporal variations were similar in chemoautotrophic and heterotrophic treatments, except for nitrite levels (significant Treatment x Time interactions; Table 25). In IMTA TH, TSS averages showed greater variability, and nitrite decreased after the third week. In IMTA TC, nitrite

had stabilized by the time of *S. neei* leveling pruning and remained constant throughout the experiment. NAT levels fluctuated in the first weeks in AMTI TC, but both this and AMTI TH subsequently showed stable NAT values close to zero. Regarding alkalinity, in both treatments, there were some fluctuations in the first three weeks (ranging from 130 to 190 mg CaCO₃ L⁻¹); however, throughout the experiment, the concentrations remained above 150 mg CaCO₃ L⁻¹ and showed no statistical difference between treatments. Phosphate levels rose more rapidly in IMTA TC than in IMTA TH.

Figure 40. Variation throughout the experiment in the average values of nitrogen compounds in IMTA systems with chemoautotrophic and heterotrophic formation of bioflocs. Quantified values are presented before (input = E) and after passage (output = S) through the hydroponic benches with *S. neei* plants. Vertical dotted lines indicate plant pruning dates (NP=Leveling cut; 1st P= 1st cut; 2nd P= 2nd cut). Legend: TAN= Total ammonia nitrogen.

Figure 41. Variation throughout the experiment in the average values of total suspended solids (TSS) in IMTA systems with chemoautotrophic and heterotrophic formation of bioflocs. Quantified values are presented before (input = E) and after passage (output = S) through the hydroponic benches with *S. Neei* plants. Vertical dotted lines indicate plant pruning dates (NP=Leveling cut; 1st P= 1st cut; 2nd P= 2nd cut). The black arrows indicate that you hear clearing that week.

Figure 42. Variation throughout the experiment in average phosphate values in IMTA systems with chemoautotrophic and heterotrophic formation of bioflocs. Quantified values are presented before (input =E) and after passage (output = S) through the hydroponic benches with *S. neei* plants. Vertical dotted lines indicate plant pruning dates (NP=Leveling cut; 1st P= 1st cut; 2nd P= 2nd cut).

The survival rates of *S. neei* plants in the AMTI TC and IMTA TH systems were 91.5% and 85.7%, respectively, with no statistical difference. In the 1st pruning, the mean stem height, number of branches ≥ 10 cm, stem biomass, and biomass allocation in stem formation were significantly higher in the IMTA TC treatment than in the IMTA TH treatment. In the 2nd pruning, the statistical differences remained, except for stem height, which showed no difference between treatments. Within each biofloc treatment, all the afore mentioned parameters were significantly higher in the 2nd pruning (Table 26). Regarding the average percentage of stem succulence, it varied slightly, between 88.11% and 89.95%, with no differences between treatments.

Table 25. Result of repeated measures ANOVAs on physicochemical parameters and water nutrients. The effects of biofloc formation strategy treatments (t), passage through the hydroponic bench (p) and cultivation weeks (w) were considered. Legend: DO = Dissolved oxygen; NAT= Total ammonia nitrogen; TSS = Total suspended solids. The parameters DO, alkalinity, NAT, nitrite, nitrate, phosphate and SST are presented in mg L⁻¹, temperature in °C and salinity in standard salinity units.

Parameter	ANOVA							
	Fp	p	Ft	p	Fw	p	Fw x t	p
DO	13.22	<0.001	39.83	<0.001	5.16	<0.001	1.07	0.39
Temperature	115.99	<0.001	1.91	0.17	54.30	<0.001	0.08	1.00
pH	4.39	<0.001	8.07	<0.001	4.48	<0.001	1.22	0.30
Alkalinity	0.56	0.46	1.49	0.23	1.84	0.11	0.25	0.97
NAT	22.33	<0.001	6.11	0.02	5.07	<0.001	1.04	0.41
Nitrite	2.78	0.10	36.72	<0.001	13.63	<0.001	12.18	<0.001
Nitrate	7.65	<0.01	155.22	<0.001	91.14	<0.001	0.29	0.96
Phosphate	1.13	0.29	22.34	<0.001	21.99	<0.001	0.22	0.98
TSS	0.07	0.80	4.46	0.04	6.12	<0.001	1.45	0.22
Salinity	0.68	0.42	66.82	<0.001	2.38	0.07	0.12	0.99

The average productivity of fresh biomass of *S. neei* stems per bench area ranged from 0.19 to 0.67 kg m⁻² 30 days⁻¹, being higher in the 2nd pruning in both biofloc treatments (Table 26). *S. neei* productivity showed no difference between the IMTA TC and IMTA TH treatments.

Table 26. Assessment of the development of *S. neei* plants during 60 days of cultivation, in both biofloc formation treatments (chemautotrophic formation = CHE; heterotrophic formation = HET). Averages (± standard error) for each biometric parameter for each cut. Different lowercase letters in the lines indicate significantly different means (p<0.05) according to the Student “t” test (parameters evaluated only after the 2nd cut) and Tukey test (after ANOVA)

Parameter	Treatment									
	CHE				HET					
	1 ^a cut		2 ^a cut		1 ^a cut		2 ^a cut			
Survival rate (%)	-	-	-	-	91.52 ± 0.29	-	-	-	-	85.67 ± 2.88
Shoot height (cm)	15.60 ± 0.28	b	17.53 ± 0.23	c	12.6 ± 0.27	a	16.97 ± 0.25	c		
Branch ≥10 cm (per shoot)	6.93 ± 0.37	b	10.43 ± 0.36	c	3.73 ± 0.26	a	7.97 ± 0.29	b		
Shoot biomass (g)	15.80 ± 0.77	b	30.99 ± 0.81	d	9.63 ± 0.53	a	27.01 ± 0.79	c		
Shoot productivity (kg m ⁻²)	0.34 ± 0.08	ab	0.67 ± 0.03	c	0.19 ± 0.04	a	0.53 ± 0.03	bc		
Shoot succulence (%)	89.20 ± 0.34	ab	88.84 ± 0.64	ab	88.10 ± 0.25	a	89.95 ± 0.16	b		
Root biomass (g)	-	-	-	-	2.21 ± 0.08	-	-	-	2.38 ± 0.09	
Shoot allocation (%)	-	-	-	-	95.42 ± 0.14	a	-	-	-	93.87 ± 0.16

In both biofloc treatments, all oysters died before the harvest of shrimps and fish. In the IMTA TC treatment, the *L. vannamei* shrimps showed higher average weights and consequent higher productivity per volume than in the IMTA TH treatment. Regarding the same performance parameters of tilapias, there were no statistical differences between treatments (Table 27).

Table 27. Evaluation of the development of *L. vannamei* shrimp and *O. niloticus* tilapia during 63 days of cultivation in both biofloc formation treatments. Means (\pm standard error) for each parameter. Different lowercase letters indicate significantly different means ($p < 0.05$) according to the Student “t” test. Source: Aquaculture Impact Assessment Laboratory (EMA-FURG)

Parameter	Treatment					
	IMTA TC		IMTA TH		t	p
Shrimp						
Survival (%)	90.5 \pm 3.75		85.09 \pm 4.21			0.31
Final mean weight (g)	11.24 \pm 1.39	a	8.25 \pm 1.06	b		<0.01
Yield (kg m ⁻³)	3.86 \pm 0.08	a	2.83 \pm 0.08	b		<0.01
Tilapia						
Survival (%)	75.05 \pm 17.27		83.81 \pm 6.31			0.59
Final mean weight (g)	171.6 \pm 12.59		180.28 \pm 6.53			0.47
Yield (kg m ⁻³)	1.11 \pm 0.26		1.29 \pm 0.13			0.48

5.7.4 Discussion and Conclusions

The study investigated the impact of integrating hydroponic benches with halophytes into a biofloc technology (BFT) system on water quality and the growth of cultured organisms. In both winter 2021 and summer 2022 experiments, passing water through the hydroponic benches had minimal effects on water quality parameters, with slight reductions in dissolved oxygen and increases in pH observed. There were variations in nutrient concentrations, but they remained within suitable ranges for the cultured organisms. The accumulation of bioflocs in the hydroponic benches necessitated regular cleaning to prevent obstruction and water overflow. Interestingly, the accumulated solids did not hinder the growth of halophyte plants, indicating their potential adaptability to such conditions^{456,457}. Regarding nutrient levels, phosphates and nitrates remained within safe limits for the cultured organisms^{458,459,460}, although variations were observed between treatments and experiments. While hydroponic benches reduced phosphate concentrations, they did not significantly affect nitrate levels

⁴⁵⁶ Santos, D, Pinheiro, Ic, & Seiffert, WQ. 2020. Cultivo aquapônico de salicornia ambigua e camarão marinho em duas fases do sistema de bioflocos: heterotrófica e quimioautotrófica. In: Valença, A.R., Santos, P.R.D., & Guzella, L. (Eds), Aquicultura no Século XXI: desenvolvimento econômico, meio ambiente e pesquisas. Florianópolis, UFSC, pp 25-39.

⁴⁵⁷ Doncato, KB & Costa, CSB. 2023. Evaluation of nitrogen and phosphorus nutritional needs of halophytes for saline aquaponics. Horticulture, Environment, and Biotechnology, 63 (no prelo).

⁴⁵⁸ Lin, YC & JC Chen. 2001. Acute toxicity of ammonia on *Litopenaeus vannamei* Boone juveniles at different salinity levels. Journal of experimental marine biology and ecology, 259(1), 109-119.

⁴⁵⁹ Lin, YC & Chen, JC. 2003. Acute toxicity of nitrite on *Litopenaeus vannamei* (Boone) juveniles at different salinity levels. Aquaculture, 224(1-4), 193–201.

⁴⁶⁰ Costa, L, Poersch, L, Abreu, P. 2021. Biofloc removal by the oyster *Crassostrea gasar* as a candidate species to an Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture (IMTA) system with the marine shrimp *Litopenaeus vannamei*. Aquaculture, 540, 13 736731.

due to intense nitrification processes in the bioflocs⁴⁶¹. These findings suggest that hydroponic benches with laminar flow may aid in phosphate and alkalinity control, possibly through microbial processes. In both experiments, high nitrate concentrations indicated nitrifying conditions typical of biofloc systems. The rapid accumulation of nitrate despite plant assimilation highlights the efficiency of nitrification processes, particularly in chemoautotrophic treatments. The development of a mixed heterotrophic microbial community in the bioflocs likely contributed to this process, impacting nutrient dynamics and water quality management. Overall, integrating hydroponic benches with halophytes into BFT systems shows potential for nutrient control and improved water quality, warranting further investigation into microbial community dynamics^{462,463}.

The study examined the growth and productivity of *S. neei* irrigated with saline water in IMTA (Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture) systems using biofloc technology. Survival rates were high, indicating the species' adaptability to such systems. Biomass production was influenced by various factors like the cultivation system, irrigation frequency, stocking density, salinity, nutrient availability, light, and temperature. Summer 2022 cultivations showed similar productivity to previous systems, while winter 2021 cultivation exhibited reduced biomass production due to lower temperatures and solar radiation. The best performance of *S. neei* was observed in the IMTA TC treatment in summer 2022, attributed to higher nitrate and phosphate concentrations. Differences in plant performance between biofloc formation strategies were notable, with IMTA TC showing higher nitrate concentrations favoring plant growth. Further studies are needed to understand the physiological limitations imposed by solar radiation and temperature on *S. neei* development^{464,465,466}.

The best nutritional conditions in IMTA TC resulted not only in high individual biomasses and productivity per bench area, but also in better agronomic features, such as greater allocation of primary production to stem biomass, as well as taller plants and a higher number of stem branches with lengths ≥ 10 cm (a size often commercially marketed). The lower biomass allocation to stems in winter and the higher in IMTA TC than in IMTA TH reflect the adaptive plasticity of this plant to

⁴⁶¹ Krummenauer, D, Samocha, T, Poersch, L, Lara, G & Wasielesky, W. 2014. The reuse of water on the culture of Pacific white shrimp, *Litopenaeus vannamei*, in BFT system. *Journal of the World Aquaculture Society*, 45(1), 3-14.

⁴⁶² Michaud, L, Blancheton, Jp, Bruni, V, Piedrahita, R. 2006. Effect of particulate organic carbon on heterotrophic bacterial populations and nitrification efficiency in biological filters *Aquac. Eng.*, 34, pp. 224-233.

⁴⁶³ Ferreira, GS, Santos, D, Schmachtl, F, Machado, C, Fernandes, V, Boegner, M, Vieira, FN. 2021. Heterotrophic, chemoautotrophic and mature approaches in biofloc system for Pacific white shrimp. *Aquaculture*, 533, 736099.

⁴⁶⁴ Poli, MA, Legarda, EC, De Lorenzo, MA, Pinheiro, I, Martins, MA, Seiffert, WG & Do Nascimento Vieira, F. 2019. Integrated multitrophic aquaculture applied to shrimp rearing in a biofloc system. *Aquaculture*, 511, e734274.

⁴⁶⁵ Fierro-Sañudo, JF, Rodríguez-Montes De Oca, GA & Páez-Osuna, F. 2020. Co-culture of shrimp with commercially important plants: a review. *Review in Aquaculture*, 12: 2411-2428.

⁴⁶⁶ Doncato, KB & Costa, CSB. 2022. Influence of saline irrigation schedules on vegetative growth and reproduction of different progenies of the sea asparagus *Salicornia neei* Lag. *Biotemas*, 35(1), 1-9. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5007/2175-7925.2022.e84731>

environmental stressors. Mean stem heights after 4-week cultivation periods are similar to those in previous studies with the same species and vary depending on cultivation time and nutrient conditions. Regarding stem branching numbers, the results obtained are intermediate compared to other studies, indicating good performance in terms of the commercial value of the plants produced. The average succulence of *S. neei* plants was similar to previous studies, reflecting good growth conditions and being a desirable trait for culinary purposes. The cylindrical, succulent, segmented stems of *Salicornia* plants are adaptations for survival in saline environments, avoiding toxicity and maintaining osmotic balance with the external saline medium^{467,468,469,470,471,472,473}.

During the experiments, significant findings emerged regarding the zootechnical development of shrimps and fish, as well as the growth of macroalgae in Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture (IMTA) systems with biofloc technology and benches featuring halophytes. In the winter 2021 experiment, shrimps exhibited higher survival rates and production in BFT systems with halophytes compared to those without. While slight numerical differences in alkalinity, phosphate concentrations, and salinities were noted between treatments, they did not fully account for the observed outcomes. The average water temperature in the winter experiment (16°C) was notably lower than the ideal ranges for both shrimp (28-30°C) and tilapia (26-30°C). Despite temperature variations and tank management differences, survival rates (85-92%) and shrimp sizes (8.11-8.25g) were similar across both experiments, with higher productivity in summer 2022 potentially attributed to increased initial stocking density. However, mortality of all *C. gasar* oysters occurred in summer 2022, seemingly due to particulate matter accumulation on their shells. Shrimp performance, indicated by final average weight, productivity, and survival after 8 weeks, was superior in the treatment connected to halophyte benches compared to the other treatment. Tilapia showed comparable performance between IMTA systems with different biofloc formation strategies in both experiments, underscoring their resilience

⁴⁶⁷Singh, D, Buhmann, AK, Flowers, TI, Seal, CE, Papenbrock, J. 2014. *Salicornia* as a crop plant in temperate regions: selection of genetically characterized ecotypes and optimization of their cultivation conditions. *AoB plants*, 6, e71.

⁴⁶⁸ Greis, G. 2009. Cultivo de *Salicornia gaudichaudiana* Moq. irrigada com efluente de camarão no clima temperado na costa sul do Brasil. Dissertação Mestrado. Rio Grande, FURG, 62p.

⁴⁶⁹ Beyer, CP, Gómez, S, Lara, G, Monsalve, JP, Orellana, J, Hurtado, C. F. 2021. *Sarcocornia neei*: A novel halophyte species for bioremediation of marine aquaculture wastewater and production diversification in integrated systems. *Aquaculture*, 543, e736971.

⁴⁷⁰ Ventura, Y, Wuddineh, WA, Myrzabayeva, M, Alikulov, Z, Khozin-Goldberg, I, Shpigel, M, Sagi, M. 2011. Effect of seawater concentration on the productivity and nutritional value of annual *Salicornia* and perennial *Sarcocornia* halophytes as leafy vegetable crops. *Scientia Horticulturae*, 128(3), 189-196

⁴⁷¹ Ventura, Y & Sagi, M. 2013. Halophyte crop cultivation: The case for *Salicornia* and *Sarcocornia*. *Environmental and experimental botany*, 92, 144–153.

⁴⁷² Flowers, TI, Hajibagheri, MA, & Clipson, NJW. 1986. Halophytes. *The Quarterly Review of Biology*, 61(3), 313–337. doi:10.1086/415032.

⁴⁷³ Grigore, MN, Toma, C. 2021. Morphological and Anatomical Adaptations of Halophytes: A Review. In: Grigore, MN. (eds) *Handbook of Halophytes*. Springer, Cham.

across varying conditions. The growth of *U. lactuca* macroalgae in IMTA systems varied considerably, with greater growth observed in systems with halophytes, possibly due to increased sunlight exposure (less TSS in IMTA TC). Previous studies have highlighted the critical role of light intensity in macroalgae growth, with variations impacting performance. Despite challenges in interpreting macroalgae performance differences between treatments, the insertion of halophyte benches did not compromise the overall productivity of organisms in the IMTA system, since there were abundant nutrients in the experimental systems. These findings shed light on the complex interplay between environmental factors, species interactions, and system design in IMTA setups, offering insights for optimizing productivity and sustainability in aquaculture practices^{474,475,476,477,478,479,480}.

⁴⁷⁴ Delong, DP, Losordo, T, Rakocy, J. 2009. Tank culture of tilapia. SRAC Publication No. 282. Stoneville (MS, U.S.A.), Southern Regional Aquaculture Center, 8p.

⁴⁷⁵ Costa, L, Poersch, L, Abreu, P. 2021. Biofloc removal by the oyster *Crassostrea gasar* as a candidate species to an Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture (IMTA) system with the marine shrimp *Litopenaeus vannamei*. *Aquaculture*, 540, 13 736731

⁴⁷⁶ Santos, D, Pinheiro, IC, & Seiffert, WQ. 2020. Cultivo aquapônico de *salicornia ambigua* e camarão marinho em duas fases do sistema de bioflocos: heterotrófica e quimioautotrófica. In: Valença, A.R., Santos, P.R.D., & Guzella, L. (Eds), *Aquicultura no Século XXI: desenvolvimento econômico, meio ambiente e pesquisas*. Florianópolis, UFSC, pp 25-39.

⁴⁷⁷ Ferreira, GS, Santos, D, Schmachtl, F, Machado, C, Fernandes, V, Boegner, M, Vieira, FN. 2021. Heterotrophic, chemoautotrophic and mature approaches in biofloc system for Pacific white shrimp. *Aquaculture*, 533, 736099

⁴⁷⁸ Khanjani, MH, Zahedi, S, Mohammadi, A. 2022. Integrated multitrophic aquaculture (IMTA) as an environmentally friendly system for sustainable aquaculture: functionality, species, and application of biofloc technology (BFT). *Environ Sci Pollut Res.*, 45: 67513-67531.

⁴⁷⁹ Shpigel, M, Guttman, L, Ben-Ezra, D, Yu, J & Chen, S. 2019. Is *Ulva sp.* able to be an efficient biofilter for mariculture effluents? *Journal of Applied Phycology*, 31(4), 2449-2459.

⁴⁸⁰ Mhatre, A, Navale, M, Trivedi, N, Pandit, R, & Lali, A. 2018. Pilot scale flat panel photobioreactor system for mass production of *Ulva lactuca* (Chlorophyta). *Bioresource Technology*, 249, 582-591.

6. General comments about ASTRAL IMTA Production Species/Production Value Chain

This document focuses on part of the Value Chain, relating to "Production Processes" of aquatic organisms (Figure 43) within integrated systems developed with bioflocs, aiming to reduce effluent emissions into the environment by up to 95%. Integrating species from various trophic levels aids in water treatment by reducing particulate matter and dissolved nutrients, allowing for water reuse across different production cycles.

Integrating species into a biofloc system is complex and often requires decisions that may not fully benefit all species. For instance, working with marine shrimp and tilapia at optimal growth temperatures (30°C) leads to increased oyster mortality and often reduces macroalgae biomass. Conversely, operating at temperatures up to 27°C favors macroalgae and oysters but compromises the growth of shrimp and fish. Perhaps introducing species at different times of the year could be a viable option, but further studies are needed to confirm this approach.

Figure 43. Shaded area indicates the section of the aquaculture production value chain covered by IMTA Lab Brazil

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growth of shrimp and fish. Perhaps introducing species at different times of the year could be a viable option, but further studies are needed to confirm this approach.

Another critical factor is biofloc concentration in the water. Concentrations between 300 and 450 mg/L promote maximum growth of tilapia and shrimp and enhance microorganism efficiency in converting ammonia and nitrite into nitrate, but this sacrifices the development of algae, halophytes, and molluscs. Oysters, for instance, cannot tolerate particulate matter concentrations exceeding 250 mg/L, and algae require placement closer to the water's surface to benefit from light and produce biomass, necessitating adjustments in the production system layout. Halophytes maintained in high concentrations of bioflocs (above 250 -300 mg/L) have clogged roots and the absorption of phosphate and nitrate is compromised and plant growth is not ideal.

The use of organic versus inorganic fertilizers also influences biofloc concentration. Inorganic fertilizers are preferable for reducing particulate matter concentration and stimulating algae growth (due to improved light penetration), although the growth rate of tilapia and shrimp may be lower compared to those sustained by bioflocs formed through organic fertilization.

Considering the best results from the experiments carried out at IMTA Brazil system, it is possible to produce between 42-45 tons of shrimp/ha/cycle (3 cycles per year), 137-142 tons/ha/cycle (2 cycles per year) and between 5.6-6.1 ton of *Ulva*/ha/month. The production of halophytes still requires more studies to reach greater conclusions. It should be noted that this production in the BFT system occurs without water renewal and therefore without effluents emission, with the water being reused in successive cycles.

Decisions regarding management and adopting the biofloc production system are made by the producer, who may prioritize the growth of certain species over others to enhance overall productivity or maintain water/effluent quality. Achieving a "green" seal and securing better market prices for the product may make maintaining water/effluent quality within the system a compelling decision.